

Selfie Numbers: Basic Operations

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Abstract

*Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers, quadratic numbers, cubic numbers, etc.** This paper brings selfie numbers with basic operations up to 7 digit's numbers. The previous work up to 6 digits numbers can be seen in [14, 15, 16].*

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1 Introduction

Let's analyse historical aspects of some numbers:

- (i) Consider the following classical number famous as **printer's error** (Dudeney, 1917, pp. 379 [5]):

$$2592 := 2^5 \times 9^2 \quad (1)$$

Actually it is not a **printer's error**, it represents a number in its own digits. The first number with similar property is $25 = 5^2$, but is in **reverse order**.

- (ii) Let consider another examples (Madachy, 1966, pp.167-175 [11]):

$$\begin{aligned} 34425 &:= 3^4 \times 425 \\ 312325 &:= 31^2 \times 325 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Above two are represented their own digits. Moreover, if we multiply by both sides by 10, they continued with property of same digits both sides. These kinds of numbers are famous as **number patterns**. Still there is another number with different property, i.e.,

$$27594 := 73 \times 9 \times 42 = 7 \times 3942 \quad (3)$$

In this case, the two expressions on right side of (4) are with same digits, but the total value is with different digits. This type of study is not under work.

- (iii) Madachy, 1966, pp.167-275 [11] also gave an interesting property with factorials known by **sum of factorials**:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= 1! \\ 2 &:= 2! \\ 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Above numbers also have the property of same digits on both sides, but with factorial and addition.

In all the three situations, we observe that we are dealing with numbers that have same digits on both sides, where one side is a number and the other with same digits with certain operations. Based on the above idea of numbers, the author studies numbers calling **selfie numbers**, i.e., numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. Some studies in this direction can be seen in the works of Friedman [6, 7] and Rose [2, 3, 4].

Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** extending the idea of equation (2) using the operations of addition and subtraction with **factorial**:

$$\begin{aligned}145 &= 1! + 4! + 5! & 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! \\733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! \\1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1! \\5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\403199 &:= 40319 + 9! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9!\end{aligned}$$

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

1. Selfie numbers with **Basic Operations**; [14, 15, 16] - also this work;
2. Selfie numbers with **Factorial**: [26, 27];
3. Selfie numbers with **Square-root**: [14, 15];
4. Selfie numbers with **Factorial and Square-root**: [14, 15, 16];
5. Selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**: [23, 24];
6. Selfie numbers with **Triangular numbers**: [21];
7. Selfie numbers with **Binomial coefficients**: [22];
8. Selfie numbers with **S-gonal numbers**: [17];
9. Selfie numbers with **Centered Polygonal**: [17];
10. Selfie numbers with **Concatenation-Type**: [28];
11. Selfie numbers with **Quadratic numbers**: [25];
12. Selfie numbers with **Cubic numbers**: [29];

The last Section 4 is dedicated to summary of **selfie numbers** in different situations along with proper references.

2 Selfie Numbers: Basic Operations - Digit's Order

This section bring **selfie numbers** in digit's order using basic operations, i.e., addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation. This we have done up to 7 digits. The numbers given in expressions (2) and (4) are also included.

2.1 Without Addition and Subtraction Coefficients

$$\begin{aligned}
 2592 &:= 2^5 \times 9^2 & 1984512 &:= 19 \times 8^4 \times 51/2 \\
 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 & 2162688 &:= (2 \times 1)^{6 \times 2} \times 6 \times 88 \\
 26364 &:= 26^3 \times 6/4 & 2254714 &:= 22^5/4 \times 7 \times 1/4 \\
 34425 &:= 3^4 \times 425 & 2332800 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 800 \\
 35721 &:= 3^5 \times 7 \times 21 & 2671872 &:= 2 \times 6 \times 71 \times (8 \times 7)^2 \\
 & & 3123250 &:= 31^2 \times 3250 \\
 170471 &:= 1 \times 7^{04} \times 71 & 3149280 &:= 3^{1^4 \times 9} \times 2 \times 80 \\
 233280 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 80 & 3332340 &:= (3 \times 33)^2 \times 340 \\
 312325 &:= 31^2 \times 325 & 3365793 &:= 3 \times 3^6 \times 57 \times 9 \times 3 \\
 314928 &:= 3^{1^4 \times 9} \times 2 \times 8 & 3442500 &:= 3^4 \times 42500 \\
 333234 &:= (3 \times 33)^2 \times 34 & 3472875 &:= 3^4 \times 7^2 \times 875 \\
 344250 &:= 3^4 \times 4250 & 3572100 &:= 3^5 \times 7 \times 2100 \\
 357210 &:= 3^5 \times 7 \times 210 & 3612672 &:= 3 \times 6 \times 1 \times (2^6 \times 7)^2 \\
 484128 &:= (48 \times 41)^2/8 & 3639168 &:= 3^6 \times 39 \times 16 \times 8 \\
 492205 &:= 49^2 \times 205 & 4344192 &:= (4 \times 3)^4 \times 419/2 \\
 741321 &:= (7 \times 41 \times 3)^2 \times 1 & 4922050 &:= 49^2 \times 2050 \\
 777924 &:= 7 \times 7 \times (7 \times 9)^2 \times 4 & 5752875 &:= 575^2 \times 87/5 \\
 & & 6718464 &:= 6^7 \times 1^84 \times 6 \times 4 \\
 1492992 &:= 1 \times 4 \times 9 \times 2^9 \times 9^2 & 6967296 &:= 6 \times 9 \times 6 \times 7 \times 2^9 \times 6 \\
 1594323 &:= 1^5 \times (9^4/3)^2/3 & 7022457 &:= 702^2/4 \times 57 \\
 1679616 &:= 1 \times 6^7 \times 96/16 & 7142975 &:= (7 \times 1)^4 \times 2975 \\
 1704710 &:= 1 \times 7^{04} \times 710 & 7413210 &:= (7 \times 41 \times 3)^2 \times 10 \\
 1729665 &:= 17^2 \times 9 \times 665 & 7587328 &:= 7 \times 58 \times 73 \times 2^8 \\
 1740725 &:= 1 \times 7^4 \times 0725 & 7779240 &:= 7 \times 7 \times (7 \times 9)^2 \times 40 \\
 1769472 &:= 1^7 \times 6 \times 9 \times 4^7 \times 2 & 8786432 &:= 8 \times (786 \times 4/3)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.1. Interestingly, the first number, i.e., $2592 := 2^5 \times 9^2$ is the same as given in (1). The two numbers appearing in (2) are also appearing here. Still, we have much more numbers of similar kind.

2.2 Symmetric and Consecutive

This subsection brings selfie numbers represented in symmetric way. These are blocks of either 10 or 100.

$$\begin{aligned}
 137790 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 9 + 0 & 137794 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 9 + 4 \\
 137791 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 9 + 1 & 137795 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 9 + 5 \\
 137792 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 9 + 2 & 137796 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 9 + 6 \\
 137793 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 9 + 3 & 137797 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 9 + 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$137798 := (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 9 + 8$$

$$137799 := (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 9 + 9$$

$$156250 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 0$$

$$156251 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 1$$

$$156252 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2$$

$$156253 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 3$$

$$156254 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 4$$

$$156255 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 5$$

$$156256 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 6$$

$$156257 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 7$$

$$156258 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 8$$

$$156259 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 9$$

$$248830 := -2 + (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 0$$

$$248831 := -2 + (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 1$$

$$248832 := -2 + (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 2$$

$$248833 := -2 + (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 3$$

$$248834 := -2 + (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 4$$

$$248835 := -2 + (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 5$$

$$248836 := -2 + (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 6$$

$$248837 := -2 + (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 7$$

$$248838 := -2 + (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 8$$

$$248839 := -2 + (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 9$$

$$262140 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 4 + 0$$

$$262141 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 4 + 1$$

$$262142 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 4 + 2$$

$$262143 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 4 + 3$$

$$262144 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 4 + 4$$

$$262145 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 4 + 5$$

$$262146 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 4 + 6$$

$$262147 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 4 + 7$$

$$262148 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 4 + 8$$

$$262149 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 4 + 9$$

$$466520 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 2 + 0$$

$$466521 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 2 + 1$$

$$466522 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 2 + 2$$

$$466523 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 2 + 3$$

$$466524 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 2 + 4$$

$$466525 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 2 + 5$$

$$466526 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 2 + 6$$

$$466527 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 2 + 7$$

$$466528 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 2 + 8$$

$$466529 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 2 + 9$$

$$466560 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 6 + 0$$

$$466561 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 6 + 1$$

$$466562 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 6 + 2$$

$$466563 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 6 + 3$$

$$466564 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 6 + 4$$

$$466565 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 6 + 5$$

$$466566 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 6 + 6$$

$$466567 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 6 + 7$$

$$466568 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 6 + 8$$

$$466569 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 6 + 9$$

$$585640 := 5 \times 8 \times (5 + 6)^4 + 0$$

$$585641 := 5 \times 8 \times (5 + 6)^4 + 1$$

$$585642 := 5 \times 8 \times (5 + 6)^4 + 2$$

$$585643 := 5 \times 8 \times (5 + 6)^4 + 3$$

$$585644 := 5 \times 8 \times (5 + 6)^4 + 4$$

$$585645 := 5 \times 8 \times (5 + 6)^4 + 5$$

$$585646 := 5 \times 8 \times (5 + 6)^4 + 6$$

$$585647 := 5 \times 8 \times (5 + 6)^4 + 7$$

$$585648 := 5 \times 8 \times (5 + 6)^4 + 8$$

$$585649 := 5 \times 8 \times (5 + 6)^4 + 9$$

$$656250 := 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 0$$

$$656251 := 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 1$$

$$656252 := 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 2$$

$$656253 := 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 3$$

$$656254 := 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 4$$

$$656255 := 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 5$$

$$\begin{aligned}656256 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 6 \\656257 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 7 \\656258 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 8 \\656259 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1176450 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) \times 5 + 0 \\1176451 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) \times 5 + 1 \\1176452 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) \times 5 + 2 \\1176453 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) \times 5 + 3 \\1176454 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) \times 5 + 4 \\1176455 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) \times 5 + 5 \\1176456 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) \times 5 + 6 \\1176457 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) \times 5 + 7 \\1176458 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) \times 5 + 8 \\1176459 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) \times 5 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1176490 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7^6 \times (4 - 9) + 0 \\1176491 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7^6 \times (4 - 9) + 1 \\1176492 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7^6 \times (4 - 9) + 2 \\1176493 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7^6 \times (4 - 9) + 3 \\1176494 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7^6 \times (4 - 9) + 4 \\1176495 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7^6 \times (4 - 9) + 5 \\1176496 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7^6 \times (4 - 9) + 6 \\1176497 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7^6 \times (4 - 9) + 7 \\1176498 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7^6 \times (4 - 9) + 8 \\1176499 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7^6 \times (4 - 9) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1377900 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 90 + 0 \\1377901 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 90 + 1 \\1377902 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 90 + 2 \\1377903 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 90 + 3 \\1377904 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 90 + 4 \\1377905 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 90 + 5 \\1377906 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 90 + 6 \\1377907 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 90 + 7 \\1377908 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 90 + 8 \\1377909 &:= (1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times 90 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1518750 &:= (1^5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 + 0 \\1518751 &:= (1^5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 + 1 \\1518752 &:= (1^5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 + 2 \\1518753 &:= (1^5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 + 3 \\1518754 &:= (1^5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 + 4 \\1518755 &:= (1^5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 + 5 \\1518756 &:= (1^5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 + 6 \\1518757 &:= (1^5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 + 7 \\1518758 &:= (1^5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 + 8 \\1518759 &:= (1^5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1562488 &:= (1 + 5^{6+2}) \times 4 - 8 - 8 \\1562490 &:= -1 + 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 9 + 0 \\1562491 &:= -1 + 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 9 + 1 \\1562492 &:= -1 + 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 9 + 2 \\1562493 &:= -1 + 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 9 + 3 \\1562494 &:= -1 + 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 9 + 4 \\1562495 &:= -1 + 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 9 + 5 \\1562496 &:= -1 + 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 9 + 6 \\1562497 &:= -1 + 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 9 + 7 \\1562498 &:= -1 + 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 9 + 8 \\1562499 &:= -1 + 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 9 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1562500 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 50 + 0 \\1562501 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 50 + 1 \\1562502 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 50 + 2 \\1562503 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 50 + 3 \\1562504 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 50 + 4 \\1562505 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 50 + 5 \\1562506 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 50 + 6 \\1562507 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 50 + 7 \\1562508 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 50 + 8 \\1562509 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 50 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1574640 &:= 15 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6)^4 + 0 \\1574641 &:= 15 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6)^4 + 1 \\1574642 &:= 15 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6)^4 + 2 \\1574643 &:= 15 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6)^4 + 3\end{aligned}$$

$$1574644 := 15 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6)^4 + 4$$

$$1574645 := 15 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6)^4 + 5$$

$$1574646 := 15 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6)^4 + 6$$

$$1574647 := 15 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6)^4 + 7$$

$$1574648 := 15 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6)^4 + 8$$

$$1574649 := 15 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6)^4 + 9$$

$$1679680 := 1^6 + 7 \times 9 + 6^8 + 0$$

$$1679681 := 1^6 + 7 \times 9 + 6^8 + 1$$

$$1679682 := 1^6 + 7 \times 9 + 6^8 + 2$$

$$1679683 := 1^6 + 7 \times 9 + 6^8 + 3$$

$$1679684 := 1^6 + 7 \times 9 + 6^8 + 4$$

$$1679685 := 1^6 + 7 \times 9 + 6^8 + 5$$

$$1679686 := 1^6 + 7 \times 9 + 6^8 + 6$$

$$1679687 := 1^6 + 7 \times 9 + 6^8 + 7$$

$$1679688 := 1^6 + 7 \times 9 + 6^8 + 8$$

$$1679689 := 1^6 + 7 \times 9 + 6^8 + 9$$

$$1682210 := (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 1 + 0$$

$$1682211 := (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 1 + 1$$

$$1682212 := (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 1 + 2$$

$$1682213 := (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 1 + 3$$

$$1682214 := (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 1 + 4$$

$$1682215 := (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 1 + 5$$

$$1682216 := (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 1 + 6$$

$$1682217 := (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 1 + 7$$

$$1682218 := (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 1 + 8$$

$$1682219 := (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 1 + 9$$

$$1764690 := (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9) + 0$$

$$1764691 := (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9) + 1$$

$$1764692 := (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9) + 2$$

$$1764693 := (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9) + 3$$

$$1764694 := (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9) + 4$$

$$1764695 := (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9) + 5$$

$$1764696 := (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9) + 6$$

$$1764697 := (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9) + 7$$

$$1764698 := (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9) + 8$$

$$1764699 := (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9) + 9$$

$$1764750 := (1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) \times 5 + 0$$

$$1764751 := (1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) \times 5 + 1$$

$$1764752 := (1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) \times 5 + 2$$

$$1764753 := (1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) \times 5 + 3$$

$$1764754 := (1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) \times 5 + 4$$

$$1764755 := (1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) \times 5 + 5$$

$$1764756 := (1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) \times 5 + 6$$

$$1764757 := (1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) \times 5 + 7$$

$$1764758 := (1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) \times 5 + 8$$

$$1764759 := (1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) \times 5 + 9$$

$$1764765 := (1 \times 7^6 \times (-4 + 7) + 6) \times 5$$

$$1764775 := (1 + 7^6 \times (-4 + 7) + 7) \times 5$$

$$1764780 := (-1 + 7^6 + 4) \times (7 + 8) + 0$$

$$1764781 := (-1 + 7^6 + 4) \times (7 + 8) + 1$$

$$1764782 := (-1 + 7^6 + 4) \times (7 + 8) + 2$$

$$1764783 := (-1 + 7^6 + 4) \times (7 + 8) + 3$$

$$1764784 := (-1 + 7^6 + 4) \times (7 + 8) + 4$$

$$1764785 := (-1 + 7^6 + 4) \times (7 + 8) + 5$$

$$1764786 := (-1 + 7^6 + 4) \times (7 + 8) + 6$$

$$1764787 := (-1 + 7^6 + 4) \times (7 + 8) + 7$$

$$1764788 := (-1 + 7^6 + 4) \times (7 + 8) + 8$$

$$1764789 := (-1 + 7^6 + 4) \times (7 + 8) + 9$$

$$1771560 := -1^7 + (7 - 1 + 5)^6 + 0$$

$$1771561 := -1^7 + (7 - 1 + 5)^6 + 1$$

$$1771562 := -1^7 + (7 - 1 + 5)^6 + 2$$

$$1771563 := -1^7 + (7 - 1 + 5)^6 + 3$$

$$1771564 := -1^7 + (7 - 1 + 5)^6 + 4$$

$$1771565 := -1^7 + (7 - 1 + 5)^6 + 5$$

$$1771566 := -1^7 + (7 - 1 + 5)^6 + 6$$

$$1771567 := -1^7 + (7 - 1 + 5)^6 + 7$$

$$1771568 := -1^7 + (7 - 1 + 5)^6 + 8$$

$$1771569 := -1^7 + (7 - 1 + 5)^6 + 9$$

$$1866250 := (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times 5 + 0$$

$$1866251 := (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times 5 + 1$$

$$1866252 := (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times 5 + 2$$

$$1866253 := (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times 5 + 3$$

$$1866254 := (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times 5 + 4$$

$$1866255 := (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times 5 + 5$$

$$1866256 := (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times 5 + 6$$

$$1866257 := (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times 5 + 7$$

$$1866258 := (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times 5 + 8$$

$$1866259 := (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times 5 + 9$$

$$1889540 := (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times 4 + 0$$

$$1889541 := (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times 4 + 1$$

$$1889542 := (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times 4 + 2$$

$$1889543 := (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times 4 + 3$$

$$1889544 := (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times 4 + 4$$

$$1889545 := (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times 4 + 5$$

$$1889546 := (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times 4 + 6$$

$$1889547 := (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times 4 + 7$$

$$1889548 := (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times 4 + 8$$

$$1889549 := (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times 4 + 9$$

$$2097170 := 2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^7 + 0$$

$$2097171 := 2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^7 + 1$$

$$2097172 := 2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^7 + 2$$

$$2097173 := 2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^7 + 3$$

$$2097174 := 2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^7 + 4$$

$$2097175 := 2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^7 + 5$$

$$2097176 := 2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^7 + 6$$

$$2097177 := 2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^7 + 7$$

$$2097178 := 2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^7 + 8$$

$$2097179 := 2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9$$

$$2099440 := 20 \times ((9 + 9)^4 - 4) + 0$$

$$2099441 := 20 \times ((9 + 9)^4 - 4) + 1$$

$$2099442 := 20 \times ((9 + 9)^4 - 4) + 2$$

$$2099443 := 20 \times ((9 + 9)^4 - 4) + 3$$

$$2099444 := 20 \times ((9 + 9)^4 - 4) + 4$$

$$2099445 := 20 \times ((9 + 9)^4 - 4) + 5$$

$$2099446 := 20 \times ((9 + 9)^4 - 4) + 6$$

$$2099447 := 20 \times ((9 + 9)^4 - 4) + 7$$

$$2099448 := 20 \times ((9 + 9)^4 - 4) + 8$$

$$2099449 := 20 \times ((9 + 9)^4 - 4) + 9$$

$$2358720 := (2^{3 \times 5} - 8) \times 72 + 0$$

$$2358721 := (2^{3 \times 5} - 8) \times 72 + 1$$

$$2358722 := (2^{3 \times 5} - 8) \times 72 + 2$$

$$2358723 := (2^{3 \times 5} - 8) \times 72 + 3$$

$$2358724 := (2^{3 \times 5} - 8) \times 72 + 4$$

$$2358725 := (2^{3 \times 5} - 8) \times 72 + 5$$

$$2358726 := (2^{3 \times 5} - 8) \times 72 + 6$$

$$2358727 := (2^{3 \times 5} - 8) \times 72 + 7$$

$$2358728 := (2^{3 \times 5} - 8) \times 72 + 8$$

$$2358729 := (2^{3 \times 5} - 8) \times 72 + 9$$

$$2359280 := (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 0$$

$$2359281 := (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 1$$

$$2359282 := (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 2$$

$$2359283 := (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 3$$

$$2359284 := (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 4$$

$$2359285 := (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 5$$

$$2359286 := (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 6$$

$$2359287 := (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 7$$

$$2359288 := (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 8$$

$$2359289 := (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 9$$

$$2785280 := 2^7 \times 85 \times 2^8 + 0$$

$$2785281 := 2^7 \times 85 \times 2^8 + 1$$

$$2785282 := 2^7 \times 85 \times 2^8 + 2$$

$$2785283 := 2^7 \times 85 \times 2^8 + 3$$

$$2785284 := 2^7 \times 85 \times 2^8 + 4$$

$$2785285 := 2^7 \times 85 \times 2^8 + 5$$

$$2785286 := 2^7 \times 85 \times 2^8 + 6$$

$$2785287 := 2^7 \times 85 \times 2^8 + 7$$

$$2785288 := 2^7 \times 85 \times 2^8 + 8$$

$$2785289 := 2^7 \times 85 \times 2^8 + 9$$

$$2883850 := 2 + 88 \times (3 + 8^5) + 0$$

$$2883851 := 2 + 88 \times (3 + 8^5) + 1$$

$$2883852 := 2 + 88 \times (3 + 8^5) + 2$$

$$2883853 := 2 + 88 \times (3 + 8^5) + 3$$

$$2883854 := 2 + 88 \times (3 + 8^5) + 4$$

$$2883855 := 2 + 88 \times (3 + 8^5) + 5$$

$$2883856 := 2 + 88 \times (3 + 8^5) + 6$$

$$2883857 := 2 + 88 \times (3 + 8^5) + 7$$

$$2883858 := 2 + 88 \times (3 + 8^5) + 8$$

$$2883859 := 2 + 88 \times (3 + 8^5) + 9$$

$$2952550 := 2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 \times 5 + 0$$

$$2952551 := 2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 \times 5 + 1$$

$$2952552 := 2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 \times 5 + 2$$

$$2952553 := 2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 \times 5 + 3$$

$$2952554 := 2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 \times 5 + 4$$

$$2952555 := 2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 \times 5 + 5$$

$$2952556 := 2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 \times 5 + 6$$

$$2952557 := 2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 \times 5 + 7$$

$$2952558 := 2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 \times 5 + 8$$

$$2952559 := 2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 \times 5 + 9$$

$$3484340 := 3 + 4^8 + 43^4 + 0$$

$$3484341 := 3 + 4^8 + 43^4 + 1$$

$$3484342 := 3 + 4^8 + 43^4 + 2$$

$$3484343 := 3 + 4^8 + 43^4 + 3$$

$$3484344 := 3 + 4^8 + 43^4 + 4$$

$$3484345 := 3 + 4^8 + 43^4 + 5$$

$$3484346 := 3 + 4^8 + 43^4 + 6$$

$$3484347 := 3 + 4^8 + 43^4 + 7$$

$$3484348 := 3 + 4^8 + 43^4 + 8$$

$$3484349 := 3 + 4^8 + 43^4 + 9$$

$$3515580 := (3 + 5 + 1) \times (-5 + 5^8) + 0$$

$$3515581 := (3 + 5 + 1) \times (-5 + 5^8) + 1$$

$$3515582 := (3 + 5 + 1) \times (-5 + 5^8) + 2$$

$$3515583 := (3 + 5 + 1) \times (-5 + 5^8) + 3$$

$$3515584 := (3 + 5 + 1) \times (-5 + 5^8) + 4$$

$$3515585 := (3 + 5 + 1) \times (-5 + 5^8) + 5$$

$$3515586 := (3 + 5 + 1) \times (-5 + 5^8) + 6$$

$$3515587 := (3 + 5 + 1) \times (-5 + 5^8) + 7$$

$$3515588 := (3 + 5 + 1) \times (-5 + 5^8) + 8$$

$$3515589 := (3 + 5 + 1) \times (-5 + 5^8) + 9$$

$$3729670 := (37^2 + 9^6) \times 7 + 0$$

$$3729671 := (37^2 + 9^6) \times 7 + 1$$

$$3729672 := (37^2 + 9^6) \times 7 + 2$$

$$3729673 := (37^2 + 9^6) \times 7 + 3$$

$$3729674 := (37^2 + 9^6) \times 7 + 4$$

$$3729675 := (37^2 + 9^6) \times 7 + 5$$

$$3729676 := (37^2 + 9^6) \times 7 + 6$$

$$3729677 := (37^2 + 9^6) \times 7 + 7$$

$$3729678 := (37^2 + 9^6) \times 7 + 8$$

$$3729679 := (37^2 + 9^6) \times 7 + 9$$

$$3925930 := 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 - 3 + 0$$

$$3925931 := 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 - 3 + 1$$

$$3925932 := 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 - 3 + 2$$

$$3925933 := 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 - 3 + 3$$

$$3925934 := 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 - 3 + 4$$

$$3925935 := 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 - 3 + 5$$

$$3925936 := 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 - 3 + 6$$

$$3925937 := 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 - 3 + 7$$

$$3925938 := 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 - 3 + 8$$

$$3925939 := 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 - 3 + 9$$

$$4117710 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 - 1) + 0$$

$$4117711 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 - 1) + 1$$

$$4117712 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 - 1) + 2$$

$$4117713 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 - 1) + 3$$

$$4117714 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 - 1) + 4$$

$$4117715 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 - 1) + 5$$

$$4117716 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 - 1) + 6$$

$$4117717 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 - 1) + 7$$

$$4117718 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 - 1) + 8$$

$$4117719 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 - 1) + 9$$

$$4117720 := (4 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^7 + 2) + 0$$

$$4117721 := (4 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^7 + 2) + 1$$

$$4117722 := (4 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^7 + 2) + 2$$

$$4117723 := (4 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^7 + 2) + 3$$

$$4117724 := (4 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^7 + 2) + 4$$

$$4117725 := (4 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^7 + 2) + 5$$

$$4117726 := (4 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^7 + 2) + 6$$

$$4117727 := (4 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^7 + 2) + 7$$

$$4117728 := (4 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^7 + 2) + 8$$

$$4117729 := (4 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^7 + 2) + 9$$

$$4117730 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 3) + 0$$

$$4117731 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 3) + 1$$

$$4117732 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 3) + 2$$

$$4117733 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 3) + 3$$

$$4117734 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 3) + 4$$

$$4117735 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 3) + 5$$

$$4117736 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 3) + 6$$

$$4117737 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 3) + 7$$

$$4117738 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 3) + 8$$

$$4117739 := (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 3) + 9$$

$$4117740 := (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7 + 4) + 0$$

$$4117741 := (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7 + 4) + 1$$

$$4117742 := (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7 + 4) + 2$$

$$4117743 := (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7 + 4) + 3$$

$$4117744 := (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7 + 4) + 4$$

$$4117745 := (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7 + 4) + 5$$

$$4117746 := (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7 + 4) + 6$$

$$4117747 := (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7 + 4) + 7$$

$$4117748 := (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7 + 4) + 8$$

$$4117749 := (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7 + 4) + 9$$

$$4117750 := (-4 + 11 + 7^7) \times 5 + 0$$

$$4117751 := (-4 + 11 + 7^7) \times 5 + 1$$

$$4117752 := (-4 + 11 + 7^7) \times 5 + 2$$

$$4117753 := (-4 + 11 + 7^7) \times 5 + 3$$

$$4117754 := (-4 + 11 + 7^7) \times 5 + 4$$

$$4117755 := (-4 + 11 + 7^7) \times 5 + 5$$

$$4117756 := (-4 + 11 + 7^7) \times 5 + 6$$

$$4117757 := (-4 + 11 + 7^7) \times 5 + 7$$

$$4117758 := (-4 + 11 + 7^7) \times 5 + 8$$

$$4117759 := (-4 + 11 + 7^7) \times 5 + 9$$

$$4135260 := 41^3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 6 + 0$$

$$4135261 := 41^3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 6 + 1$$

$$4135262 := 41^3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 6 + 2$$

$$4135263 := 41^3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 6 + 3$$

$$4135264 := 41^3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 6 + 4$$

$$4135265 := 41^3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 6 + 5$$

$$4135266 := 41^3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 6 + 6$$

$$4135267 := 41^3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 6 + 7$$

$$4135268 := 41^3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 6 + 8$$

$$4135269 := 41^3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 6 + 9$$

$$4194140 := (4^{1+9} - 41) \times 4 + 0$$

$$4194141 := (4^{1+9} - 41) \times 4 + 1$$

$$4194142 := (4^{1+9} - 41) \times 4 + 2$$

$$4194143 := (4^{1+9} - 41) \times 4 + 3$$

$$4194144 := (4^{1+9} - 41) \times 4 + 4$$

$$4194145 := (4^{1+9} - 41) \times 4 + 5$$

$$4194146 := (4^{1+9} - 41) \times 4 + 6$$

$$4194147 := (4^{1+9} - 41) \times 4 + 7$$

$$4194148 := (4^{1+9} - 41) \times 4 + 8$$

$$4194149 := (4^{1+9} - 41) \times 4 + 9$$

$$4194240 := ((4 \times 1)^9 - 4) \times 2^4 + 0$$

$$4194241 := ((4 \times 1)^9 - 4) \times 2^4 + 1$$

$$4194242 := ((4 \times 1)^9 - 4) \times 2^4 + 2$$

$$4194243 := ((4 \times 1)^9 - 4) \times 2^4 + 3$$

$$4194244 := ((4 \times 1)^9 - 4) \times 2^4 + 4$$

$$4194245 := ((4 \times 1)^9 - 4) \times 2^4 + 5$$

$$4194246 := ((4 \times 1)^9 - 4) \times 2^4 + 6$$

$$4194247 := ((4 \times 1)^9 - 4) \times 2^4 + 7$$

$$4194248 := ((4 \times 1)^9 - 4) \times 2^4 + 8$$

$$4194249 := ((4 \times 1)^9 - 4) \times 2^4 + 9$$

$$4194290 := -4 - 1 - 9 + 4^{2+9} + 0$$

$$4194291 := -4 - 1 - 9 + 4^{2+9} + 1$$

$$4194292 := -4 - 1 - 9 + 4^{2+9} + 2$$

$$4194293 := -4 - 1 - 9 + 4^{2+9} + 3$$

$$4194294 := -4 - 1 - 9 + 4^{2+9} + 4$$

$$4194295 := -4 - 1 - 9 + 4^{2+9} + 5$$

$$4194296 := -4 - 1 - 9 + 4^{2+9} + 6$$

$$4194297 := -4 - 1 - 9 + 4^{2+9} + 7$$

$$4194298 := -4 - 1 - 9 + 4^{2+9} + 8$$

$$4194299 := -4 - 1 - 9 + 4^{2+9} + 9$$

$$4194380 := 4 \times 19 + 4^{3+8} + 0$$

$$4194381 := 4 \times 19 + 4^{3+8} + 1$$

$$4194382 := 4 \times 19 + 4^{3+8} + 2$$

$$4194383 := 4 \times 19 + 4^{3+8} + 3$$

$$4194384 := 4 \times 19 + 4^{3+8} + 4$$

$$4194385 := 4 \times 19 + 4^{3+8} + 5$$

$$4194386 := 4 \times 19 + 4^{3+8} + 6$$

$$4194387 := 4 \times 19 + 4^{3+8} + 7$$

$$4194388 := 4 \times 19 + 4^{3+8} + 8$$

$$4194389 := 4 \times 19 + 4^{3+8} + 9$$

$$4644860 := -4 + (6 \times 4)^4 \times (8 + 6) + 0$$

$$4644861 := -4 + (6 \times 4)^4 \times (8 + 6) + 1$$

$$4644862 := -4 + (6 \times 4)^4 \times (8 + 6) + 2$$

$$4644863 := -4 + (6 \times 4)^4 \times (8 + 6) + 3$$

$$4644864 := -4 + (6 \times 4)^4 \times (8 + 6) + 4$$

$$4644865 := -4 + (6 \times 4)^4 \times (8 + 6) + 5$$

$$4644866 := -4 + (6 \times 4)^4 \times (8 + 6) + 6$$

$$4644867 := -4 + (6 \times 4)^4 \times (8 + 6) + 7$$

$$4644868 := -4 + (6 \times 4)^4 \times (8 + 6) + 8$$

$$4644869 := -4 + (6 \times 4)^4 \times (8 + 6) + 9$$

$$4665200 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 20 + 0$$

$$4665201 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 20 + 1$$

$$4665202 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 20 + 2$$

$$4665203 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 20 + 3$$

$$4665204 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 20 + 4$$

$$4665205 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 20 + 5$$

$$4665206 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 20 + 6$$

$$4665207 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 20 + 7$$

$$4665208 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 20 + 8$$

$$4665209 := (-4 + 6^6) \times 5 \times 20 + 9$$

$$4665600 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 60 + 0$$

$$4665601 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 60 + 1$$

$$4665602 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 60 + 2$$

$$4665603 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 60 + 3$$

$$4665604 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 60 + 4$$

$$4665605 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 60 + 5$$

$$4665606 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 60 + 6$$

$$4665607 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 60 + 7$$

$$4665608 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 60 + 8$$

$$4665609 := (4 + 6) \times 6^5 \times 60 + 9$$

$$4782970 := 4 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 9^7 + 0$$

$$4782971 := 4 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 9^7 + 1$$

$$4782972 := 4 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 9^7 + 2$$

$$4782973 := 4 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 9^7 + 3$$

$$4782974 := 4 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 9^7 + 4$$

$$4782975 := 4 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 9^7 + 5$$

$$4782976 := 4 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 9^7 + 6$$

$$4782977 := 4 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 9^7 + 7$$

$$4782978 := 4 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 9^7 + 8$$

$$4782979 := 4 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 9^7 + 9$$

$$5242850 := 5 \times (-2 - 4 + (2 \times 8)^5) + 0$$

$$5242851 := 5 \times (-2 - 4 + (2 \times 8)^5) + 1$$

$$5242852 := 5 \times (-2 - 4 + (2 \times 8)^5) + 2$$

$$5242853 := 5 \times (-2 - 4 + (2 \times 8)^5) + 3$$

$$5242854 := 5 \times (-2 - 4 + (2 \times 8)^5) + 4$$

$$5242855 := 5 \times (-2 - 4 + (2 \times 8)^5) + 5$$

$$5242856 := 5 \times (-2 - 4 + (2 \times 8)^5) + 6$$

$$\begin{aligned}5242857 &:= 5 \times (-2 - 4 + (2 \times 8)^5) + 7 \\5242858 &:= 5 \times (-2 - 4 + (2 \times 8)^5) + 8 \\5242859 &:= 5 \times (-2 - 4 + (2 \times 8)^5) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5242860 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 6) + 0 \\5242861 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 6) + 1 \\5242862 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 6) + 2 \\5242863 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 6) + 3 \\5242864 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 6) + 4 \\5242865 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 6) + 5 \\5242866 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 6) + 6 \\5242867 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 6) + 7 \\5242868 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 6) + 8 \\5242869 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 6) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5242880 &:= 5 \times 2^{4^2} \times (8 + 8) + 0 \\5242881 &:= 5 \times 2^{4^2} \times (8 + 8) + 1 \\5242882 &:= 5 \times 2^{4^2} \times (8 + 8) + 2 \\5242883 &:= 5 \times 2^{4^2} \times (8 + 8) + 3 \\5242884 &:= 5 \times 2^{4^2} \times (8 + 8) + 4 \\5242885 &:= 5 \times 2^{4^2} \times (8 + 8) + 5 \\5242886 &:= 5 \times 2^{4^2} \times (8 + 8) + 6 \\5242887 &:= 5 \times 2^{4^2} \times (8 + 8) + 7 \\5242888 &:= 5 \times 2^{4^2} \times (8 + 8) + 8 \\5242889 &:= 5 \times 2^{4^2} \times (8 + 8) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5625720 &:= (5^6 + 2) \times 5 \times 72 + 0 \\5625721 &:= (5^6 + 2) \times 5 \times 72 + 1 \\5625722 &:= (5^6 + 2) \times 5 \times 72 + 2 \\5625723 &:= (5^6 + 2) \times 5 \times 72 + 3 \\5625724 &:= (5^6 + 2) \times 5 \times 72 + 4 \\5625725 &:= (5^6 + 2) \times 5 \times 72 + 5 \\5625726 &:= (5^6 + 2) \times 5 \times 72 + 6 \\5625727 &:= (5^6 + 2) \times 5 \times 72 + 7 \\5625728 &:= (5^6 + 2) \times 5 \times 72 + 8 \\5625729 &:= (5^6 + 2) \times 5 \times 72 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5667630 &:= ((5 + 6)^6 + 7^6) \times 3 + 0 \\5667631 &:= ((5 + 6)^6 + 7^6) \times 3 + 1 \\5667632 &:= ((5 + 6)^6 + 7^6) \times 3 + 2 \\5667633 &:= ((5 + 6)^6 + 7^6) \times 3 + 3 \\5667634 &:= ((5 + 6)^6 + 7^6) \times 3 + 4 \\5667635 &:= ((5 + 6)^6 + 7^6) \times 3 + 5 \\5667636 &:= ((5 + 6)^6 + 7^6) \times 3 + 6 \\5667637 &:= ((5 + 6)^6 + 7^6) \times 3 + 7 \\5667638 &:= ((5 + 6)^6 + 7^6) \times 3 + 8 \\5667639 &:= ((5 + 6)^6 + 7^6) \times 3 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5781250 &:= 5^7 \times (81 - 2 - 5) + 0 \\5781251 &:= 5^7 \times (81 - 2 - 5) + 1 \\5781252 &:= 5^7 \times (81 - 2 - 5) + 2 \\5781253 &:= 5^7 \times (81 - 2 - 5) + 3 \\5781254 &:= 5^7 \times (81 - 2 - 5) + 4 \\5781255 &:= 5^7 \times (81 - 2 - 5) + 5 \\5781256 &:= 5^7 \times (81 - 2 - 5) + 6 \\5781257 &:= 5^7 \times (81 - 2 - 5) + 7 \\5781258 &:= 5^7 \times (81 - 2 - 5) + 8 \\5781259 &:= 5^7 \times (81 - 2 - 5) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6718140 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81) \times 4 + 0 \\6718141 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81) \times 4 + 1 \\6718142 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81) \times 4 + 2 \\6718143 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81) \times 4 + 3 \\6718144 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81) \times 4 + 4 \\6718145 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81) \times 4 + 5 \\6718146 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81) \times 4 + 6 \\6718147 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81) \times 4 + 7 \\6718148 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81) \times 4 + 8 \\6718149 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81) \times 4 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6718440 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times (8 + 4 \times 4) + 0 \\6718441 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times (8 + 4 \times 4) + 1 \\6718442 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times (8 + 4 \times 4) + 2 \\6718443 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times (8 + 4 \times 4) + 3 \\6718444 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times (8 + 4 \times 4) + 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6718445 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times (8 + 4 \times 4) + 5 \\6718446 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times (8 + 4 \times 4) + 6 \\6718447 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times (8 + 4 \times 4) + 7 \\6718448 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times (8 + 4 \times 4) + 8 \\6718449 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times (8 + 4 \times 4) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6718480 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 8 + 0 \\6718481 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 8 + 1 \\6718482 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 8 + 2 \\6718483 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 8 + 3 \\6718484 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 8 + 4 \\6718485 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 8 + 5 \\6718486 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 8 + 6 \\6718487 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 8 + 7 \\6718488 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 8 + 8 \\6718489 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 8 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6765140 &:= -67 + 6 + 51^4 + 0 \\6765141 &:= -67 + 6 + 51^4 + 1 \\6765142 &:= -67 + 6 + 51^4 + 2 \\6765143 &:= -67 + 6 + 51^4 + 3 \\6765144 &:= -67 + 6 + 51^4 + 4 \\6765145 &:= -67 + 6 + 51^4 + 5 \\6765146 &:= -67 + 6 + 51^4 + 6 \\6765147 &:= -67 + 6 + 51^4 + 7 \\6765148 &:= -67 + 6 + 51^4 + 8 \\6765149 &:= -67 + 6 + 51^4 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7529560 &:= (7 + 5) \times 2 + (9 + 5)^6 + 0 \\7529561 &:= (7 + 5) \times 2 + (9 + 5)^6 + 1 \\7529562 &:= (7 + 5) \times 2 + (9 + 5)^6 + 2 \\7529563 &:= (7 + 5) \times 2 + (9 + 5)^6 + 3 \\7529564 &:= (7 + 5) \times 2 + (9 + 5)^6 + 4 \\7529565 &:= (7 + 5) \times 2 + (9 + 5)^6 + 5 \\7529566 &:= (7 + 5) \times 2 + (9 + 5)^6 + 6 \\7529567 &:= (7 + 5) \times 2 + (9 + 5)^6 + 7 \\7529568 &:= (7 + 5) \times 2 + (9 + 5)^6 + 8\end{aligned}$$

$$7529569 := (7 + 5) \times 2 + (9 + 5)^6 + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}7864320 &:= (7 + 8) \times 64^3 \times 2 + 0 \\7864321 &:= (7 + 8) \times 64^3 \times 2 + 1 \\7864322 &:= (7 + 8) \times 64^3 \times 2 + 2 \\7864323 &:= (7 + 8) \times 64^3 \times 2 + 3 \\7864324 &:= (7 + 8) \times 64^3 \times 2 + 4 \\7864325 &:= (7 + 8) \times 64^3 \times 2 + 5 \\7864326 &:= (7 + 8) \times 64^3 \times 2 + 6 \\7864327 &:= (7 + 8) \times 64^3 \times 2 + 7 \\7864328 &:= (7 + 8) \times 64^3 \times 2 + 8 \\7864329 &:= (7 + 8) \times 64^3 \times 2 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7864650 &:= (7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 \times 5 + 0 \\7864651 &:= (7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 \times 5 + 1 \\7864652 &:= (7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 \times 5 + 2 \\7864653 &:= (7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 \times 5 + 3 \\7864654 &:= (7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 \times 5 + 4 \\7864655 &:= (7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 \times 5 + 5 \\7864656 &:= (7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 \times 5 + 6 \\7864657 &:= (7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 \times 5 + 7 \\7864658 &:= (7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 \times 5 + 8 \\7864659 &:= (7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 \times 5 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8066448 &:= (806 \times (((6 + 4)^4) + 8)) \\8067520 &:= 80 \times (6 \times 7^5 + 2) + 0 \\8067521 &:= 80 \times (6 \times 7^5 + 2) + 1 \\8067522 &:= 80 \times (6 \times 7^5 + 2) + 2 \\8067523 &:= 80 \times (6 \times 7^5 + 2) + 3 \\8067524 &:= 80 \times (6 \times 7^5 + 2) + 4 \\8067525 &:= 80 \times (6 \times 7^5 + 2) + 5 \\8067526 &:= 80 \times (6 \times 7^5 + 2) + 6 \\8067527 &:= 80 \times (6 \times 7^5 + 2) + 7 \\8067528 &:= 80 \times (6 \times 7^5 + 2) + 8 \\8067529 &:= 80 \times (6 \times 7^5 + 2) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8388560 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 6) + 0 \\8388561 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 6) + 1 \\8388562 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 6) + 2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8388563 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 6) + 3 \\8388564 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 6) + 4 \\8388565 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 6) + 5 \\8388566 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 6) + 6 \\8388567 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 6) + 7 \\8388568 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 6) + 8 \\8388569 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 6) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8388600 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 00 \\8388601 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 01 \\8388602 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 02 \\8388603 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 03 \\8388604 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 04 \\8388605 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 05 \\8388606 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 06 \\8388607 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 07 \\8388608 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 08 \\8388609 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 09 \\8388610 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 10 \\8388611 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 11 \\8388612 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 12 \\8388613 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 13 \\8388614 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 14 \\8388615 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 15 \\8388616 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 16 \\8388617 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 17 \\8388618 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 18 \\8388619 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 19 \\8388620 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 20 \\8388621 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 21 \\8388622 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 22 \\8388623 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 23 \\8388624 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 24 \\8388625 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 25 \\8388626 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 26 \\8388627 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 27 \\8388628 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 28\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8388629 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 29 \\8388630 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 30 \\8388631 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 31 \\8388632 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 32 \\8388633 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 33 \\8388634 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 34 \\8388635 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 35 \\8388636 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 36 \\8388637 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 37 \\8388638 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 38 \\8388639 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 39 \\8388640 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 40 \\8388641 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 41 \\8388642 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 42 \\8388643 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 43 \\8388644 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 44 \\8388645 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 45 \\8388646 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 46 \\8388647 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 47 \\8388648 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 48 \\8388649 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 49 \\8388650 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 50 \\8388651 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 51 \\8388652 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 52 \\8388653 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 53 \\8388654 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 54 \\8388655 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 55 \\8388656 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 56 \\8388657 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 57 \\8388658 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 58 \\8388659 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 59 \\8388660 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 60 \\8388661 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 61 \\8388662 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 62 \\8388663 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 63 \\8388664 &:= -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 64\end{aligned}$$

$$8388665 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 65$$

$$8388666 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 66$$

$$8388667 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 67$$

$$8388668 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 68$$

$$8388669 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 69$$

$$8388670 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 70$$

$$8388671 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 71$$

$$8388672 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 72$$

$$8388673 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 73$$

$$8388674 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 74$$

$$8388675 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 75$$

$$8388676 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 76$$

$$8388677 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 77$$

$$8388678 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 78$$

$$8388679 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 79$$

$$8388680 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 80$$

$$8388681 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 81$$

$$8388682 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 82$$

$$8388683 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 83$$

$$8388684 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 84$$

$$8388685 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 85$$

$$8388686 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 86$$

$$8388687 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 87$$

$$8388688 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 88$$

$$8388689 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 89$$

$$8388690 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 90$$

$$8388691 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 91$$

$$8388692 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 92$$

$$8388693 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 93$$

$$8388694 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 94$$

$$8388695 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 95$$

$$8388696 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 96$$

$$8388697 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 97$$

$$8388698 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 98$$

$$8388699 := -8 + 3 \times 8^8 / 6 + 99$$

$$8389120 := 8^3 + 8^{9-1} / 2 + 0$$

$$8389121 := 8^3 + 8^{9-1} / 2 + 1$$

$$8389122 := 8^3 + 8^{9-1} / 2 + 2$$

$$8389123 := 8^3 + 8^{9-1} / 2 + 3$$

$$8389124 := 8^3 + 8^{9-1} / 2 + 4$$

$$8389125 := 8^3 + 8^{9-1} / 2 + 5$$

$$8389126 := 8^3 + 8^{9-1} / 2 + 6$$

$$8389127 := 8^3 + 8^{9-1} / 2 + 7$$

$$8389128 := 8^3 + 8^{9-1} / 2 + 8$$

$$8389129 := 8^3 + 8^{9-1} / 2 + 9$$

$$8454240 := 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 4) + 0$$

$$8454241 := 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 4) + 1$$

$$8454242 := 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 4) + 2$$

$$8454243 := 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 4) + 3$$

$$8454244 := 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 4) + 4$$

$$8454245 := 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 4) + 5$$

$$8454246 := 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 4) + 6$$

$$8454247 := 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 4) + 7$$

$$8454248 := 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 4) + 8$$

$$8454249 := 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 4) + 9$$

$$8454280 := 8 + (4^5 + 4)^2 \times 8 + 0$$

$$8454281 := 8 + (4^5 + 4)^2 \times 8 + 1$$

$$8454282 := 8 + (4^5 + 4)^2 \times 8 + 2$$

$$8454283 := 8 + (4^5 + 4)^2 \times 8 + 3$$

$$8454284 := 8 + (4^5 + 4)^2 \times 8 + 4$$

$$8454285 := 8 + (4^5 + 4)^2 \times 8 + 5$$

$$8454286 := 8 + (4^5 + 4)^2 \times 8 + 6$$

$$8454287 := 8 + (4^5 + 4)^2 \times 8 + 7$$

$$8454288 := 8 + (4^5 + 4)^2 \times 8 + 8$$

$$8454289 := 8 + (4^5 + 4)^2 \times 8 + 9$$

$$9436860 := 9 \times 4 \times (-3 - 6 + 8^6) + 0$$

$$9436861 := 9 \times 4 \times (-3 - 6 + 8^6) + 1$$

$$9436862 := 9 \times 4 \times (-3 - 6 + 8^6) + 2$$

$$9436863 := 9 \times 4 \times (-3 - 6 + 8^6) + 3$$

$$9436864 := 9 \times 4 \times (-3 - 6 + 8^6) + 4$$

$$9436865 := 9 \times 4 \times (-3 - 6 + 8^6) + 5$$

$$9436866 := 9 \times 4 \times (-3 - 6 + 8^6) + 6$$

$$9436867 := 9 \times 4 \times (-3 - 6 + 8^6) + 7$$

$$9436868 := 9 \times 4 \times (-3 - 6 + 8^6) + 8$$

$$9436869 := 9 \times 4 \times (-3 - 6 + 8^6) + 9$$

$$9437220 := 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 + 2) + 0$$

$$9437221 := 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 + 2) + 1$$

$$9437222 := 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 + 2) + 2$$

$$9437223 := 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 + 2) + 3$$

$$9437224 := 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 + 2) + 4$$

$$9437225 := 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 + 2) + 5$$

$$9437226 := 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 + 2) + 6$$

$$9437227 := 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 + 2) + 7$$

$$9437228 := 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 + 2) + 8$$

$$9437229 := 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 + 2) + 9$$

$$9437440 := 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4^4 + 0$$

$$9437441 := 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4^4 + 1$$

$$9437442 := 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4^4 + 2$$

$$9437443 := 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4^4 + 3$$

$$9437444 := 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4^4 + 4$$

$$9437445 := 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4^4 + 5$$

$$9437446 := 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4^4 + 6$$

$$9437447 := 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4^4 + 7$$

$$9437448 := 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4^4 + 8$$

$$9437449 := 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4^4 + 9$$

2.3 General Representations

Below are selfie numbers in a general way. The appearing in above two subsections 2.1 and 2.2 are excluded from the list below.

$$127 := -1 + 2^7$$

$$343 := (3 + 4)^3$$

$$736 := 7 + 3^6$$

$$1285 := (1 + 2^8) \times 5$$

$$2187 := (2 + 1^8)^7$$

$$2502 := 2 + 50^2$$

$$2737 := (2 \times 7)^3 - 7$$

$$3125 := (3 \times 1 + 2)^5$$

$$3685 := (3^6 + 8) \times 5$$

$$3864 := 3 \times (-8 + 6^4)$$

$$3972 := 3 + (9 \times 7)^2$$

$$4096 := 4^{0 \times 9 + 6}$$

$$6455 := (6^4 - 5) \times 5$$

$$11264 := 11 \times 2^{6+4}$$

$$11664 := (1 - 1 + 6)^6 / 4$$

$$12850 := (1 + 2^8) \times 50$$

$$13825 := 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5}$$

$$14641 := (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1$$

$$15552 := (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2$$

$$15585 := (1 \times 5^5 - 8) \times 5$$

$$15612 := -1 + 5^6 + 12$$

$$15613 := 1 + 5^6 - 13$$

$$15617 := 1 \times 5^6 - 1 - 7$$

$$15618 := 1 \times 5^6 + 1 - 8$$

$$15621 := -1 + 5^6 + 2 - 1$$

$$15622 := 1 + 5^6 - 2 - 2$$

$$15623 := -1 + 5^6 + 2 - 3$$

$$15624 := 1 + 5^6 + 2 - 4$$

$$15626 := 1 + 5^{6 \times 2 - 6}$$

$$15632 := 1 + 5^6 + 3 \times 2$$

$$15633 := -1 + 5^6 + 3 \times 3$$

$$15642 := 1 + 5^6 + 4^2$$

$$15645 := 1 \times 5^6 + 4 \times 5$$

$$15655 := 1 \times 5 \times (6 + 5^5)$$

$$15656 := 1 + 5^6 + 5 \times 6$$

$$15662 := 1 + 5^6 + 6^2$$

$$15667 := 1 \times 5^6 + 6 \times 7$$

$$15688 := -1 + 5^6 + 8 \times 8$$

$$15698 := 1 + 5^6 + 9 \times 8$$

$$16377 := (1^6 + 3)^7 - 7$$

$$16384 := (1^6 + 3)^8 / 4$$

$$16447 := -1 + 64 + 4^7$$

$$16875 := 1 \times 68 + 7^5$$

$$17536 := 1 \times 7^5 + 3^6$$

$$18432 := 18 \times 4^{3+2}$$

$$19453 := 19 \times 4^5 - 3$$

$$19683 := (1 \times 9 - 6)^8 \times 3$$

$$19739 := (-1 + 9) \times 7 + 3^9$$

$$24546 := (2 + 4) \times (-5 + 4^6)$$

$$24576 := (-2 + 4)^{5+7} \times 6$$

$$27639 := 2^7 \times 6^3 - 9$$

$$28224 := (2 + 82)^2 \times 4$$

$$28559 := -2 + (8 + 5)^{-5+9}$$

$$29282 := 2 \times (9 + 2)^{8/2}$$

$$29524 := (2 \times 9^5 - 2) / 4$$

$$32759 := (3 - 2 + 7)^5 - 9$$

$$32765 := -3 + (2 \times 7 - 6)^5$$

$$32768 := (3 - 2 + 7)^6 / 8$$

$$32771 := 3 + 2^{7+7+1}$$

$$32785 := 3 + 2 \times 7 + 8^5$$

$$36850 := (3^6 + 8) \times 50$$

$$37179 := 3^7 \times (1 + 7 + 9)$$

$$38856 := (3^8 - 85) \times 6$$

$$39283 := 3^9 \times 2 - 83$$

$$39342 := (3^9 - 3 \times 4) \times 2$$

$$39343 := 39 + 34^3$$

$$39358 := 3^9 \times (-3 + 5) - 8$$

$$39363 := 3^9 / 3 \times 6 - 3$$

$$39366 := 3^9 \times (3 - 6/6)$$

$$39369 := 3 + 9^3 \times 6 \times 9$$

$$39372 := (3 + 9 \times 3^7) \times 2$$

$$39382 := ((3 \times 9)^3 + 8) \times 2$$

$$43775 := (4 \times 3^7 + 7) \times 5$$

$$45632 := -4^5 + 6^{3 \times 2}$$

$$45927 := ((4 + 5) \times 9)^2 \times 7$$

$$45947 := 4 \times 5 + 9^4 \times 7$$

$$46626 := -4 + 6^6 - 26$$

$$46630 := 4 + 6^6 - 30$$

$$46632 := -4 \times 6 + 6^{3 \times 2}$$

$$46633 := 4 + 6^6 - 3^3$$

$$46644 := 4 + 6^6 - 4 \times 4$$

$$46648 := 4 + 6^6 - 4 - 8$$

$$46651 := -4 + 6 \times 6^5 - 1$$

$$46652 := -4 + (6 \times 6)^{5-2}$$

$$46655 := 4 + 6 \times 6^5 - 5$$

$$46656 := ((4 \times 6 + 6) / 5)^6$$

$$46660 := 4 + 6^6 + 6 \times 0$$

$$46663 := 4 + 6^6 + 6 - 3$$

$$46673 := -4 + 6^6 + 7 \times 3$$

$$46684 := -4 + 6^6 + 8 \times 4$$

$$46688 := (4 + 6^6 / 8) \times 8$$

$$52488 := (5 + 2 - 4)^8 \times 8$$

$$59052 := 5 + 9^{05} - 2$$

$$63945 := 63 \times (-9 + 4^5)$$

$$64550 := (6^4 - 5) \times 50$$

$$65471 := -65 + 4^{7+1}$$

$$66339 := (6 \times 6)^3 + 3^9$$

$$67234 := 6 + 7^{2+3} \times 4$$

$$69984 := 6^{-9/9+8} / 4$$

$$98415 := 9^{8-4} \times 15$$

$$103823 := (-1 + (03 \times 8) \times 2)^3$$

$$114244 := (1 + 14 - 2)^4 \times 4$$

$$116565 := (1 - 16) \times (5 - 6^5)$$

$$117128 := 11^{(7+1)/2} \times 8$$

$$117396 := (-117 + 3^9) \times 6$$

$$117476 := 1 - 174 + 7^6$$

$$117571 := (-11 + 7^5) \times 7 + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} 117576 &:= 1 + 1 - 75 + 7^6 \\ 117587 &:= 1 + (-1 + 7^5 - 8) \times 7 \\ 117597 &:= 11 + (7^5 - 9) \times 7 \\ 117619 &:= -11 + 7^6 - 19 \\ 117624 &:= -1 + 1 \times 7^6 + 24 \\ 117625 &:= 1 + 1 \times 7^6 - 25 \\ 117626 &:= -11 + 7^6 - 2 \times 6 \\ 117628 &:= -11 + 7^6 - 2 - 8 \\ 117629 &:= -1 - 1 + 7^6 - 2 \times 9 \\ 117630 &:= 11 + 7^6 - 30 \\ 117632 &:= -11 + 7^6 - 3 \times 2 \\ 117633 &:= 11 + 7^6 - 3^3 \\ 117635 &:= 1 + 1 \times 7^6 - 3 \times 5 \\ 117637 &:= -1 - 1 + 7^6 - 3 - 7 \\ 117638 &:= (1 - 1 + 7)^6 - 3 - 8 \\ 117639 &:= 1 + 1 + 7^6 - 3 - 9 \\ 117641 &:= -11 + 7^6 + 4 - 1 \\ 117642 &:= 1 + 1 \times 7^6 - 4 \times 2 \\ 117643 &:= 1 + 1 \times 7^6 - 4 - 3 \\ 117644 &:= 11 + 7^6 - 4 \times 4 \\ 117646 &:= -1 + 1 \times 7^6 + 4 - 6 \\ 117647 &:= 1 + 1 \times 7^6 + 4 - 7 \\ 117648 &:= 11 + 7^6 - 4 - 8 \\ 117650 &:= 1 + 1 \times 7^6 + 5 \times 0 \\ 117651 &:= -1 - 1 + 7^6 + 5 - 1 \\ 117652 &:= (1 - 1 + 7)^6 + 5 - 2 \\ 117653 &:= 1 + 1 + 7^6 + 5 - 3 \\ 117655 &:= (1 + (1 + 7^6)/5) \times 5 \\ 117660 &:= 11 + 7^6 + 6 \times 0 \\ 117662 &:= 1 + 1 \times 7^6 + 6 \times 2 \\ 117663 &:= 11 + 7^6 + 6 - 3 \\ 117686 &:= -11 + 7^6 + 8 \times 6 \\ 117695 &:= 1 + 1 \times 7^6 + 9 \times 5 \\ 117763 &:= 117 + 7^6 - 3 \\ 117777 &:= (1 + 1)^7 + 7^7 / 7 \\ 118328 &:= (1 + (-1 + 8)^3)^2 - 8 \\ 124386 &:= (12^4 + 3 - 8) \times 6 \\ 124416 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 4)^4 \times 1 \times 6 \\ 125003 &:= 1 + 2 + 50^{03} \\ 125012 &:= 12 + 50^{1+2} \\ 128500 &:= (1 + 2^8) \times 500 \\ 129283 &:= (-1 + 2^9) \times (2^8 - 3) \\ 131071 &:= (-1 + 3)^{10+7} - 1 \\ 131072 &:= (1 + 3)^{1+07} \times 2 \\ 134456 &:= (1 \times 3 + 4)^4 \times 56 \\ 136162 &:= 1 + (3 + 61 \times 6)^2 \\ 137718 &:= (-1 + 3^7) \times (71 - 8) \\ 137772 &:= (-1 + 3^7 \times 7) \times (7 + 2) \\ 137781 &:= 1 \times 3^7 \times 7 \times (8 + 1) \\ 137839 &:= -1 + 3 + 7 \times (8 + 3^9) \\ 137948 &:= -1 + 3 \times 7 \times (9^4 + 8) \\ 139965 &:= -1 \times 3 + (9 + 9) \times 6^5 \\ 139966 &:= 1 - 3 \times (9/9 - 6^6) \\ 146410 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 10 \\ 146461 &:= (1^4 + 6)^4 \times 61 \\ 147249 &:= (1 + 4^7 - 24) \times 9 \\ 147349 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 3 \times 4) \times 9 \\ 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4 \times 1) \times 9 \\ 147429 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4 + 2) \times 9 \\ 147447 &:= (-1 + 4^7) \times (4 \times 4 - 7) \\ 147453 &:= 1 \times 4^7 \times (4 + 5) - 3 \\ 147455 &:= -1 + 4^7 \times 45/5 \\ 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 \\ 147519 &:= (1 + 4^7 + 5 + 1) \times 9 \\ 155520 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 20 \\ 155850 &:= 1 \times (5^5 - 8) \times 50 \\ 156225 &:= (-1 + (5^6 - 2) \times 2) \times 5 \\ 156235 &:= 1 \times (5^6 \times 2 - 3) \times 5 \\ 156245 &:= (-1 + 5^6 \times (-2 + 4)) \times 5 \\ 156249 &:= -1 + 5^6 \times 2 \times (-4 + 9) \\ 156275 &:= ((-1 + 5^6) \times 2 + 7) \times 5 \\ 156285 &:= (-1 + 5^6 \times 2 + 8) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 156295 &:= (1 \times 5^6 \times 2 + 9) \times 5 \\ 157463 &:= -1 + ((5 + 7) \times 4 + 6)^3 \\ 158466 &:= (15 - 8)^4 \times 66 \\ 161051 &:= (1^6 + 10)^5 \times 1 \\ 163835 &:= (-1 + (-6 + 38)^3) \times 5 \\ 163855 &:= (1^6 \times 3 + 8^5) \times 5 \\ 163875 &:= (16^3 \times 8 + 7) \times 5 \\ 167286 &:= (167^2 - 8) \times 6 \\ 175232 &:= (-1 + 75)^2 \times 32 \\ 175274 &:= 1 + (75 - 2) \times 7^4 \\ 176466 &:= (-1 + 7^6) / 4 \times 6 - 6 \\ 176472 &:= (1 - 7^6) \times (4 - 7) / 2 \\ 177147 &:= (1 + 7 / 7 + 1)^{4+7} \\ 182476 &:= (1 + 8 - 2)^4 \times 76 \\ 184275 &:= (-1 + 8^4) \times (2 + 7) \times 5 \\ 184325 &:= (1 + 8^4 \times 3^2) \times 5 \\ 184329 &:= (1 + 8^4) \times (3 + 2) \times 9 \\ 184335 &:= (1 + 8^4 \times 3) \times (3 \times 5) \\ 184365 &:= (1 + 8^4) \times (3 + 6) \times 5 \\ 184495 &:= (-1 + (8^4 + 4) \times 9) \times 5 \\ 184545 &:= (1 \times 8^4 + 5) \times 45 \\ 184877 &:= (-1 + 8)^{-4+8} \times 77 \\ 185193 &:= ((1 \times 8 - 5) \times 19)^3 \\ 186615 &:= -1 - 8 + 6^6 \times (-1 + 5) \\ 186622 &:= 1 \times 8 \times 6^6 / 2 - 2 \\ 186624 &:= 1 \times 8 + (6^6 - 2) \times 4 \\ 186631 &:= -1 + 8 + 6^6 \times (3 + 1) \\ 186641 &:= 18 + 6^6 \times 4 - 1 \\ 186642 &:= (1 + 8) \times ((6 + 6)^4 + 2) \\ 186644 &:= (1 + 8 + 6^6 - 4) \times 4 \\ 186646 &:= (-1 + 8 + 6^6) \times 4 + 6 \\ 186648 &:= (1 \times 8 + 6^6) \times 4 - 8 \\ 186684 &:= (-1 + 8 + 6^6 + 8) \times 4 \\ 187278 &:= ((-1 + 8) \times 7)^2 \times 78 \\ 196608 &:= (-1 + 9)^6 \times 6 / 08 \\ 196830 &:= (1 \times 9 - 6)^8 \times 30 \\ 209944 &:= 2 \times ((09 + 9)^4 - 4) \\ 209946 &:= 2 \times (09 + 9)^4 - 6 \\ 209952 &:= (2 \times 09)^{9-5} \times 2 \\ 210125 &:= (2^{10} + 1)^2 / 5 \\ 216003 &:= 2 + 1 + 60^{03} \\ 216021 &:= 21 + 60^{2+1} \\ 218491 &:= (-2 + 1 + 8)^4 \times 91 \\ 227529 &:= (22 \times 7 + 5)^2 \times 9 \\ 229373 &:= 2^{2 \times 9 - 3} \times 7 - 3 \\ 229378 &:= 2 + 2^{9+3} \times 7 \times 8 \\ 232324 &:= (-2 + 3^{2+3})^2 \times 4 \\ 233255 &:= ((2 \times 3)^{3 \times 2} - 5) \times 5 \\ 234224 &:= 2 - 34 + 22^4 \\ 234248 &:= ((2 + 3) \times 4 + 2)^4 - 8 \\ 234254 &:= -2 + (34 / 2 + 5)^4 \\ 234264 &:= 2^3 + (4^2 + 6)^4 \\ 234375 &:= (2 + 3)^4 \times 375 \\ 234377 &:= 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 3 - 7)^7 \\ 235296 &:= -2 + (-3 + 5) \times (-2 + 9)^6 \\ 235768 &:= 2 \times (3^5 + 7^6 - 8) \\ 236194 &:= -2 + 36 \times 1 \times 9^4 \\ 236196 &:= 2 \times 3^{6+1} \times 9 \times 6 \\ 236764 &:= 2 \times (3^6 + 7^6 + 4) \\ 238648 &:= 23 \times (8 + 6^4 \times 8) \\ 245760 &:= (-2 + 4)^{5+7} \times 60 \\ 247167 &:= -2 \times 4^7 - 1 + 6^7 \\ 249318 &:= (2 + 4 \times 9) \times (3 \times 1)^8 \\ 250002 &:= 2 + 500^{02} \\ 252928 &:= 2^{5 \times 2} \times (-9 + 2^8) \\ 253135 &:= (2 + (5 \times 3)^{1+3}) \times 5 \\ 255886 &:= -2 \times 5^5 - 8 + 8^6 \\ 257049 &:= (2^5 + 7)^{04} / 9 \\ 259549 &:= -2595 + 4^9 \\ 261883 &:= -261 + (8 \times 8)^3 \\ 262118 &:= -26 + (2 \times 1)^{18} \\ 262122 &:= 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 22 \end{aligned}$$

$$262128 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} - 2 \times 8$$

$$262136 := -2 - 6 + (2 \times 1)^{3 \times 6}$$

$$262137 := (2 + 62 \times 1)^3 - 7$$

$$262139 := -2 - 6/2 + (1 + 3)^9$$

$$262156 := 2 \times 6 + (2 + 1 + 5)^6$$

$$262176 := 2^6/2 + (1 + 7)^6$$

$$262196 := 26 \times 2 + (-1 + 9)^6$$

$$262286 := (2 \times 6)^2 - 2 + 8^6$$

$$262438 := -2 + (6^2 + 4) \times 3^8$$

$$263866 := (2 \times 6)^3 + 8^6 - 6$$

$$265617 := -2 - 6 + 5^6 \times 17$$

$$265689 := 2^6 + 5^6 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$266565 := (2^{6+6} + 5) \times 65$$

$$268321 := -2 + (6 + 8^3)^2 - 1$$

$$268323 := 2 + (6 + 8^3)^2 - 3$$

$$268324 := (2 \times (6 + 8^3))^2/4$$

$$273375 := (2 + 7)^3 \times 375$$

$$274623 := -2 + (7 - 4 + 62)^3$$

$$275686 := (2 \times 7)^5 + 6 - 8^6$$

$$279666 := ((2 - 7) \times 9 + 6^6) \times 6$$

$$279841 := (2 \times 7 + 9)^{8-4} \times 1$$

$$279867 := 2 - 79 + 8 + 6^7$$

$$279934 := -2 + (7 - 9/9)^{3+4}$$

$$279936 := ((2 - 7 + 9) \times 9)^3 \times 6$$

$$279937 := (2 + 7)/9 + (9 - 3)^7$$

$$279967 := 279/9 + 6^7$$

$$282240 := (2 + 82)^2 \times 40$$

$$287496 := ((2 + 8) \times 7 - 4)^{9-6}$$

$$289536 := 2^8 \times (9 \times 5^3 + 6)$$

$$291602 := 2 + (9 \times 1 \times 60)^2$$

$$294778 := 2 \times 9 \times (4^7 - 7) - 8$$

$$294782 := -2 + 94 \times (7 \times 8)^2$$

$$294829 := -2 + (-9 + 4^8/2) \times 9$$

$$294838 := -2 + 9 \times ((4 \times 8)^3 - 8)$$

$$294894 := 2 \times (-9 + 4^8 \times 9/4)$$

$$294895 := (2 + (9^4 - 8) \times 9) \times 5$$

$$294912 := 2 \times 9 \times 4^{9 \times 1 - 2}$$

$$294928 := 2 \times (9 \times 4^{9-2} + 8)$$

$$295195 := (-2 + 9^5 + 1 - 9) \times 5$$

$$295235 := (-2 + 9^5) \times (-2 + 3) \times 5$$

$$295243 := -2 + 9^5 \times (-2 + 4 + 3)$$

$$295245 := (2 + 9^5 + 2 - 4) \times 5$$

$$295247 := 2 + 9^5 \times (2 - 4 + 7)$$

$$295255 := (2 + 9^5) \times 25/5$$

$$295285 := (2 + 9^5 - 2 + 8) \times 5$$

$$295465 := (-2 + 9^5 + 46) \times 5$$

$$295505 := (2 + 9^5 + 50) \times 5$$

$$296346 := ((-2 + 9) \times 6)^3 \times 4 - 6$$

$$296384 := (((-2 + 9) \times 6)^3 + 8) \times 4$$

$$299575 := (2^9 + 9) \times 575$$

$$314431 := ((3 + 14) \times 4)^3 - 1$$

$$325125 := ((3 + 2) \times 51)^2 \times 5$$

$$326557 := (3 \times 2 \times 6^5 - 5) \times 7$$

$$326586 := 3 \times (-2 + 6^5 \times (8 + 6))$$

$$326592 := (3 \times 2)^6 \times (5 + 9)/2$$

$$326617 := 32 + (6^6 - 1) \times 7$$

$$326634 := ((3 \times 2)^6 + 6) \times (3 + 4)$$

$$326697 := ((3 \times 2)^6 + 6 + 9) \times 7$$

$$327485 := (-32 - 7 + 4^8) \times 5$$

$$331683 := 3 \times (-31 + (6 \times 8)^3)$$

$$331773 := -3 + (31 - 7)^{7-3}$$

$$347736 := 3 + 477 \times 3^6$$

$$351232 := (3 + 51 + 2)^3 \times 2$$

$$352926 := 3 \times (-5 - 2 + (9 - 2)^6)$$

$$352932 := 3 \times (-5 + (-2 + 9)^{3 \times 2})$$

$$352947 := 3 \times (5 + 2)^{9+4-7}$$

$$352961 := 3 \times (5 + (-2 + 9)^6) - 1$$

$$354276 := (-3 + (5 + 4)^{-2+7}) \times 6$$

$$354277 := ((3 \times 5)^4 - 2 \times 7) \times 7$$

$$354292 := 3^{5+4} \times 2 \times 9 - 2$$

$$354294 := 3 \times (5 + 4) \times 2 \times 9^4$$

$$354627 := ((3 \times 5)^4 + 6^2) \times 7$$

$$\begin{aligned}360855 &:= 3^{6 \times 0 + 8} \times 55 \\367272 &:= (3^6 \times 7 - 2) \times 72 \\368500 &:= (3^6 + 8) \times 500 \\371314 &:= 3 \times 7 + 13^{1+4} \\372573 &:= 3^7 + 2 \times 57^3 \\373239 &:= (-3 + 73 + 2)^3 - 9 \\373248 &:= (3 \times (7 - 3))^{2+4} / 8 \\374439 &:= (-3 + 7^4 \times 4) \times 39 \\374529 &:= 3 \times (7^4 \times 52 - 9) \\375021 &:= 3 \times (7 + 50^{2+1}) \\375168 &:= 3 \times (7 + (5 \times 1)^6) \times 8 \\379793 &:= (-3 + 7)^9 + 7^{9-3} \\386758 &:= -3867 + 5^8 \\388560 &:= (3^8 - 85) \times 60 \\388993 &:= -3 \times 8 + (-8 + 9 \times 9)^3 \\389342 &:= ((3 + 89)^3 - 4) / 2 \\390358 &:= 3 - 90 \times 3 + 5^8 \\390583 &:= -39 + 05^8 - 3 \\390589 &:= -3 \times 9 + 05^8 - 9 \\390628 &:= 3 + (9 - 06 + 2)^8 \\390658 &:= 3 \times 9 + 06 + 5^8 \\391864 &:= (-3^9 + (-1 + 8)^6) \times 4 \\393189 &:= 3 \times (-9 + (3 - 1)^{8+9}) \\393216 &:= (3 + 9/3) \times 2^{16} \\393420 &:= (3^9 - 3 \times 4) \times 20 \\393660 &:= 3^9 / (-3 + 6) \times 60 \\393720 &:= (3 + 9 \times 3^7) \times 20 \\393820 &:= ((3 \times 9)^3 + 8) \times 20 \\397535 &:= (3 \times (9 + 7) - 5)^3 \times 5 \\413466 &:= (41^3 - 4 - 6) \times 6 \\413496 &:= (41^3 + 4 - 9) \times 6 \\413518 &:= 41^3 \times (5 + 1) - 8 \\417625 &:= (4 + 17^{6-2}) \times 5 \\419904 &:= 4 \times (1 \times 9 + 9)^{04} \\420175 &:= (4 + 20 + 1) \times 7^5 \\425984 &:= (4 \times 2)^5 \times (9 + 8 - 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}432964 &:= 4 \times 329^{6-4} \\437564 &:= 4^3 + 7 \times 5^6 \times 4 \\437656 &:= 4 \times (-3 + 7 \times (6 + 5^6)) \\437750 &:= (4 \times 3^7 + 7) \times 50 \\455625 &:= (4 \times 5 - 5)^6 / 25 \\456533 &:= (4 + 5 + 65 + 3)^3 \\456976 &:= (4 \times 5 + 6)^{-9+7+6} \\459270 &:= ((4 + 5) \times 9)^2 \times 70 \\466536 &:= (-4 + 6^6 \times 5/3) \times 6 \\466552 &:= (-4 + 6 \times 6^5 \times 5) \times 2 \\466553 &:= -4 + 6^6 \times (5 + 5) - 3 \\466557 &:= 4 + 6^6 \times (5 + 5) - 7 \\466652 &:= (46 + 6^6 \times 5) \times 2 \\466880 &:= (4 + 6^6 / 8) \times 80 \\470576 &:= 4 \times (7 \times 0 - 5 + 7^6) \\470596 &:= 4 \times 7^{0 \times 59 + 6} \\470616 &:= 4 \times (7^{06} - 1 + 6) \\470632 &:= 4 \times (7^{06} + 3^2) \\471576 &:= (471 + 5^7) \times 6 \\472364 &:= 4 \times (-7 + 2 \times 3^{6+4}) \\472384 &:= -4 + 72 \times 3^8 + 4 \\472388 &:= 4 + 72 \times 3^8 - 8 \\472392 &:= (4 + 7 \times 2)^3 \times 9^2 \\472395 &:= -4 + 7 + 2^3 \times 9^5 \\472398 &:= (-4 + 7) \times (2 + 3^9 \times 8) \\472439 &:= 47 + 24 \times 3^9 \\474552 &:= (4 + 74)^{5/5+2} \\475136 &:= 4^7 \times (5 + (1 + 3) \times 6) \\475281 &:= (4^7 + 5) \times (28 + 1) \\476254 &:= 4 + 762 \times 5^4 \\483153 &:= ((-4 + 8) \times 3 - 1)^5 \times 3 \\493837 &:= -4 + 9 \times 38^3 - 7 \\493852 &:= 4 + 9 \times 38^{5-2} \\497657 &:= 4 \times (9 + 7) \times 6^5 - 7 \\497662 &:= (-4 + 9 + 7)^6 / 6 - 2 \\497664 &:= 4 \times (9 + 7) \times 6 \times 6^4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 508276 &:= 5^{08} + 2 + 7^6 \\ 515816 &:= -5^{1+5} + (8+1)^6 \\ 523665 &:= ((5-2) \times 3)^6 - 6^5 \\ 524088 &:= (-5^2 + 4^{08}) \times 8 \\ 524248 &:= (-5 + (2 \times 4 \times 2)^4) \times 8 \\ 524282 &:= -5 + (-2 + 4^{2+8})/2 \\ 524283 &:= -5 + 2^{4 \times 2 + 8 + 3} \\ 524285 &:= -5 + 2 + 4^2 \times 8^5 \\ 524288 &:= (5 \times 2 - 4 - 2)^8 \times 8 \\ 524293 &:= 5 + 2^{4+2 \times 9-3} \\ 524298 &:= 5 \times 2 + 4^{2+9}/8 \\ 524488 &:= (5^{-2+4} + 4^8) \times 8 \\ 524880 &:= (5 + 2 - 4)^8 \times 80 \\ 526833 &:= (-5 + (2^6 - 8)^3) \times 3 \\ 531296 &:= 5 \times (-31 + 2) + 9^6 \\ 531396 &:= -5 \times 3 \times 1 \times 3 + 9^6 \\ 531426 &:= -5 \times 3 + (1 + 4 \times 2)^6 \\ 531428 &:= -5 + 3^{14-2} - 8 \\ 531433 &:= -5 + (3 \times 1)^{4 \times 3} - 3 \\ 531436 &:= -5 + (3 - 1 + 4 + 3)^6 \\ 531438 &:= 5 + (3 \times 1)^{4 \times 3} - 8 \\ 531439 &:= -5 + 3 + (-1 + 4)^{3+9} \\ 531441 &:= (5 - 3 + 1)^{4 \times (4-1)} \\ 531443 &:= 5 + (31 - 4)^4 - 3 \\ 531446 &:= 5 + 3^{14+4-6} \\ 531456 &:= 5 \times 3 + (1 \times 4 + 5)^6 \\ 531494 &:= 53 + ((-1 + 4) \times 9)^4 \\ 531496 &:= 5 \times (-3 + 14) + 9^6 \\ 531566 &:= 5^3 + (15 - 6)^6 \\ 531966 &:= 531 + 9^6 - 6 \\ 538412 &:= (5 + 3^8) \times 41 \times 2 \\ 546875 &:= 5^{4-6+8} \times 7 \times 5 \\ 549365 &:= 5 \times (49^3 - 6^5) \\ 551343 &:= -5 \times 5 + (1 + 3^4)^3 \\ 559539 &:= 5^5 + (9^5 - 3) \times 9 \\ 562419 &:= ((5^6 - 2) \times 4 - 1) \times 9 \\ 563922 &:= ((56 + 3) \times 9)^2 \times 2 \\ 577602 &:= -5 + 7 + 760^2 \\ 583443 &:= (5 \times (8 - 3) - 4)^4 \times 3 \\ 583889 &:= -5 \times 8 + 3^8 \times 89 \\ 584647 &:= (5 + 8/4 \times 6)^4 \times 7 \\ 588765 &:= ((5 + 8) \times 8 + 7^6) \times 5 \\ 589748 &:= -5 - 8 + 9 \times (-7 + 4^8) \\ 589864 &:= 5 \times 8 + 9 \times 8^6/4 \\ 590945 &:= 5 + 90 \times (9^4 + 5) \\ 592763 &:= 59 + (2 \times 7 \times 6)^3 \\ 597878 &:= 5 + (9^7 + 8 + 7)/8 \\ 606476 &:= (6^{06} - 4) \times (7 + 6) \\ 614125 &:= (6 \times 14 + 1)^{-2+5} \\ 624978 &:= -6 + (-2 + (-4 + 9)^7) \times 8 \\ 629844 &:= 6 \times (-2 + (9 \times 8/4)^4) \\ 629848 &:= (6/2)^9 \times 8 \times 4 - 8 \\ 635993 &:= -63 + (5 + 9 \times 9)^3 \\ 640024 &:= (6 + 400^2) \times 4 \\ 645500 &:= (6^4 - 5) \times 500 \\ 649495 &:= (6 - 4 + 9) \times (-4 + 9^5) \\ 649529 &:= -6 - 4 + 9^5 \times (2 + 9) \\ 653184 &:= 6^5 \times (3 + 18) \times 4 \\ 655284 &:= (6^5 + 5^2) \times 84 \\ 655354 &:= -6 + 5 \times (5 + 3)^5 \times 4 \\ 655935 &:= (6 \times 5^5 - 9) \times 35 \\ 656187 &:= (6 \times 5^6 - 1 - 8) \times 7 \\ 656244 &:= -6 + 5^6 \times (-2 + 44) \\ 656298 &:= 6 \times (5^6 \times (-2 + 9) + 8) \\ 656373 &:= 6 \times (5^6 + 3) \times 7 - 3 \\ 656376 &:= (6 + 5^6 - 3) \times 7 \times 6 \\ 656418 &:= 6 \times (5^6 + 4) \times (-1 + 8) \\ 656790 &:= 6 \times (5^6 \times 7 + 90) \\ 656817 &:= (6 \times 5^6 + 81) \times 7 \\ 657874 &:= (-6 + 5 \times 7 \times 8) \times 7^4 \\ 659685 &:= (6^5 - 9 - 6) \times 85 \\ 663552 &:= 6 \times (6 \times (3 + 5))^{5-2} \end{aligned}$$

$$677328 := 6 \times ((-7 + 7^3)^2 - 8)$$

$$699875 := (6^9 / (9 \times 8) + 7) \times 5$$

$$705642 := (7^{05} - 6) \times 42$$

$$715821 := 71^{-5+8} \times 2 - 1$$

$$728993 := -7 + ((2 + 8) \times 9)^{9/3}$$

$$729014 := 7 \times 2 + 90^{-1+4}$$

$$742572 := ((7 + 4 + 2)^5 - 7) \times 2$$

$$742586 := (7 + 4 + 2)^5 \times (8 - 6)$$

$$756045 := (7^5 - 6) \times 045$$

$$756315 := 7^5 \times (6 - 3) \times 15$$

$$756325 := (7^5 \times (6 + 3) + 2) \times 5$$

$$756549 := ((7^5 + 6) \times 5 - 4) \times 9$$

$$756585 := (7^5 + 6) \times (5 \times 8 + 5)$$

$$759359 := -7 + (5 \times 9/3)^5 - 9$$

$$759375 := (7 - 5 + 9 - 3 + 7)^5$$

$$765392 := 7^6 \times 5 + 3^{9+2}$$

$$766927 := (7 + 6 \times 6 \times 9)^2 \times 7$$

$$774137 := 7 \times (7 + 41)^3 - 7$$

$$776887 := 7^7 - 6^{-8/8+7}$$

$$777922 := ((7 + 7) \times 7 \times 9)^2 - 2$$

$$781257 := 7 + (8 \times 1 + 2) \times 5^7$$

$$786385 := -7 + 8^6 \times 3 - 8 \times 5$$

$$786393 := (-7 + 8^6 + 3 - 9) \times 3$$

$$786396 := (-7 + 8^6) \times 3 - 9 - 6$$

$$786411 := (-7 + 8^6) \times (4 - 1) \times 1$$

$$786413 := -7 + (8^6 - 4 \times 1) \times 3$$

$$786425 := -7 - 8^6 + 4^{2 \times 5}$$

$$786433 := -7 + 8 + 64^3 \times 3$$

$$786439 := 7 + (8 \times 6 \times 4)^3 / 9$$

$$786441 := (7 + 8^6 - 4) \times (4 - 1)$$

$$786453 := (7 + 8^6) \times (4 + 5) / 3$$

$$789264 := 7 \times (89 - 2) \times 6^4$$

$$805255 := (8 + 05 - 2)^5 \times 5$$

$$805655 := (80 + (5 + 6)^5) \times 5$$

$$806752 := 8 \times (06 \times 7^5 + 2)$$

$$823297 := -82 \times 3 + (-2 + 9)^7$$

$$823461 := -82 + (3 + 4)^{6+1}$$

$$823527 := -8 - 2^3 + (5 + 2)^7$$

$$823543 := ((8 - 2) / 3 + 5)^{4+3}$$

$$824577 := 8 + 2 + 4^5 + 7^7$$

$$839424 := 8 \times (-3 + 9^4) \times 2^4$$

$$839673 := ((-8 + 3) \times 9 + 6^7) \times 3$$

$$839812 := (8 + (-3 + 9)^8) / (1 \times 2)$$

$$839827 := -8 + 3 \times (9 + (8 - 2)^7)$$

$$839867 := 8 + 3 \times (9 + 8 + 6^7)$$

$$844277 := (8 + 4)^4 - 2 + 7^7$$

$$851942 := (8^5 - 1) \times (9 + 4) \times 2$$

$$851968 := (8 + 5) \times (1 + 9 - 6)^8$$

$$856192 := (8^5 + 6^{-1+9}) / 2$$

$$857383 := 8 + (57 + 38)^3$$

$$875336 := 8 \times 7 \times (5^{3+3} + 6)$$

$$884733 := (8 \times 84/7)^3 - 3$$

$$884736 := 8 \times 8^4 \times (7 \times 3 + 6)$$

$$886464 := (8 \times 86 - 4) \times 6^4$$

$$907569 := 9 \times 07^5 \times 6 - 9$$

$$912247 := (9 + 12 - 2)^4 \times 7$$

$$923314 := -9 \times 23 + 31^4$$

$$924385 := (9 - 2)^4 \times 385$$

$$937577 := (9 + 3) \times (7 + 5^7) - 7$$

$$944784 := 9^4 \times (4 \times 7 + 8) \times 4$$

$$973944 := ((9 \times 7)^3 - 9^4) \times 4$$

$$984150 := 9^{8-4} \times 150$$

$$1020101 := 1010^2 + 01$$

$$1026366 := (10 + 2 \times 6) \times (-3 + 6^6)$$

$$1036322 := (10^3 + 6 \times 3)^2 - 2$$

$$1036324 := (10^3 + 6 \times 3)^{-2+4}$$

$$1046666 := 10 + (4 + 6)^6 + 6^6$$

$$1046875 := (1 + 04)^6 \times (-8 + 75)$$

$$1047285 := (104 + 7)^2 \times 85$$

$$1048249 := 1 + 04 \times (-82 + 4^9)$$

$$1048424 := ((-10 + 4^8) \times 4 + 2) \times 4$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1048449 &:= 1 - 04 \times (8 \times 4 - 4^9) \\ 1048464 &:= -104 - 8 + 4^{6+4} \\ 1048483 &:= -10 + (4 \times 8)^4 - 83 \\ 1048488 &:= (1 \times 04 \times 8)^4 - 88 \\ 1048493 &:= 10 + (4 \times 8)^4 - 93 \\ 1048558 &:= -10 + (-4 + 8)^{5+5} - 8 \\ 1048581 &:= 1 + 04 \times (8^5 \times 8 + 1) \\ 1048582 &:= (1 + 04 \times 8^5) \times 8 - 2 \\ 1048583 &:= 10 + 4 \times 8^5 \times 8 - 3 \\ 1048586 &:= -10 + (-4 + 8) \times (5 + 8^6) \\ 1048592 &:= (1 + 04^8) \times (5 + 9 + 2) \\ 1048608 &:= 1 \times 04 \times (8^6 + 08) \\ 1048618 &:= 10 + 4 \times (8^6 \times 1 + 8) \\ 1048624 &:= 10 \times 4 + (8^6 + 2) \times 4 \\ 1048634 &:= 10 + 4 \times (8^6 + 3 \times 4) \\ 1048635 &:= -1 + 04 \times (8^6 + 3 \times 5) \\ 1048682 &:= 10 + (4^8 + 6) \times 8 \times 2 \\ 1048688 &:= (1 + 04^8 + 6) \times (8 + 8) \\ 1048736 &:= (10 + 4^8) \times (7 + 3 + 6) \\ 1048769 &:= -10^4 + (-8 + 7^6) \times 9 \\ 1058769 &:= (1 \times 0 \times 5 - 8 + 7^6) \times 9 \\ 1062762 &:= (-10 \times 6 + (2 + 7)^6) \times 2 \\ 1062942 &:= 10 \times 6 + 2 \times 9^{4+2} \\ 1062954 &:= (10 + 6 + 2) \times (9^5 + 4) \\ 1062962 &:= 10 \times (6 + 2) + 9^6 \times 2 \\ 1073733 &:= (1 + (07 + 3) \times 7)^3 \times 3 \\ 1075488 &:= (-10 + 7^5 \times 4) \times (8 + 8) \\ 1075644 &:= 1 \times 07^5 \times 64 - 4 \\ 1075649 &:= 10 + 7^5 \times 64 - 9 \\ 1075658 &:= 10 + 7^5 \times (6 + 58) \\ 1075712 &:= (1 + 07^5) \times (7 + 1)^2 \\ 1092592 &:= (109^2 - 5) \times 92 \\ 1124853 &:= -11 + (2 \times 4 \times (8 + 5))^3 \\ 1124863 &:= -1 + (1 \times 2 \times (4 + 8 \times 6))^3 \\ 1127287 &:= (11^{-2+7} - 2 - 8) \times 7 \\ 1127357 &:= (1^{12} + 7 + 3)^5 \times 7 \\ 1127374 &:= (11^{-2+7} + 3) \times 7 - 4 \\ 1127567 &:= (11^{-2+7} + 5 \times 6) \times 7 \\ 1142053 &:= 11 \times (42 + 05)^3 \\ 1142440 &:= (1 + 14 - 2)^4 \times 40 \\ 1146875 &:= (-1 + 1 \times 4^6 \times 8 \times 7) \times 5 \\ 1148175 &:= (-1 \times 1 + 4)^8 \times 175 \\ 1153275 &:= (1 + (-1 + 5^3)^2) \times 75 \\ 1156174 &:= -1 - 1 + (5^6 - 1) \times 74 \\ 1156175 &:= -1 + (-1 + 5^6) \times (-1 + 75) \\ 1157622 &:= -1 + (15 \times 7)^{6/2} - 2 \\ 1157623 &:= 1 + (15 \times 7)^{6/2} - 3 \\ 1157624 &:= -1 + (15 \times 7)^{6 \times 2/4} \\ 1157625 &:= (1 \times 15 \times 7)^{6+2-5} \\ 1164485 &:= (1 \times 1 + 6)^4 \times 485 \\ 1166125 &:= (-11 + 6^6) \times 1 \times 25 \\ 1166325 &:= ((1 - 1 + 6)^6 - 3) \times 25 \\ 1166355 &:= (1 + (1 + 6^6 - 3) \times 5) \times 5 \\ 1166374 &:= -1 + (-1 + 6^6) \times (3 \times 7 + 4) \\ 1166395 &:= (-1 + (-1 + 6) \times 6^{-3+9}) \times 5 \\ 1166525 &:= ((1 - 1 + 6)^6 + 5) \times 25 \\ 1166555 &:= (1 + (1 + 6^6 + 5) \times 5) \times 5 \\ 1171280 &:= 11^{(7+1)/2} \times 80 \\ 1171874 &:= -1 + (-1 + 7 - 1)^8 \times (7 - 4) \\ 1173960 &:= (-117 + 3^9) \times 60 \\ 1176375 &:= (-11 + 7^6) \times (3 + 7) - 5 \\ 1176435 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (7^6 - 4) - 3) \times 5 \\ 1176440 &:= (-1 + (-1 + 7^6)/4) \times 40 \\ 1176465 &:= (-1 - 1 + 7^6) \times (4 + 6) + 5 \\ 1176475 &:= ((1 + 1) \times 7^6 + 4 - 7) \times 5 \\ 1176476 &:= -(1 + 1) \times 7 + (6 + 4) \times 7^6 \\ 1176502 &:= (1 + (1 + 7^6) \times 5) \times 02 \\ 1176510 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 \times 5 + 10) \\ 1176512 &:= (11 + 7^6 \times 5) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 1176515 &:= ((1 + 1) \times 7^6 + 5) \times 1 \times 5 \\ 1176525 &:= ((1 + 1) \times 7^6 + 5 + 2) \times 5 \\ 1176538 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 \times 5 + 3 \times 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1176550 &:= (1 + (1 + 7^6)/5) \times 50 \\ 1176552 &:= (1 + (1 + 7^6 + 5) \times 5) \times 2 \\ 1176562 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 \times 5 + 6^2) \\ 1176575 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (7^6 + 5) + 7) \times 5 \\ 1176586 &:= (1 + 1) \times (7^6 \times 5 + 8 \times 6) \\ 1176975 &:= ((1 + 1) \times 7^6 + 97) \times 5 \\ 1179483 &:= (1 + 17) \times (-9 + 4^8) - 3 \\ 1179639 &:= (1 + 1)^{7+9} \times 6 \times 3 - 9 \\ 1179647 &:= -1 + (-1 + 79 - 6) \times 4^7 \\ 1179648 &:= (1 + 1)^{7+9} \times (6 + 4 + 8) \\ 1185392 &:= (1 + (-1 + 85)^3 - 9) \times 2 \\ 1185922 &:= 1 + (1 + 8 \times (-5 + 9))^{2+2} \\ 1191635 &:= (-1 + (-1 + 9 \times (1 + 6))^3) \times 5 \\ 1198152 &:= (1 + 1) \times (9 \times (81 + 5))^2 \\ 1221024 &:= -1 + 2210^2/4 \\ 1225043 &:= (1 + 22 \times 5 - 04)^3 \\ 1228875 &:= (1 + 2^{-2+8+8}) \times 75 \\ 1229312 &:= (1 - 2 + 29)^{3+1} \times 2 \\ 1229314 &:= 1 \times 2 + 2 \times (9 \times 3 + 1)^4 \\ 1234256 &:= (-1 + 23)^4 + (2 \times 5)^6 \\ 1237248 &:= 12^3 \times (724 - 8) \\ 1239579 &:= (-1 + (-2 + 3^9 - 5) \times 7) \times 9 \\ 1239663 &:= 12 + (3^9 - 6) \times 63 \\ 1239917 &:= (1 - (2 - 3^9) \times 9 - 1) \times 7 \\ 1239977 &:= -1 - 2 + (3^9 \times 9 - 7) \times 7 \\ 1239987 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3^9 \times 9 - 8) \times 7 \\ 1243860 &:= (12^4 + 3 - 8) \times 60 \\ 1244155 &:= 12^4 \times 4 \times 15 - 5 \\ 1244160 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 4)^4 \times 1 \times 60 \\ 1244165 &:= (1 + 2 \times 4 + 4)^{-1+6} \times 5 \\ 1244485 &:= (1 + 2 + 4 + 4)^4 \times 85 \\ 1245185 &:= 1 + 2 \times (4 \times 5 - 1) \times 8^5 \\ 1250235 &:= (-1 + 2^5 \times 02)^3 \times 5 \\ 1257537 &:= 12 + 575 \times 3^7 \\ 1258944 &:= (-1 + 25) \times 8 \times (9^4 - 4) \\ 1259644 &:= (-1 + (-2 + 5)^9) \times 64 - 4 \\ 1259684 &:= -1 + (-2 + 5) \times (-9 + 6^8/4) \\ 1259712 &:= (1 + 2 \times 5 + 97)^{1+2} \\ 1259713 &:= 1 + (2 \times 5 + 97 + 1)^3 \\ 1265239 &:= 1 + (-26 + 52^3) \times 9 \\ 1265625 &:= (1 + 26) \times 5^6 \times (-2 + 5) \\ 1265634 &:= 1 + 2 + 6 + 5^6 \times 3^4 \\ 1265766 &:= (12 \times 6^5 + 7^6) \times 6 \\ 1266325 &:= (1^2 + 6 \times 6)^3 \times 25 \\ 1273158 &:= ((1 + 27)^3 - 1) \times 58 \\ 1275408 &:= (1 + (-2 + 7)^5) \times 408 \\ 1277946 &:= (-1 + 2^{7+7} \times (9 + 4)) \times 6 \\ 1279265 &:= ((1 + 2)^7 \times 9 - 2) \times 65 \\ 1279392 &:= -1 + (2 + 7 \times 9) \times 3^9 - 2 \\ 1279393 &:= 1 + (2 + 7 \times 9) \times 3^9 - 3 \\ 1279394 &:= -1 + (2 + 7 \times 9) \times 3 \times 9^4 \\ 1279395 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 7) \times (9/3)^9 \times 5 \\ 1282048 &:= (1 \times 2^8 + 20^4) \times 8 \\ 1284535 &:= (1 - 2 + 8)^4 \times 535 \\ 1285000 &:= (1 + 2^8) \times 5000 \\ 1285245 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 85)^2 \times 45 \\ 1288475 &:= 1 + 2 + 8 \times (8 + (4 + 7)^5) \\ 1293876 &:= 1 - (2 + 9) \times (3 \times 8 - 7^6) \\ 1296036 &:= -(1 + 2 - 9) \times (60^3 + 6) \\ 1296337 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (9 \times 6 + 3)^3) \times 7 \\ 1299666 &:= ((1 + 2)^9 + 9) \times 66 - 6 \\ 1299672 &:= ((1 + 2)^9 + 9) \times (-6 + 72) \\ 1310720 &:= (1 + 3)^{1+07} \times 20 \\ 1310725 &:= (1 + (3 + 1)^{07+2}) \times 5 \\ 1310865 &:= (-1 + 3 \times 10 + 8^6) \times 5 \\ 1311048 &:= 131 \times (10^4 + 8) \\ 1318760 &:= -1 + 3^{1+8} \times (7 + 60) \\ 1325424 &:= (1 + (3 + 2)^5) \times 424 \\ 1327104 &:= (1 + 3) \times (2 \times 7 + 10)^4 \\ 1327347 &:= 1 \times 3 \times 27 \times (3 + 4^7) \\ 1327989 &:= (1 + (3 + 2)^7 - 9) \times (8 + 9) \\ 1334288 &:= (1 + 33)^4 - 2^8 \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1336268 &:= (1 + 33)^{6-2} - 68 \\1336328 &:= (1 + 33)^{6/3+2} - 8 \\1336344 &:= 1 + 3/3 + 6 + 34^4 \\1338443 &:= -1 + 3 \times 3^8 \times (4 + 4^3) \\1342367 &:= 13^4 \times (2 + 3 + 6 \times 7) \\1342461 &:= (13^4 + 2) \times (46 + 1) \\1344560 &:= (1 \times 3 + 4)^4 \times 560 \\1361347 &:= 1 + (-3 + ((6 + 1) \times 3)^4) \times 7 \\1361374 &:= (1^3 + 6) \times (1 + (3 \times 7)^4) \\1363492 &:= 13 \times ((6 \times 3)^4 - 92) \\1364679 &:= (1 \times 3 \times 6)^4 \times (6 + 7) - 9 \\1364684 &:= (-1 + 3^6 \times 468) \times 4 \\1367631 &:= (-1 + 36 + 76)^3 \times 1 \\1368483 &:= ((-1^3 + 6)^8 + 4^8) \times 3 \\1373125 &:= (1 + (-3 + 7)^3)^{1+2} \times 5 \\1375033 &:= (1 + 3 + 7) \times (50^3 + 3) \\1375624 &:= 1 + 3^7 \times (5 + 624) \\1376253 &:= -1 \times 3 + 7 \times 6 \times 2^{5 \times 3} \\1376256 &:= 1^3 \times 7 \times (6 + 2)^5 \times 6 \\1376269 &:= 13 + 7 \times 6 \times 2^{6+9} \\1376385 &:= 1 \times 3 + 7 \times 6 \times (3 + 8^5) \\1377099 &:= ((-1 + 3^7) \times 70 - 9) \times 9 \\1377739 &:= -1 + (3 + 7) \times (-7 + 7 \times 3^9) \\1377990 &:= ((-1 + 3^7) \times 7 + 9) \times 90 \\1378175 &:= 1 + (3 + 78 + 1) \times 7^5 \\1382974 &:= 1 - 3 + 8^2 \times 9 \times 7^4 \\1392385 &:= ((1 + 3)^{9-2} - 3) \times 85 \\1397422 &:= (-1 + 3^9) \times (7 + (4 \times 2)^2) \\1397493 &:= 1 \times 3^9 \times (74 - 9/3) \\1399464 &:= (-1 + 39) \times 9 \times (4^6 - 4) \\1399667 &:= 13 + (-9/9 + 6) \times 6^7 \\1399675 &:= 13 - 9 - 9 + 6^7 \times 5 \\1399685 &:= (1 - 3 + 9)^{9+6-8} \times 5 \\1411763 &:= -1 + 4 \times (-1 - 1 + 7^6) \times 3 \\1411764 &:= (-1 + 4) \times (-1 - 1 + 7^6) \times 4 \\1416959 &:= -1 + 4 \times 1 \times 6 \times (9^5 - 9) \\1417468 &:= -(1 + 4^{1+7}) \times 4 + 6^8 \\1419815 &:= -1 - 41 + ((9 + 8) \times 1)^5 \\1419816 &:= -1 \times 41 + (9 + 8)^{-1+6} \\1419851 &:= -1 - 4 + (1 \times 9 + 8)^5 - 1 \\1419852 &:= 1 - 4 + (1 \times 9 + 8)^5 - 2 \\1419853 &:= -1^4 + (1 \times 9 + 8)^5 - 3 \\1419854 &:= 1^4 + (1 \times 9 + 8)^5 - 4 \\1419855 &:= 1 \times 4 - 1 + (9 + 8)^5 - 5 \\1419856 &:= 1 + 4 + (1 \times 9 + 8)^5 - 6 \\1419861 &:= 1 \times 4 + (1 \times 9 + 8)^{6-1} \\1419872 &:= 14 + 1 + (9 + 8)^{7-2} \\1423737 &:= (1 + 4 \times 23) \times 7 \times 3^7 \\1436859 &:= (1 + 4 \times 3 \times 6) \times (8 - 5)^9 \\1441788 &:= -1 \times 4 + (4 \times 1)^7 \times 88 \\1441792 &:= (1 + 4/4)^{17} \times (9 + 2) \\1443425 &:= (1 + 44 \times 3^{4 \times 2}) \times 5 \\1445625 &:= (1 + 4^4) \times 5625 \\1449459 &:= (1 \times 4 \times 4 - 9 + 4)^5 \times 9 \\1449475 &:= 1 \times 4 \times 4 + 9 \times (4 + 7)^5 \\1449984 &:= (-1 + 4^4 + 99) \times 8^4 \\1464100 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 100 \\1464610 &:= (1^4 + 6)^4 \times 610 \\1466494 &:= ((1 + 4)^6 - 6 \times 4) \times 94 \\1469664 &:= 14 \times ((6 - 9 + 6) \times 6)^4 \\1472490 &:= (1 + 4^7 - 24) \times 90 \\1474199 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times (1 + 9) \times 9 \\1474245 &:= (1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 2) \times 45 \\1474290 &:= (-1 + 4^7 - 4 + 2) \times 90 \\1474552 &:= (1 + 4^7 \times 45 - 5) \times 2 \\1474559 &:= -1 + 4^7 \times (45 + 5 \times 9) \\1474566 &:= (1 + 4^7 \times (4 + 5 + 6)) \times 6 \\1474572 &:= (-1 + 4^7 \times 45 + 7) \times 2 \\1474910 &:= (-1 + (4^7 + 4) \times 9) \times 10 \\1474919 &:= -1 + (4^7 + 4) \times (9 + 1) \times 9 \\1474925 &:= (1 + (4^7 + 4) \times 9 \times 2) \times 5 \\1475190 &:= (1 + 4^7 + 5 + 1) \times 90\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1476225 &:= (-1 + 4)^{7+6/2} \times 25 \\ 1478575 &:= (-1 + (4 + 7) \times 8) \times (-5 + 7^5) \\ 1478753 &:= 1 + (4 + 7) \times 8 \times (7^5 - 3) \\ 1484375 &:= (1 + 4)^8 \times (4 \times 3 + 7)/5 \\ 1485124 &:= ((1 + 4 + 8)^5 - 12) \times 4 \\ 1485141 &:= ((14 - 1)^5 - 8) \times 4 + 1 \\ 1485171 &:= -1 + 4 \times (8 + 5)^{-1+7-1} \\ 1485172 &:= (1 + 4 + 8)^5 \times (1 + 7)/2 \\ 1485173 &:= 1 + 4 \times (8 + 5)^{1+7-3} \\ 1485284 &:= ((1 + 4 + 8)^5 + 28) \times 4 \\ 1485428 &:= (1 + 4 + 8)^5 \times 4 + 2^8 \\ 1491476 &:= -14 + 91 \times (4^7 + 6) \\ 1492668 &:= 1 \times 4 \times (-9^2 + 6^6 \times 8) \\ 1492993 &:= 1 + 4 \times ((9 - 2) \times 9 + 9)^3 \\ 1493857 &:= 1 + 4 \times (-9 + 3^8) \times 57 \\ 1498172 &:= -1 \times 4 + (9 \times 8 \times 17)^2 \\ 1500574 &:= -1 - 50 + (05 \times 7)^4 \\ 1512675 &:= 15 \times (1 + 2 + 6 \times 7^5) \\ 1518565 &:= (1 \times 5 + 1)^8 - (5 + 6)^5 \\ 1518745 &:= (-1 + (5 + 1) \times (8 + 7)^4) \times 5 \\ 1518746 &:= 1 - 5 \times (1 - (8 + 7)^4 \times 6) \\ 1524635 &:= (1 \times 5 + 2)^4 \times 635 \\ 1529436 &:= -1 + (-5 + 2 \times 9) \times (4 + 3)^6 \\ 1535267 &:= (1 + 5 + 3)^5 \times 26 - 7 \\ 1535274 &:= (1 + 5 + 3)^5 \times (-2 + 7 \times 4) \\ 1539633 &:= 15 + (-3 + 9)^6 \times 33 \\ 1539727 &:= (1 - 53 \times 9 + 7)^2 \times 7 \\ 1542294 &:= 1 \times 54 \times (2 + 2 + 9)^4 \\ 1542464 &:= (1 + 5^4) \times 2464 \\ 1548359 &:= 1 + (5 + 48^3) \times (5 + 9) \\ 1548372 &:= (1 + 5 + 48^3) \times 7 \times 2 \\ 1548384 &:= (1 + 5) \times (-4 + 8^3)^{8/4} \\ 1550496 &:= (1 + 5^5) \times 0496 \\ 1555200 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 200 \\ 1555848 &:= (1 + 5 \times 5 - 5)^{8-4} \times 8 \\ 1556475 &:= (-1 + (5 \times 5 - 6) \times 4^7) \times 5 \\ 1558500 &:= (1 \times 5^5 - 8) \times 500 \\ 1558900 &:= -(1 - 5) \times (5^8 - 900) \\ 1562250 &:= (-1 + (5^6 - 2) \times 2) \times 50 \\ 1562350 &:= (1 \times 5^6 \times 2 - 3) \times 50 \\ 1562384 &:= (1 - 5 \times 6 + (2 + 3)^8) \times 4 \\ 1562448 &:= (-1 + 5^{6+2}) \times 4 - 48 \\ 1562450 &:= 1 \times 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 50 \\ 1562452 &:= (1 + 5^{6+2}) \times 4 - 52 \\ 1562458 &:= -(15 + 6) \times 2 + 4 \times 5^8 \\ 1562459 &:= (1 + 5^{6+2}) \times 4 - 5 \times 9 \\ 1562464 &:= (1 + 5^{6+2} - 4 - 6) \times 4 \\ 1562484 &:= (1 \times 5^{6+2} - 4) \times (8 - 4) \\ 1562486 &:= 1 \times 5^{6+2} \times 4 - 8 - 6 \\ 1562488 &:= (1 + 5^{6+2}) \times 4 - 8 - 8 \\ 1562510 &:= (1 + 5^6 \times 2 \times 5) \times 10 \\ 1562520 &:= (1 + 5^{6 \times 2 - 5}) \times 20 \\ 1562522 &:= (1 + (5^{6+2} + 5) \times 2) \times 2 \\ 1562524 &:= (1 + 5 + 625^2) \times 4 \\ 1562528 &:= (1 + (5^{6+2} + 5)/2) \times 8 \\ 1562544 &:= (1 \times 5 + 6 + 25^4) \times 4 \\ 1572868 &:= (-1^5 + 7) \times (2 + 8^6) + 8 \\ 1572886 &:= 15 + 7 + (-2 + 8) \times 8^6 \\ 1572936 &:= ((-1 + 5)^{7+2} + 9 + 3) \times 6 \\ 1572996 &:= (15 + 7 + 2^{9+9}) \times 6 \\ 1573086 &:= (1 + 5) \times (7 + 30 + 8^6) \\ 1574639 &:= -1^5 + (74 + 6) \times 3^9 \\ 1579225 &:= (1 + (-5 + 7 \times 9^2)^2) \times 5 \\ 1579951 &:= -1 + (-5 + 99) \times (7^5 + 1) \\ 1583725 &:= ((-1 + 5)^8 - 3^7) \times 25 \\ 1584660 &:= (15 - 8)^4 \times 660 \\ 1593999 &:= (1 - 5 + (9/3)^9) \times 9 \times 9 \\ 1594279 &:= 1 + (-5 + 9^4 \times 27) \times 9 \\ 1594283 &:= -1 + (-5 + 9^{4+2} - 8) \times 3 \\ 1594293 &:= (-1^5 + 9^{4+2} - 9) \times 3 \\ 1594313 &:= -1 \times 5 - 9 + 4 + 3^{13} \\ 1594321 &:= -(1 + 5 - 9^{4+3})/(2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1594325 &:= (1 + 5 + 9^{4+3}) / (-2 + 5) & 1658845 &:= (-1 - 6 + ((-5 + 8) \times 8)^4) \times 5 \\ 1594334 &:= 15 + 9^{4+3} / 3 - 4 & 1661521 &:= (-1 - 6 + 6^{-1+5})^2 \times 1 \\ 1594341 &:= 14 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1 & 1663242 &:= (1 + 66 \times 3)^2 \times 42 \\ 1594349 &:= 1 + 5 \times (9 - 4) + 3^{4+9} & 1663991 &:= -(-1 + 6)^6 + (-3 + 9)^{9-1} \\ 1594358 &:= -1^5 + 9 \times 4 + 3^{5+8} & 1664101 &:= 1 + (-6 + 6^4)^{1+01} \\ 1594365 &:= 1 + 5 + 9 \times (4 + 3^{6+5}) & 1664227 &:= -1 + (-6 + 6^4)^2 + 2^7 \\ 1594374 &:= 15 + 9 \times (4 + 3^{7+4}) & 1667268 &:= -(1 + 6) \times (6 \times 7)^2 + 6^8 \\ 1594385 &:= -1 + 59 + 4 + 3^{8+5} & 1672860 &:= (167^2 - 8) \times 60 \\ 1597519 &:= -1 + 5 \times (9 + 7^5) \times 19 & 1673159 &:= 1 - 6^7 - 31 + 5^9 \\ 1602445 &:= (1 + 60^2) \times 445 & 1673189 &:= -1 \times 6^7 + (-3 \times 1 + 8)^9 \\ 1608572 &:= (1 \times 60 + 8^5) \times 7^2 & 1676016 &:= (1 + (6^7 - 601)) \times 6 \\ 1610510 &:= (1^6 + 10)^5 \times 10 & 1676873 &:= 1 + 6^7 \times 6 - 8 \times 7^3 \\ 1613456 &:= 16 \times (-1 + (3 + 4)^5) \times 6 & 1678267 &:= 1 - 6 \times ((7 + 8)^2 - 6^7) \\ 1632925 &:= (-1 + 6^{3 \times 2}) \times (9 - 2) \times 5 & 1678808 &:= (-1^6 + 7)^8 - 808 \\ 1632968 &:= -1 - 6^{3 \times 2} + 9 + 6^8 & 1678938 &:= -1 \times 678 + (9 - 3)^8 \\ 1633683 &:= -1 \times 6 + 3^{3+6} \times 83 & 1678968 &:= (1 \times 6 - 78) \times 9 + 6^8 \\ 1638325 &:= ((1^6 + 3)^8 - 3) \times 25 & 1678986 &:= (1 + 6^7 - 8 - 98) \times 6 \\ 1638350 &:= (-1 + (-6 + 38)^3) \times 50 & 1679046 &:= (1 + 6 + 7 + 9)^{04} \times 6 \\ 1638425 &:= (1 + (6/3 \times 8)^4) \times 25 & 1679065 &:= (-1 + 6^7 - 90) \times 6 + 5 \\ 1638525 &:= ((1^6 + 3)^8 + 5) \times 25 & 1679068 &:= (1 \times 6^7 - 90) \times 6 - 8 \\ 1638550 &:= (1^6 \times 3 + 8^5) \times 50 & 1679082 &:= (1 + 6^7 - 90) \times (8 - 2) \\ 1638750 &:= (16^3 \times 8 + 7) \times 50 & 1679168 &:= -(1 + 6) \times (7 \times 9 + 1) + 6^8 \\ 1640962 &:= 1 + (6^4 - 09 - 6)^2 & 1679237 &:= -1 + 6 \times (-7 \times 9 + (2 \times 3)^7) \\ 1643522 &:= (1 + 6^4 - 3 \times 5)^2 - 2 & 1679238 &:= -1 \times 6 \times 7 \times 9 + (2 \times 3)^8 \\ 1643524 &:= (1 + 6^4 - 3 \times 5)^{-2+4} & 1679273 &:= 1 \times 6^{(7+9)/2} - 7^3 \\ 1646977 &:= -1 + (6 - 4) \times (-6 \times 9 + 7^7) & 1679286 &:= (1 + 6^7 - (9 - 2) \times 8) \times 6 \\ 1647072 &:= -1 \times 6 + (-4 + 7^{07}) \times 2 & 1679406 &:= (1 + 6^7 - 9 \times 4) \times 06 \\ 1647075 &:= -1 + (6 - 4) \times (7^{07} - 5) & 1679454 &:= (1 + 6^7 / 9 - 4) \times 54 \\ 1647078 &:= (1 \times 6 - 4) \times 7^{07} - 8 & 1679468 &:= -16 \times 7 - 9 \times 4 + 6^8 \\ 1647087 &:= 1 + (6 - 4) \times 7^{08} / 7 & 1679526 &:= (1 + 6^7 - 9 - 5 - 2) \times 6 \\ 1647711 &:= (-1 + 6)^4 + 7^7 \times (1 + 1) & 1679532 &:= (1 \times 6^7 - 9 - 5) \times 3 \times 2 \\ 1647772 &:= ((1 + 6)^4 / 7 + 7^7) \times 2 & 1679533 &:= 1 + (6^7 - 9 - 5) \times (3 + 3) \\ 1647773 &:= 1 + (6 - 4) \times (7^7 + 7^3) & 1679556 &:= (1 - 6^7 + 9) \times (5 - 5 - 6) \\ 1648353 &:= (-1 + 6^4 \times 8) \times 3 \times 53 & 1679562 &:= (-1 + 6^7 / 9) \times (56 - 2) \\ 1654134 &:= 1 \times 6 \times (5 + 41^3 \times 4) & 1679568 &:= (1 - 6 - 7) \times (9 - 5) + 6^8 \\ 1658834 &:= -1 \times 6 + 5 \times (-8 + (8 \times 3)^4) & 1679586 &:= (1 + 6^7 - 9 - 5 + 8) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1679593 &:= 1 + (6^7 - 9 + 5) \times (9 - 3) \\ 1679608 &:= 1^{67} - 9 + 6^{08} \\ 1679612 &:= ((-1 + 6^7) \times (9 - 6) + 1) \times 2 \\ 1679613 &:= (-1 + 6^7 \times (9 - 6 - 1)) \times 3 \\ 1679615 &:= -1 + 6^{7-9+6-1+5} \\ 1679617 &:= 1 + 6^{(7 \times 9 - 6 - 1)/7} \\ 1679618 &:= -1^6 \times 7 + 9 + (6 \times 1)^8 \\ 1679621 &:= (1 + 6^7) \times (9 - 6) \times 2 - 1 \\ 1679622 &:= (1 + 6^7) \times 9 / (6/2) \times 2 \\ 1679623 &:= -1 + 6 - 7 + 9 + 6^{23} \\ 1679624 &:= (1 \times 6^7 \times 9/6 + 2) \times 4 \\ 1679626 &:= (1 \times 6^7 - 9) \times 6 + 2^6 \\ 1679628 &:= (-1 + 6^7 + 9 - 6) \times (-2 + 8) \\ 1679632 &:= (-1 + 6^7 + 9) \times 6 - 32 \\ 1679633 &:= -1 + (6^7 + 9 - 6) \times (3 + 3) \\ 1679635 &:= (1 \times 6^7 + 9) \times 6 - 35 \\ 1679637 &:= 1 \times 6^{-7+9+6} + 3 \times 7 \\ 1679638 &:= (1 + 6^7 + 9) \times 6 - 38 \\ 1679642 &:= (-1 + 6) \times 7 - 9 + 6^{4 \times 2} \\ 1679646 &:= (1 \times 6^7 + 9) \times 6 - 4 \times 6 \\ 1679648 &:= 1 \times 6^{-7+9+6} + 4 \times 8 \\ 1679657 &:= -1 + (6^7 + 9) \times 6 - 5 - 7 \\ 1679658 &:= 1 + (6^7 + 9) \times 6 - 5 - 8 \\ 1679662 &:= (1 \times 6^7 + 9) \times 6 - 6 - 2 \\ 1679664 &:= (-1 + 6 + 7 + 9 \times 6^6) \times 4 \\ 1679665 &:= (1 + 6^7 + 9) \times 6 - 6 - 5 \\ 1679667 &:= 1 \times 6 \times 7 + 9 + 6 \times 6^7 \\ 1679668 &:= (1 \times 6^7 + 9) \times 6 + 6 - 8 \\ 1679669 &:= -1 + (6^7/9 \times 6 + 6) \times 9 \\ 1679670 &:= (1 \times 6^7 + 9) \times 6 + 7 \times 0 \\ 1679671 &:= (-1 + 6^7 + 9) \times 6 + 7 \times 1 \\ 1679672 &:= (-1^6 + 7) \times (9 + 6^7) + 2 \\ 1679673 &:= -1 + (6^7 + 9) \times 6 + 7 - 3 \\ 1679674 &:= 1 + (6^7 + 9) \times 6 + 7 - 4 \\ 1679675 &:= (-1^6 + 7) \times (9 + 6^7) + 5 \\ 1679676 &:= (1 \times 6^7 + 9 - 6 + 7) \times 6 \\ 1679677 &:= (1 + 6^7 + 9) \times 6 + 7/7 \\ 1679678 &:= (-1^6 + 7) \times (9 + 6^7) + 8 \\ 1679679 &:= (1 \times 6^7/9 \times 6 + 7) \times 9 \\ 1679691 &:= -1 + 67 + 9 + 6^{9-1} \\ 1679706 &:= (-1 + 6^7 + 9 + 7) \times 06 \\ 1679736 &:= (1 + 6^7 + 9 + 7 + 3) \times 6 \\ 1679826 &:= (1 + 6^7 + (9 + 8) \times 2) \times 6 \\ 1680129 &:= 1 + 6^8 + (0 \times 1 + 2)^9 \\ 1680645 &:= -1 + 6^8 + 06 + 4^5 \\ 1681343 &:= 1 \times 6^8 - 1 + (3 \times 4)^3 \\ 1681568 &:= -1 + 6^8 + (-1 + 5^6)/8 \\ 1681673 &:= 1 \times 6^8 - 1 + 6 \times 7^3 \\ 1682209 &:= (1 + 6^{8/2})^2 + 0 \times 9 \\ 1682593 &:= 1 + 6^8 + 2^5 \times 93 \\ 1682741 &:= 1 \times 6^8 + (-2 + 7)^{4+1} \\ 1682755 &:= 1 \times 6^8 + 2 \times 7 + 5^5 \\ 1683714 &:= -1 + 6^8 + 3 + (7 + 1)^4 \\ 1683723 &:= 1 \times 6^8 + 37^2 \times 3 \\ 1683972 &:= 1 \times 6^8 + (3 + 9 \times 7)^2 \\ 1685158 &:= -1 + (68 + 51)^{-5+8} \\ 1686184 &:= 1 + 6^8 + 6 + (1 + 8)^4 \\ 1686238 &:= -1 + 6^8 + 62 + 3^8 \\ 1686394 &:= 1 + 6^8 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\ 1686672 &:= 1 \times 6^8 + ((6 + 6) \times 7)^2 \\ 1687465 &:= -1 + 6^8 + 74 + 6^5 \\ 1692394 &:= (-1 \times 6 + 92) \times (3^9 - 4) \\ 1693449 &:= (1 + (6 + 9^3) \times 4^4) \times 9 \\ 1694768 &:= ((16 \times 947) + (6^8)) \\ 1705214 &:= (-1 + 70 \times 5)^2 \times 14 \\ 1708594 &:= (1 + (7 + 08)^5 \times 9)/4 \\ 1712385 &:= 1 + (7 - 1)^{23} + 8^5 \\ 1713987 &:= (17 + 1 + 3^9) \times 87 \\ 1715742 &:= (-1 + 715) \times (7^4 + 2) \\ 1718722 &:= 1 + (7 \times 187 + 2)^2 \\ 1725552 &:= (1 + (7 - 2)^5) \times 552 \\ 1739762 &:= 1 + (7^3 + 976)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1741823 &:= -1 + 7 \times (4 \times 1 + 8)^{2+3} \\ 1741825 &:= 1 + 7 \times ((4 - 1) \times 8/2)^5 \\ 1741845 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (4 - 1 + (8 + 4)^5) \\ 1743126 &:= 1 \times 7^4 \times (-3 + (1 + 2)^6) \\ 1744712 &:= (1 + 7) \times (-4 + 471)^2 \\ 1744896 &:= (1 + 7)^4 \times (48 \times 9 - 6) \\ 1748933 &:= -1 + (7^4 + 8) \times (9^3 - 3) \\ 1749344 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times 9^3 - 4^4 \\ 1752192 &:= (1 + 7) \times (52 \times 1 \times 9)^2 \\ 1752320 &:= (-1 + 75)^2 \times 320 \\ 1759934 &:= 1 + 7^{-5+9} \times (9^3 + 4) \\ 1764135 &:= (1 + 7^6 - 41) \times 3 \times 5 \\ 1764496 &:= 1 + (7^6 - 4 \times 4) \times (9 + 6) \\ 1764715 &:= ((1 - 7^6) \times (4 - 7) - 1) \times 5 \\ 1764725 &:= (1 \times 7^6 \times (-4 + 7) - 2) \times 5 \\ 1764734 &:= -1 + 7^6 \times (-4 + 7 + 3 \times 4) \\ 1764735 &:= (1^7 + 6)^4 \times 735 \\ 1764736 &:= 1 + 7^6 \times ((-4 + 7) \times 3 + 6) \\ 1764745 &:= (1 + 7^6) \times (4 + 7 + 4) - 5 \\ 1764765 &:= (1 \times 7^6 \times (-4 + 7) + 6) \times 5 \\ 1764775 &:= (1 + 7^6 \times (-4 + 7) + 7) \times 5 \\ 1764795 &:= ((1 + 7^6) \times (-4 + 7) - 9) \times 5 \\ 1764915 &:= (-1 + 7^6 + 4 + 9) \times 15 \\ 1764935 &:= (1 + (7^6 + 4 + 9) \times 3) \times 5 \\ 1766937 &:= (1 + 7^6) \times (6 + 9) + 3^7 \\ 1769466 &:= (1 + 7) \times 6 \times 9 \times 4^6 - 6 \\ 1769471 &:= (-1 + 7 + 6) \times 9 \times 4^7 - 1 \\ 1769483 &:= 17 - 6 + 9 \times 4^8 \times 3 \\ 1769489 &:= 17 + (-6 + 9) \times 4^8 \times 9 \\ 1769857 &:= 1 \times 7 + 6 \times 9 \times (8^5 + 7) \\ 1771546 &:= -1 - 7 - 7 + (15 - 4)^6 \\ 1771576 &:= 1 + 7 + 7 + (-1 + 5 + 7)^6 \\ 1784643 &:= 17 \times ((8 + 4 + 6)^4 + 3) \\ 1804275 &:= (1 + 8)^{04} \times 275 \\ 1815156 &:= 18 \times (1 + 5 + 1)^5 \times 6 \\ 1815839 &:= (1 + 81 + 5 \times 8)^3 - 9 \\ 1824760 &:= (1 + 8 - 2)^4 \times 760 \\ 1833497 &:= 1 + (-8 \times 3^3 + 4^9) \times 7 \\ 1834497 &:= (1 \times 8 - 3^4 + 4^9) \times 7 \\ 1834847 &:= (1 - 8 \times 3 + 4^8 \times 4) \times 7 \\ 1834867 &:= -1 + (-8 \times 3 + 4 + 8^6) \times 7 \\ 1834868 &:= (-1 + 8) \times (-3 \times 4 + 8^6 - 8) \\ 1834917 &:= -1 - 83 + (4^9 - 1) \times 7 \\ 1834925 &:= -1 \times 83 + 4^9 \times (2 + 5) \\ 1834951 &:= (-1 + 8) \times (-3 + 4^9 - 5) - 1 \\ 1834959 &:= (-1 + 8) \times (-3 + 4^9 + 5 - 9) \\ 1834966 &:= (-1 + 8) \times ((3 - 4 + 9)^6 - 6) \\ 1834967 &:= 1^83 + (4^9 - 6) \times 7 \\ 1834971 &:= -1 + (-8 + 3 + 4^9) \times 7 - 1 \\ 1834972 &:= 1 + (-8 + 3 + 4^9) \times 7 - 2 \\ 1834974 &:= -1 - 8 + (-3 + 4^9) \times 7 - 4 \\ 1834975 &:= (1 - 8 + 3 + 4^9) \times 7 - 5 \\ 1834977 &:= -1 \times 8 \times 3 + 4^9 \times 7 - 7 \\ 1834978 &:= -1^8 + (-3 + 4^9) \times 7 - 8 \\ 1834979 &:= 1^8 + (-3 + 4^9) \times 7 - 9 \\ 1834981 &:= -(1 + 8) \times 3 + 4^9 \times (8 - 1) \\ 1834985 &:= 1 + 8 \times (-3 + 4^9 - 8^5) \\ 1834987 &:= (1 - 8) \times 3 - 4^9 + 8^7 \\ 1834988 &:= (-1 + 8) \times (-3 + 4^9) + 8/8 \\ 1835197 &:= ((1 + 8) \times 3 + (5 - 1)^9) \times 7 \\ 1835476 &:= (1 \times 8 - 3)^{5+4} - 7^6 \\ 1842750 &:= (-1 + 8^4) \times (2 + 7) \times 50 \\ 1843250 &:= (1 + 8^4 \times 3^2) \times 50 \\ 1843275 &:= (1 + 8^4 \times 3 \times 2) \times 75 \\ 1843290 &:= (1 + 8^4 \times (3 + 2)) \times 90 \\ 1843350 &:= (1 + 8^4 \times 3) \times 3 \times 50 \\ 1843650 &:= (1 + 8^4) \times (3 + 6) \times 50 \\ 1844950 &:= (-1 + (8^4 + 4) \times 9) \times 50 \\ 1845450 &:= (1 \times 8^4 + 5) \times 450 \\ 1847042 &:= (-1 + 8 \times 4)^{7 \times 0 + 4} \times 2 \\ 1848149 &:= -18^4 + (8 + 1 - 4)^9 \\ 1848770 &:= (-1 + 8)^{-4+8} \times 770 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1855975 &:= (-1 + (8 + 5)^5 - 97) \times 5 \\ 1856495 &:= 1^8 \times 5 \times (6 + (4 + 9)^5) \\ 1856848 &:= 18^5 + (6 - 8^4) \times 8 \\ 1858374 &:= 18 \times (5 \times 8 + 3) \times 7^4 \\ 1865577 &:= (1 \times 8 + 6)^5 \times 5 - 7^7 \\ 1865965 &:= (-1 + (8 \times 6^5 - 9) \times 6) \times 5 \\ 1866125 &:= (1 + 8 \times (6^6 - 1 - 2)) \times 5 \\ 1866165 &:= (1 + 8 \times 6^6 - 16) \times 5 \\ 1866168 &:= (-1 - 8 + 6^6 \times (-1 + 6)) \times 8 \\ 1866169 &:= 1 + 8 \times (6^6 \times (-1 + 6) - 9) \\ 1866195 &:= (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 - 1 \times 9) \times 5 \\ 1866220 &:= (-1^8 + 6^6 \times 2) \times 20 \\ 1866225 &:= (1 + (8 \times 6^6 - 2 - 2)) \times 5 \\ 1866231 &:= -1 + 8 \times (6^6 \times (2 + 3) - 1) \\ 1866235 &:= 1 \times 8 \times 6^6 \times (2 + 3) - 5 \\ 1866240 &:= (18 \times (6 + 6))^2 \times 40 \\ 1866241 &:= 1 + 8 \times 6^6 \times (2 + 4 - 1) \\ 1866245 &:= (1^8 + 6^6 \times 2 \times 4) \times 5 \\ 1866249 &:= -1 + (8 \times 6^6 + 2) \times (-4 + 9) \\ 1866265 &:= (1 + 8 \times 6^6 - 2 + 6) \times 5 \\ 1866285 &:= (1 - 8 + (6^6 + 2) \times 8) \times 5 \\ 1866295 &:= (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 2 + 9) \times 5 \\ 1866315 &:= (-1 + 8 \times (6^6 + 3 - 1)) \times 5 \\ 1866325 &:= (1 + 8 \times ((6 \times 6)^3 + 2)) \times 5 \\ 1866345 &:= (1 + 8 \times (6^6 + 3) - 4) \times 5 \\ 1866351 &:= -1 + 8 \times ((6^6 + 3) \times 5 - 1) \\ 1866355 &:= 1 \times 8 \times (6^6 + 3) \times 5 - 5 \\ 1866361 &:= 1 + 8 \times (6^6 + 3) \times (6 - 1) \\ 1866365 &:= (1 + 8 \times (6^6 - 3 + 6)) \times 5 \\ 1866405 &:= (1 + 8 \times (6^6 + 4)) \times 05 \\ 1866440 &:= (1 + 8 + 6^6 - 4) \times 40 \\ 1866457 &:= 1 + 8 \times ((6^6 + 4) \times 5 + 7) \\ 1866465 &:= (-1 + (8 \times 6^6 + 46)) \times 5 \\ 1866475 &:= (1 \times 8 \times 6^6 + 47) \times 5 \\ 1866485 &:= (1 + 8 \times 6^6 + 48) \times 5 \\ 1866525 &:= (1 + 8 \times (6^6 + 5 + 2)) \times 5 \\ 1866537 &:= 1 + 8 \times (6^6 \times 5 + 37) \\ 1866559 &:= -1 + (8 + 6^6) \times (-5 + 5 \times 9) \\ 1866568 &:= ((-1 + 8 + 6^6) \times 5 + 6) \times 8 \\ 1866576 &:= 1 \times 8 \times (6^6 \times 5 + 7 \times 6) \\ 1866595 &:= (-1 + 8 \times (6 \times 6^5 + 9)) \times 5 \\ 1866645 &:= (1 + 8 \times (6^6 + 6 + 4)) \times 5 \\ 1866765 &:= (1 + 8 \times (6^6 + 7 + 6)) \times 5 \\ 1866840 &:= (-1 + 8 + 6^6 + 8) \times 40 \\ 1866885 &:= (1 + 8 \times (6^6 + 8 + 8)) \times 5 \\ 1872119 &:= (-1 + 8)^7 + 2^{1+19} \\ 1872761 &:= 18^{7-2} - 7^{6-1} \\ 1872780 &:= ((-1 + 8) \times 7)^2 \times 780 \\ 1874048 &:= ((1 + 87)/4)^{04} \times 8 \\ 1874162 &:= 1 + (8 + 7 \times 4 + 1)^{6-2} \\ 1875181 &:= (-1 + 8)^{-1+5} \times 781 \\ 1882035 &:= (1 + 88^2) \times 03^5 \\ 1882376 &:= -1 \times 8 + (8 + 2^3) \times 7^6 \\ 1884785 &:= (-1 + 8)^{8-4} \times 785 \\ 1885527 &:= (-1 + 8 \times (8 + 5) \times 5)^2 \times 7 \\ 1889424 &:= 18 \times (-8 + (9 \times 4/2)^4) \\ 1889481 &:= 18^{-4+9} - 88 + 1 \\ 1889484 &:= 18^{-8+9+4} - 84 \\ 1889495 &:= -1^8 + 8 \times (-9 + 4 \times 9^5) \\ 1889504 &:= 1 \times 8 \times (-8 + 9^5 \times 04) \\ 1889524 &:= (-1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5 - 2) \times 4 \\ 1889528 &:= (-1 + (-8 + 8 \times 9^5)/2) \times 8 \\ 1889534 &:= (1^8 + 8 + 9)^5 - 34 \\ 1889537 &:= 1 + (-8 + 8 \times 9^5) \times (-3 + 7) \\ 1889553 &:= (1^8 + 8 + 9)^5 - 5 \times 3 \\ 1889559 &:= ((1^8 + 89)/5)^5 - 9 \\ 1889561 &:= (1^8 + 8 + 9)^5 - 6 - 1 \\ 1889564 &:= (1 - 8 + 8 \times 9^5 + 6) \times 4 \\ 1889567 &:= (1^8 + 8 + 9)^5 + 6 - 7 \\ 1889568 &:= 18^{8-(9-5) \times 6/8} \\ 1889582 &:= (-1 + (8 + 8) \times 9^5 + 8) \times 2 \\ 1889584 &:= 1 \times 8 + 8 + 9^5 \times 8 \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1897255 &:= (((-1 + 89) \times 7)^2 - 5) \times 5 \\1906623 &:= -1 + (90 + 6 \times 6 - 2)^3 \\1906659 &:= 190 - 6^6 + 5^9 \\1913759 &:= -(19 - 1) \times 3^7 + 5^9 \\1926785 &:= 1 + (9 - 2) \times 6^7 - 8^5 \\1928444 &:= (1 + 92) \times (8 + 4)^4 - 4 \\1928448 &:= (1 + 92) \times (8 + 4)^{-4+8} \\1938275 &:= 19^{-3+8} - (2 \times 7)^5 \\1946558 &:= -1 \times 9^4 - 6 + 5 \times 5^8 \\1950937 &:= -1^9 + 5^{09} - 3^7 \\1952159 &:= -(1 + 9 \times 5) \times 21 + 5^9 \\1952773 &:= -1 \times 9 + 5^{2+7} - 7^3 \\1952925 &:= (1 - 9 + 5^{-2+9}) \times 25 \\1952959 &:= -195 + 29 + 5^9 \\1952991 &:= -19 \times (9 - 2) + 5^9 - 1 \\1953029 &:= -1 - 95 + (3 + 02)^9 \\1953059 &:= -1 - 95 + 30 + 5^9 \\1953085 &:= (1 - 9 + 5^{3 \times 0+8}) \times 5 \\1953098 &:= -19 + 5^{3 \times 0+9} - 8 \\1953106 &:= -19 + 5^{3 \times 1+06} \\1953113 &:= -1 \times 9 + 5^{3^{1+1}} - 3 \\1953115 &:= -1 - 9 + 5^{3 \times 1+1+5} \\1953116 &:= -1 \times 9 + 5^{3-1+1+6} \\1953117 &:= 1 - 9 + 5^{3-1 \times 1+7} \\1953118 &:= 1^9 + 5^{3^{1+1}} - 8 \\1953119 &:= -1^9 - 5 + (3 + 1 + 1)^9 \\1953122 &:= -1^9 + 5^{(3 \times 1)^2} - 2 \\1953123 &:= 1^9 + 5^{(3 \times 1)^2} - 3 \\1953124 &:= -1^9 + 5^{3 \times 12/4} \\1953125 &:= (1 + 9 - 5)^{3-1+2+5} \\1953126 &:= 1^9 + 5^{3+12-6} \\1953127 &:= 1 \times 9 + 5^{(3 \times 1)^2} - 7 \\1953129 &:= 1 \times 9 - 5 + (3 \times 1 + 2)^9 \\1953132 &:= 1 \times 9 + (5^3 \times 1)^3 - 2 \\1953133 &:= -1 + 9 + 5^{(3-1) \times 3+3} \\1953134 &:= 1 \times 9 + 5^{3-1+3+4}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1953135 &:= 1 + 9 + (5^3)^{1-3+5} \\1953137 &:= 19 + (5^3 \times 1)^3 - 7 \\1953139 &:= 1 \times 9 + 5 + (3 - 1 + 3)^9 \\1953141 &:= (1 \times 4 + 1) \times 3 + 5^9 + 1 \\1953144 &:= 19 + 5^{3^{1+4/4}} \\1953148 &:= -1 + 9 + 5 \times (3 + (1 + 4)^8) \\1953149 &:= 1 \times 9 + 5 \times 3 + (1 + 4)^9 \\1953159 &:= 19 + 5 \times 3 + 1 \times 5^9 \\1953165 &:= (-1 + 9 + 5^{3-1+6}) \times 5 \\1953219 &:= -1 + 95 + ((3 + 2) \times 1)^9 \\1953259 &:= 1 + 9 \times 5 \times 3 - 2 + 5^9 \\1953585 &:= (1 \times 95 - 3 + 5^8) \times 5 \\1953596 &:= 1 \times 9 \times 53 + 5^9 - 6 \\1953629 &:= 1 - 9 + 5^{3+6} + 2^9 \\1953659 &:= -195 + 3^6 + 5^9 \\1953691 &:= 1 \times 9 \times 63 + 5^9 - 1 \\1953759 &:= 1 \times 9 + 5^{-3+7} + 5^9 \\1953793 &:= 1 + 9 \times 53 \times (7 + 9)^3 \\1953846 &:= 1 \times 9 \times (53 \times 8^4 + 6) \\1956246 &:= (1 + 95 \times 6)^{-2+4} \times 6 \\1958769 &:= ((1 + 9)^5 - 8 + 7^6) \times 9 \\1959677 &:= -1 + (9 + 5) \times 9 + 6^7 \times 7 \\1961984 &:= ((-1 + 9) \times 61 - 9) \times 8^4 \\1964635 &:= (-1 + 96 \times (4^6 - 3)) \times 5 \\1965848 &:= -1 + 9 + 6 \times 5 \times (-8 + 4^8) \\1965985 &:= (-19 + 6 \times (-5 + 9)^8) \times 5 \\1968128 &:= (1 + 9 + 6 \times 81)^2 \times 8 \\1968300 &:= (1 \times 9 - 6)^8 \times 300 \\1972544 &:= ((-1 + 9) \times 7)^2 \times (5^4 + 4) \\1975392 &:= (1^9 + 75)^3 \times 9/2 \\1982464 &:= (19 - 8)^2 \times 4^6 \times 4 \\1994542 &:= 19 \times (9 + 4 + 5)^4 - 2 \\1994544 &:= 19 \times 9^4 \times (5 \times 4 - 4) \\1999962 &:= (-19 + (9/9 + 9)^6) \times 2 \\2037677 &:= (2 + 03)^7 + 6^7 \times 7 \\2044436 &:= 20 + 4 \times 44^3 \times 6\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2048383 &:= (2 \times (0 - 4 + 8^3)/8)^3 & 2117663 &:= 2 - (1 + (1 - 7^6) \times 6) \times 3 \\ 2052866 &:= 2 + (052 - 8) \times 6^6 & 2117682 &:= (2 + 1) \times 1 \times 7^6 \times (8 - 2) \\ 2074896 &:= ((2 \times 07)^4 + 8) \times 9 \times 6 & 2117694 &:= 2 \times (1 + 1 + 7^6 \times 9 + 4) \\ 2085133 &:= (-2 + 08 \times 5)^{1+3} - 3 & 2117695 &:= 2 \times (1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times 9 - 5 \\ 2085134 &:= -2 + (08 \times 5 + 1 - 3)^4 & 2117696 &:= 2 \times (1 + 1 \times 7^6 \times 9 + 6) \\ 2085136 &:= (-2 + 08 \times 5)^{1-3+6} & 2117697 &:= 2 \times (11 + 7^6 \times 9) - 7 \\ 2086384 &:= 208 \times 6 + 38^4 & 2117698 &:= 2 \times ((1 - 1 + 7^6) \times 9 + 8) \\ 2086394 &:= (20 + 86) \times 3^9 - 4 & 2117699 &:= -2 + 1 + (1 + 7^6) \times (9 + 9) \\ 2091045 &:= 209 \times (10^4 + 5) & 2121843 &:= ((2 - 1) \times 21 + 8)^4 \times 3 \\ 2096587 &:= 20 - 9 \times 65 + 8^7 & 2125748 &:= -(2 - (1 + 2)^{5+7}) \times 4 - 8 \\ 2096852 &:= -20 \times (9 + 6) + 8^{5+2} & 2125762 &:= -2 + (1 + 2)^{5+7} \times (6 - 2) \\ 2096987 &:= -20 \times 9 + 6 + 9 + 8^7 & 2125764 &:= (2 + 1)^{25-7-6} \times 4 \\ 2097087 &:= -2 - 09 \times 7 + 08^7 & 2125964 &:= (2 \times 1 \times 25 + 9^6) \times 4 \\ 2097134 &:= -2 \times 09 + (7 + 1)^{3+4} & 2126493 &:= (2 + 1)^{2 \times 6} \times 4 + 9^3 \\ 2097143 &:= 2 \times 0 - 9 + (7 + 1)^{4+3} & 2146176 &:= (2 - 1) \times 46 \times (-1 + 7)^6 \\ 2097144 &:= 2 \times ((09 + 7)^{1+4} - 4) & 2146266 &:= -2 + 1 \times 46 \times (2 + 6^6) \\ 2097146 &:= 2^{0 \times 9 + 7 + 14} - 6 & 2146592 &:= 2 \times (14 \times (65 + 9))^2 \\ 2097151 &:= 2^{09+7 \times 1+5} - 1 & 2146725 &:= 21 \times (4^6 - 7) \times 25 \\ 2097152 &:= (2 \times 0 + 9 + 7 \times 1)^5 \times 2 & 2151275 &:= -21 + (5 - 1) \times (2 \times 7)^5 \\ 2097154 &:= 2 + (09 - 7)^{1+5 \times 4} & 2162679 &:= 2^{16} + (2 + 6)^7 - 9 \\ 2097161 &:= 2 \times 0 + 9 + (7 + 1)^{6+1} & 2184910 &:= (-2 + 1 + 8)^4 \times 910 \\ 2097168 &:= (2 + (0 \times 9 + 7 + 1)^6) \times 8 & 2187572 &:= 2 \times (18 + 7 \times 5^7) \times 2 \\ 2097181 &:= 20 + 9 + (7 + 1)^{8-1} & 2187574 &:= 2 + (18 + 7 \times 5^7) \times 4 \\ 2097184 &:= (2^{09+7} + 1) \times 8 \times 4 & 2187648 &:= (218 - 7) \times 6^4 \times 8 \\ 2097187 &:= 20 + 9 + 7 - 1 + 8^7 & 2193776 &:= -2 + 19 \times (-3^7 + 7^6) \\ 2097247 &:= -2 + 097 + (2 \times 4)^7 & 2217121 &:= (-2 + 21 \times 71)^2 \times 1 \\ 2098587 &:= 20 \times 9 \times 8 - 5 + 8^7 & 2218524 &:= 22 \times (-1 + 8)^5 \times (2 + 4) \\ 2099460 &:= 20 \times (9 + 9)^4 - 60 & 2227756 &:= -2 + (-2/2 + 7 + 7)^5 \times 6 \\ 2099493 &:= 20 \times (9 + 9)^4 - 9 \times 3 & 2228224 &:= (2 + (2 + 2) \times 8) \times 2^{2^4} \\ 2099515 &:= 20 \times (9 + 9)^{5-1} - 5 & 2237438 &:= -2 + (-2 + 3^7) \times 4^{-3+8} \\ 2099520 &:= (2 \times 09)^{9-5} \times 20 & 2239265 &:= -223 + 9 \times (2 \times 6)^5 \\ 2099665 &:= (20 + 9 + 9 \times 6^6) \times 5 & 2239466 &:= -22 + (3 + 9) \times 4 \times 6^6 \\ 2101242 &:= ((2^{10} + 1)^2 - 4) \times 2 & 2239476 &:= -2 + (2^3 \times 9)^{-4+7} \times 6 \\ 2101262 &:= ((2^{10} + 1)^2 + 6) \times 2 & 2239485 &:= 2 - 2 - 3 + 9 \times (4 + 8)^5 \\ 2117661 &:= (2 + 1) \times ((-1 + 7^6) \times 6 - 1) & 2239519 &:= 22 + ((3 + 9)^5 + 1) \times 9 \\ 2117662 &:= (2 + 1) \times (-1 + 7^6) \times 6 - 2 & 2239678 &:= -2 + (2 \times (3 + 9) + 6^7) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2265857 &:= ((2+2) \times 6 + 5) \times (8 + 5^7) \\ 2275290 &:= (22 \times 7 + 5)^2 \times 90 \\ 2284855 &:= ((-2 + 28)^{-4+8} - 5) \times 5 \\ 2284875 &:= ((-2 + 28)^4 - 8 + 7) \times 5 \\ 2284885 &:= ((-2 + 28)^4 + 8/8) \times 5 \\ 2284945 &:= ((-2 + 28)^4 + 9 + 4) \times 5 \\ 2286166 &:= 22 + (8 \times 6 + 1) \times 6^6 \\ 2286372 &:= 228 + (6^3 \times 7)^2 \\ 2294586 &:= (-2 - 2^{9+4} + 5^8) \times 6 \\ 2302913 &:= 2 + 3^{02+9} \times 13 \\ 2313433 &:= -2 + (3 \times 13)^4 - 3 - 3 \\ 2313435 &:= 2 + (3 \times 13)^4 - 3 - 5 \\ 2313436 &:= -2 + (3 \times 13)^4 + 3 - 6 \\ 2313438 &:= 2 + (3 \times 13)^4 + 3 - 8 \\ 2313439 &:= -2 + 3 \times 13^4 \times 3 \times 9 \\ 2313441 &:= (2 \times 3 - 1 + 34)^4 \times 1 \\ 2313443 &:= 2 + (3 \times 13)^4 \times (4 - 3) \\ 2313444 &:= (2 + (3 \times 13)^4) + 4/4 \\ 2313464 &:= 23 + (-1 + 34 + 6)^4 \\ 2322447 &:= -2 + 3 + (2 + 24^4) \times 7 \\ 2323240 &:= (-2 + 3^{2+3})^2 \times 40 \\ 2328745 &:= 23 \times 2 \times (8 + 7)^4 - 5 \\ 2332550 &:= ((2 \times 3)^{3 \times 2} - 5) \times 50 \\ 2333744 &:= (2 + 3 \times (-3 + (3 \times 7)^4)) \times 4 \\ 2339358 &:= 2 \times 3 \times (-3 - 9^3 + 5^8) \\ 2343558 &:= 2 \times 3 \times (-4 \times (3 + 5) + 5^8) \\ 2343584 &:= 2 \times (-3^4 + 3 \times 5^8) - 4 \\ 2343586 &:= -2 + (-3^4/3 + 5^8) \times 6 \\ 2343658 &:= -2 \times (3 + 43) + 6 \times 5^8 \\ 2343745 &:= 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 3 \times 7)^4 - 5 \\ 2343748 &:= -2 + 3 \times (43 + 7)^4/8 \\ 2343750 &:= (2 + 3)^4 \times 3750 \\ 2343786 &:= 2 \times 3 \times ((4 \times 3 - 7)^8 + 6) \\ 2348838 &:= (2 + 348 + 8) \times 3^8 \\ 2352643 &:= 2 \times 3 + (5 + 2 \times 64)^3 \\ 2352982 &:= 2 + (3^5 + 2) \times 98^2 \\ 2356727 &:= 2 + 3 \times (5 \times 67)^2 \times 7 \\ 2358639 &:= (-2 \times 35 + 8^6 - 3) \times 9 \\ 2359168 &:= (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 16) \times 8 \\ 2359248 &:= (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 - 2 - 4) \times 8 \\ 2359263 &:= 2 - 35 + 9 \times 2^{6 \times 3} \\ 2359266 &:= -2 \times 3 \times 5 + 9 \times (2 + 6)^6 \\ 2359292 &:= 2 \times (3 - 5) + 9 \times 2^{9 \times 2} \\ 2359293 &:= 2^{3 \times 5} \times (9^2 - 9) - 3 \\ 2359296 &:= 2^{3 \times 5} \times (9 \times 2 + 9 \times 6) \\ 2359298 &:= 2 + (3 + 5)^{9-2} \times 9/8 \\ 2359299 &:= 2^3 - 5 + 9 \times 2^{9+9} \\ 2359359 &:= (2 + (3 + 5)^{9-3} + 5) \times 9 \\ 2359368 &:= (2^{3 \times 5} \times 9 + 3 + 6) \times 8 \\ 2359560 &:= 2^3 \times 5 \times (9^5 - 60) \\ 2359586 &:= 2 + 3^5 + 9 \times (5 + 8^6) \\ 2359928 &:= ((2^{3 \times 5} + 9) \times 9 - 2) \times 8 \\ 2359944 &:= (2^{3 \times 5} + 9) \times 9 \times (4 + 4) \\ 2361954 &:= 2 \times (-3 + (6 - 1) \times 9^5 \times 4) \\ 2361955 &:= 2^3 \times (6 - 1) \times 9^5 - 5 \\ 2361960 &:= 2 \times 3^{6+1} \times 9 \times 60 \\ 2362927 &:= (23 + 62 \times 9)^2 \times 7 \\ 2364985 &:= (-2 + 3 + 6)^4 \times 985 \\ 2371328 &:= (2 + (3 \times 7 \times 1)^3) \times 2^8 \\ 2371841 &:= 2 \times (3 \times (-7 + 18))^4 - 1 \\ 2371842 &:= (2^3 + 7 + 18)^4 \times 2 \\ 2372783 &:= 23 + (7 - 2) \times 78^3 \\ 2387476 &:= (-2 + 3^8) \times 7 \times 4 \times (7 + 6) \\ 2394473 &:= ((2 + 3) \times 9^4 - 4) \times 73 \\ 2394665 &:= (-23 + 9 \times 4^6) \times 65 \\ 2394735 &:= (-2 \times 3 + 9^4 \times 73) \times 5 \\ 2402502 &:= 2 + (40^2 - 50)^2 \\ 2423537 &:= (2^{4^2} - 35) \times 37 \\ 2424832 &:= 2^{4^2} \times (4 \times 8 + 3 + 2) \\ 2439762 &:= (2 \times (-4 + 3^9) - 7) \times 62 \\ 2454375 &:= ((2 \times 4)^5 - 43) \times 75 \\ 2457075 &:= ((2 \times 4)^5 - 7) \times 075 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2457550 &:= (2 \times 4)^5 \times 75 - 50 \\2457586 &:= (2 \times 4)^5 \times 75 - 8 - 6 \\2457591 &:= (2 \times 4)^5 \times 75 - 9 \times 1 \\2457599 &:= (2 \times 4)^5 \times 75 - 9/9 \\2457600 &:= (-2 + 4)^{5+7} \times 600 \\2457675 &:= ((2 \times 4)^5 + 7 - 6) \times 75 \\2458575 &:= ((2 \times 4)^5 + 8 + 5) \times 75 \\2458624 &:= (2 - 4 + 58)^{6-2}/4 \\2458744 &:= 24 \times 5 + (8 \times 7)^4/4 \\2459353 &:= 2 - 4^5 + (9 \times 3 \times 5)^3 \\2459762 &:= 2 \times (4^5 + 9 + 76)^2 \\2469538 &:= (2^4 - 6 + 9)^5 - 3^8 \\2470613 &:= -2^4 + 7^{06+1} \times 3 \\2470621 &:= -2 \times 4 + 7^{06} \times 21 \\2470637 &:= 2 \times 4 + 7^{06} \times 3 \times 7 \\2476115 &:= 2^4 + (7 + 6 \times (1 + 1))^5 \\2480195 &:= 2^{4+8} + 019^5 \\2488315 &:= (2 \times (4 + 8)^{8-3} - 1) \times 5 \\2488335 &:= (2 \times (4 + 8)^{8-3} + 3) \times 5 \\2513702 &:= 2 + 513 \times 70^2 \\2517696 &:= (-2^5 + (-1 + 7)^6) \times 9 \times 6 \\2519367 &:= (2 - 5) \times (19 - 3 \times 6^7) \\2519424 &:= (2 \times 5 - 1 + 9)^4 \times 24 \\2519426 &:= 2 + (5 + 1) \times 9 \times (4 + 2)^6 \\2519427 &:= -2 + 5 + 1 \times 9 \times (4 + 2)^7 \\2519467 &:= 2 + 5 + 1 \times 9 \times (4 + 6^7) \\2531350 &:= (2 + (5 \times 3)^{1+3}) \times 50 \\2531385 &:= (-2 \times 5 + 31^3) \times 85 \\2543328 &:= 2^5 \times (43^3 - 28) \\2543968 &:= 2^5 \times (43^{9-6} - 8) \\2544352 &:= 2^5 \times (4 + 43^{5-2}) \\2562582 &:= (2 \times (5^6 - 2) + 5) \times 82 \\2562824 &:= 2 \times (5^6 + 2) \times 82 - 4 \\2566055 &:= -25 + 6^6 \times 055 \\2566115 &:= (2 + 5 + 6^6 \times 11) \times 5 \\2566117 &:= 2 + 5 \times (6^6 \times 11 + 7)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2566118 &:= -2 + 5 \times (6^6 \times 11 + 8) \\2571353 &:= (2^5 + 7 \times 1 \times 3 \times 5)^3 \\2578123 &:= -2 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1 + 2) \times 3 \\2578257 &:= (-2 + 5 \times 7) \times (8/2 + 5^7) \\2578383 &:= (-2 + (5^7 + 8) \times (3 + 8)) \times 3 \\2587439 &:= -25 + (-8 + 74)^3 \times 9 \\2587627 &:= (2 - 5 + (8 \times 76)^2) \times 7 \\2588276 &:= -2 + ((-5 + 8) \times 8 - 2) \times 7^6 \\2599344 &:= ((-2 + 5)^9 + 9) \times 3 \times 44 \\2611044 &:= 261 \times (10^4 + 4) \\2612736 &:= 2^{6+1+2} \times 7 \times 3^6 \\2613247 &:= (-2 + 613)^{-2+4} \times 7 \\2615373 &:= -2 + 61 \times 5^3 \times 7^3 \\2621280 &:= (2^{-6+21} - 2) \times 80 \\2621395 &:= (2^6 \times 2^{13} - 9) \times 5 \\2621440 &:= ((2 + 6) \times 2 \times 1)^4 \times 40 \\2621526 &:= (26^2 - 15)^2 \times 6 \\2626632 &:= 2 \times (-6 + 2^6 \times 6 \times 3)^2 \\2632375 &:= (2^{6 \times 3} \times 2 + 3^7) \times 5 \\2636325 &:= (26^3 \times 6 - 3) \times 25 \\2636525 &:= (26^3 \times 6 + 5) \times 25 \\2647965 &:= (-264 \times 7 + 9^6) \times 5 \\2649344 &:= 2 \times (-6^4 \times 9 + 34^4) \\2651273 &:= -2 + (6^5 - 1) \times (-2 + 7^3) \\2654208 &:= (2^6 \times (5 + 4))^2 \times 08 \\2656805 &:= ((-2 + 6 + 5)^6 - 80) \times 5 \\2656885 &:= ((-2 + 6 + 5)^6 - 8 \times 8) \times 5 \\2656965 &:= (2 + 6 - 56 + 9^6) \times 5 \\2657134 &:= (26 + 5^7) \times 1 \times 34 \\2657196 &:= 26 + 5 \times (-7 + 1 \times 9^6) \\2657217 &:= 2 \times 6 + 5 \times (7 + 2)^{-1+7} \\2657265 &:= 2 \times 6 \times 5 + (7 + 2)^6 \times 5 \\2657295 &:= (-2 \times 6 + 57) \times (2 + 9^5) \\2659385 &:= -2 + 6^5 \times 9 \times 38 - 5 \\2659387 &:= 2 + 6^5 \times 9 \times 38 - 7 \\2659468 &:= (2 + 6^5 \times 9) \times (46 - 8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2663422 &:= ((2 + 6) \times 6 \times 34)^2 - 2 \\ 2663424 &:= ((2 + 66) \times 3 \times 4)^2 \times 4 \\ 2665650 &:= (2^{6+6} + 5) \times 650 \\ 2665796 &:= (2 - 6 + 6^5) \times 7^{9-6} \\ 2669286 &:= ((-2 + 669)^2 - 8) \times 6 \\ 2672684 &:= 2 \times (6 + (-7 \times 2 + 6 \times 8)^4) \\ 2683275 &:= (2 \times (6 + 8^3)^2 + 7) \times 5 \\ 2685582 &:= (-2 \times 6 + 8^5 + 5) \times 82 \\ 2685817 &:= -2^6 \times 8^5 + (8 + 1)^7 \\ 2686976 &:= (-2 + 6)^8 \times (6 \times 9 - 7 - 6) \\ 2706739 &:= -2^7 + 067^3 \times 9 \\ 2722572 &:= (2 \times 7^5 - 2) \times (2 + 7)^2 \\ 2722734 &:= 2 \times 7 \times ((2 - 2 + 7) \times 3)^4 \\ 2731572 &:= 2 \times ((7 + 51)^3 \times 7 + 2) \\ 2731687 &:= (-2^7 \times 3 + (-1 + 6)^8) \times 7 \\ 2733750 &:= (2 + 7)^3 \times 3750 \\ 2734258 &:= 2 + 7 \times (-34/2 + 5^8) \\ 2734328 &:= 2 + 7 \times (-3 - 4 + (3 + 2)^8) \\ 2734358 &:= -2 \times 7 - 3 + (4 + 3) \times 5^8 \\ 2734375 &:= (-2 + 7)^{3 \times 4 - 3} \times 7/5 \\ 2734377 &:= 2 + (7 \times 3 + 4)^{-3+7} \times 7 \\ 2734587 &:= 2^7 + (3 \times 4 + 5^8) \times 7 \\ 2741856 &:= (-2 + 7 \times 4)^{1+8-5} \times 6 \\ 2742328 &:= ((-2 + 74) \times 23)^2 - 8 \\ 2743973 &:= -27 + (43 + 97)^3 \\ 2746744 &:= 2 \times 7^4 \times (6 + 7) \times 44 \\ 2752466 &:= -2 + (7 + 52) \times (-4 + 6^6) \\ 2752848 &:= 2 \times 7 \times (5 - 2) \times (8 + 4^8) \\ 2764752 &:= -2 + (7^6 \times 47 + 5)/2 \\ 2764754 &:= 2 \times (7^6 \times 47 + 5)/4 \\ 2765954 &:= 2 + (7 + 65) \times (9 + 5)^4 \\ 2767989 &:= (-27 + 6^7)/9 \times 89 \\ 2784385 &:= (2 + (7 + 8)^4 \times (3 + 8)) \times 5 \\ 2785253 &:= -27 + 85 \times 2^{5 \times 3} \\ 2785877 &:= 2 + (7 + 8^5) \times (8 + 77) \\ 2788425 &:= (2 - 7 + 8)^8 \times 425 \\ 2793472 &:= (-2 + 7^{9/3}) \times 4^7 / 2 \\ 2796660 &:= ((2 - 7) \times 9 + 6^6) \times 60 \\ 2798410 &:= (2 \times 7 + 9)^{8-4} \times 10 \\ 2799360 &:= ((2 - 7 + 9) \times 9)^3 \times 60 \\ 2812329 &:= (281 \times 2 - 3)^2 \times 9 \\ 2812572 &:= 2 \times (8 + 1) \times 2 \times (5^7 + 2) \\ 2812574 &:= 2 + (8 + 1) \times (2 + 5^7) \times 4 \\ 2822400 &:= (2 + 82)^2 \times 400 \\ 2823576 &:= (28 - 2 + 3 - 5) \times 7^6 \\ 2823624 &:= (2 + (8/2 + 3)^6) \times 24 \\ 2823768 &:= 2 \times 8/2 \times 3 \times (7^6 + 8) \\ 2825759 &:= -2 + (8 - 2 + 5 \times 7)^{-5+9} \\ 2825764 &:= (-2 + 8)/2 + (5 \times 7 + 6)^4 \\ 2829134 &:= 2 + 8 + 29^{1+3} \times 4 \\ 2829154 &:= -2 + (8 + 29^{-1+5}) \times 4 \\ 2833918 &:= -2 + 8 \times (-3 + 3^9) \times 18 \\ 2834256 &:= 2 \times 8 \times (3^{4^2-5} - 6) \\ 2834344 &:= 2 \times (8 \times 3^{4+3+4} - 4) \\ 2834346 &:= 2 \times 8 \times (3^{4+3+4} - 6) \\ 2834351 &:= 2 \times 8 \times (3^{-4+3 \times 5} - 1) \\ 2834352 &:= 2 \times 8 \times 3^{4 \times 3} / (5 - 2) \\ 2834676 &:= (-2 + 8 \times (3^{4+6} + 7)) \times 6 \\ 2834752 &:= 2 \times 8 \times (3^{4+7} + 5^2) \\ 2838672 &:= (2 + 8 + 3^8) \times 6 \times 72 \\ 2839714 &:= 2 \times (8 + 3^{9-7})^{1+4} \\ 2850816 &:= (2 + 85) \times 08^{-1+6} \\ 2857143 &:= (2^8 \times 5^7 + 1)/(4 + 3) \\ 2857216 &:= 2^8 \times (5^7 + 2)/(1 + 6) \\ 2857525 &:= 2 \times 85 \times (7^5 + 2) - 5 \\ 2857728 &:= (2 \times 8 + 5^7)/7 \times 2^8 \\ 2858935 &:= (2 \times 8 + 58 + 9)^3 \times 5 \\ 2858963 &:= 28 + 5 \times (89 - 6)^3 \\ 2859936 &:= 2 \times (8 + 5 \times 9 + 9)^3 \times 6 \\ 2863288 &:= (2 \times (8 + 63))^{2+8/8} \\ 2869782 &:= (-2 + 8 + 6 \times 9^7)/(8 + 2) \\ 2882878 &:= -2 + 88 \times (2^{8+7} - 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2883234 &:= 2 + 88 \times (32^3 - 4) \\ 2883446 &:= (2^{8+8} - 3) \times 44 - 6 \\ 2883497 &:= -2 - 8 + (8 + 3) \times (4^9 - 7) \\ 2883561 &:= (-2 + (8 \times 8)^3) \times (5 + 6) - 1 \\ 2883568 &:= (-2 + 8^{8-3} \times (5 + 6)) \times 8 \\ 2883582 &:= -2 + (8 \times 8)^3 \times (5 + 8 - 2) \\ 2883582 &:= -2 + 8^5 \times (3 \times 8 + 8^2) \\ 2883584 &:= 2 \times 8^{8-3} \times (5 \times 8 + 4) \\ 2883586 &:= 2 - (8 - 8 \times 3 + 5) \times 8^6 \\ 2883846 &:= -2 + 88 \times (3 + 8 \times 4^6) \\ 2883862 &:= 2^8 + (8 + 3) \times (8^6 + 2) \\ 2884992 &:= (2 \times 8 \times 8 + 4^9) \times (9 + 2) \\ 2893695 &:= (-2 + (8 + 9) \times 3) \times (6 + 9^5) \\ 2923235 &:= (292 - 3)^2 \times 35 \\ 2939244 &:= (2 - 9) \times (3 - (9 \times 2)^4) \times 4 \\ 2939328 &:= (2 \times 9)^{(3+9)/3} \times 28 \\ 2939657 &:= (2 + 9 \times ((-3 + 9)^6 + 5)) \times 7 \\ 2941225 &:= (-2 + 9)^4 \times 1225 \\ 2948445 &:= (-2 - 9 + 4^8 - 4) \times 45 \\ 2948599 &:= -2^9 + 4^8 \times 5 \times 9 - 9 \\ 2948725 &:= (2 - (9 - 4^8) \times (7 + 2)) \times 5 \\ 2948755 &:= (2 + 9 \times 4^8 - 75) \times 5 \\ 2948765 &:= (-2 + 9 \times (4^8 - 7) - 6) \times 5 \\ 2948795 &:= (-2 + 9 \times 4^8 - 7 \times 9) \times 5 \\ 2948815 &:= (2 + 9 \times (4^8 - 8 + 1)) \times 5 \\ 2948859 &:= (2 + 9 + (4^8 - 8) \times 5) \times 9 \\ 2948950 &:= (2 + (9^4 - 8) \times 9) \times 50 \\ 2949115 &:= (-2 + 9 \times 4^{9-1} + 1) \times 5 \\ 2949154 &:= -2 + 9 \times (4^{9-1} \times 5 + 4) \\ 2949155 &:= (2 + 9 \times 4^{9-1} + 5) \times 5 \\ 2951950 &:= (-2 + 9^5 + 1 - 9) \times 50 \\ 2952325 &:= (2 \times 9^5 - 2 - 3) \times 25 \\ 2952350 &:= (-2 + 9^5) \times (-2 + 3) \times 50 \\ 2952432 &:= 2 \times (-9 + (5 \times 243)^2) \\ 2952448 &:= -2 + 9^5 \times (-2 + 4 + 48) \\ 2952450 &:= (2 + 9^5 + 2 - 4) \times 50 \\ 2952452 &:= 2 + 9^5 \times (2 - 4 + 52) \\ 2952525 &:= (2 \times 9^5 - 2 - 5) \times 25 \\ 2952535 &:= (2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 - 3) \times 5 \\ 2952542 &:= ((2 + 9^5) \times 25 - 4) \times 2 \\ 2952550 &:= 2 \times (9^5 \times 25 + 50) \\ 2952562 &:= ((2 + 9^5) \times 25 + 6) \times 2 \\ 2952595 &:= (2 \times (9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 9) \times 5 \\ 2952725 &:= (2 \times (9^5 + 2) + 7) \times 25 \\ 2952850 &:= (2 + 9^5 - 2 + 8) \times 50 \\ 2953773 &:= ((2 + 9)^5 - 3 + 7^7) \times 3 \\ 2954650 &:= (-2 + 9^5 + 46) \times 50 \\ 2955050 &:= (2 + 9^5 + 50) \times 50 \\ 2956583 &:= 2 + 9 \times (5 + 6 + 58)^3 \\ 2957312 &:= 2 \times (9 - (5 \times 7)^{3-1})^2 \\ 2958236 &:= 2 + (95 - 8 \times 2)^3 \times 6 \\ 2963568 &:= (((-2 + 9) \times 6)^3 \times 5 + 6) \times 8 \\ 2963840 &:= (((-2 + 9) \times 6)^3 + 8) \times 40 \\ 2978694 &:= (2^9 \times 7/8 + 6) \times 9^4 \\ 2982912 &:= 2^9 \times (8^2 \times 91 + 2) \\ 2985264 &:= 2 \times 9 \times 8 \times (-5 + (2 \times 6)^4) \\ 2985466 &:= -2^9 + ((8 - 5) \times 4)^6 - 6 \\ 2985626 &:= 2 - 9 \times 8 \times 5 + (6 \times 2)^6 \\ 2985662 &:= 2^9/8 \times (-5 + 6^6) - 2 \\ 2985892 &:= (2 \times 9 \times 8)^{-5+8} - 92 \\ 2985896 &:= -(2 + 9) \times 8 + (-5 + 8 + 9)^6 \\ 2985963 &:= -2 \times 9 + (8 - 5 + 9)^6 - 3 \\ 2985966 &:= -2 \times (9 + 8 \times (5 - 9) \times 6^6) \\ 2985977 &:= (2 \times 9 \times 8)^{5-9+7} - 7 \\ 2985982 &:= -2 + (9/(8 - 5) + 9)^{8-2} \\ 2985984 &:= (2 \times 9 \times 8 \times 5 + 9) \times 8^4 \\ 2985986 &:= 2 + (9 + 8 - 5)^{(9-8) \times 6} \\ 2986216 &:= 29 \times 8 + (6 \times 2 \times 1)^6 \\ 2986282 &:= 298 + (6 \times 2)^{8-2} \\ 2986496 &:= 2^9 + (8 \times 6 - 4 \times 9)^6 \\ 2986688 &:= ((2 + 9) \times 8 + 6^6 \times 8) \times 8 \\ 2986756 &:= -2 + 9 \times 86 + (7 + 5)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2995750 &:= (2^9 + 9) \times 5750 \\ 2996352 &:= 2 \times ((9 + 9) \times (63 + 5))^2 \\ 2999824 &:= (2 + (9 + 99) \times 8)^2 \times 4 \\ 3111664 &:= -31 - 1 + ((1 + 6) \times 6)^4 \\ 3111674 &:= (-3 + 1) \times 11 + (6 \times 7)^4 \\ 3116475 &:= 3^{1+1+6} \times 475 \\ 3124988 &:= 3 + 1 + (-2 + (-4 + 9)^8) \times 8 \\ 3127323 &:= (-3 + 1 \times 2^{7+3})^2 \times 3 \\ 3133452 &:= 3 \times (1^3 - 3 + 4^5)^2 \\ 3145488 &:= (3 - 1 + 4) \times (-5 + 4^8) \times 8 \\ 3145557 &:= 3 \times (1 \times 4^{5+5} - 57) \\ 3145569 &:= 3 \times (1 + 4^{5+5} - 6 \times 9) \\ 3145593 &:= ((3 - 1)^{4 \times 5} - 5 \times 9) \times 3 \\ 3145722 &:= 3 \times (1 \times 4^{5+7-2} - 2) \\ 3145724 &:= 3 \times 1 \times 4^{5+7-2} - 4 \\ 3145725 &:= 3 \times (-1 + 4^{5 \times 7 - 25}) \\ 3145728 &:= (3 - 1)^{4 \times 5} \times (-7 + 2 + 8) \\ 3145731 &:= 3 \times (1 + 4^{5+7-3+1}) \\ 3145746 &:= 3 \times (((1 + 4) \times 5 + 7)^4 + 6) \\ 3145749 &:= 3 \times (-1 + 4 \times (-5 + 7 + 4^9)) \\ 3176379 &:= (3 \times (1 \times 7^6 - 3) - 7) \times 9 \\ 3176418 &:= 3 \times (1 + (7^6 - 4) \times (1 + 8)) \\ 3176439 &:= -3 + (1 + 7^6 - 4) \times 3 \times 9 \\ 3176469 &:= 3 \times (1 \times 7^6 + 4 - 6) \times 9 \\ 3176499 &:= 3 - (1 - 7^6) \times (4 \times 9 - 9) \\ 3176523 &:= ((31 - 7) \times 6 + 5 - 2)^3 \\ 3176525 &:= 3 - 1 + 7^6 \times (-5 + 2^5) \\ 3176526 &:= 3 \times (1 + 7^6 \times (5 - 2 + 6)) \\ 3176529 &:= -3 + (1 + 7^6 \times (5 - 2)) \times 9 \\ 3176545 &:= 3 \times (1 + 7^6) \times (5 + 4) - 5 \\ 3176547 &:= 3 \times (1 + 7^6 \times (5 + 4) + 7) \\ 3176559 &:= (3 \times (1 + 7^6) + 5/5) \times 9 \\ 3176649 &:= (3 \times (1 \times 7^6 + 6) - 4) \times 9 \\ 3176691 &:= 3 \times (1 + (7^6 + 6) \times 9 + 1) \\ 3176694 &:= 3 \times (-1 + (7^6 + 6) \times 9 + 4) \\ 3176709 &:= 3 \times (-1 + (7^6 + 7) \times 09) \\ 3176739 &:= (3 + (1 \times 7^6 + 7) \times 3) \times 9 \\ 3176793 &:= (3 + 1 \times 7^6 + 7) \times 9 \times 3 \\ 3188628 &:= (-3 + (1^8 + 8)^6) \times (-2 + 8) \\ 3188646 &:= 3^{1^8 \times 8 + 6} \times 4/6 \\ 3188662 &:= (3 + (1^8 + 8)^6) \times 6 - 2 \\ 3189375 &:= (3 \times 18 - 9)^3 \times 7 \times 5 \\ 3195396 &:= (3^{1+9} + 5^3) \times 9 \times 6 \\ 3219264 &:= 3^{2+1} \times 92 \times 6^4 \\ 3226955 &:= 3^2 + 2 + 6 \times (9 + 5)^5 \\ 3240125 &:= (3 + 2 \times 401)^2 \times 5 \\ 3247695 &:= (3 - 24 + 76) \times 9^5 \\ 3251250 &:= ((3 + 2) \times 51)^2 \times 50 \\ 3255199 &:= (3 \times (25^5 - 1)/9 - 9) \\ 3255209 &:= 3 \times (25^5 + 2)/09 \\ 3255212 &:= 3 + (25^5 + 2)/(1 + 2) \\ 3255213 &:= 3 + 2 + (5^{5 \times 2} - 1)/3 \\ 3265570 &:= (3 \times 2 \times 6^5 - 5) \times 70 \\ 3265816 &:= 3^{2 \times 6} + 5^8 \times (1 + 6) \\ 3265837 &:= 3^{2 \times 6} + (5^8 + 3) \times 7 \\ 3265915 &:= ((3 \times 2)^6 \times (5 + 9) - 1) \times 5 \\ 3265935 &:= ((3 \times 2)^6 \times (5 + 9) + 3) \times 5 \\ 3266235 &:= (3^2 + 6^6 \times 2) \times 35 \\ 3266970 &:= ((3 \times 2)^6 + 6 + 9) \times 70 \\ 3274850 &:= (-32 - 7 + 4^8) \times 50 \\ 3278125 &:= (3 + 2)^7 + (8 + 12)^5 \\ 3281376 &:= ((3 + 2)^{8-1} + 3) \times 7 \times 6 \\ 3285669 &:= 3 \times ((2 \times 8)^5 + 6^6 - 9) \\ 3286972 &:= 3 + ((2^8 - 6 + 9) \times 7)^2 \\ 3289755 &:= -(3 + 2)^8 + (9 + 7)^5 \times 5 \\ 3290724 &:= (32 + 907^2) \times 4 \\ 3292515 &:= (3 \times 29)^{-2+5} \times 1 \times 5 \\ 3292525 &:= ((3 \times 29)^{-2+5} + 2) \times 5 \\ 3294177 &:= 3 + 2 + (9 - 4 - 1) \times 7^7 \\ 3294187 &:= 3 \times 2 + 9 + 4 \times (-1 + 8)^7 \\ 3294675 &:= 3 \times ((2 + 9)^4 + 6) \times 75 \\ 3307275 &:= (-3 + (30 \times 7)^2) \times 75 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3325582 &:= (3^3 - 5) \times (5 + 8)^2 \\ 3342336 &:= (3 \times 34) \times 2^{3 \times 3 + 6} \\ 3342357 &:= 3 \times (34 \times 2^{3 \times 5} + 7) \\ 3342489 &:= 3 \times (3 + 4^{2 \times 4}) \times (8 + 9) \\ 3352671 &:= -3^{3+5} + 2 \times 6^{7+1} \\ 3352689 &:= -3^{3+5} + 2 \times (6^8 + 9) \\ 3359226 &:= (3 + 3)^{(-5+9) \times 2} \times 2 - 6 \\ 3359232 &:= (3/3 + 5)^{9+2-3} \times 2 \\ 3359243 &:= -3 + (-3 + 5^{9-2}) \times 43 \\ 3359244 &:= (3 + (3 + 5) \times (9 \times 2)^4) \times 4 \\ 3359259 &:= (3 + ((3 + 5) \times 9)^{-2+5}) \times 9 \\ 3359268 &:= (3 \times 3 - 5) \times 9 + 2 \times 6^8 \\ 3359367 &:= 3^3 \times 5 + (9 + 3) \times 6^7 \\ 3359442 &:= (3 \times 35 + (9 \times 4)^4) \times 2 \\ 3365739 &:= 3 \times (-3 \times 6 + 57 \times 3^9) \\ 3365796 &:= 3 + (3 + 6)^5 \times (7 \times 9 - 6) \\ 3374583 &:= 3 \times (-3 + ((-7 + 4 \times 5) \times 8)^3) \\ 3375024 &:= (3 + 3) \times (750^2 + 4) \\ 3375648 &:= 3^3 \times (7 + 5^6 - 4) \times 8 \\ 3407355 &:= (3^4 + 07)^3 \times 5 - 5 \\ 3417974 &:= (3 + (4 + 1^7)^9) \times 7/4 \\ 3421956 &:= 3^4 + 219 \times 5^6 \\ 3429248 &:= (3 \times (42 \times 9)^2 + 4) \times 8 \\ 3444765 &:= -3 + (-4 + 447) \times 6^5 \\ 3445435 &:= (-3 + 44) \times 5 \times (4 + 3)^5 \\ 3449928 &:= (-3 + 44 \times 99^2) \times 8 \\ 3451273 &:= (3 + 4) \times (-5 + 12 \times 7)^3 \\ 3473408 &:= (3 + 47 + 3) \times 4^{08} \\ 3478225 &:= (-3 + 47 \times 8)^2 \times 25 \\ 3479895 &:= 3 \times (4^7 \times 9 \times 8) - 9^5 \\ 3484656 &:= 3 \times ((4 + 8)^4 + 6) \times 56 \\ 3504384 &:= (3 \times 5^{04} - 3)^{8/4} \\ 3511793 &:= -3 \times 5 + (-1 + 17 \times 9)^3 \\ 3512320 &:= (3 + 51 + 2)^3 \times 20 \\ 3515622 &:= -3 + (5^{-1+5} \times 6/2)^2 \\ 3515625 &:= (3 + 5 + 1) \times 5^6 \times 25 \\ 3515778 &:= 3 \times (51 + 5^7 \times (7 + 8)) \\ 3515795 &:= (35 - 1 + 5^7 \times 9) \times 5 \\ 3518739 &:= (3 + (5 \times 1)^8 + 7^3) \times 9 \\ 3529470 &:= 3 \times (5 + 2)^{9-4} \times 70 \\ 3538629 &:= (-35 + 3 \times 8^6/2) \times 9 \\ 3542770 &:= ((3 \times 5)^4 - 2 \times 7) \times 70 \\ 3543115 &:= (35 + 4 \times 3^{11}) \times 5 \\ 3543116 &:= (3 + 5)/4 \times (-3 + 11^6) \\ 3543122 &:= ((3 \times 5 - 4)^3 \times 1)^2 \times 2 \\ 3546270 &:= ((3 \times 5)^4 + 6^2) \times 70 \\ 3556544 &:= 3^5 \times (-5 + (6 + 5)^4) - 4 \\ 3556548 &:= 3^5 \times (-5 + (6 + 5)^{-4+8}) \\ 3562576 &:= (3 \times (5^6 + 2) - 5) \times 76 \\ 3562848 &:= 356 \times ((2 + 8)^4 + 8) \\ 3569184 &:= (-35 + 69) \times 18^4 \\ 3573587 &:= 3 + (-5 + (7 \times 3)^5)/8 \times 7 \\ 3577392 &:= 3 \times ((5 \times 7 - 7) \times 39)^2 \\ 3585746 &:= (-3 \times 58 + 5^7) \times 46 \\ 3594824 &:= 3 + 5 + 948^2 \times 4 \\ 3608550 &:= 3^{6 \times 0 + 8} \times 550 \\ 3639870 &:= (36^3 + 9) \times (8 + 70) \\ 3640464 &:= (3 \times (640 - 4))^{6-4} \\ 3646944 &:= 3 \times 6^4 \times (-6 + 944) \\ 3650103 &:= 3^6 \times (5010 - 3) \\ 3652993 &:= 3^6 + (5 \times 29 + 9)^3 \\ 3656133 &:= (-3 + 6 \times 5^6) \times 13 \times 3 \\ 3656276 &:= (3 \times 6 \times 5^6 + 2) \times (7 + 6) \\ 3656367 &:= 3 \times (6 \times 5^6 + 3) \times (6 + 7) \\ 3657393 &:= -3 + 6 \times (5^7 + 3^{9+3}) \\ 3662877 &:= -(3 + 6)^6 + 2 \times (8^7 + 7) \\ 3672702 &:= 3^6 \times (72 \times 70 - 2) \\ 3672720 &:= (3^6 \times 7 - 2) \times 720 \\ 3676491 &:= (3 \times 67)^{6-4} \times 91 \\ 3685000 &:= (3^6 + 8) \times 5000 \\ 3687936 &:= (36 - 8)^{7-9/3} \times 6 \\ 3696834 &:= 3 \times (6 \times (-9 + 68)^3 + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3697929 &:= (3^6 - 9 - 79)^2 \times 9 \\ 3704832 &:= (-3 + 70) \times 48^3 / 2 \\ 3718953 &:= 3 \times 7 \times (-18 + 9^5) \times 3 \\ 3718967 &:= ((-3 \times 7 + 1) \times 8 + 9^6) \times 7 \\ 3719583 &:= 3 \times 7 \times (1 \times 9^5 - 8) \times 3 \\ 3719643 &:= -3 + 7 \times (1 + 9^6 - 4^3) \\ 3719951 &:= -3 + 7 \times (-19 + 9^{5+1}) \\ 3728761 &:= (3^7 - 2^8)^{7-6+1} \\ 3732555 &:= 3 \times ((7 + 3 + 2)^5 + 5) \times 5 \\ 3735552 &:= (-3 + 7)^{3+5} \times (5 + 52) \\ 3744390 &:= (-3 + 7^4 \times 4) \times 390 \\ 3746522 &:= (37^4 - (6 \times 5)^2) \times 2 \\ 3747328 &:= (-3 + (7 + 4)^{7-3}) \times 2^8 \\ 3747375 &:= ((3 + 7)^4 - 7) \times 375 \\ 3747552 &:= (37^4 - 7 \times 55) \times 2 \\ 3747593 &:= 37^4 \times (7 - 5) - 9^3 \\ 3748224 &:= (-3 + 7) \times 4 \times (8 + 22^4) \\ 3748242 &:= (37^4 - (8 + 2) \times 4) \times 2 \\ 3748253 &:= (37^4 - 8) \times 2 - 53 \\ 3748269 &:= (37^4 + 8) \times 2 - 69 \\ 3748282 &:= (37^4 + 8 - 28) \times 2 \\ 3748289 &:= (37^4 - 8) \times 2 - 8 - 9 \\ 3748292 &:= (37^4 - 8 + 2 - 9) \times 2 \\ 3748312 &:= (37^4 - 8 + 3 \times 1) \times 2 \\ 3748316 &:= 37^4 \times 8 / (3 + 1) - 6 \\ 3748321 &:= 37^{(4+8)/3} \times 2 - 1 \\ 3748322 &:= 37^4 \times (8 \times 3 - 22) \\ 3748326 &:= ((37^4 + 8) / 3 - 2) \times 6 \\ 3748338 &:= (37^4 + 8) \times (-3 - 3 + 8) \\ 3748352 &:= (37^{-4+8} + 3 \times 5) \times 2 \\ 3748382 &:= (37^4 - 8 + 38) \times 2 \\ 3748386 &:= ((37^4 + 8) / 3 + 8) \times 6 \\ 3748392 &:= (37^4 + 8 + 3 \times 9) \times 2 \\ 3748402 &:= (37^{-4+8} + 40) \times 2 \\ 3748422 &:= (37^4 + 8 + 42) \times 2 \\ 3749042 &:= (37^4 + 90 \times 4) \times 2 \\ 3749852 &:= (37^4 + 9 \times 85) \times 2 \\ 3751680 &:= 3 \times (7 + (5 \times 1)^6) \times 80 \\ 3752775 &:= 3 \times (7^5 - 2^7) \times 75 \\ 3758445 &:= (3^{7-5} + 8)^4 \times 45 \\ 3764488 &:= (-3 + 7^6 \times 4 - 4 \times 8) \times 8 \\ 3764624 &:= ((-3 + 7^6) \times 4 - 6) \times 2 \times 4 \\ 3764666 &:= (3 - 7^6) \times (4 - 6 \times 6) - 6 \\ 3764672 &:= (3 - 7^6) \times 4 \times (6 - 7 \times 2) \\ 3764688 &:= ((-3 + 7^6) \times 4 - 6 + 8) \times 8 \\ 3764724 &:= (3 + (7^6 \times 4 - 7) \times 2) \times 4 \\ 3764744 &:= (-3 + 7^6 \times 4) \times (7 + 4/4) \\ 3764759 &:= (3 \times 76 - 4) \times 7^5 - 9 \\ 3764765 &:= -3 + 7^6 \times 4 \times (7 + 6 - 5) \\ 3764768 &:= (3 + 7 + 6) / 4 \times (7^6 \times 8) \\ 3764792 &:= (3 + 7^6 \times 4) \times (7 + 9) / 2 \\ 3764808 &:= (-3 + 7^6 \times 4 + 8) \times 08 \\ 3764832 &:= (3 + 7^6) \times 4 \times 8 - 32 \\ 3764835 &:= 3 + (7^6 \times 4 + 8) \times (3 + 5) \\ 3764848 &:= ((3 + 7^6) \times 4 - 8/4) \times 8 \\ 3764864 &:= (3 + 7^6) \times 48/6 \times 4 \\ 3764865 &:= (3 + 7^6) \times 4 \times 8 + 6 - 5 \\ 3764871 &:= (3 + 7^6) \times 4 \times 8 + 7 \times 1 \\ 3764884 &:= (-3 + (7^6 + 4) \times 8) \times (8 - 4) \\ 3764925 &:= -3 + (7^6 - 4 + 9) \times 2^5 \\ 3765632 &:= (-3 + 7^6 + 5 \times 6) \times 32 \\ 3766848 &:= (-3 + 7^6 + 68) \times 4 \times 8 \\ 3776768 &:= (3 \times 7 - 7 - 6)^7 + 6^8 \\ 3779264 &:= (3^{7/7+9} + 2) \times 64 \\ 3779588 &:= -3 + 7 + (7 + 9^5) \times 8 \times 8 \\ 3781575 &:= (37 + 8 \times 1) \times 5 \times 7^5 \\ 3782475 &:= 3 \times (-7 + 82) \times (4 + 7^5) \\ 3782969 &:= -(3 + 7)^{8-2} + 9^6 \times 9 \\ 3795655 &:= 3^7 / 9 \times (5^6 - 5) - 5 \\ 3796368 &:= (((-3 + 7 + 9) \times 6)^3 - 6) \times 8 \\ 3796875 &:= (3 \times 7 + 9) / 6 \times (8 + 7)^5 \\ 3816336 &:= (3 \times 8 - 1 + 63)^3 \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3819231 &:= ((38 + 1) \times 9)^2 \times 31 \\ 3833853 &:= (38 \times 3 + 3) \times 8^5 - 3 \\ 3844746 &:= 3^8 \times ((4 + 4) \times 74 - 6) \\ 3865224 &:= 3 \times 8 \times (6 + 5)^{2/2+4} \\ 3865233 &:= 3 \times (8 \times (6 + 5)^{2+3} + 3) \\ 3865272 &:= 3 \times 8 \times ((6 + 5)^{-2+7} + 2) \\ 3865512 &:= 3 \times 8 \times ((6 + 5)^5 + 12) \\ 3868711 &:= (3 + 8)^6 + 8^7 - 1 - 1 \\ 3868712 &:= (3 + 8)^6 + 8^7 + 1 - 2 \\ 3868713 &:= (3 + 8)^6 + 8^7 \times 1^3 \\ 3868714 &:= (3 + 8)^6 + 8^7 + 1^4 \\ 3868727 &:= (3 + 8)^6 + 8^7 + 2 \times 7 \\ 3868749 &:= (3 + 8)^6 + 8^7 + 4 \times 9 \\ 3869893 &:= ((3 + 8) \times (6 + 9) - 8)^{9/3} \\ 3875031 &:= (3 \times 8 + 7) \times (50^3 + 1) \\ 3885600 &:= (3^8 - 85) \times 600 \\ 3891945 &:= 389 \times ((1 + 9)^4 + 5) \\ 3893295 &:= ((3 + 89)^3 - 29) \times 5 \\ 3893385 &:= ((3 + 89)^3 - 3 - 8) \times 5 \\ 3893415 &:= ((3 + 89)^3 - 4 - 1) \times 5 \\ 3893435 &:= ((3 + 89)^3 - 4 + 3) \times 5 \\ 3893445 &:= ((3 + 89)^3 + 4/4) \times 5 \\ 3893875 &:= ((3 + 89)^3 + 87) \times 5 \\ 3897276 &:= (3^8 \times (97 + 2) + 7) \times 6 \\ 3906259 &:= 3 \times (9 - 06) + 2 \times 5^9 \\ 3918640 &:= (-3^9 + (-1 + 8)^6) \times 40 \\ 3925911 &:= 3^9 + 2 \times (5^9 - 11) \\ 3925917 &:= 3^9 + 2 \times (5^9 - 1 - 7) \\ 3925923 &:= 3^9 + 2 \times (5^9 - 2 - 3) \\ 3925941 &:= 3^9 + 2 \times (5^9 + 4 \times 1) \\ 3925957 &:= 3^9 + 2 \times (5^9 + 5 + 7) \\ 3931965 &:= (-39 + 3 \times (-1 + 9)^6) \times 5 \\ 3931985 &:= (3 \times (-9 + (3 + 1)^9) - 8) \times 5 \\ 3932175 &:= (3 + (9 - 3) \times 2^{17}) \times 5 \\ 3932295 &:= 3 \times (9 + (3 \times 2 - 2)^9) \times 5 \\ 3934200 &:= (3^9 - 3 \times 4) \times 200 \\ 3936375 &:= -3 + 9 \times (3 \times 6)^3 \times 75 \\ 3936600 &:= 3^9 / (-3 + 6) \times 600 \\ 3937200 &:= (3 + 9 \times 3^7) \times 200 \\ 3938200 &:= ((3 \times 9)^3 + 8) \times 200 \\ 3955747 &:= (-3 + 9^5 - 5) \times (74 - 7) \\ 3956076 &:= (-3 + 9^5) \times (60 + 7) - 6 \\ 3956295 &:= 3 + 9 + (5 + 62) \times 9^5 \\ 3956676 &:= -3 + (9^5 + 6) \times 67 - 6 \\ 3956679 &:= 3 + (9^5 + 6) \times 67 - 9 \\ 3961629 &:= -3^9 + 6^{-1+6} \times 2^9 \\ 3962865 &:= (-3 + 96^2 \times 86) \times 5 \\ 3966185 &:= (-3 + 9 + 6^6 - 1) \times 85 \\ 3969585 &:= ((-3 + 9)^6 + 9 \times 5) \times 85 \\ 3975350 &:= (3 \times (9 + 7) - 5)^3 \times 50 \\ 3997684 &:= -3 - 9 + 976 \times 8^4 \\ 4032126 &:= (40^3 + 2) \times (-1 + 2^6) \\ 4054738 &:= 40 + (5^4 - 7) \times 3^8 \\ 4088832 &:= (4 + 08) \times 88^3 / 2 \\ 4088836 &:= 4 + (0 \times 8 + 88)^3 \times 6 \\ 4088856 &:= (4 + 088^{8-5}) \times 6 \\ 4112649 &:= (-4 - 11 + 26^4) \times 9 \\ 4117565 &:= ((-4 + 11)^7 - 5 \times 6) \times 5 \\ 4117675 &:= -41 + 1 + 7^6 \times 7 \times 5 \\ 4117705 &:= (-4 + 1 + 1 + 7^7) \times 05 \\ 4117761 &:= 41 + (1 + 7^7) \times (6 - 1) \\ 4117765 &:= (4 + (1 - 1 + 7)^7 + 6) \times 5 \\ 4117768 &:= (4 + 1) \times (1 + 7^7) + 6 \times 8 \\ 4117769 &:= (4 + 1) \times 1 \times 7^7 + 6 \times 9 \\ 4117775 &:= (4 + 1) \times 1 \times (7^7 + 7 + 5) \\ 4117785 &:= (4 + 1 + 1 + 7^7 + 8) \times 5 \\ 4117795 &:= (-4 + 11 + 7^7 + 9) \times 5 \\ 4117835 &:= ((-4 + 11)^7 + 8 \times 3) \times 5 \\ 4117925 &:= (41 + 1 + 7^{9-2}) \times 5 \\ 4128579 &:= (-4 + 1 + 2 \times 8^5) \times 7 \times 9 \\ 4134516 &:= (41 \times (3 + 4)^5 - 1) \times 6 \\ 4134546 &:= (41 \times (3 + 4)^5 + 4) \times 6 \\ 4134660 &:= (41^3 - 4 - 6) \times 60 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4134960 &:= (41^3 + 4 - 9) \times 60 \\ 4135284 &:= (41^3 \times 5 + 2) \times (8 + 4) \\ 4135752 &:= 41 \times 3 \times (5 + 7^5) \times 2 \\ 4152923 &:= 4 - 1 + 5 \times (2 + 92)^3 \\ 4161282 &:= (4^{1+6} - 1) \times (2^8 - 2) \\ 4176250 &:= (4 + 17^{6-2}) \times 50 \\ 4186112 &:= -4 + (186 \times 11)^2 \\ 4192256 &:= 4^{1 \times 9 + 2} - 2^{5+6} \\ 4193924 &:= (4^{1+9} - 3 - 92) \times 4 \\ 4194104 &:= (-41 - 9 + 4^{10}) \times 4 \\ 4194152 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 - 152 \\ 4194164 &:= (4^{1+9} - 41 + 6) \times 4 \\ 4194251 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 - 2 - 51 \\ 4194252 &:= 4^{1 \times 9 + 4 - 2} - 52 \\ 4194253 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 2 - 53 \\ 4194254 &:= -41 - 9 + 4^{2 \times 5} \times 4 \\ 4194257 &:= 4 \times (-1 - 9 + 4^{2 \times 5}) - 7 \\ 4194259 &:= 4^{1 \times 9 + 4 - 2} - 5 \times 9 \\ 4194264 &:= (4^{1+9} - 4^2 + 6) \times 4 \\ 4194266 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 - 2 - 6 \times 6 \\ 4194269 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 - 26 - 9 \\ 4194272 &:= 4 \times (1 - 9) + (4 \times 2)^7 \times 2 \\ 4194274 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 - 2 - 7 \times 4 \\ 4194281 &:= -4 - 19 + 4^{2+8+1} \\ 4194284 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 - 2 \times 8 - 4 \\ 4194287 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 - 2 - 8 - 7 \\ 4194288 &:= 4^{1 \times 9 + 4 - 2} - 8 - 8 \\ 4194289 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 2 - 8 - 9 \\ 4194301 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 - 3 \times 01 \\ 4194302 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 - 3 \times 0 - 2 \\ 4194303 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 - 3/03 \\ 4194304 &:= 4^{1^9 \times 4 + 3 + 04} \\ 4194307 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 3 + 0 \times 7 \\ 4194308 &:= 4 + 1^9 \times 4^{3+08} \\ 4194312 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + (3 + 1) \times 2 \\ 4194313 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 3 \times 1 \times 3 \\ 4194315 &:= (4^{1+9} + 4) \times (3 + 1) - 5 \\ 4194316 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + (3 - 1) \times 6 \\ 4194317 &:= 4 \times 1 + 9 + 4^{3+1+7} \\ 4194318 &:= 4 + 1 + 9 + 4^{3 \times 1 + 8} \\ 4194319 &:= -4 + 19 + 4^{3-1+9} \\ 4194322 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 3^2 \times 2 \\ 4194324 &:= ((41 - 9)^4 + 3 + 2) \times 4 \\ 4194325 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 3 \times (2 + 5) \\ 4194327 &:= 4 + 19 + 4^{-3+2 \times 7} \\ 4194328 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 32 - 8 \\ 4194331 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 3^3 \times 1 \\ 4194344 &:= 4 \times (1 + 9) + 4^{3+4+4} \\ 4194346 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + (3 + 4) \times 6 \\ 4194354 &:= 41 + 9 + 4^{3 \times 5 - 4} \\ 4194367 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + (3 + 6) \times 7 \\ 4194372 &:= 4 \times (19 + 4^{3+7} - 2) \\ 4194375 &:= 4 \times (19 + 4^{3+7}) - 5 \\ 4194432 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 4 \times 32 \\ 4194433 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 43 \times 3 \\ 4194452 &:= 4 \times (1 + 9 \times 4 + 4^{5 \times 2}) \\ 4194464 &:= 4 \times (1 + 9 + (4 + 4)^6) \times 4 \\ 4194504 &:= ((41 - 9)^4 + 50) \times 4 \\ 4194529 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 5^2 \times 9 \\ 4194549 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 5 \times 49 \\ 4194688 &:= ((4 \times 1)^9 / 4 + 6) \times 8 \times 8 \\ 4194723 &:= 419 + 4^{7 \times 2 - 3} \\ 4194766 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 7 \times 66 \\ 4194816 &:= ((4 \times 1)^9 + 4 \times 8) \times 16 \\ 4194864 &:= 4 \times (-1 + 9 \times 4 + 8^6) \times 4 \\ 4194944 &:= (4 \times (1 + 9) + 4^9) \times 4 \times 4 \\ 4194997 &:= 4^{1+9} \times 4 + 99 \times 7 \\ 4195704 &:= (4^{1+9} + 5 \times 70) \times 4 \\ 4195924 &:= (4^{1+9} + 5 \times 9^2) \times 4 \\ 4197888 &:= (4^{-1+9} + 7 \times 8) \times 8 \times 8 \\ 4218754 &:= 4 + (-2 - 1 + 8)^7 \times 54 \\ 4239872 &:= (4 \times 2)^3 \times (98 - 7)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4251496 &:= 4 \times (2 - 5 + 1) \times (4 - 9^6) \\4251528 &:= (4 \times 2 - 5)^{(1+5) \times 2} \times 8 \\4251696 &:= 4 \times 2 \times (5 + 16 + 9^6) \\4251968 &:= 4 \times (2 \times (51 + 9^6) + 8) \\4252175 &:= 4 + (252 + 1) \times 7^5 \\4284296 &:= 4 \times (2 \times 8^4 + 2 \times 9^6) \\4285275 &:= (4 + 2^8 - 5) \times (-2 + 7^5) \\4287616 &:= (4 - 2) \times (8^7 + (6 \times 1)^6) \\4292336 &:= -4^2 + 92 \times (3 + 3)^6 \\4302586 &:= (4 \times 3 + 02)^5 \times 8 - 6 \\4324848 &:= (4^3 - 2 + 4) \times (-8 + 4^8) \\4334722 &:= 4 \times (3 \times 347)^2 - 2 \\4342992 &:= -4^3 + (4 \times (2^9 + 9))^2 \\4359356 &:= -4 + 3 \times (-5 + 93 \times 5^6) \\4373936 &:= -4^3 + ((7 + 3) \times 9)^3 \times 6 \\4374957 &:= -43 + (7 + 49) \times 5^7 \\4375035 &:= (4 + 3 + 7 \times 50^3) \times 5 \\4377500 &:= (4 \times 3^7 + 7) \times 500 \\4386694 &:= -4 + (3 + 8 + 6^6) \times 94 \\4393952 &:= -(4^3 + 9)^3 + 9^{5+2} \\4410937 &:= (4 \times 41)^{0 \times 9 + 3} - 7 \\4428675 &:= (4/4 + 2)^8 \times 675 \\4429575 &:= (4 + 4 \times 2 + 9^5) \times 75 \\4431975 &:= (44 + 3^{1+9}) \times 75 \\4435236 &:= 4 \times (4 + 35)^2 \times 3^6 \\4452357 &:= ((-4 + 45 \times 2)^3 - 5) \times 7 \\4452392 &:= (-4 + 45 \times 2)^3 \times (9 - 2) \\4455516 &:= (4 + 4 + 5)^5 \times (5 + 1 + 6) \\4456448 &:= (4 \times 4 - 5 + 6) \times 4 \times 4^8 \\4473917 &:= (4 + 4^7) \times 3 \times 91 - 7 \\4477446 &:= -4 + (-4 \times 7 + 74)^4 - 6 \\4477448 &:= (4/4 + 7 \times 7 - 4)^4 - 8 \\4477464 &:= 4 + 4 + 7 - 7 + 46^4 \\4477644 &:= 4 \times 47 + (7 \times 6 + 4)^4 \\4478973 &:= 4 \times 4 \times (7 + 8 - 9)^7 - 3 \\4483072 &:= 4^4 \times 8 \times (3^{07} + 2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4484877 &:= -4 + 48^4 + 8 - 7^7 \\4492125 &:= (-4 + (4 + 9)^2)^{-1 \times 2 + 5} \\4498556 &:= -4 + (4 \times 9 \times 8) \times (-5 + 5^6) \\4499856 &:= 4 \times (-4 \times 9 + 9 \times 8 \times 5^6) \\4532969 &:= -(4 \times (5^3))^2 + 9^6 \times 9 \\4538462 &:= (-4 + 5 \times (3 + 8)^4) \times 62 \\4553975 &:= (4^{5+5} - 3^9 \times 7) \times 5 \\4556196 &:= ((4 \times 5 - 5)^{6-1} - 9) \times 6 \\4556250 &:= ((4 + 5) \times 5)^{6/2} \times 50 \\4556256 &:= (-4 + 5 + (5 \times 6/2)^5) \times 6 \\4556295 &:= (45 \times 5 - 6)^2 \times 95 \\4562496 &:= -4 + 5^6 \times (-2 + 49 \times 6) \\4563376 &:= 4 \times (5^6 + 3) \times (-3 + 76) \\4574296 &:= ((4 + 5 + 74) \times 2)^{9-6} \\4579245 &:= (4 + 5 \times 7 \times 9)^2 \times 45 \\4587475 &:= -45 + 8 \times 7 \times 4^7 \times 5 \\4587479 &:= 4 + 5 \times (8 \times 7 \times 4^7 - 9) \\4588528 &:= (-4 + 5 \times (8 + 8^5)) \times 28 \\4592700 &:= ((4 + 5) \times 9)^2 \times 700 \\4593726 &:= (-4 + 5^{9-3} \times 7^2) \times 6 \\4595616 &:= (-4 + 595) \times 6^{-1+6} \\4616157 &:= (4^6 \times 161 - 5) \times 7 \\4616192 &:= 4^6 \times 161 \times (9 - 2) \\4644936 &:= (-4^6 + 4 + 4^9) \times 3 \times 6 \\4644986 &:= -4 + ((6 \times 4)^4 + 9) \times (8 + 6) \\4645214 &:= ((4 \times 6)^4 + 5^2) \times 14 \\4651897 &:= (4 - 6) \times (5 - 1)^8 + 9^7 \\4652488 &:= (4 + 65 + 2) \times (4^8 - 8) \\4657463 &:= (-4 + 6 \times 57 / (-4 + 6))^3 \\4665125 &:= (4 \times (6^6 - 5) + 1) \times 25 \\4665280 &:= 4 \times (6^6 \times 5^2 - 80) \\4665360 &:= (-4 + 6^6 \times 5/3) \times 60 \\4665520 &:= 4 \times (6^6 \times 5 \times 5 - 20) \\4665550 &:= 4 \times (6^6 \times 5 \times 5 - 50) \\4665552 &:= 4 \times 6 \times (6^5 \times 5 \times 5 - 2) \\4665556 &:= 4 \times (6^6 \times 5 \times 5 - 5 - 6)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4665568 &:= 4 \times (6^6 \times 5 \times 5 - 6) - 8 \\ 4665571 &:= 4 \times (6^6 \times 5 \times 5 - 7) - 1 \\ 4665584 &:= 4 \times (6^6 \times 5 \times 5 - 8 + 4) \\ 4665585 &:= (4 \times 6^6 \times 5 + 5 - 8) \times 5 \\ 4665586 &:= 4 \times 6^6 \times 5 \times 5 - 8 - 6 \\ 4665591 &:= 4 \times 6^6 \times 5 \times 5 - 9 \times 1 \\ 4665592 &:= (-4 + 6^6 \times (5 + 5 \times 9)) \times 2 \\ 4665596 &:= -4 + 6^6 \times 5 \times (5 + 9 + 6) \\ 4665599 &:= 4 \times 6^6 \times 5 \times 5 - 9/9 \\ 4665625 &:= (4 \times 6^6 - 5 + 6) \times 25 \\ 4665655 &:= (4 \times 6^6 \times 5 + 6 + 5) \times 5 \\ 4665725 &:= (4 \times 6^6 + 5) \times (7 - 2) \times 5 \\ 4665775 &:= (4 \times (6^6 \times 5 + 7) + 7) \times 5 \\ 4666520 &:= (46 + 6^6 \times 5) \times 20 \\ 4667544 &:= 4 \times 6 \times (-6 + 7 + 5 \times 4)^4 \\ 4667544 &:= 4 \times 6 \times (-6 + 7 + 5 \times 4)^4 \\ 4668800 &:= (4 + 6^6/8) \times 800 \\ 4687556 &:= 4 \times (6 + 8 + 75 \times 5^6) \\ 4687584 &:= 4 \times 6/8 \times (7 + 5^8) \times 4 \\ 4688732 &:= -4 + 6 \times (887 - 3)^2 \\ 4715760 &:= (471 + 5^7) \times 60 \\ 4718348 &:= 4 \times (-7 + 18 \times (-3 + 4^8)) \\ 4718529 &:= (4^{7+1} \times 8 - 5 - 2) \times 9 \\ 4718549 &:= 47 + 18 \times (-5 + 4^9) \\ 4718568 &:= (4 - 7) \times (1 - 8^5 \times 6) \times 8 \\ 4718592 &:= 4 \times (7 + 1) \times 8^5 \times 9/2 \\ 4718616 &:= ((-4 + 7) \times (1 + 8^6) + 1) \times 6 \\ 4718629 &:= 4 \times 7 + (1 + 8^6 \times 2) \times 9 \\ 4718636 &:= -4 + (7 + 1 + 8^6 \times 3) \times 6 \\ 4718646 &:= (4 - 7) \times (1 - 8^6 - 4) \times 6 \\ 4718688 &:= (4^7 \times 18 + 6) \times (8 + 8) \\ 4718692 &:= (-4 + (7 - 1 + 8^6) \times 9) \times 2 \\ 4718848 &:= (4^7 \times (1 + 8) + 8) \times 4 \times 8 \\ 4719672 &:= (4^{7+1} + 9 + 6) \times 72 \\ 4723968 &:= ((4 \times 7 + 2) \times 3^9 + 6) \times 8 \\ 4733817 &:= -4^7 \times 3 + 3^{8-1+7} \\ 4734964 &:= 4^7 + 3 \times (4^9 \times 6 - 4) \\ 4734968 &:= 4^7 + 3 \times 4^9 \times 6 - 8 \\ 4739574 &:= 47 \times (5 \times 9 - 3) \times 7^4 \\ 4739574 &:= 47 \times 3 \times (9 + 5) \times 7^4 \\ 4741631 &:= (4 \times 7)^{4-1} \times 6^3 - 1 \\ 4741633 &:= 4 + (7 \times 4 \times 1 \times 6)^3 - 3 \\ 4741643 &:= 4 + 7 + (4 + 164)^3 \\ 4741683 &:= 47 + 4 + 168^3 \\ 4743428 &:= 4 \times ((7 + 4) \times 3)^4 - 2^8 \\ 4743684 &:= 4 \times (7 \times 4 + 3 - 6 + 8)^4 \\ 4751360 &:= 4^7 \times 5 \times (1 - 3 + 60) \\ 4752372 &:= -4 \times 7 + (-5 - 2 + 3^7)^2 \\ 4753158 &:= (4^7 \times 5 + 31) \times 58 \\ 4758967 &:= (4 + 7) \times 5 + (8 + 9) \times 6^7 \\ 4767737 &:= 4^7 \times (6 \times 7 \times 7 - 3) - 7 \\ 4767744 &:= 4^7 \times (6 \times 7 - 7 + 4^4) \\ 4773969 &:= ((-4 + 7 + 7)^3 + 9^6) \times 9 \\ 4775926 &:= 4 \times 7 \times (7 \times 59)^2 - 6 \\ 4778297 &:= (4 - 77) \times 8^2 + 9^7 \\ 4779397 &:= -47 \times (79 - 3) + 9^7 \\ 4779567 &:= (4 + 77) \times (9^5 - 6 \times 7) \\ 4781597 &:= -4 \times 7^{8 \times 1 - 5} + 9^7 \\ 4782497 &:= 4 - 7 \times (8^2 + 4) + 9^7 \\ 4782657 &:= -4 \times 78 + (-2 + 6 + 5)^7 \\ 4782697 &:= -4 \times (7 \times 8 + 2 \times 6) + 9^7 \\ 4782817 &:= 4 - 78 \times 2 + (8 + 1)^7 \\ 4782897 &:= (4 - 7 - 8 + 2) \times 8 + 9^7 \\ 4782907 &:= -4 - 7 \times 8 - 2 + 9^{07} \\ 4782916 &:= 4 + 7 - 8^2 + 9^{1+6} \\ 4782917 &:= -4 \times (7 + 8 - 2) + (9 \times 1)^7 \\ 4782918 &:= -47 - 8/2 + 9^{-1+8} \\ 4782925 &:= -(4 + 7) \times 8/2 + 9^{2+5} \\ 4782929 &:= -(4 \times 7 - 8) \times 2 + 9^{-2+9} \\ 4782934 &:= 47 - 82 + 9^{3+4} \\ 4782943 &:= (4 - 7) \times 8 - 2 + 9^{4+3} \\ 4782952 &:= 47 - 8^2 + 9^{5+2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4782961 &:= 4 \times (7 - 8) \times 2 + 9^{6+1} \\ 4782963 &:= (4 - 7) \times (8 - (2 + 9^6) \times 3) \\ 4782969 &:= ((4 + 7 - 8 - 2) \times 9)^6 \times 9 \\ 4782981 &:= 4 \times 7 - 8 \times 2 + 9^{8-1} \\ 4782996 &:= 4 + 7 + 8 \times 2 + 9 \times 9^6 \\ 4782997 &:= 4 \times 7 + ((8 + 2 - 9) \times 9)^7 \\ 4783133 &:= -4 + (7 \times 8 + 3^{13}) \times 3 \\ 4783197 &:= 4 \times 7 \times 8 + 3 + 1 + 9^7 \\ 4783277 &:= 4 \times 7 \times (8 + 3) + (2 + 7)^7 \\ 4783281 &:= 4 \times 78 + (3^2)^{8-1} \\ 4783297 &:= 4 + (7 + 8 + 3)^2 + 9^7 \\ 4783597 &:= 4 + 78 \times (3 + 5) + 9^7 \\ 4783697 &:= 4 \times 7 \times (8 + 3 \times 6) + 9^7 \\ 4783897 &:= 4 \times 78 \times 3 - 8 + 9^7 \\ 4784397 &:= 4 \times 7 \times (8 + 43) + 9^7 \\ 4785146 &:= -4 + (7 + 8^5) \times 146 \\ 4785359 &:= 478 \times 5 + 3^{5+9} \\ 4787372 &:= 4 \times 7 + (8 - 7 + 3^7)^2 \\ 4787897 &:= (4 + 7) \times 8 \times 7 \times 8 + 9^7 \\ 4789525 &:= (-4 + 7)^8 + 9^{5+2} - 5 \\ 4791297 &:= 47 + 91^2 + 9^7 \\ 4793397 &:= 4 \times 79 \times 33 + 9^7 \\ 4799342 &:= 4^7 - 9 + 9^{3+4} - 2 \\ 4799353 &:= 4^7 + 9 \times 9^{3 \times (5-3)} \\ 4799362 &:= 4^7 + 9 + 9^{3+6-2} \\ 4813632 &:= -4 + (8 - 1 + 3^6 \times 3)^2 \\ 4816896 &:= 4^8 \times (1 + 6 \times 8) \times 9/6 \\ 4826723 &:= -4 - 82 + (6 + 7)^{2 \times 3} \\ 4826793 &:= -4 \times 8/2 + (6 + 7)^{9-3} \\ 4826813 &:= 4 + (82 + 6 + 81)^3 \\ 4828574 &:= (4^8 - 285) \times 74 \\ 4831530 &:= ((-4 + 8) \times 3 - 1)^5 \times 30 \\ 4832897 &:= (-4 + 83)^2 \times 8 + 9^7 \\ 4848457 &:= 4^8 - 48 + (4 + 5)^7 \\ 4848497 &:= 4^8 - 4 - 8 + 4 + 9^7 \\ 4848697 &:= 4^8 + 4 \times 8 \times 6 + 9^7 \\ 4849368 &:= (4^8 - 4) \times (9 - 3 + 68) \\ 4849664 &:= 4^8 \times (4^{9-6} + 6 + 4) \\ 4855285 &:= (-4 + (8 - 5)^5)^2 \times 85 \\ 4861944 &:= 486 \times ((1 + 9)^4 + 4) \\ 4875264 &:= (-4 + 8 \times 7 \times 5)^2 \times 64 \\ 4882812 &:= ((4 + 8/8)^{2+8} - 1)/2 \\ 4915575 &:= (4^{9-15} + 5) \times 75 \\ 4917248 &:= (4 + 9 + 17 - 2)^4 \times 8 \\ 4917284 &:= 4 \times 9 + (1 + 7) \times 28^4 \\ 4923522 &:= (4 + 9 + (2 + 3)^5)^2/2 \\ 4939776 &:= (-4 - 9 \times 3 \times 9 + 7^7) \times 6 \\ 4941257 &:= 49^4 - 1 - (2 + 5)^7 \\ 4941258 &:= 49^{4-1} \times (2 + 5 \times 8) \\ 4943445 &:= (4 + 9^4) \times 3 \times (4^4 - 5) \\ 4946994 &:= (4 + 9) \times (4 + 6 \times 9) \times 9^4 \\ 4958373 &:= (4 \times 9^5 - 83) \times 7 \times 3 \\ 4973238 &:= (4 \times 9 \times 7 \times 3 + 2) \times 3^8 \\ 4974836 &:= 4 \times (-9 + 7^4 \times (8^3 + 6)) \\ 4976595 &:= (4 \times ((9 - 7) \times 6)^5 - 9) \times 5 \\ 4980736 &:= 4^9 \times (8 - 07 + 3 \times 6) \\ 4983576 &:= ((-4 + 98)^3 + 5 + 7) \times 6 \\ 5032969 &:= 50^3 \times 2 + 9^6 \times 9 \\ 5036448 &:= (-50 + (3 \times 6)^4) \times 48 \\ 5038683 &:= (-5 \times (03 + 8) + 6^8) \times 3 \\ 5038798 &:= -50 + 3 \times (8 + 7 - 9)^8 \\ 5038848 &:= 5 \times 0 + 3 \times (8 - 8/4)^8 \\ 5039068 &:= -50 + 3 \times (90 + 6^8) \\ 5046277 &:= 5 + 04^{6+2} \times 77 \\ 5092545 &:= 509 \times ((2 \times 5)^4 + 5) \\ 5098853 &:= 5^{09} + (8 + 8)^5 \times 3 \\ 5119483 &:= -5 + (-1 + (1 + 9)^4) \times 8^3 \\ 5153566 &:= (5 \times 1 \times 5 - 3)^5 - 66 \\ 5153627 &:= -5 + (1 + 5 \times 3 + 6)^{-2+7} \\ 5153632 &:= (5 \times 1 \times 5 - 3)^{6-3+2} \\ 5156556 &:= (51 + 5^6 \times 55) \times 6 \\ 5173592 &:= 5^{1+7} + 3^{5+9} - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5174576 &:= (51 - 7) \times (-45 + 7^6) \\ 5176517 &:= 5 + (-1 + 7^6) \times (51 - 7) \\ 5176556 &:= (51 - 7) \times (6 + 5/5)^6 \\ 5176644 &:= (-5 + 1 + 7^6 + 6) \times 44 \\ 5183995 &:= (5 \times 1 \times 8)^3 \times 9 \times 9 - 5 \\ 5211042 &:= 521 \times (10^4 + 2) \\ 5239755 &:= 5 \times 2^{3 \times 9 - 7} - 5^5 \\ 5240880 &:= (-5^2 + 4^{08}) \times 80 \\ 5242480 &:= 5 \times (2^4 \times 2)^4 - 80 \\ 5242565 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5} - 65) \\ 5242730 &:= 5 \times (2^{4 \times (-2+7)} - 30) \\ 5242755 &:= 5 \times (2^{4 \times (-2+7)} - 5 \times 5) \\ 5242790 &:= 5 \times (2^{4 \times (-2+7)} - 90) \\ 5242799 &:= 5 \times (2^{4 \times (-2+7)} - 9 \times 9) \\ 5242815 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 15) \\ 5242826 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8}) - 2^6 \\ 5242835 &:= 5 \times (-2 + 4^{2+8}) - 35 \\ 5242840 &:= 5 \times 2^{4+2 \times 8} - 40 \\ 5242845 &:= 5 \times (2 + 4^{2+8} - 4 - 5) \\ 5242846 &:= 5 \times (-2 + 4^{2+8}) - 4 \times 6 \\ 5242848 &:= 5 \times 2^{4+2 \times 8} - 4 \times 8 \\ 5242870 &:= 5 \times (-2 + 4^{2+8}) + 7 \times 0 \\ 5242915 &:= 5 + 2 + 4^{2+9-1} \times 5 \\ 5242925 &:= 5 \times (2 \times 9/2 + 4^{2 \times 5}) \\ 5242945 &:= (52 + 4^{2+9})/4 \times 5 \\ 5243280 &:= 5 \times (2^{4 \times (3+2)} + 80) \\ 5244880 &:= (5^{-2+4} + 4^8) \times 80 \\ 5245530 &:= 5 \times (2^{4 \times 5} + 530) \\ 5246525 &:= 5 \times ((-2 + 5)^6 + 4^{2 \times 5}) \\ 5248800 &:= (5 + 2 - 4)^8 \times 800 \\ 5254885 &:= 5 \times ((2 + 5)^4 + (8 + 8)^5) \\ 5265675 &:= (5^2 + 6^5) \times 675 \\ 5268330 &:= (-5 + (2^6 - 8)^3) \times 30 \\ 5293845 &:= ((5 + 2)^{9-3} - 8) \times 45 \\ 5308424 &:= 5 + 3 + (08 \times (4 + 2))^4 \\ 5314392 &:= (5 \times (3 \times 1)^{4 \times 3} - 9) \times 2 \\ 5314412 &:= (5 \times (31 - 4)^4 + 1) \times 2 \\ 5314653 &:= (-5 + (-3 + 14)^6 - 5) \times 3 \\ 5314667 &:= 5 + 3 \times ((1 + 4 + 6)^6 - 7) \\ 5314669 &:= -5 + 3 \times (1 + 4 + 6)^6 - 9 \\ 5315567 &:= (5 - 3 + 15^5 - 6) \times 7 \\ 5315571 &:= -53 + 15^5 \times 7 - 1 \\ 5315597 &:= ((5 \times 3 \times 1)^5 + 5 - 9) \times 7 \\ 5315617 &:= -5 - 3 + 15^{6-1} \times 7 \\ 5315625 &:= (5 + 3 - 1) \times (5 \times 6/2)^5 \\ 5334381 &:= (5 + (3 + 3^4)^3) \times (8 + 1) \\ 5345324 &:= (-5 + 34^{(5+3)/2}) \times 4 \\ 5345344 &:= ((5 + 3) \times 4 + 5 - 3)^4 \times 4 \\ 5345364 &:= (5 + 34^{-5+3+6}) \times 4 \\ 5356974 &:= (5 \times 35)^{-6+9} - 7^4 \\ 5359225 &:= 5 \times (3 + 5 \times 92)^2 \times 5 \\ 5359347 &:= (5 \times 35)^{9/3} - 4 \times 7 \\ 5359373 &:= -5 + 3 + 5^{9-3} \times 7^3 \\ 5359375 &:= (5 \times 35)^{(9-3)/(7-5)} \\ 5359376 &:= (5 \times 35)^{9/3} + 7 - 6 \\ 5365465 &:= 5 \times (3 \times 6^5 \times 46) + 5 \\ 5373912 &:= (5 + 3^{7+3}) \times 91 - 2 \\ 5378235 &:= -5 + (3 + 7) \times (8 + 2 \times 3)^5 \\ 5378245 &:= 5 + (3 + 7) \times (8 + 2 + 4)^5 \\ 5384120 &:= (5 + 3^8) \times 41 \times 20 \\ 5411762 &:= (5 + 41) \times (1 \times 7^6 - 2) \\ 5418656 &:= (5^4 + 1) \times 8656 \\ 5429592 &:= -54^2 + 9^5 \times 92 \\ 5439483 &:= -5 + (4 + 3 + 9)^4 \times 83 \\ 5439488 &:= (5^4 + 39) \times 4^8/8 \\ 5462275 &:= (54 \times 6 + 2/2) \times 7^5 \\ 5463745 &:= 5^4 \times (-6 + 3^7 \times 4) - 5 \\ 5468742 &:= (5^{4 \times (-6+8)} \times 7 - 4) \times 2 \\ 5468750 &:= 5^{4-6+8} \times 7 \times 50 \\ 5468762 &:= (5^{4 \times (-6+8)} \times 7 + 6) \times 2 \\ 5469484 &:= (5^4 - 6) \times 94^{8/4} \\ 5473434 &:= -(5 + 4)^7 + 3 \times 43^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5475564 &:= (-5 + (4 + 7)^5) \times (5 \times 6 + 4) \\5475739 &:= 5 + (4 + 7)^5 \times (7 + 3 \times 9) \\5514264 &:= (5^5 + 1) \times 42^{6-4} \\5529926 &:= (-5 + 52) \times (9 + (9 - 2)^6) \\5545233 &:= ((5 + 5) \times 4 \times 5 - 23)^3 \\5571342 &:= (-5 + 57 - 1)^3 \times 42 \\5584653 &:= (5 \times 5 - 8) \times (4 + 65)^3 \\5595390 &:= (5^5 + 9^5 - 3) \times 90 \\5598745 &:= 5 \times (5 + 9 - 8)^7 \times 4 + 5 \\5624190 &:= ((5^6 - 2) \times 4 - 1) \times 90 \\5639220 &:= ((56 + 3) \times 9)^2 \times 20 \\5639752 &:= (-5 - 6 + 3 \times 9 \times 7)^{5-2} \\5643755 &:= 5 + 6 \times 43 \times 7 \times 5^5 \\5647162 &:= (5 + 6 \times 4 \times (7 \times 1)^6) \times 2 \\5647688 &:= (-5 + 6 \times (4 + 7^6 + 8)) \times 8 \\5657284 &:= (-5 + 6^5) \times 728 - 4 \\5658248 &:= (5 \times 6 + 5 - 8 + 2)^4 \times 8 \\5658368 &:= (-5 + 6^5) \times 8^3 + 6^8 \\5667687 &:= 5 + 66 \times 7^6 - 8^7 \\5668893 &:= (56 + 6^8) / 8 \times 9 \times 3 \\5672349 &:= (5 + 6^{7-2}) \times 3^4 \times 9 \\5679634 &:= -5 + (6^7 + 9^6) \times (3 + 4) \\5679672 &:= (5 + 6^7 + 9^6) \times 7 - 2 \\5679697 &:= -5 + (6^7 + 9^6 + 9) \times 7 \\5684329 &:= 5^6 + 8 \times 4 \times 3^{2+9} \\5692845 &:= 569 \times ((2 + 8)^4 + 5) \\5695312 &:= (5 \times ((6 + 9)^5 \times 3) - 1) / 2 \\5695325 &:= (5 + (6 + 9)^5 \times 3) / 2 \times 5 \\5695362 &:= ((5 + 6) \times 9 + (5 \times 3)^6) / 2 \\5702375 &:= (5 \times 7)^3 \times (2^{07} + 5) \\5714375 &:= -5 + (7^{-1+4} - 3) \times 7^5 \\5714375 &:= -5 + (7^3 - 4 + 1) \times 7^5 \\5729772 &:= (5 + 7) \times (-2 + 9 \times 77)^2 \\5731228 &:= (-5 + 7^{3+1} - 2)^2 - 8 \\5737875 &:= 5 \times (7 \times 3^7 - 8) \times 75 \\5738683 &:= -5 + 738 \times 6^{8-3}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5740816 &:= (-5 + 7^4)^{08 \times 1 - 6} \\5740875 &:= (-5 \times 7 + 80)^4 \times 7 / 5 \\5758238 &:= (5 \times 7 / 5)^8 - 2 - 3^8 \\5761777 &:= (-5 - 7 \times 61 + 7^7) \times 7 \\5763777 &:= 5 + (7^6 - 3 \times 7) \times 7 \times 7 \\5764348 &:= -5 - 7 \times 64 + (3 + 4)^8 \\5764378 &:= -5 \times 76 - 43 + 7^8 \\5764548 &:= (-5 + 7^6) \times (45 + 4) - 8 \\5764698 &:= -5 + 7^{6-4+6} + 98 \\5764724 &:= -5 - 76 + 4 + 7^{2 \times 4} \\5764726 &:= 5 - 76 - 4 + 7^{2+6} \\5764735 &:= 5 - 7 - 64 + 7^{3+5} \\5764742 &:= -57 - 6 + 4 + 7^{4 \times 2} \\5764744 &:= -57 + (6 + 47 - 4)^4 \\5764752 &:= (-5 + 7^6 + 4) \times 7 \times (5 + 2) \\5764753 &:= (5 - 7) \times 6 \times 4 + 7^{5+3} \\5764775 &:= -5 + 7 \times (6 - 4 + 7^7 - 5) \\5764776 &:= -5 - 7 \times (6 - 4 - 7^7) - 6 \\5764777 &:= 5 - 7 + 6 - (4 - 7^7) \times 7 \\5764778 &:= (5 - 7) \times 6 - 4 - 7 + 7^8 \\5764781 &:= (5 - 7) \times (6 + 4) + 7^8 \times 1 \\5764783 &:= 5 \times (7 - 6 - 4) + 7^8 - 3 \\5764785 &:= -5 \times 7 + 6 \times 4 + 7^8 - 5 \\5764786 &:= 5 - 7 \times (6 - 4) + 7^8 - 6 \\5764787 &:= 57 - 64 + 7^8 - 7 \\5764788 &:= -5 + ((7 - 6)^4 \times 7)^8 - 8 \\5764789 &:= (5 - 7) \times 6 / 4 + 7^8 - 9 \\5764791 &:= -5 - 7 + 6 - 4 + 7^{9-1} \\5764792 &:= 5 + 7 \times (-6 + 4 + 7^{9-2}) \\5764793 &:= -5 + 7^{6 \times 4 - 7 - 9} - 3 \\5764796 &:= -5 + 7^6 \times (-47 + 96) \\5764797 &:= 5 - 7 - 6 + 4 + 7^9 / 7 \\5764798 &:= 5 + 7^{6 \times 4 - 7 - 9} - 8 \\5764801 &:= (-57 + 64)^8 \times 01 \\5764803 &:= 5 + 7^{64/8} - 03 \\5764806 &:= 5 + 7^{6+4-8+06}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5764858 &:= 57 + (6 + 4 - 8 + 5)^8 \\5764875 &:= 5 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5 \\5764878 &:= 5 \times 7 - 6 + 48 + 7^8 \\5764973 &:= (5 + 7^6) \times 49 - 73 \\5764982 &:= (5 + 7^6) \times 49 - 8^2 \\5767855 &:= 5 - 76 + 7^8 + 5^5 \\5768777 &:= (576 - 8 + 7^7) \times 7 \\5769678 &:= 5 + 7 \times 696 + 7^8 \\5772975 &:= (5^7 - 9 \times 2^7) \times 75 \\5774352 &:= -57 + (7^4 - 3 + 5)^2 \\5778304 &:= (-5 + 7^7) \times 8 + 30^4 \\5781842 &:= (5^7 + 8) \times (18 \times 4 + 2) \\5782575 &:= (5^7 - (8/2)^5) \times 75 \\5782762 &:= 5 + 7^8 + (2^7 + 6)^2 \\5786874 &:= (5^7 + 8 + 68) \times 74 \\5788125 &:= 5 \times (7 \times (8 + 8 - 1))^{-2+5} \\5794888 &:= (5 \times 7 \times 9 + 4^8) \times 88 \\5803236 &:= (-5 + 803^2) \times (3 + 6) \\5814648 &:= 581 \times ((4 + 6)^4 + 8) \\5832764 &:= -5^8 - 3 + 2 \times (7 \times 6)^4 \\5834430 &:= (5 \times (8 - 3) - 4)^4 \times 30 \\5846470 &:= (5 + 8/4 \times 6)^4 \times 70 \\5851635 &:= (5^8 - 516) \times 3 \times 5 \\5856675 &:= (5^8/5 - 6 \times 6) \times 75 \\5856974 &:= 5^8 \times 5 \times (-6 + 9) - 7^4 \\5857215 &:= (5^8 - (5 + 7)^2) \times 15 \\5858475 &:= (5^8/5 - 8 - 4) \times 75 \\5859135 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + 1) - 3^5 \\5859168 &:= (-5 + 8) \times ((5^9 - 1) - 68) \\5859183 &:= (5^8 \times 5 - (9 - 1) \times 8) \times 3 \\5859201 &:= (-58 + 5^9) \times (2 + 01) \\5859225 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 - 2 \times 25) \\5859243 &:= (5^8 \times 5 - (9 + 2) \times 4) \times 3 \\5859247 &:= (-5 + 8) \times 5^9 - (-2 + 4)^7 \\5859255 &:= (-5 \times 8 + 5^9) \times (2 + 5/5) \\5859259 &:= (-58 + 5^9) \times 2 + 5^9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5859276 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 - 27 - 6) \\5859277 &:= (-5 + 8) \times 5^9 - 2 \times 7 \times 7 \\5859279 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 - 2 \times (7 + 9)) \\5859285 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + (2 - 8) \times 5) \\5859285 &:= 5^8 + 2 \times (-9 + 5^8) \times 5 \\5859291 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 - 29 + 1) \\5859292 &:= (-5 + 8) \times 5^9 - 2 - 9^2 \\5859385 &:= (5 - (8 - 3)^9) \times (5 - 8) - 5 \\5859403 &:= 5 \times 8 + (5^9 - 4) \times 03 \\5859412 &:= (5 + 8 + 5^9) \times (4 - 1) - 2 \\5859413 &:= 5 + (8 + 5^9 + 4 - 1) \times 3 \\5859414 &:= (5 + 8 + 5^9) \times (4 - 1^4) \\5859415 &:= 5 \times (8 + (5^9 \times (4 - 1))/5) \\5859421 &:= 58 + (5^9 - 4) \times (2 + 1) \\5859423 &:= (58 + 5^9 - 42) \times 3 \\5859426 &:= (5 + 8 + 5^9 + 4)/2 \times 6 \\5859429 &:= (-5 + 8) \times 5^9 + (4 + 2) \times 9 \\5859433 &:= 58 + 5^9 \times (4 - 3) \times 3 \\5859435 &:= (-5 + 8) \times 5^9 + 4 \times 3 \times 5 \\5859443 &:= (-5 + 8) \times 5^9 + 4 + 4^3 \\5859447 &:= (-5 + 8) \times ((5^9 - 4) + 4 \times 7) \\5859463 &:= 58 + (5^9 + 4 + 6) \times 3 \\5859471 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + 4 \times (7 + 1)) \\5859483 &:= (5 \times 8 + 5^9 + 4 - 8) \times 3 \\5859493 &:= -5 + (-8 + 5^9 + 49) \times 3 \\5859498 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + 49 - 8) \\5859513 &:= 5 \times 8 + (5^9 + 5 + 1) \times 3 \\5859519 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + 51) - 9 \\5859522 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + (5 + 2)^2) \\5859525 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + 5 \times 2 \times 5) \\5859531 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + 53 - 1) \\5859532 &:= (58 + 5^9 - 5) \times 3 - 2 \\5859543 &:= (5^8 \times 5 + (9 + 5) \times 4) \times 3 \\5859553 &:= 5 + 8 + (5^9 + 55) \times 3 \\5859555 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + 5 + 55) \\5859570 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 - 5 + 70)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5859573 &:= (5^8 \times 5 + 9 + 57) \times 3 \\ 5859579 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + 5 + 7 \times 9) \\ 5859582 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + 5 + 8^2) \\ 5859585 &:= (5^8 + 5 + 9) \times 5 \times (8 - 5) \\ 5859627 &:= (-5 + 8) \times 5^9 + 6^2 \times 7 \\ 5859645 &:= (-5 + 8) \times 5^9 + 6 \times 45 \\ 5859663 &:= (5^8 \times 5 + 96) \times (6 - 3) \\ 5859699 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (5^9 + 6 \times (9 + 9)) \\ 5859745 &:= (-5 + 8) \times 5^9 + 74 \times 5 \\ 5859783 &:= (58 + 5^9 + 78) \times 3 \\ 5859879 &:= (-5 + 8) \times 5^9 + 8 \times 7 \times 9 \\ 5859915 &:= (5^8 + 5 \times 9 - 9) \times 15 \\ 5862615 &:= (5^8 + 6^2 \times 6) \times 15 \\ 5878656 &:= (-5 + 8)^7 \times 8 \times 6 \times 56 \\ 5878677 &:= (-5 + 8) \times (-7 + 8 + 6^7) \times 7 \\ 5883462 &:= (-5^8 + 83^4) / (6 + 2) \\ 5887650 &:= ((5 + 8) \times 8 + 7^6) \times 50 \\ 5895649 &:= 5^8 + (-9 + 5 \times 6) \times 4^9 \\ 5915965 &:= ((5 + 9 \times 1)^5 - 9) \times (6 + 5) \\ 5924342 &:= -5 - 9 + 2434^2 \\ 5929741 &:= (59 \times 2 + 9 \times 7)^{4-1} \\ 5929976 &:= (5^{9-2} - 99) \times 76 \\ 5933463 &:= 5^9 \times 3 + ((3 + 4) \times 6)^3 \\ 5935858 &:= (59 \times 3)^{-5+8} + 5^8 \\ 5937507 &:= 5^9 \times 3 + 7 + 5^{07} \\ 5946374 &:= (59 \times 46) \times (3^7 + 4) \\ 5963949 &:= (5 + 96) \times (3 \times 9)^4 / 9 \\ 5971928 &:= (-5 + ((97 - 1) \times 9)^2) \times 8 \\ 5972328 &:= (5 \times 9 + 72^3 \times 2) \times 8 \\ 5978645 &:= (-5 + 9^7 + 8 \times 6) / 4 \times 5 \\ 5978715 &:= (5 \times 9^7 + 8 + 7) / (-1 + 5) \\ 6046656 &:= ((6 + 04)^6 + 6^5) \times 6 \\ 6158592 &:= 6^{1+5} \times (8 \times 5 + 92) \\ 6171793 &:= ((6 - 1)^7 - 1) \times 79 - 3 \\ 6176574 &:= 6 \times (1 + 7^6 \times 5 \times 7) / 4 \\ 6184669 &:= (6 + 1)^8 + (-4 + 6^6) \times 9 \\ 6223394 &:= 6 + 2 \times (-2 + (3 + 39)^4) \\ 6223454 &:= 62 + 2 \times (-3 + 45)^4 \\ 6249888 &:= (-6 + 2 \times (4 - 9)^8 - 8) \times 8 \\ 6249994 &:= -6 + (2 + 49 - 9/9)^4 \\ 6250004 &:= 6 - 2 + 50^{004} \\ 6250062 &:= 62 + 50^{06-2} \\ 6259353 &:= (6 \times (-2 + 5)^9 + 3) \times 53 \\ 6262784 &:= (6 \times 2^{6+2} - 7) \times 8^4 \\ 6283488 &:= 6 \times 2 \times (-83 + 4^8) \times 8 \\ 6286848 &:= 6 \times 2 \times 8 \times (-6 \times 8 + 4^8) \\ 6287384 &:= (6 + 2 + 8^7) \times 3 - 8^4 \\ 6291168 &:= 6 \times (2^{9+11} - 6 \times 8) \\ 6291426 &:= (-6/2 + 4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 6291432 &:= ((6 - 2)^9 - 1) \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \\ 6291442 &:= 6 \times (-2 + ((9 - 1) \times 4)^4) - 2 \\ 6291444 &:= 6 \times (2 + ((9 - 1) \times 4)^4 - 4) \\ 6291448 &:= 6 \times (2 \times 9 + 14)^4 - 8 \\ 6291453 &:= 6 \times (2 + 9 + 1 + 4)^5 - 3 \\ 6291456 &:= (6 \times 2 - 9 - 1)^{4 \times 5} \times 6 \\ 6291477 &:= 6/2 \times ((9 - 1^4)^7 + 7) \\ 6291496 &:= (6 - 2) \times (9 + 1 + 4^9 \times 6) \\ 6291564 &:= 6 \times (2 \times 9 + (-1 + 5)^{6+4}) \\ 6291624 &:= ((6 - 2)^9 + 1 + 6) \times 24 \\ 6291654 &:= 6 \times (29 + 16^5 + 4) \\ 6291864 &:= 6 \times (2 \times 9 - 1 + 8^6) \times 4 \\ 6292224 &:= 6 \times (2^9 + 2^{22}) / 4 \\ 6292428 &:= 6 \times (2 \times 9^2 + 4^{2+8}) \\ 6294524 &:= 6 \times (2^9 + 4^{5 \times 2}) - 4 \\ 6298555 &:= (6 \times 2 \times 9)^{8-5} \times 5 - 5 \\ 6327639 &:= (-6 + (3 + 2)^7) \times (6 + 3) \times 9 \\ 6331625 &:= (6^3 - 31)^{6+2-5} \\ 6338297 &:= -63^3 + 8 \times (-2 + 9)^7 \\ 6362544 &:= 636 \times ((2 \times 5)^4 + 4) \\ 6376536 &:= 6 \times (3^{5+6} - 7 \times 3) \times 6 \\ 6376924 &:= ((6 - 3)^{7+6} - 92) \times 4 \\ 6377291 &:= 6 \times 3^{7+7} \times 2/9 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6377292 &:= 6 \times 3^{7/7+2+9} \times 2 \\ 6377324 &:= (6 + 3^{7+7}/3 + 2) \times 4 \\ 6377436 &:= 6 \times (3^{4+7} + 7 - 3) \times 6 \\ 6378745 &:= 6 \times 3 \times 7 \times (8 + 7)^4 - 5 \\ 6396945 &:= (-6 + 3^9 \times (69 - 4)) \times 5 \\ 6400240 &:= (6 + 400^2) \times 40 \\ 6413526 &:= 6 \times (41^3 + (5 \times 2)^6) \\ 6422528 &:= (64 \times 2 \times (2 + 5))^2 \times 8 \\ 6423998 &:= (6 + 4^{2^3} + 9) \times 98 \\ 6434846 &:= (-6 + 48 \times 4)^3 - 4 - 6 \\ 6436235 &:= -6 \times (4 \times 3 + 6) + 23^5 \\ 6436345 &:= 6 - 4 + ((3 + 6) \times 3 - 4)^5 \\ 6436415 &:= 6 \times 4 \times 3 + (6 \times 4 - 1)^5 \\ 6438528 &:= 6^{4+3} \times (8 + 5 + 2 + 8) \\ 6455000 &:= (6^4 - 5) \times 5000 \\ 6474397 &:= 6 + 47 \times (-4 + 3^9) \times 7 \\ 6481304 &:= 6^4 + 8 \times (1 + 30^4) \\ 6482592 &:= 6^4 \times 82 \times (59 + 2) \\ 6487965 &:= (6 + 4^8 - 7) \times 9 \times (6 + 5) \\ 6488658 &:= (6 + 4^8) \times (86 + 5 + 8) \\ 6495385 &:= (6 + 4) \times 9^5 \times (3 + 8) - 5 \\ 6496262 &:= 6 + (4^9 + (6 \times 2)^6) \times 2 \\ 6519843 &:= (6 + 5) \times (1 \times 9 + 84^3) \\ 6531840 &:= 6^5 \times (3 + 18) \times 40 \\ 6539139 &:= -(6 \times 5)^3 + 91^3 \times 9 \\ 6539203 &:= ((6 + 5 \times 3) \times 9 - 2)^{0^3} \\ 6552840 &:= (6^5 + 5^2) \times 840 \\ 6553494 &:= -6 + 5^{5-3} \times (4^9 - 4) \\ 6553495 &:= -6 \times 5 + 5 \times (-3 + 4^9) \times 5 \\ 6553519 &:= -6 + 5 \times 5 \times (-3 + (5 - 1)^9) \\ 6553586 &:= 6 - 5 + 5 \times (-3 + 5 \times 8^6) \\ 6553625 &:= (6 - 5 + (5 + 3)^6) \times 25 \\ 6553655 &:= (6 + 5 + (5 + 3)^6 \times 5) \times 5 \\ 6554439 &:= (65 \times 5 + 4 + 4) \times 3^9 \\ 6559350 &:= (6 \times 5^5 - 9) \times 350 \\ 6561870 &:= (6 \times 5^6 - 1 - 8) \times 70 \\ 6562577 &:= (6 + 5 + 6 \times 2 \times 5^7) \times 7 \\ 6563760 &:= (6 + 5^6 - 3) \times 7 \times 60 \\ 6565248 &:= 656 \times ((5 \times 2)^4 + 8) \\ 6568170 &:= (6 \times 5^6 + 81) \times 70 \\ 6572778 &:= -(6^5 + 7) \times 2 + 7^7 \times 8 \\ 6577254 &:= (6 \times 57 + 7)^2 \times 54 \\ 6579255 &:= (6 + (57 \times 9)^2 \times 5) \times 5 \\ 6584362 &:= 6 + (5 \times 8 \times 4^3 + 6)^2 \\ 6587768 &:= (-6 \times (5 + 8) + 7^7 + 6) \times 8 \\ 6587798 &:= 6 \times 5 + 8 \times (7^7 - 9 \times 8) \\ 6587928 &:= (6 - 58 + 7^{9-2}) \times 8 \\ 6588347 &:= 6 + 5 - 8 + 8 \times (3 + 4)^7 \\ 6588377 &:= 6 - 5 + 8 + 8 \times (3 + 7^7) \\ 6588778 &:= -6 + 5 \times 88 + 7^7 \times 8 \\ 6596850 &:= (6^5 - 9 - 6) \times 850 \\ 6612523 &:= (66^{1+2} + 5) \times 23 \\ 6625152 &:= 6^6 \times (-2 \times 5 + 152) \\ 6635782 &:= 6 + ((63 \times 5 + 7) \times 8)^2 \\ 6639684 &:= (-6 - 6 - 3^9 + 6^8) \times 4 \\ 6644358 &:= 6 + 6 \times 44^3 \times (5 + 8) \\ 6644734 &:= 66 + (4 \times 47)^3 - 4 \\ 6666939 &:= 6 \times 6 \times (66 - 9)^3 - 9 \\ 6671808 &:= 6^6 \times (71 + 80 - 8) \\ 6677748 &:= 6 \times 6 \times 77 \times (7^4 + 8) \\ 6684384 &:= 6 \times (6 + 8)^4 \times (-3 + 8 \times 4) \\ 6684529 &:= (6 \times (6 + 8)^4 + 5) \times 29 \\ 6684624 &:= 6 \times (68 \times 4^6 - 2) \times 4 \\ 6684672 &:= 6 \times 68 \times (-4 + 6)^{7 \times 2} \\ 6684738 &:= 6 \times (68 \times 4^7 + 3 + 8) \\ 6685684 &:= -6 - 6 - 8^5 + 6^8 \times 4 \\ 6716744 &:= (6 \times (-71 + 6^7) - 4) \times 4 \\ 6717264 &:= (6^7 - 1 - 7^2) \times 6 \times 4 \\ 6717864 &:= (6^7 - 17 - 8) \times 6 \times 4 \\ 6718164 &:= (6^{7+1} - 81 + 6) \times 4 \\ 6718224 &:= (6^7 \times 1 - 8 - 2) \times 24 \\ 6718244 &:= (6^7 - 1 - 8) \times 24 - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6718248 &:= (6^7 - 1 - 8) \times (2^4 + 8) & 6718648 &:= (6^7 \times 1 + 8) \times 6 \times 4 - 8 \\ 6718296 &:= (6^7 + 1 - 8) \times (2 \times 9 + 6) & 6718656 &:= (6^7 \times 1 + 8) \times (6 \times 5 - 6) \\ 6718370 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times 8 \times 3 - 70 & 6718674 &:= 6 \times (7 - (1 - 8 - 6^7)) \times 4 \\ 6718374 &:= -6 + ((7 - 1)^8 - 3 \times 7) \times 4 & 6718684 &:= (6 - 7 \times (1 - 8) + 6^8) \times 4 \\ 6718382 &:= 6^7 \times 1 \times 8 \times 3 - 82 & 6718824 &:= (6^7 - 1 + 8 + 8) \times 24 \\ 6718394 &:= (6^7 + 1) \times 8 \times 3 - 94 & 6718896 &:= (6^7 + 18) \times 8 \times (9 - 6) \\ 6718395 &:= (6^7 - 1) \times 8 \times 3 - 9 \times 5 & 6719424 &:= (6^7 + (1 + 9) \times 4) \times 24 \\ 6718416 &:= (6^{7+1} - 8) \times 4 - 16 & 6720048 &:= 6 \times (7 \times (20^{04}) + 8) \\ 6718420 &:= (-6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 20 & 6720480 &:= 6 \times (7 \times 20^4 + 80) \\ 6718424 &:= (6^{7+1} - 8) \times 4 - 2 \times 4 & 6723649 &:= (6^{7-2} + 3)^{6-4} / 9 \\ 6718425 &:= (6^{7+1} - 8) \times 4 - 2 - 5 & 6745235 &:= (6 \times 74 - 5)^2 \times 35 \\ 6718427 &:= (6^{7+1} - 8) \times 4 + 2 - 7 & 6749487 &:= (67 + 4 \times 9) \times (4^8 - 7) \\ 6718429 &:= -6 + (7 - 1)^8 \times 4 - 29 & 6754002 &:= (-6 + 7^5) \times (400 + 2) \\ 6718432 &:= (6^{7+1} - 8) \times 4 \times (3 - 2) & 6756408 &:= -6 + 7^5 \times (-6 + 408) \\ 6718433 &:= (6^{7+1} - 8) \times 4 + 3/3 & 6756414 &:= 6 \times 7^5 \times (64 - 1 + 4) \\ 6718435 &:= 6 + (7 - 1)^8 \times 4 - 35 & 6756749 &:= 67 \times (5 + 6 \times 7^{-4+9}) \\ 6718437 &:= -6 + (7 - 1)^8 \times 4 - 3 \times 7 & 6765131 &:= 6 - 76 + 51^{3+1} \\ 6718452 &:= (6^7 \times 1 \times 8 - 4) \times (5 - 2) & 6765182 &:= -6 - 7 - 6 + 51^{8/2} \\ 6718454 &:= -6 + ((7 - 1)^8 + 4 - 5) \times 4 & 6765195 &:= (6 - 7) \times 6 + 51^{9-5} \\ 6718462 &:= 6 + (7 - 1)^8 \times 4 - 6 - 2 & 6765214 &:= 6 + 7 + (6 \times 5 + 21)^4 \\ 6718465 &:= 6^{7+1} \times (8 - 4) + 6 - 5 & 6782139 &:= ((6 + 7) \times (8 - 2 + 1))^3 \times 9 \\ 6718468 &:= (6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 + 6 - 8 & 6823816 &:= (-6 + 8^2) \times (3 + (8 - 1)^6) \\ 6718470 &:= 6 + (7 - 1)^8 \times 4 + 7 \times 0 & 6834375 &:= (-6 + 8 + 3)^4 \times 3^7 \times 5 \\ 6718471 &:= 6^{7+1} \times (8 - 4) + 7 \times 1 & 6835723 &:= 6^8 \times 3 + 5^7 \times 23 \\ 6718472 &:= -6 + (7 - 1)^8 \times 4 + 7 \times 2 & 6835944 &:= (6 + 8) \times (3 + 5^9) / 4 - 4 \\ 6718473 &:= (6^7 \times 1 \times 8 - 4 + 7) \times 3 & 6835948 &:= (6 + 8) \times (3 + 5^9) / (-4 + 8) \\ 6718475 &:= (-6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 + 7 \times 5 & 6835972 &:= (6 \times 8 + (3 + 5^9) \times 7) / 2 \\ 6718476 &:= (6^7 \times 4 + 8 + 1 - 7) \times 6 & 6899256 &:= (((((6 \times 8) - 9) \times 9)^2) \times 56) \\ 6718479 &:= (6^7 + 1) \times 8 \times (-4 + 7) - 9 & 6917814 &:= 6 \times (9 - (1 - 7^8) / (1 + 4)) \\ 6718493 &:= (6^{7+1} + 8) \times 4 - 9/3 & 6928383 &:= (6^9 / (2 \times 8) - 3) \times (8 + 3) \\ 6718494 &:= (-6 + (7 - 1)^8) \times 4 - 9 \times 4 & 6928416 &:= 6^9 / (2 \times 8) \times (4 + 1 + 6) \\ 6718503 &:= ((6^7 + 1) \times 8 + 5) \times 03 & 6952688 &:= 6^9 - 5^{2+6} \times 8 - 8 \\ 6718524 &:= (6^{7+1} + 8 + 5 + 2) \times 4 & 6952947 &:= (6 - 95) \times (2 - (9 - 4)^7) \\ 6718533 &:= ((6^7 + 1) \times 8 + 5 \times 3) \times 3 & 6954684 &:= (6 + 9^5) \times 4 + 6^8 \times 4 \\ 6718544 &:= (6^{7+1^8} + 5 \times 4) \times 4 & 6987492 &:= 69 \times ((8 + 7)^4 + 9) \times 2 \\ 6718624 &:= ((6^7 - 1 + 8) \times 6 - 2) \times 4 & 6998325 &:= (6^{-9/9+8} - 3) \times 25 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6998525 &:= (6^{-9/9+8} + 5) \times 25 \\ 6998750 &:= (6^9 / (9 \times 8) + 7) \times 50 \\ 7056420 &:= (7^{05} - 6) \times 420 \\ 7112844 &:= 711 \times ((2 + 8)^4 + 4) \\ 7176162 &:= (-7 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (-1 + 62) \\ 7176583 &:= -7 + 1 + 7^6 \times (58 + 3) \\ 7176589 &:= 7^{-1+7} \times (-6 + 58 + 9) \\ 7176643 &:= -7 + (1 + 7^6) \times (64 - 3) \\ 7247565 &:= (7 + 2) \times ((4 + 7)^5 + 6) \times 5 \\ 7252495 &:= -72 + 52^4 - 9^5 \\ 7267391 &:= (7 \times 2)^6 - (7 - 3)^9 - 1 \\ 7285374 &:= (7^2 + 8^5) \times 3 \times 74 \\ 7285565 &:= 7 \times ((2 \times 8)^5 - 5 - 6^5) \\ 7286784 &:= (7 \times 2^8 - 6 - 7) \times 8^4 \\ 7289903 &:= -7 + (2 + 8) \times (-9 + 90^3) \\ 7289993 &:= -7 + (2 + 8) \times (99 - 9)^3 \\ 7290035 &:= (7 + 2 \times 90^{03}) \times 5 \\ 7290049 &:= 7^2 + 90^{04} / 9 \\ 7294176 &:= (7^2 + 9 + 4) \times (-1 + 7^6) \\ 7339864 &:= 7 \times ((3 - 3 \times 9) + 8^6 \times 4) \\ 7340872 &:= 7 \times (3 \times 40 + 8^7 / 2) \\ 7349844 &:= (7 + 3^4) \times (9 + 8)^4 - 4 \\ 7349848 &:= (7 + 3^4) \times (9 + 8)^{-4+8} \\ 7397847 &:= (-7 + (3^9 - 7) \times 8) \times 47 \\ 7408346 &:= (7 + 4)^{08-3} \times 46 \\ 7411779 &:= (-7 - 4 - 1 + 1 \times 7^7) \times 9 \\ 7411799 &:= -7 + ((-4 + 11)^7 - 9) \times 9 \\ 7411869 &:= (7^{-4+11} - 8 + 6) \times 9 \\ 7411877 &:= -7 - 4 + 1 + (1 + 8) \times 7^7 \\ 7411887 &:= 7^{4+1} \times (-1 + 8 \times 8) \times 7 \\ 7418157 &:= 7 \times 4^{1+8+1} + 5^7 \\ 7423367 &:= (-7^4 + 2 \times (3 \times 3)^6) \times 7 \\ 7425720 &:= ((7 + 4 + 2)^5 - 7) \times 20 \\ 7425855 &:= (7 \times 4 - 2)^5 / 8 \times 5 - 5 \\ 7428694 &:= 7^4 \times (-2 + 86 \times 9 \times 4) \\ 7439628 &:= 7 \times ((-43 + 9^6) \times 2 + 8) \\ 7464925 &:= (-7 + (4 \times 6)^4 \times 9 / 2) \times 5 \\ 7465248 &:= (7 \times (4 + 65))^2 \times 4 \times 8 \\ 7476445 &:= (7^4 \times 7 - 6) \times 445 \\ 7481516 &:= 7^4 \times (-8 - 1 + 5^{-1+6}) \\ 7493745 &:= 749 \times ((3 + 7)^4 + 5) \\ 7496644 &:= (7 \times 4 + 9 - 6 + 6)^4 \times 4 \\ 7499657 &:= -7 \times 49 + 96 \times 5^7 \\ 7503125 &:= (7 \times 5)^{03-1+2} \times 5 \\ 7503145 &:= ((7 \times 5)^{03+1} + 4) \times 5 \\ 7512726 &:= -7^5 - 1 - 2 + (7 \times 2)^6 \\ 7512728 &:= -7^5 - 1 + (2 \times 7)^{-2+8} \\ 7519344 &:= 7 \times (-(5 - 1)^9 + 34^4) \\ 7525776 &:= -752 \times 5 + (7 + 7)^6 \\ 7528776 &:= -752 - 8 + (7 + 7)^6 \\ 7529386 &:= -75 \times 2 + (9 - 3 + 8)^6 \\ 7529461 &:= -75 + (2 \times 9 - 4)^6 \times 1 \\ 7529515 &:= -7 \times (5 - 2) + (9 + 5)^{1+5} \\ 7529528 &:= (7 + 5 + 2)^{9-5+2} - 8 \\ 7529532 &:= -7 + 5 - 2 + (9 + 5)^{3 \times 2} \\ 7529533 &:= ((7 + 5 + 2) \times (9 + 5))^3 - 3 \\ 7529536 &:= (7 \times 5 - 29 + 5 + 3)^6 \\ 7529542 &:= (7 + 5) / 2 + (9 + 5)^{4+2} \\ 7529664 &:= (7 - 5 + (-2 + 9)^6) \times 64 \\ 7533568 &:= (7^5 + 3 \times 3) \times 56 \times 8 \\ 7537534 &:= -7^5 \times 3 \times 7 + 53^4 \\ 7541465 &:= -7^5 + 4 \times ((-1 + 4) \times 6)^5 \\ 7546343 &:= 7^5 + ((46 + 3) \times 4)^3 \\ 7558272 &:= (7 - 5 / 5)^8 / 2 \times (7 + 2) \\ 7560035 &:= 7 \times (5 + 60^{03} \times 5) \\ 7560350 &:= 7 \times (5 \times 60^3 + 50) \\ 7560375 &:= (75 + 60^3 \times 7) \times 5 \\ 7560450 &:= (7^5 - 6) \times 0450 \\ 7562775 &:= (7^5 \times 6 + 2 - 7) \times 75 \\ 7563125 &:= (7^5 \times 6 \times 3 - 1) \times 25 \\ 7563150 &:= 7^5 \times (6 - 3) \times 150 \\ 7563250 &:= (7^5 \times (6 + 3) + 2) \times 50 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7565490 &:= ((7^5 + 6) \times 5 - 4) \times 90 & 7864313 &:= -7 + 8^6 \times (-4 + 31 + 3) \\ 7565775 &:= (7^5 \times 6 + 5 \times 7) \times 75 & 7864335 &:= 7 + 8 + 6 \times 4^{3 \times 3} \times 5 \\ 7565973 &:= -75 + 6^5 \times 973 & 7864355 &:= (7 + 8^6 \times (4 - 3 + 5)) \times 5 \\ 7592832 &:= (7 + 5 + 9 \times 2 \times 8)^3 \times 2 & 7864596 &:= ((7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 5 - 9) \times 6 \\ 7596764 &:= 7^5 \times ((9 + 67) \times 6 - 4) & 7864635 &:= ((7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 - 3) \times 5 \\ 7597638 &:= ((7 + 5) \times 97 - 6) \times 3^8 & 7864695 &:= ((7 + 8^6 + 4) \times 6 + 9) \times 5 \\ 7602176 &:= (-7 + 6^{02}) \times (1 + 7)^6 & 7867544 &:= 78 \times 6 \times (7^5 + 4) - 4 \\ 7623175 &:= 7^{6-2} \times 3175 & 7867548 &:= 78 \times 6 \times (7^5 - 4 + 8) \\ 7645373 &:= (7 + (6 \times 4 - 5) \times (3 + 7))^3 & 7875336 &:= 7 \times 8 \times (75^3 / 3 + 6) \\ 7646665 &:= (7^6 + 4 - 6 - 6) \times 65 & 7879249 &:= (7 \times 8 \times 7 + 9)^2 \times 49 \\ 7646925 &:= (7^6 - 4) \times (6 + 9 - 2) \times 5 & 7924225 &:= (7 \times 9^2 - 4)^2 \times 25 \\ 7647185 &:= 7^6 \times (4 + 7 \times 1 \times 8 + 5) & 7934495 &:= (7 + 9 - 3 + 4)^4 \times 95 \\ 7647445 &:= (7^6 + 4) \times (74 - 4 - 5) & 7962545 &:= -79 + ((6 - 2) \times 5 + 4)^5 \\ 7647965 &:= (7^6 - 4 + 7 + 9) \times 65 & 7962562 &:= (7 + 9 + 6 + 2)^5 - 62 \\ 7655795 &:= 7 \times (-65 + 5^7 \times (9 + 5)) & 7962617 &:= (7 + 9 + 6 + 2)^{6-1} - 7 \\ 7669270 &:= (7 + 6 \times 6 \times 9)^2 \times 70 & 7962624 &:= (7 + 9 + 6 + 2)^6 / 24 \\ 7719236 &:= (7 + 7) \times ((1 + 9^2)^3 + 6) & 7962645 &:= 7 \times 9 / (6/2) + (6 \times 4)^5 \\ 7764372 &:= (7 - 7^6) \times (4 - 37) \times 2 & 7963296 &:= (7 + (96 \times 3)^2) \times 96 \\ 7764647 &:= (7 + (7^6 - 4) \times 6) \times (4 + 7) & 7964462 &:= (7 \times 9^6 + (4 + 4)^6) \times 2 \\ 7764827 &:= -7 + 7^6 \times (-4 + (8 + 2) \times 7) & 7964534 &:= ((7 + 9 + 6)^4 - 5) \times 34 \\ 7764876 &:= (7 - 7^6 \times (4 - 8 - 7)) \times 6 & 7968757 &:= 7 + (9 + 6 + 87) \times 5^7 \\ 7764966 &:= (7 + 7^6 + 4 - 9) \times 66 & 7971510 &:= (-7 + 9^{7-1}) \times (5 + 10) \\ 7765625 &:= (77 - 6) \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) & 7971513 &:= ((-7 + 9^{7-1}) \times 5 + 1) \times 3 \\ 7765667 &:= ((77 - 6) \times 5^6 + 6) \times 7 & 7971573 &:= (-7 + 9^{7-1} \times 5 - 7) \times 3 \\ 7797153 &:= 7 \times (7 \times (9 - 7) - 1)^5 \times 3 & 7971599 &:= -7 + 9^7 \times 15 / 9 - 9 \\ 7836693 &:= 7 \times 8 \times 3 \times (6^6 - 9) - 3 & 7971613 &:= (-7 + 9^7 \times (-1 + 6) + 1) / 3 \\ 7861892 &:= 7^8 - 61 + 8^{9-2} & 7971615 &:= ((7 + 9 - 7) \times 1)^6 \times 15 \\ 7863365 &:= (7 + (8^6 - 33) \times 6) \times 5 & 7971625 &:= (7 + 9^7 - 1) / (6/2) \times 5 \\ 7863930 &:= (-7 + 8^6 + 3 - 9) \times 30 & 7971635 &:= (7 + 9^7 - 1 + 6) / 3 \times 5 \\ 7864110 &:= (-7 + 8^6) \times (4 - 1) \times 10 & 7997584 &:= (-7 + 9 \times 9 \times 7 \times 5)^{8/4} \\ 7864116 &:= ((-7 + 8^6) \times (4 + 1) + 1) \times 6 & 8052550 &:= (8 + 05 - 2)^5 \times 50 \\ 7864165 &:= (-7 + (8^6 - 4 \times 1) \times 6) \times 5 & 8056550 &:= (80 + (5 + 6)^5) \times 50 \\ 7864193 &:= -7 + (8^6 - 4) \times (1 + 9) \times 3 & 8066448 &:= 806 \times ((6 + 4)^4 + 8) \\ 7864215 &:= (-7 + 8^6 \times 4/2) \times 15 & 8128512 &:= 8 \times (12 \times (85 - 1))^2 \\ 7864235 &:= (7 + (8^6 - 4) \times 2 \times 3) \times 5 & 8165772 &:= 81 \times 6 \times (-5 + 7^{7-2}) \\ 7864285 &:= (-7 + 8^6 \times (-4 + 2 + 8)) \times 5 & 8193532 &:= (-8 + 19 + 3^5)^3 / 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8235775 &:= (8 + 2) \times (35 + 7^7) - 5 \\ 8253738 &:= (8 + 2 \times 5^{-3+7}) \times 3^8 \\ 8253952 &:= (8 \times (2 + 5))^3 \times (9 \times 5 + 2) \\ 8290528 &:= 8 \times (2 \times 509)^2 - 8 \\ 8301447 &:= (8 + 30 - 1 - 4)^4 \times 7 \\ 8338947 &:= (8^3 - 3) \times (8 - 9 + 4^7) \\ 8339552 &:= 8 \times (3 + (-3 + (9 - 5)^5)^2) \\ 8340544 &:= (83 - 40 - 5)^4 \times 4 \\ 8347648 &:= 8^3 \times (4^7 - (6 + 4) \times 8) \\ 8353125 &:= (8 + 3) \times (5 \times 3)^{1^2 \times 5} \\ 8353258 &:= (8 \times 3)^5 + 3^2 + 5^8 \\ 8369235 &:= (83 \times 6 - 9)^2 \times 35 \\ 8374272 &:= 8^3 \times (-7 \times 4 + 2^{7 \times 2}) \\ 8374652 &:= (8 + 3)^{7+4-6} \times 52 \\ 8382528 &:= (8^3 - 8)^2 \times (5 + 28) \\ 8384512 &:= 8^3 \times (-8 + 4^{5 \times 1 + 2}) \\ 8385536 &:= 8^3 \times (8^5 / (5 - 3) - 6) \\ 8385792 &:= (-8 - 3 + 8^5) \times (7 + 9)^2 \\ 8385864 &:= -8 \times (3 + (85 - 8^6) \times 4) \\ 8386784 &:= (-8^3 + (8^6 + 7) \times 8) \times 4 \\ 8387784 &:= -8^3 + (8^7 - 78) \times 4 \\ 8388256 &:= 8 \times (-38 + (8 \times 2)^5 - 6) \\ 8388276 &:= (-8^3 + 8^8) / 2 - 76 \\ 8388288 &:= (-8^3 + 8^8) / 2 - 8 \times 8 \\ 8388351 &:= (8^3 - 8^8) / (3 - 5) - 1 \\ 8388442 &:= (-83 + 8^8 / 4) \times (4 - 2) \\ 8388452 &:= (-83 + 8^8 / 4 + 5) \times 2 \\ 8388512 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 12) \\ 8388525 &:= -83 + (8^8 \times 5) / (2 \times 5) \\ 8388528 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 2 - 8) \\ 8388536 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 3 - 6) \\ 8388542 &:= -8 \times (3 - (8 + 8)^5) - 42 \\ 8388544 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 4 - 4) \\ 8388546 &:= -8 \times (3 - (8 + 8)^5 + 4) - 6 \\ 8388552 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 5 - 2) \\ 8388554 &:= 8 \times (3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 54 \\ 8388559 &:= 8 \times ((3 \times 8 - 8)^5 - 5) - 9 \\ 8388573 &:= 8 \times (3 + (8 + 8)^5 - 7) - 3 \\ 8388576 &:= 8 \times (-3 + (8 + 8)^5 - 7 + 6) \\ 8388577 &:= -8 \times 3 + 8^8 / (-5 + 7) - 7 \\ 8388582 &:= -8 \times 3 + (8 + 8)^5 \times 8 - 2 \\ 8388584 &:= -8 \times 3 + 8 \times 8^5 \times 8 \times 4 \\ 8388586 &:= 8 + (-3 + (8 + 8)^5) \times 8 - 6 \\ 8388592 &:= 8 + (-3 + 8^8 - 5 \times 9) / 2 \\ 8388596 &:= (-8 \times 3 + 8^8) / (5 - 9 + 6) \\ 8388597 &:= -8 - 3 + 8^8 / ((5 + 9) / 7) \\ 8388728 &:= (8 + 3 + (8 + 8^7) / 2) \times 8 \\ 8388744 &:= (-8 + 38 + 8^7 + 4) \times 4 \\ 8388746 &:= -8 + (38 + 8^7) \times 4 - 6 \\ 8388768 &:= 8 \times 3 \times (-8 + 8^7) / 6 - 8 \\ 8388784 &:= -8 + (38 + 8^7 + 8) \times 4 \\ 8388862 &:= (8^3 + 8^8) / (8 - 6) - 2 \\ 8388864 &:= (8^3 + 8^8) \times (8 - 6) / 4 \\ 8388868 &:= (8^3 + 8^8 + 8) / (-6 + 8) \\ 8388912 &:= 8 \times 38 + 8^{9-1} / 2 \\ 8394752 &:= 8^3 \times (9 + 4^7 + 5 - 2) \\ 8396730 &:= -(8 - 3) \times 9 + 6^7 \times 30 \\ 8398072 &:= -8 + (-3 + 9)^8 \times (07 - 2) \\ 8398075 &:= (-8 + (-3 + 9)^8 + 07) \times 5 \\ 8398115 &:= (8 + (-3 + 9)^8 - 1) \times 1 \times 5 \\ 8398135 &:= (8 + (-3 + 9)^8 + 1 \times 3) \times 5 \\ 8398145 &:= (8 + (-3 + 9)^8 + 1 + 4) \times 5 \\ 8398235 &:= (8 + (-3 + 9)^8 + 23) \times 5 \\ 8399685 &:= (8 \times 39 + 9 + 6^8) \times 5 \\ 8425452 &:= (8^4 - 2) \times (5 + 4^5) \times 2 \\ 8433224 &:= 8 + 4 \times 3 \times 3 \times 22^4 \\ 8454208 &:= 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 08) \\ 8454216 &:= 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 1 - 6) \\ 8454224 &:= 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 2 - 4) \\ 8454232 &:= 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 3 - 2) \\ 8454236 &:= 8 \times (4^5 + 4)^2 - 36 \\ 8454239 &:= 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 - 3) - 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8454263 &:= 8 \times (4^5 + 4)^2 - 6 - 3 & 8675516 &:= 8 + (6 + 7^5) \times 516 \\ 8454269 &:= 8 \times (4^5 + 4)^2 + 6 - 9 & 8675733 &:= (8^6 + 757) \times 33 \\ 8454296 &:= 8 \times ((4^5 + 4)^2 + 9 - 6) & 8677985 &:= (8 - 6^7 - 7) \times (9 - 8 \times 5) \\ 8459982 &:= ((8 + 4)^5 - 9) \times (9 + 8) \times 2 & 8678256 &:= -8 + (6^7 + 8) \times (25 + 6) \\ 8470693 &:= 8 \times (-4 + 7^{06} \times 9) - 3 & 8745813 &:= (-8 + 7^4 \times 5) \times (8 + 1)^3 \\ 8487364 &:= -8 + (4 + 8) \times (-7 + 36)^4 & 8747271 &:= (8 + 7^4/7)^2 \times 71 \\ 8489631 &:= 8 \times (-4 + ((8 + 9) \times 6)^3) - 1 & 8752149 &:= (8 \times 7 + 5 \times 21^4) \times 9 \\ 8489664 &:= ((8 + 4) \times (8 + 9))^{(6+6)/4} & 8752279 &:= (-8 + 7^5) \times (2^{2+7} + 9) \\ 8489696 &:= 8 \times (4 + ((8 + 9) \times 6)^{9-6}) & 8754375 &:= 87 \times (5^4 + (3 + 7)^5) \\ 8502544 &:= -8^{5-02} + 54^4 & 8759664 &:= (-8 + 759) \times 6^6/4 \\ 8502964 &:= 8 - 50 \times 2 + (9 \times 6)^4 & 8765127 &:= (8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 1)^2/7 \\ 8502968 &:= 8 \times (5 + 02 \times (9^6 - 8)) & 8773236 &:= (87 \times 7^{3+2} - 3) \times 6 \\ 8503296 &:= 8 \times (5 + 03^{2+9}) \times 6 & 8794653 &:= 87 \times (9 + 4) \times 6^5 - 3 \\ 8519420 &:= (8^5 - 1) \times (9 + 4) \times 20 & 8796928 &:= 8^7 \times 9 - 6^9 + 2^8 \\ 8522739 &:= (852/2 + 7) \times 3^9 & 8817978 &:= (8 + (-8 + (-1 + 7)^9) \times 7)/8 \\ 8535824 &:= 8^5 + ((35 - 8) \times 2)^4 & 8823675 &:= (8 - 8/2 + 3)^6 \times 75 \\ 8547697 &:= 8 \times (-5 + 4 \times 7^6) + 9^7 & 8857765 &:= (-8 + (8 - 5 - 7 - 7)^6) \times 5 \\ 8552444 &:= 8^5 \times (5 + 2^{4+4}) - 4 & 8869743 &:= (8 \times 8 + 69 + 74)^3 \\ 8552448 &:= 8^5 \times (5 + (2 \times 4/4)^8) & 8871456 &:= 88 \times (7^{1+4} - 5) \times 6 \\ 8561915 &:= (8^5 + 6^{-1+9} - 1) \times 5 & 8871656 &:= 8 \times (8 + 71 \times (-6 + 5^6)) \\ 8561935 &:= (8^5 + 6^{-1+9} + 3) \times 5 & 8874096 &:= 88 \times 7^{-4+09} \times 6 \\ 8566884 &:= (8 + 5^6) \times (68 \times 8 + 4) & 8912488 &:= (8 + 9) \times (-1 - 2 + 4^8) \times 8 \\ 8567575 &:= 85 \times (6 \times (7^5 - 7) - 5) & 8912862 &:= (8 + 9) \times (1 \times 2 \times 8^6 - 2) \\ 8571546 &:= (85 \times (7 \times 1)^5 - 4) \times 6 & 8933376 &:= 8^{(9+3)/3} \times (3^7 - 6) \\ 8571565 &:= 85 \times (7 \times 1)^5 \times 6 - 5 & 8937676 &:= (-8 \times (9 - 3) + 7^6) \times 76 \\ 8573184 &:= (8 \times (5 \times 73 + 1))^{8/4} & 8943376 &:= (8 \times 9 + 4) \times (3^3 + 7^6) \\ 8588553 &:= (8 \times (5^8 - 8^5) - 5) \times 3 & 8945276 &:= (8 \times 9 + 4) \times (52 + 7^6) \\ 8593758 &:= 8 + (59 - 37) \times 5^8 & 8957685 &:= (-89 + (5 + 7)^6) \times (8 - 5) \\ 8605216 &:= ((8 + 6)^{05} + 2) \times 16 & 8957933 &:= 8 + (-9 + (5 + 7)^{9-3}) \times 3 \\ 8613677 &:= (8^6 + 1) \times 36 - 7^7 & 8957944 &:= -8 + 9 \times (5 + 7)^{9-4} \times 4 \\ 8615133 &:= 8 + (615 \times 1/3)^3 & 8957951 &:= (8 + 9 - 5)^7/(9 - 5) - 1 \\ 8629248 &:= (8 \times (62 - 9))^2 \times 48 & 8968323 &:= ((8 \times 9)^{-6+8} + 3)^2/3 \\ 8643375 &:= ((8 + 6)^4 \times 3 - 3) \times 75 & 8974926 &:= (89 \times 7^{-4+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 8650587 &:= (8^6 - 5) \times (05 \times 8 - 7) & 8974986 &:= (89 \times 7^{-4+9} + 8) \times 6 \\ 8650746 &:= 8^6 \times (5 + 07 \times 4) - 6 & 8998912 &:= ((8 + 9 + 9) \times 8)^{9/(1+2)} \\ 8650752 &:= 8^6 \times ((5 \times 0 + 7) \times 5 - 2) & 8999856 &:= 8 \times (-9 - 9 + 9 \times 8 \times 5^6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9036595 &:= -90^3 + (-6 + 5^9) \times 5 & 9375516 &:= 93 \times (7^5 - 5) \times 1 \times 6 \\ 9075690 &:= 90 \times 7^5 \times 6 - 90 & 9375864 &:= (-9 \times (3 - 7) + 5^8) \times 6 \times 4 \\ 9075699 &:= 90 \times 7^5 \times 6 - 9 \times 9 & 9377469 &:= 93 \times (7 \times 7^4 \times 6 - 9) \\ 9075726 &:= (90 \times 7^5 - 7 - 2) \times 6 & 9378306 &:= 93 \times 7^{8-3} \times 06 \\ 9075786 &:= (90 \times 7^5 - 7 + 8) \times 6 & 9383112 &:= 9 \times 38^{3+1} / (1 \times 2) \\ 9075828 &:= (90 \times 7^5 + 8) \times (-2 + 8) & 9383121 &:= 9 \times (38^{3+1} / 2 + 1) \\ 9122470 &:= (9 + 12 - 2)^4 \times 70 & 9391653 &:= 9 \times (3^9 \times 1 + 6) \times 53 \\ 9139571 &:= 9 \times 13 \times (-9 + 5^7) - 1 & 9434882 &:= (9^{4+3} - 4^8 + 8) \times 2 \\ 9142569 &:= ((91 \times 4)^2 + 5) \times 69 & 9434988 &:= 9 \times 4 \times (3 + 4^9 - 8 \times 8) \\ 9174925 &:= (-9 + 1 \times 7 \times (4^9 - 2)) \times 5 & 9436536 &:= 9 \times 4 \times (-3 \times 6 + (5 + 3)^6) \\ 9174935 &:= (-9 - 1 + 7 + 4^9) \times 35 & 9436824 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+6} - 8 - 2) \times 4 \\ 9174945 &:= (9 + 1 \times 7 \times (4^9 - 4)) \times 5 & 9437067 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} - 06 - 7) \\ 9174949 &:= -91 + 7 \times 4^9 \times (-4 + 9) & 9437092 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} - 092 \\ 9174965 &:= (-9 + (1 \times 7 \times 4^9 - 6)) \times 5 & 9437139 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 1 + 3 - 9) \\ 9174975 &:= (-91/7 + 4^9 \times 7) \times 5 & 9437142 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} - 1 \times 42 \\ 9174995 &:= ((9 - 1)^7 - 4^9 - 9) \times 5 & 9437144 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} - 1 \times 4) - 4 \\ 9175049 &:= 9 + 1 \times 7 \times 5 \times 04^9 & 9437147 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} - 1) - 4 \times 7 \\ 9176328 &:= ((9 + 1 + 7) \times 63)^2 \times 8 & 9437148 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 1 \times 4 - 8 \\ 9176378 &:= -9 - 1 + (7^6 - 3) \times 78 & 9437149 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 1 - 4 \times 9 \\ 9176457 &:= (9 + 1)^7 - (6 - 4 + 5)^7 & 9437157 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} - 1 + 5 - 7) \\ 9176613 &:= -9 + 1 \times 7^6 \times 6 \times 13 & 9437163 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} - (1 + 6) \times 3 \\ 9176676 &:= (9 + 1 \times 7^6 \times (6 + 7)) \times 6 & 9437164 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} - 16 - 4 \\ 9176778 &:= (9 + 1 \times 7^6 - 7) \times 78 & 9437166 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} - 1 - 6/6) \\ 9216447 &:= 921 \times ((6 + 4)^4 + 7) & 9437169 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} - 1 \times 6 - 9 \\ 9236799 &:= (9 + 2) \times (3 \times 6^7 - 99) & 9437172 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + (1 - 7) \times 2 \\ 9237884 &:= (9 \times 2)^{-3+7} \times 88 - 4 & 9437173 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} - 1 - 7 - 3 \\ 9237888 &:= (9 \times 2)^{3-7+8} \times 88 & 9437174 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 1 - 7 - 4 \\ 9243850 &:= (9 - 2)^4 \times 3850 & 9437175 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} - 1^7 5) \\ 9252846 &:= -9 \times (2 + (5 - 2^8) \times 4^6) & 9437176 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} - 1) + 7 - 6 \\ 9253764 &:= (9 \times 2)^{5-3} \times (7 + 6)^4 & 9437177 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} - 1^7 \times 7 \\ 9277462 &:= 92 \times 7 \times 7^4 \times 6 - 2 & 9437178 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 1) - 7 - 8 \\ 9294645 &:= 929 \times ((4 + 6)^4 + 5) & 9437182 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} - 1^8 \times 2 \\ 9334953 &:= ((9 + 33)^4 - 9 \times 5) \times 3 & 9437183 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} - 1^8 3 \\ 9338595 &:= (-9/3 + 3 \times 8^5) \times 95 & 9437184 &:= (9 - 4 + 3)^7 \times 18/4 \\ 9363276 &:= (9 \times (36 + 3))^2 \times 76 & 9437185 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 1^8 5 \\ 9363744 &:= 936 \times ((3 + 7)^4 + 4) & 9437186 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 1 \times 8 - 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9437191 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} - 1 + 9 - 1 \\ 9437192 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 1 + 9 - 2 \\ 9437193 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 1^9 3) \\ 9437196 &:= 9 + (4^{3+7} + 1) \times 9 - 6 \\ 9437201 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2) - 01 \\ 9437202 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 \times 0 + 2) \\ 9437211 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 \times 1 + 1) \\ 9437216 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 2 \times 16 \\ 9437234 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 \times 3) - 4 \\ 9437247 &:= 9 \times ((4 \times (3 + 7 - 2))^4 + 7) \\ 9437248 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 2 \times 4 \times 8 \\ 9437265 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} - 2 + 6 + 5) \\ 9437274 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 2 \times 7 - 4) \\ 9437304 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 30 \times 4 \\ 9437346 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 3 \times 4 + 6) \\ 9437358 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 3 \times 58 \\ 9437382 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 3 \times 8 - 2) \\ 9437472 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 4 \times 72 \\ 9437481 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 4 \times 8 + 1) \\ 9437499 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 4 \times 9) - 9 \\ 9437544 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 5 \times (4 + 4)) \\ 9437579 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 5 \times 79 \\ 9437597 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 59 \times 7 \\ 9437652 &:= 9 \times (4^{-3+7+6} + 52) \\ 9437688 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 6 \times 8 + 8) \\ 9437697 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} - 6 + 9 \times 7) \\ 9437786 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 7 \times 86 \\ 9437832 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 8 \times 3^2) \\ 9437868 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 8 + 68) \\ 9437886 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} - 8 + 86) \\ 9437888 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + 8 \times 88 \\ 9437913 &:= 9 \times 4^{3+7} + (9 \times 1)^3 \\ 9437949 &:= 9 \times (4^{3+7} + 94 - 9) \\ 9437949 &:= 9 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9 \\ 9443745 &:= 9^4 + 4^{3+7} \times (4 + 5) \\ 9445977 &:= 9 \times ((4 \times 4)^5 + 977) \\ 9446144 &:= (9 \times (4 + 4^6) - 1) \times 4^4 \\ 9446445 &:= 9 \times ((4 + 4^6) \times 4^4 + 5) \\ 9447840 &:= 9^4 \times (4 \times 7 + 8) \times 40 \\ 9483264 &:= (9 + 4 + 8)^3 \times 2^{6+4} \\ 9487404 &:= 9 \times 4 + 8 \times (-7 + 40)^4 \\ 9492552 &:= -9 + (-4 \times (9 + 2) + 5^5)^2 \\ 9528759 &:= 9 \times (-5 + 7^{8-2} - 5) \times 9 \\ 9529569 &:= (9 \times 5 - 29 + 5)^6 / 9 \\ 9557692 &:= 9 \times (5^5 + 7^6 \times 9) - 2 \\ 9559724 &:= (9 - (5^5 - 9^7) / 2) \times 4 \\ 9563949 &:= 9 \times (-5 + 6 \times (3^9 - 4) \times 9) \\ 9564399 &:= 9 \times ((5 - 6 \times (4 - 3^9)) \times 9) \\ 9565929 &:= 9^{5+6-5} \times 9 \times 2 - 9 \\ 9565932 &:= (9^{5+6+5-9} - 3) \times 2 \\ 9565938 &:= 9^5 \times 6^5 / ((9 - 3) \times 8) \\ 9565972 &:= 9 \times 5 - 6 - 5 + 9^7 \times 2 \\ 9565973 &:= 9 \times 5 + 6 \times (-5 + 9^7) / 3 \\ 9566127 &:= (9^5 \times 6 + 6 + 1) \times 27 \\ 9566913 &:= ((9^5 + 6) \times 6 \times 9 + 1) \times 3 \\ 9567668 &:= (9 \times 5^6 + 76) \times 68 \\ 9567944 &:= 9 + 5 \times 67 \times (9 + 4)^4 \\ 9573417 &:= (9 \times (5 + 7) + 3)^{4-1} \times 7 \\ 9637744 &:= (-96^3 + 7^7 \times 4) \times 4 \\ 9653622 &:= ((9 + 6 - 5 + 3)^6 + 2) \times 2 \\ 9663597 &:= (-9 + 6 + 6^3)^{5-9+7} \\ 9663693 &:= 96 + (6^3 + 6 - 9)^3 \\ 9677568 &:= 96 \times ((-7 + 7^5) \times 6 + 8) \\ 9680832 &:= 9 \times (6 + 8)^{08-3} \times 2 \\ 9683892 &:= (9^6 - 8 + 3^8) \times 9 \times 2 \\ 9684426 &:= (-9 + 6^8 - 4^{4 \times 2}) \times 6 \\ 9711942 &:= 971 \times ((1 + 9)^4 + 2) \\ 9715592 &:= -97 + (1 + 5^5 - 9)^2 \\ 9739440 &:= ((9 \times 7)^3 - 9^4) \times 40 \\ 9739557 &:= 9 \times (-7 + 3^9) \times 55 + 7 \\ 9763573 &:= -9 \times 76 \times 3 + 5^{7+3} \\ 9765521 &:= -97 - 6 + 5^{5 \times 2} - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9765527 &:= -97 + 6 + 5^{5 \times 2} - 7 \\
 9765528 &:= -97 + (6 - 5) \times 5^{2+8} \\
 9765553 &:= -9 \times 7 - 6 + (5 \times 5)^5 - 3 \\
 9765554 &:= 9 - 76 + (5 \times 5)^5 - 4 \\
 9765556 &:= -9 \times 7 + (6 \times 5 - 5)^5 - 6 \\
 9765558 &:= 9 - 76 + 5 \times 5 \times 5^8 \\
 9765559 &:= -9 \times 7 + 6 + (5 \times 5)^5 - 9 \\
 9765561 &:= -(9 - 7)^6 + 5^{5+6-1} \\
 9765562 &:= -9 \times 7 + (6 + 5^5 - 6)^2 \\
 9765568 &:= -9 \times 7 + 6 + 5^{5 \times (-6+8)} \\
 9765573 &:= -9 \times 7 + 6 + 5 + 5^{7+3} \\
 9765585 &:= (-9 + 7 - 6 + 5 \times 5^8) \times 5 \\
 9765591 &:= 9 - 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 5^9 - 1 \\
 9765594 &:= -9 - 7 \times 6 + 5 \times (5^9 + 4) \\
 9765598 &:= 9 - 76 + 5 \times (5^9 + 8) \\
 9765613 &:= -(9 - 7) \times 6 + 5^{6+1+3} \\
 9765615 &:= -9 - 7 + 6 + 5^{6-1+5} \\
 9765616 &:= -9 + (7 - 6) \times 5^{-6+16} \\
 9765625 &:= ((9 - 7) \times 6 + 5 + 6 + 2)^5 \\
 9765635 &:= 9 + 7 - 6 + 5^{(6/3) \times 5} \\
 9765637 &:= (9 - 7) \times 6 + 5^{6-3+7} \\
 9765659 &:= (9 - 7)^6 + 5 \times (-6 + 5^9) \\
 9765682 &:= 9 \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+8/2} \\
 9765721 &:= (9 + 7) \times 6 + 5^{7+2+1} \\
 9765736 &:= 9 \times (7 + 6) + 5^{7+3} - 6 \\
 9765825 &:= (9 - 7 + 6 + 5^8) \times 25 \\
 9765855 &:= (9 + 7 + (6 + 5^8) \times 5) \times 5 \\
 9765915 &:= (9 \times 7 - 6 + 5^9 + 1) \times 5 \\
 9765955 &:= (-9 + 76 + 5^9) \times 5 - 5 \\
 9765985 &:= ((9 - 7)^6 + 5^9 + 8) \times 5 \\
 9766255 &:= 9 \times (76 - 6) + 25^5 \\
 9766595 &:= 976 - 6 + 5^9 \times 5 \\
 9772573 &:= 9 \times 772 + 5^{7+3} \\
 9781674 &:= 97 \times (8 - 1) \times 6 \times 7^4 \\
 9809424 &:= (9 \times (80 + 94))^2 \times 4 \\
 9830485 &:= (9 + 8 + 30 \times 4^8) \times 5 \\
 9834424 &:= -9 \times 8 + ((3 + 4) \times 4 \times 2)^4 \\
 9834448 &:= ((9 + 8 - 3) \times 4)^4 - 48 \\
 9834475 &:= -9 + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 7 - 5 \\
 9834484 &:= ((9 + 8 - 3) \times 4)^4 - 8 - 4 \\
 9834487 &:= -9 + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 \times (8 - 7) \\
 9834488 &:= -9 + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 + (8/8) \\
 9834543 &:= 9 \times ((8 + 3) \times (4 + 5) + 4)^3 \\
 9834874 &:= ((9 \times (8 + 34)) + ((8 \times 7)^4)) \\
 9841500 &:= 9^{8-4} \times 1500 \\
 9842679 &:= 9 \times 8^4 \times 267 - 9 \\
 9863177 &:= 9 + 86 \times (3 + 1)^7 \times 7 \\
 9871875 &:= (98/7 - 1) \times (8 + 7)^5 \\
 9874284 &:= (-98 + 7^{4+2}) \times 84 \\
 9882477 &:= 9 - (8 + 8/2) \times (4 - 7^7) \\
 9933858 &:= ((9^9 - 3)/3 - 8)/(5 + 8) \\
 9938957 &:= (-(9 + 9)/3 + (8 + 9)^5) \times 7 \\
 9961472 &:= (99 - 61) \times 4^{7+2} \\
 9966788 &:= ((-9 + (9 + 6)^6) \times 7 - 8)/8 \\
 9966789 &:= (9 + (9 + 6)^6 \times 7)/8 - 9 \\
 9987516 &:= 99 \times (8 + 7^5 - 1) \times 6 \\
 9987534 &:= -99 + 8^7 + 53^4 \\
 9999744 &:= ((9/9)^9 + 9)^7 - 4^4 \\
 9999976 &:= -9 - 9 + (9/9 + 9)^7 - 6
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Reverse Order of Digits

This section brings **selfie numbers** written in reverse order of Digits. The results are up to 7-digits numbers. It is divided in three subsections. One with symmetric and consecutive. Second symmetric and nonconsecutive and third general values.

3.1 Without Addition and Subtraction Coefficients

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= 5^2 \\ 126 &:= 6 \times 21 \\ 153 &:= 3 \times 51 \\ 688 &:= 8 \times 86 \\ 1395 &:= 5 \times 9 \times 31 \\ 2048 &:= 8^4/02 \\ 2916 &:= (6 \times 1 \times 9)^2 \\ 22264 &:= 46 \times 22^2 \\ 22528 &:= (8/2)^5 \times 22 \\ 26973 &:= 37 \times 9^{6/2} \\ 33579 &:= 9 \times 7 \times 533 \\ 36864 &:= (4 \times 6 \times 8)^{6/3} \\ 37668 &:= 86 \times 6 \times 73 \\ 015625 &:= 5^{2 \times 6 \times 5/10} \\ 102912 &:= (2 \times 1)^9 \times 201 \\ 112536 &:= 6^3 \times 521 \times 1 \\ 124416 &:= 6 \times 144^2 \times 1 \\ 170471 &:= 1 \times 7^4 \times 071 \\ 187029 &:= 9 \times 20781 \\ 209952 &:= 2^5 \times (9 \times 9)^{02} \\ 223524 &:= 42 \times 5322 \\ 262144 &:= (4^4 \times 12/6)^2 \\ 267034 &:= 4307 \times 62 \\ 314928 &:= 8 \times 2 \times 9^4 \times 1 \times 3 \\ 354375 &:= 5 \times 7 \times 3^4 \times 5^3 \\ 441344 &:= 4 \times 431 \times 4^4 \\ 589824 &:= 4^2/8 \times 9 \times 8^5 \\ 1008126 &:= 6 \times 21 \times 8001 \\ 1240029 &:= 9^{20/04} \times 21 \\ 1329264 &:= 4 \times 6^2 \times 9231 \\ 1333248 &:= 84 \times 2^{3 \times 3} \times 31 \\ 1480368 &:= 8 \times 6 \times 30841 \\ 1492992 &:= 2^9 \times 9^2 \times 9 \times 4 \times 1 \\ 1514955 &:= 5 \times 5941 \times 51 \\ 1574253 &:= 3 \times 524751 \\ 1766196 &:= 691 \times 6 \times 6 \times 71 \\ 1791495 &:= 5 \times 9 \times 41 \times 971 \\ 1831086 &:= 6 \times 801 \times 381 \\ 1945944 &:= 44 \times 9 \times 54 \times 91 \\ 2162688 &:= 88 \times 6 \times (2^6 \times 1)^2 \\ 2328576 &:= 6 \times 758 \times 2^{3^2} \\ 2336064 &:= (46 \times 06)^3/(3^2) \\ 2624832 &:= 2 \times 3 \times 84^2 \times 62 \\ 2722734 &:= 4 \times (3 \times 7)^{2 \times 2} \times 7/2 \\ 2784384 &:= 4834 \times 8 \times 72 \\ 2794764 &:= 4 \times 6 \times 7^4 \times 97/2 \\ 3359232 &:= 2^{3^2} \times 9^5/(3 \times 3) \\ 3927552 &:= 2557 \times 2^9 \times 3 \\ 3981312 &:= 2^{13} \times 18 \times 9 \times 3 \\ 4456448 &:= 8/4 \times 4^6 \times 544 \\ 4499712 &:= 217 \times 9 \times 9 \times 4^4 \\ 4782969 &:= 9^6 \times 9 \times 28/(7 \times 4) \\ 6377292 &:= 2 \times (9^2 \times 7/7)^3 \times 6 \\ 7012352 &:= 2^{5 \times 3} \times 2 \times 107 \\ 7483392 &:= 29 \times 3 \times 3 \times 8^4 \times 7 \\ 7503125 &:= (5 \times 21/3)^{05}/7 \\ 8126464 &:= 4^6 \times 4 \times 62 \times 1 \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned} 013950 &:= 0 + 5 \times 9 \times 310 \\ 013951 &:= 1 + 5 \times 9 \times 310 \\ 013952 &:= 2 + 5 \times 9 \times 310 \\ 013953 &:= 3 + 5 \times 9 \times 310 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}013954 &:= 4 + 5 \times 9 \times 310 \\013955 &:= 5 + 5 \times 9 \times 310 \\013956 &:= 6 + 5 \times 9 \times 310 \\013957 &:= 7 + 5 \times 9 \times 310 \\013958 &:= 8 + 5 \times 9 \times 310 \\013959 &:= 9 + 5 \times 9 \times 310\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}061440 &:= 0 + 4^{4+1} \times 60 \\061441 &:= 1 + 4^{4+1} \times 60 \\061442 &:= 2 + 4^{4+1} \times 60 \\061443 &:= 3 + 4^{4+1} \times 60 \\061444 &:= 4 + 4^{4+1} \times 60 \\061445 &:= 5 + 4^{4+1} \times 60 \\061446 &:= 6 + 4^{4+1} \times 60 \\061447 &:= 7 + 4^{4+1} \times 60 \\061448 &:= 8 + 4^{4+1} \times 60 \\061449 &:= 9 + 4^{4+1} \times 60\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}081920 &:= 0 + 2^{9+1} \times 80 \\081921 &:= 1 + 2^{9+1} \times 80 \\081922 &:= 2 + 2^{9+1} \times 80 \\081923 &:= 3 + 2^{9+1} \times 80 \\081924 &:= 4 + 2^{9+1} \times 80 \\081925 &:= 5 + 2^{9+1} \times 80 \\081926 &:= 6 + 2^{9+1} \times 80 \\081927 &:= 7 + 2^{9+1} \times 80 \\081928 &:= 8 + 2^{9+1} \times 80 \\081929 &:= 9 + 2^{9+1} \times 80\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}163840 &:= 0 + (4 \times 8)^3 \times (6 - 1) \\163841 &:= 1 + (4 \times 8)^3 \times (6 - 1) \\163842 &:= 2 + (4 \times 8)^3 \times (6 - 1) \\163843 &:= 3 + (4 \times 8)^3 \times (6 - 1) \\163844 &:= 4 + (4 \times 8)^3 \times (6 - 1) \\163845 &:= 5 + (4 \times 8)^3 \times (6 - 1) \\163846 &:= 6 + (4 \times 8)^3 \times (6 - 1) \\163847 &:= 7 + (4 \times 8)^3 \times (6 - 1) \\163848 &:= 8 + (4 \times 8)^3 \times (6 - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$163849 := 9 + (4 \times 8)^3 \times (6 - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}328510 &:= 0 + 1 + (5 + 8^2)^3 \\328511 &:= 1 + 1 + (5 + 8^2)^3 \\328512 &:= 2 + 1 + (5 + 8^2)^3 \\328513 &:= 3 + 1 + (5 + 8^2)^3 \\328514 &:= 4 + 1 + (5 + 8^2)^3 \\328515 &:= 5 + 1 + (5 + 8^2)^3 \\328516 &:= 6 + 1 + (5 + 8^2)^3 \\328517 &:= 7 + 1 + (5 + 8^2)^3 \\328518 &:= 8 + 1 + (5 + 8^2)^3 \\328519 &:= 9 + 1 + (5 + 8^2)^3\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}466520 &:= 0 + 2 \times 5 \times (6^6 - 4) \\466521 &:= 1 + 2 \times 5 \times (6^6 - 4) \\466522 &:= 2 + 2 \times 5 \times (6^6 - 4) \\466523 &:= 3 + 2 \times 5 \times (6^6 - 4) \\466524 &:= 4 + 2 \times 5 \times (6^6 - 4) \\466525 &:= 5 + 2 \times 5 \times (6^6 - 4) \\466526 &:= 6 + 2 \times 5 \times (6^6 - 4) \\466527 &:= 7 + 2 \times 5 \times (6^6 - 4) \\466528 &:= 8 + 2 \times 5 \times (6^6 - 4) \\466529 &:= 9 + 2 \times 5 \times (6^6 - 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}466560 &:= 0 + 6^5 \times 6 \times (6 + 4) \\466561 &:= 1 + 6^5 \times 6 \times (6 + 4) \\466562 &:= 2 + 6^5 \times 6 \times (6 + 4) \\466563 &:= 3 + 6^5 \times 6 \times (6 + 4) \\466564 &:= 4 + 6^5 \times 6 \times (6 + 4) \\466565 &:= 5 + 6^5 \times 6 \times (6 + 4) \\466566 &:= 6 + 6^5 \times 6 \times (6 + 4) \\466567 &:= 7 + 6^5 \times 6 \times (6 + 4) \\466568 &:= 8 + 6^5 \times 6 \times (6 + 4) \\466569 &:= 9 + 6^5 \times 6 \times (6 + 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}468750 &:= 0 + 5^7 \times (8 - 6 + 4) \\468751 &:= 1 + 5^7 \times (8 - 6 + 4) \\468752 &:= 2 + 5^7 \times (8 - 6 + 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$468753 := 3 + 5^7 \times (8 - 6 + 4)$$

$$468754 := 4 + 5^7 \times (8 - 6 + 4)$$

$$468755 := 5 + 5^7 \times (8 - 6 + 4)$$

$$468756 := 6 + 5^7 \times (8 - 6 + 4)$$

$$468757 := 7 + 5^7 \times (8 - 6 + 4)$$

$$468758 := 8 + 5^7 \times (8 - 6 + 4)$$

$$468759 := 9 + 5^7 \times (8 - 6 + 4)$$

$$573440 := 0 + 4^{4+3} \times 7 \times 5$$

$$573441 := 1 + 4^{4+3} \times 7 \times 5$$

$$573442 := 2 + 4^{4+3} \times 7 \times 5$$

$$573443 := 3 + 4^{4+3} \times 7 \times 5$$

$$573444 := 4 + 4^{4+3} \times 7 \times 5$$

$$573445 := 5 + 4^{4+3} \times 7 \times 5$$

$$573446 := 6 + 4^{4+3} \times 7 \times 5$$

$$573447 := 7 + 4^{4+3} \times 7 \times 5$$

$$573448 := 8 + 4^{4+3} \times 7 \times 5$$

$$573449 := 9 + 4^{4+3} \times 7 \times 5$$

$$656250 := 0 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6$$

$$656251 := 1 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6$$

$$656252 := 2 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6$$

$$656253 := 3 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6$$

$$656254 := 4 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6$$

$$656255 := 5 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6$$

$$656256 := 6 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6$$

$$656257 := 7 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6$$

$$656258 := 8 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6$$

$$656259 := 9 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6$$

$$937500 := 0 + 05^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937501 := 1 + 05^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937502 := 2 + 05^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937503 := 3 + 05^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937504 := 4 + 05^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937505 := 5 + 05^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937506 := 6 + 05^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937507 := 7 + 05^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937508 := 8 + 05^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937509 := 9 + 05^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$0012600 := 0 + 06 \times 2100$$

$$0012601 := 1 + 06 \times 2100$$

$$0012602 := 2 + 06 \times 2100$$

$$0012603 := 3 + 06 \times 2100$$

$$0012604 := 4 + 06 \times 2100$$

$$0012605 := 5 + 06 \times 2100$$

$$0012606 := 6 + 06 \times 2100$$

$$0012607 := 7 + 06 \times 2100$$

$$0012608 := 8 + 06 \times 2100$$

$$0012609 := 9 + 06 \times 2100$$

$$0015300 := 0 + 03 \times 5100$$

$$0015301 := 1 + 03 \times 5100$$

$$0015302 := 2 + 03 \times 5100$$

$$0015303 := 3 + 03 \times 5100$$

$$0015304 := 4 + 03 \times 5100$$

$$0015305 := 5 + 03 \times 5100$$

$$0015306 := 6 + 03 \times 5100$$

$$0015307 := 7 + 03 \times 5100$$

$$0015308 := 8 + 03 \times 5100$$

$$0015309 := 9 + 03 \times 5100$$

$$0068800 := 0 + 08 \times 8600$$

$$0068801 := 1 + 08 \times 8600$$

$$0068802 := 2 + 08 \times 8600$$

$$0068803 := 3 + 08 \times 8600$$

$$0068804 := 4 + 08 \times 8600$$

$$0068805 := 5 + 08 \times 8600$$

$$0068806 := 6 + 08 \times 8600$$

$$0068807 := 7 + 08 \times 8600$$

$$0068808 := 8 + 08 \times 8600$$

$$0068809 := 9 + 08 \times 8600$$

$$0138240 := 0 + (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 10$$

$$0138241 := 1 + (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 10$$

$$0138242 := 2 + (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 10$$

$$0138243 := 3 + (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 10$$

$$\begin{aligned}0138244 &:= 4 + (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 10 \\0138245 &:= 5 + (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 10 \\0138246 &:= 6 + (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 10 \\0138247 &:= 7 + (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 10 \\0138248 &:= 8 + (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 10 \\0138249 &:= 9 + (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 10\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}0155620 &:= 0 + 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 10 \\0155621 &:= 1 + 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 10 \\0155622 &:= 2 + 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 10 \\0155623 &:= 3 + 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 10 \\0155624 &:= 4 + 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 10 \\0155625 &:= 5 + 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 10 \\0155626 &:= 6 + 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 10 \\0155627 &:= 7 + 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 10 \\0155628 &:= 8 + 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 10 \\0155629 &:= 9 + 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 10\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}0155850 &:= 0 - 5 \times (8 - 5^5) \times 10 \\0155851 &:= 1 - 5 \times (8 - 5^5) \times 10 \\0155852 &:= 2 - 5 \times (8 - 5^5) \times 10 \\0155853 &:= 3 - 5 \times (8 - 5^5) \times 10 \\0155854 &:= 4 - 5 \times (8 - 5^5) \times 10 \\0155855 &:= 5 - 5 \times (8 - 5^5) \times 10 \\0155856 &:= 6 - 5 \times (8 - 5^5) \times 10 \\0155857 &:= 7 - 5 \times (8 - 5^5) \times 10 \\0155858 &:= 8 - 5 \times (8 - 5^5) \times 10 \\0155859 &:= 9 - 5 \times (8 - 5^5) \times 10\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}0156550 &:= 0 + (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 10 \\0156551 &:= 1 + (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 10 \\0156552 &:= 2 + (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 10 \\0156553 &:= 3 + (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 10 \\0156554 &:= 4 + (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 10 \\0156555 &:= 5 + (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 10 \\0156556 &:= 6 + (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 10 \\0156557 &:= 7 + (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 10\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}0156558 &:= 8 + (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 10 \\0156559 &:= 9 + (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 10 \\0196830 &:= 0 - 3^8 \times (6 - 9) \times 10 \\0196831 &:= 1 - 3^8 \times (6 - 9) \times 10 \\0196832 &:= 2 - 3^8 \times (6 - 9) \times 10 \\0196833 &:= 3 - 3^8 \times (6 - 9) \times 10 \\0196834 &:= 4 - 3^8 \times (6 - 9) \times 10 \\0196835 &:= 4 - 3^8 \times (6 - 9) \times 10 \\0196836 &:= 6 - 3^8 \times (6 - 9) \times 10 \\0196837 &:= 7 - 3^8 \times (6 - 9) \times 10 \\0196838 &:= 8 - 3^8 \times (6 - 9) \times 10 \\0196839 &:= 9 - 3^8 \times (6 - 9) \times 10\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}0225280 &:= 0 + (8/2)^5 \times 220 \\0225281 &:= 1 + (8/2)^5 \times 220 \\0225282 &:= 2 + (8/2)^5 \times 220 \\0225283 &:= 3 + (8/2)^5 \times 220 \\0225284 &:= 4 + (8/2)^5 \times 220 \\0225285 &:= 5 + (8/2)^5 \times 220 \\0225286 &:= 6 + (8/2)^5 \times 220 \\0225287 &:= 7 + (8/2)^5 \times 220 \\0225288 &:= 8 + (8/2)^5 \times 220 \\0225289 &:= 9 + (8/2)^5 \times 220\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}0233920 &:= 0 + (2 + 9^3) \times 320 \\0233921 &:= 1 + (2 + 9^3) \times 320 \\0233922 &:= 2 + (2 + 9^3) \times 320 \\0233923 &:= 3 + (2 + 9^3) \times 320 \\0233924 &:= 4 + (2 + 9^3) \times 320 \\0233925 &:= 5 + (2 + 9^3) \times 320 \\0233926 &:= 6 + (2 + 9^3) \times 320 \\0233927 &:= 7 + (2 + 9^3) \times 320 \\0233928 &:= 8 + (2 + 9^3) \times 320 \\0233929 &:= 9 + (2 + 9^3) \times 320\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}0282240 &:= 0 + 42^2 \times 8 \times 20 \\0282241 &:= 1 + 42^2 \times 8 \times 20 \\0282242 &:= 2 + 42^2 \times 8 \times 20\end{aligned}$$

$$0282243 := 3 + 42^2 \times 8 \times 20$$

$$0282244 := 4 + 42^2 \times 8 \times 20$$

$$0282245 := 5 + 42^2 \times 8 \times 20$$

$$0282246 := 6 + 42^2 \times 8 \times 20$$

$$0282247 := 7 + 42^2 \times 8 \times 20$$

$$0282248 := 8 + 42^2 \times 8 \times 20$$

$$0282249 := 9 + 42^2 \times 8 \times 20$$

$$0335790 := 0 + 9 \times 7 \times 5330$$

$$0335791 := 1 + 9 \times 7 \times 5330$$

$$0335792 := 2 + 9 \times 7 \times 5330$$

$$0335793 := 3 + 9 \times 7 \times 5330$$

$$0335794 := 4 + 9 \times 7 \times 5330$$

$$0335795 := 5 + 9 \times 7 \times 5330$$

$$0335796 := 6 + 9 \times 7 \times 5330$$

$$0335797 := 7 + 9 \times 7 \times 5330$$

$$0335798 := 8 + 9 \times 7 \times 5330$$

$$0335799 := 9 + 9 \times 7 \times 5330$$

$$0376680 := 0 + 86 \times 6 \times 730$$

$$0376681 := 1 + 86 \times 6 \times 730$$

$$0376682 := 2 + 86 \times 6 \times 730$$

$$0376683 := 3 + 86 \times 6 \times 730$$

$$0376684 := 4 + 86 \times 6 \times 730$$

$$0376685 := 5 + 86 \times 6 \times 730$$

$$0376686 := 6 + 86 \times 6 \times 730$$

$$0376687 := 7 + 86 \times 6 \times 730$$

$$0376688 := 8 + 86 \times 6 \times 730$$

$$0376689 := 9 + 86 \times 6 \times 730$$

$$0393540 := 0 + 4 \times (5 \times 3^9 - 30)$$

$$0393541 := 1 + 4 \times (5 \times 3^9 - 30)$$

$$0393542 := 2 + 4 \times (5 \times 3^9 - 30)$$

$$0393543 := 3 + 4 \times (5 \times 3^9 - 30)$$

$$0393544 := 4 + 4 \times (5 \times 3^9 - 30)$$

$$0393545 := 5 + 4 \times (5 \times 3^9 - 30)$$

$$0393546 := 6 + 4 \times (5 \times 3^9 - 30)$$

$$0393547 := 7 + 4 \times (5 \times 3^9 - 30)$$

$$0393548 := 8 + 4 \times (5 \times 3^9 - 30)$$

$$0393549 := 9 + 4 \times (5 \times 3^9 - 30)$$

$$0414680 := 0 + (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 40$$

$$0414681 := 1 + (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 40$$

$$0414682 := 2 + (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 40$$

$$0414683 := 3 + (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 40$$

$$0414684 := 4 + (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 40$$

$$0414685 := 5 + (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 40$$

$$0414686 := 6 + (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 40$$

$$0414687 := 7 + (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 40$$

$$0414688 := 8 + (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 40$$

$$0414689 := 9 + (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 40$$

$$0593750 := 0 + 5^{7-3} \times 950$$

$$0593751 := 1 + 5^{7-3} \times 950$$

$$0593752 := 2 + 5^{7-3} \times 950$$

$$0593753 := 3 + 5^{7-3} \times 950$$

$$0593754 := 4 + 5^{7-3} \times 950$$

$$0593755 := 5 + 5^{7-3} \times 950$$

$$0593756 := 6 + 5^{7-3} \times 950$$

$$0593757 := 7 + 5^{7-3} \times 950$$

$$0593758 := 8 + 5^{7-3} \times 950$$

$$0593759 := 9 + 5^{7-3} \times 950$$

$$0640240 := 0 + 4 \times (20^4 + 60)$$

$$0640241 := 1 + 4 \times (20^4 + 60)$$

$$0640242 := 2 + 4 \times (20^4 + 60)$$

$$0640243 := 3 + 4 \times (20^4 + 60)$$

$$0640244 := 4 + 4 \times (20^4 + 60)$$

$$0640245 := 5 + 4 \times (20^4 + 60)$$

$$0640246 := 6 + 4 \times (20^4 + 60)$$

$$0640247 := 7 + 4 \times (20^4 + 60)$$

$$0640248 := 8 + 4 \times (20^4 + 60)$$

$$0640249 := 9 + 4 \times (20^4 + 60)$$

$$1044480 := 0 + 8^4 \times (4^4 - 01)$$

$$1044481 := 1 + 8^4 \times (4^4 - 01)$$

$$1044482 := 2 + 8^4 \times (4^4 - 01)$$

$$1044483 := 3 + 8^4 \times (4^4 - 01)$$

$$1044484 := 4 + 8^4 \times (4^4 - 01)$$

$$1044485 := 5 + 8^4 \times (4^4 - 01)$$

$$1044486 := 6 + 8^4 \times (4^4 - 01)$$

$$1044487 := 7 + 8^4 \times (4^4 - 01)$$

$$1044488 := 8 + 8^4 \times (4^4 - 01)$$

$$1044489 := 9 + 8^4 \times (4^4 - 01)$$

$$1474560 := 0 + 6 \times 5 \times 4^7 \times (4 - 1)$$

$$1474561 := 1 + 6 \times 5 \times 4^7 \times (4 - 1)$$

$$1474562 := 2 + 6 \times 5 \times 4^7 \times (4 - 1)$$

$$1474563 := 2 + 6 \times 5 \times 4^7 \times (4 - 1)$$

$$1474564 := 4 + 6 \times 5 \times 4^7 \times (4 - 1)$$

$$1474565 := 5 + 6 \times 5 \times 4^7 \times (4 - 1)$$

$$1474566 := 6 + 6 \times 5 \times 4^7 \times (4 - 1)$$

$$1474567 := 7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4^7 \times (4 - 1)$$

$$1474568 := 8 + 6 \times 5 \times 4^7 \times (4 - 1)$$

$$1474569 := 9 + 6 \times 5 \times 4^7 \times (4 - 1)$$

$$1562500 := 0 + 05^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)$$

$$1562501 := 1 + 05^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)$$

$$1562502 := 2 + 05^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)$$

$$1562503 := 3 + 05^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)$$

$$1562504 := 4 + 05^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)$$

$$1562505 := 5 + 05^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)$$

$$1562506 := 6 + 05^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)$$

$$1562507 := 7 + 05^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)$$

$$1562508 := 8 + 05^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)$$

$$1562509 := 9 + 05^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)$$

$$1594330 := 0 + 3 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1$$

$$1594331 := 1 + 3 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1$$

$$1594332 := 2 + 3 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1$$

$$1594333 := 3 + 3 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1$$

$$1594334 := 4 + 3 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1$$

$$1594335 := 5 + 3 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1$$

$$1594336 := 6 + 3 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1$$

$$1594337 := 7 + 3 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1$$

$$1594338 := 8 + 3 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1$$

$$1594339 := 9 + 3 + 3^{4+9} + 5 - 1$$

$$1771560 := 0 + (6 + 5)^{-1^7+7} - 1$$

$$1771561 := 1 + (6 + 5)^{-1^7+7} - 1$$

$$1771562 := 2 + (6 + 5)^{-1^7+7} - 1$$

$$1771563 := 3 + (6 + 5)^{-1^7+7} - 1$$

$$1771564 := 4 + (6 + 5)^{-1^7+7} - 1$$

$$1771565 := 5 + (6 + 5)^{-1^7+7} - 1$$

$$1771566 := 6 + (6 + 5)^{-1^7+7} - 1$$

$$1771567 := 7 + (6 + 5)^{-1^7+7} - 1$$

$$1771568 := 8 + (6 + 5)^{-1^7+7} - 1$$

$$1771569 := 9 + (6 + 5)^{-1^7+7} - 1$$

$$1837040 := 0 + 40 \times (7 \times 3^8 - 1)$$

$$1837041 := 1 + 40 \times (7 \times 3^8 - 1)$$

$$1837042 := 2 + 40 \times (7 \times 3^8 - 1)$$

$$1837043 := 3 + 40 \times (7 \times 3^8 - 1)$$

$$1837044 := 4 + 40 \times (7 \times 3^8 - 1)$$

$$1837045 := 5 + 40 \times (7 \times 3^8 - 1)$$

$$1837046 := 6 + 40 \times (7 \times 3^8 - 1)$$

$$1837047 := 7 + 40 \times (7 \times 3^8 - 1)$$

$$1837048 := 8 + 40 \times (7 \times 3^8 - 1)$$

$$1837049 := 9 + 40 \times (7 \times 3^8 - 1)$$

$$1866250 := 0 + 5 \times (2 + 6^6 \times 8 \times 1)$$

$$1866251 := 1 + 5 \times (2 + 6^6 \times 8 \times 1)$$

$$1866252 := 2 + 5 \times (2 + 6^6 \times 8 \times 1)$$

$$1866253 := 3 + 5 \times (2 + 6^6 \times 8 \times 1)$$

$$1866254 := 4 + 5 \times (2 + 6^6 \times 8 \times 1)$$

$$1866255 := 5 + 5 \times (2 + 6^6 \times 8 \times 1)$$

$$1866256 := 6 + 5 \times (2 + 6^6 \times 8 \times 1)$$

$$1866257 := 7 + 5 \times (2 + 6^6 \times 8 \times 1)$$

$$1866258 := 8 + 5 \times (2 + 6^6 \times 8 \times 1)$$

$$1866259 := 9 + 5 \times (2 + 6^6 \times 8 \times 1)$$

$$1941760 := 0 + 6^{7+1} + 4^9 \times 1$$

$$1941761 := 1 + 6^{7+1} + 4^9 \times 1$$

$$1941762 := 2 + 6^{7+1} + 4^9 \times 1$$

$$1941763 := 3 + 6^{7+1} + 4^9 \times 1$$

$$1941764 := 4 + 6^{7+1} + 4^9 \times 1$$

$$1941765 := 5 + 6^{7+1} + 4^9 \times 1$$

$$1941766 := 6 + 6^{7+1} + 4^9 \times 1$$

$$1941767 := 7 + 6^{7+1} + 4^9 \times 1$$

$$1941768 := 8 + 6^{7+1} + 4^9 \times 1$$

$$1941769 := 9 + 6^{7+1} + 4^9 \times 1$$

$$1952980 := 0 - 8 \times 9 \times 2 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1952981 := 1 - 8 \times 9 \times 2 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1952982 := 2 - 8 \times 9 \times 2 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1952983 := 3 - 8 \times 9 \times 2 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1952984 := 4 - 8 \times 9 \times 2 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1952985 := 5 - 8 \times 9 \times 2 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1952986 := 6 - 8 \times 9 \times 2 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1952987 := 7 - 8 \times 9 \times 2 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1952988 := 8 - 8 \times 9 \times 2 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1952989 := 9 - 8 \times 9 \times 2 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1953120 := 0 - 2 - 1 - 3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953121 := 1 - 2 - 1 - 3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953122 := 2 - 2 - 1 - 3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953123 := 3 - 2 - 1 - 3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953124 := 4 - 2 - 1 - 3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953125 := 5 - 2 - 1 - 3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953126 := 6 - 2 - 1 - 3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953127 := 7 - 2 - 1 - 3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953128 := 8 - 2 - 1 - 3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953129 := 9 - 2 - 1 - 3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953130 := 0 + 3 + 1^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953131 := 1 + 3 + 1^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953132 := 2 + 3 + 1^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953133 := 3 + 3 + 1^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953134 := 4 + 3 + 1^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953135 := 5 + 3 + 1^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953136 := 6 + 3 + 1^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953137 := 7 + 3 + 1^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953138 := 8 + 3 + 1^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953139 := 9 + 3 + 1^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953750 := 0 + 5^{7-3} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953751 := 1 + 5^{7-3} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953752 := 2 + 5^{7-3} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953753 := 3 + 5^{7-3} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953754 := 4 + 5^{7-3} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953755 := 5 + 5^{7-3} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953756 := 6 + 5^{7-3} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953757 := 7 + 5^{7-3} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953758 := 8 + 5^{7-3} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953759 := 9 + 5^{7-3} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1954420 := 0 + (2 + 4)^4 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1954421 := 1 + (2 + 4)^4 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1954422 := 2 + (2 + 4)^4 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1954423 := 3 + (2 + 4)^4 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1954424 := 4 + (2 + 4)^4 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1954425 := 5 + (2 + 4)^4 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1954426 := 6 + (2 + 4)^4 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1954427 := 7 + (2 + 4)^4 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1954428 := 8 + (2 + 4)^4 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1954429 := 9 + (2 + 4)^4 + 5^9 - 1$$

$$1965840 := 0 - (4 - 8^5) \times 6 \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1965841 := 1 - (4 - 8^5) \times 6 \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1965842 := 2 - (4 - 8^5) \times 6 \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1965843 := 3 - (4 - 8^5) \times 6 \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1965844 := 4 - (4 - 8^5) \times 6 \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1965845 := 5 - (4 - 8^5) \times 6 \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1965846 := 6 - (4 - 8^5) \times 6 \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1965847 := 7 - (4 - 8^5) \times 6 \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1965848 := 8 - (4 - 8^5) \times 6 \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1965849 := 9 - (4 - 8^5) \times 6 \times (9 + 1)$$

$$2097170 := 0 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9 \times 02$$

$$2097171 := 1 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9 \times 02$$

$$2097172 := 2 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9 \times 02$$

$$2097173 := 3 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9 \times 02$$

$$2097174 := 4 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9 \times 02$$

$$2097175 := 5 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9 \times 02$$

$$2097176 := 6 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9 \times 02$$

$$2097177 := 7 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9 \times 02$$

$$2097178 := 8 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9 \times 02$$

$$2097179 := 9 + (7 + 1)^7 + 9 \times 02$$

$$2097240 := 0 + (4 \times 2)^7 + 90 - 2$$

$$2097241 := 1 + (4 \times 2)^7 + 90 - 2$$

$$2097242 := 2 + (4 \times 2)^7 + 90 - 2$$

$$2097243 := 3 + (4 \times 2)^7 + 90 - 2$$

$$2097244 := 4 + (4 \times 2)^7 + 90 - 2$$

$$2097245 := 5 + (4 \times 2)^7 + 90 - 2$$

$$2097246 := 6 + (4 \times 2)^7 + 90 - 2$$

$$2097247 := 7 + (4 \times 2)^7 + 90 - 2$$

$$2097248 := 8 + (4 \times 2)^7 + 90 - 2$$

$$2097249 := 9 + (4 \times 2)^7 + 90 - 2$$

$$2097780 := 0 + 8^7 + 7 \times 90 - 2$$

$$2097781 := 1 + 8^7 + 7 \times 90 - 2$$

$$2097782 := 2 + 8^7 + 7 \times 90 - 2$$

$$2097783 := 3 + 8^7 + 7 \times 90 - 2$$

$$2097784 := 4 + 8^7 + 7 \times 90 - 2$$

$$2097785 := 5 + 8^7 + 7 \times 90 - 2$$

$$2097786 := 6 + 8^7 + 7 \times 90 - 2$$

$$2097787 := 7 + 8^7 + 7 \times 90 - 2$$

$$2097788 := 8 + 8^7 + 7 \times 90 - 2$$

$$2097789 := 9 + 8^7 + 7 \times 90 - 2$$

$$2137440 := 0 - 4 + 4 \times 731^2$$

$$2137441 := 1 - 4 + 4 \times 731^2$$

$$2137442 := 2 - 4 + 4 \times 731^2$$

$$2137443 := 3 - 4 + 4 \times 731^2$$

$$2137444 := 4 - 4 + 4 \times 731^2$$

$$2137445 := 5 - 4 + 4 \times 731^2$$

$$2137446 := 6 - 4 + 4 \times 731^2$$

$$2137447 := 7 - 4 + 4 \times 731^2$$

$$2137448 := 8 - 4 + 4 \times 731^2$$

$$2137449 := 9 - 4 + 4 \times 731^2$$

$$2343750 := 0 + 5^7 \times (3 \times 4 + 3) \times 2$$

$$2343751 := 1 + 5^7 \times (3 \times 4 + 3) \times 2$$

$$2343752 := 2 + 5^7 \times (3 \times 4 + 3) \times 2$$

$$2343753 := 3 + 5^7 \times (3 \times 4 + 3) \times 2$$

$$2343754 := 4 + 5^7 \times (3 \times 4 + 3) \times 2$$

$$2343755 := 5 + 5^7 \times (3 \times 4 + 3) \times 2$$

$$2343756 := 6 + 5^7 \times (3 \times 4 + 3) \times 2$$

$$2343757 := 7 + 5^7 \times (3 \times 4 + 3) \times 2$$

$$2343758 := 8 + 5^7 \times (3 \times 4 + 3) \times 2$$

$$2343759 := 9 + 5^7 \times (3 \times 4 + 3) \times 2$$

$$2584960 := 0 + 6^9/4 + 8^5 \times 2$$

$$2584961 := 1 + 6^9/4 + 8^5 \times 2$$

$$2584962 := 2 + 6^9/4 + 8^5 \times 2$$

$$2584963 := 3 + 6^9/4 + 8^5 \times 2$$

$$2584964 := 4 + 6^9/4 + 8^5 \times 2$$

$$2584965 := 5 + 6^9/4 + 8^5 \times 2$$

$$2584966 := 6 + 6^9/4 + 8^5 \times 2$$

$$2584967 := 7 + 6^9/4 + 8^5 \times 2$$

$$2584968 := 8 + 6^9/4 + 8^5 \times 2$$

$$2584969 := 9 + 6^9/4 + 8^5 \times 2$$

$$2654210 := 0 + (1 + 24^5/6) \times 2$$

$$2654211 := 1 + (1 + 24^5/6) \times 2$$

$$2654212 := 2 + (1 + 24^5/6) \times 2$$

$$2654213 := 3 + (1 + 24^5/6) \times 2$$

$$2654214 := 4 + (1 + 24^5/6) \times 2$$

$$2654215 := 5 + (1 + 24^5/6) \times 2$$

$$2654216 := 6 + (1 + 24^5/6) \times 2$$

$$2654217 := 7 + (1 + 24^5/6) \times 2$$

$$2654218 := 8 + (1 + 24^5/6) \times 2$$

$$2654219 := 9 + (1 + 24^5/6) \times 2$$

$$2733750 := 0 + 5^{7-3} \times 3^7 \times 2$$

$$2733751 := 1 + 5^{7-3} \times 3^7 \times 2$$

$$2733752 := 2 + 5^{7-3} \times 3^7 \times 2$$

$$2733753 := 3 + 5^{7-3} \times 3^7 \times 2$$

$$2733754 := 4 + 5^{7-3} \times 3^7 \times 2$$

$$2733755 := 5 + 5^{7-3} \times 3^7 \times 2$$

$$2733756 := 6 + 5^{7-3} \times 3^7 \times 2$$

$$2733757 := 7 + 5^{7-3} \times 3^7 \times 2$$

$$2733758 := 8 + 5^{7-3} \times 3^7 \times 2$$

$$2733759 := 9 + 5^{7-3} \times 3^7 \times 2$$

$$2968750 := 0 + 5^7 \times (8 + (6 + 9) \times 2)$$

$$2968751 := 1 + 5^7 \times (8 + (6 + 9) \times 2)$$

$$2968752 := 2 + 5^7 \times (8 + (6 + 9) \times 2)$$

$$2968753 := 3 + 5^7 \times (8 + (6 + 9) \times 2)$$

$$2968754 := 4 + 5^7 \times (8 + (6 + 9) \times 2)$$

$$2968755 := 5 + 5^7 \times (8 + (6 + 9) \times 2)$$

$$2968756 := 6 + 5^7 \times (8 + (6 + 9) \times 2)$$

$$2968757 := 7 + 5^7 \times (8 + (6 + 9) \times 2)$$

$$2968758 := 8 + 5^7 \times (8 + (6 + 9) \times 2)$$

$$2968759 := 9 + 5^7 \times (8 + (6 + 9) \times 2)$$

$$3255210 := 0 + 1 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$3255211 := 1 + 1 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$3255212 := 2 + 1 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$3255213 := 3 + 1 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$3255214 := 4 + 1 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$3255215 := 5 + 1 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$3255216 := 6 + 1 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$3255217 := 7 + 1 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$3255218 := 8 + 1 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$3255219 := 9 + 1 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$3542940 := 0 + 4 \times 9^{2+4} \times 5/3$$

$$3542941 := 1 + 4 \times 9^{2+4} \times 5/3$$

$$3542942 := 2 + 4 \times 9^{2+4} \times 5/3$$

$$3542943 := 3 + 4 \times 9^{2+4} \times 5/3$$

$$3542944 := 4 + 4 \times 9^{2+4} \times 5/3$$

$$3542945 := 5 + 4 \times 9^{2+4} \times 5/3$$

$$3542946 := 6 + 4 \times 9^{2+4} \times 5/3$$

$$3542947 := 7 + 4 \times 9^{2+4} \times 5/3$$

$$3542948 := 8 + 4 \times 9^{2+4} \times 5/3$$

$$3542949 := 9 + 4 \times 9^{2+4} \times 5/3$$

$$3581570 := 0 - 7 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3$$

$$3581571 := 1 - 7 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3$$

$$3581572 := 2 - 7 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3$$

$$3581573 := 3 - 7 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3$$

$$3581574 := 4 - 7 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3$$

$$3581575 := 5 - 7 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3$$

$$3581576 := 6 - 7 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3$$

$$3581577 := 7 - 7 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3$$

$$3581578 := 8 - 7 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3$$

$$3581579 := 9 - 7 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3$$

$$3639870 := 0 + 78 \times (9 + 36^3)$$

$$3639871 := 1 + 78 \times (9 + 36^3)$$

$$3639872 := 2 + 78 \times (9 + 36^3)$$

$$3639873 := 3 + 78 \times (9 + 36^3)$$

$$3639874 := 4 + 78 \times (9 + 36^3)$$

$$3639875 := 5 + 78 \times (9 + 36^3)$$

$$3639876 := 6 + 78 \times (9 + 36^3)$$

$$3639877 := 7 + 78 \times (9 + 36^3)$$

$$3639878 := 8 + 78 \times (9 + 36^3)$$

$$3639879 := 9 + 78 \times (9 + 36^3)$$

$$3895840 := 0 + 4 \times (8^5 + 98^3)$$

$$3895841 := 1 + 4 \times (8^5 + 98^3)$$

$$3895842 := 2 + 4 \times (8^5 + 98^3)$$

$$3895843 := 3 + 4 \times (8^5 + 98^3)$$

$$3895844 := 4 + 4 \times (8^5 + 98^3)$$

$$3895845 := 5 + 4 \times (8^5 + 98^3)$$

$$3895846 := 6 + 4 \times (8^5 + 98^3)$$

$$3895847 := 7 + 4 \times (8^5 + 98^3)$$

$$3895848 := 8 + 4 \times (8^5 + 98^3)$$

$$3895849 := 9 + 4 \times (8^5 + 98^3)$$

$$4117710 := 0 - (1 - 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117711 := 1 - (1 - 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117712 := 2 - (1 - 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117713 := 3 - (1 - 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117714 := 4 - (1 - 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117715 := 5 - (1 - 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117716 := 6 - (1 - 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117717 := 7 - (1 - 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117718 := 8 - (1 - 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117719 := 9 - (1 - 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117720 := 0 + (2 + 7^7 - 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117721 := 1 + (2 + 7^7 - 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117722 := 2 + (2 + 7^7 - 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117723 := 3 + (2 + 7^7 - 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117724 := 4 + (2 + 7^7 - 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117725 := 5 + (2 + 7^7 - 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117726 := 6 + (2 + 7^7 - 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117727 := 7 + (2 + 7^7 - 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117728 := 8 + (2 + 7^7 - 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117729 := 9 + (2 + 7^7 - 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117730 := 0 + (3 + 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117731 := 1 + (3 + 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117732 := 2 + (3 + 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117733 := 3 + (3 + 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117734 := 4 + (3 + 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117735 := 5 + (3 + 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117736 := 6 + (3 + 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117737 := 7 + (3 + 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117738 := 8 + (3 + 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117739 := 9 + (3 + 7^7) \times (1 \times 1 + 4)$$

$$4117740 := 0 + (4 + 7^7 + 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117741 := 1 + (4 + 7^7 + 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117742 := 2 + (4 + 7^7 + 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117743 := 3 + (4 + 7^7 + 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117744 := 4 + (4 + 7^7 + 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117745 := 5 + (4 + 7^7 + 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117746 := 6 + (4 + 7^7 + 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117747 := 7 + (4 + 7^7 + 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117748 := 8 + (4 + 7^7 + 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117749 := 9 + (4 + 7^7 + 1) \times (1 + 4)$$

$$4117750 := 0 + 5 \times (7^7 + 11 - 4)$$

$$4117751 := 1 + 5 \times (7^7 + 11 - 4)$$

$$4117752 := 2 + 5 \times (7^7 + 11 - 4)$$

$$4117753 := 3 + 5 \times (7^7 + 11 - 4)$$

$$4117754 := 4 + 5 \times (7^7 + 11 - 4)$$

$$4117755 := 5 + 5 \times (7^7 + 11 - 4)$$

$$4117756 := 6 + 5 \times (7^7 + 11 - 4)$$

$$4117757 := 7 + 5 \times (7^7 + 11 - 4)$$

$$4117758 := 8 + 5 \times (7^7 + 11 - 4)$$

$$4117759 := 9 + 5 \times (7^7 + 11 - 4)$$

$$4173290 := 0 + 9 + (23 \times 7)^{-1+4}$$

$$4173291 := 1 + 9 + (23 \times 7)^{-1+4}$$

$$4173292 := 2 + 9 + (23 \times 7)^{-1+4}$$

$$4173293 := 3 + 9 + (23 \times 7)^{-1+4}$$

$$4173294 := 4 + 9 + (23 \times 7)^{-1+4}$$

$$4173295 := 5 + 9 + (23 \times 7)^{-1+4}$$

$$4173296 := 6 + 9 + (23 \times 7)^{-1+4}$$

$$4173297 := 7 + 9 + (23 \times 7)^{-1+4}$$

$$4173298 := 8 + 9 + (23 \times 7)^{-1+4}$$

$$4173299 := 9 + 9 + (23 \times 7)^{-1+4}$$

$$4194140 := 0 - (41 - 4^{9+1}) \times 4$$

$$4194141 := 1 - (41 - 4^{9+1}) \times 4$$

$$4194142 := 2 - (41 - 4^{9+1}) \times 4$$

$$4194143 := 3 - (41 - 4^{9+1}) \times 4$$

$$4194144 := 4 - (41 - 4^{9+1}) \times 4$$

$$4194145 := 5 - (41 - 4^{9+1}) \times 4$$

$$4194146 := 6 - (41 - 4^{9+1}) \times 4$$

$$\begin{aligned}4194147 &:= 7 - (41 - 4^{9+1}) \times 4 \\4194148 &:= 8 - (41 - 4^{9+1}) \times 4 \\4194149 &:= 9 - (41 - 4^{9+1}) \times 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4194240 &:= 0 + 4^2 \times (4^9 \times 1 - 4) \\4194241 &:= 1 + 4^2 \times (4^9 \times 1 - 4) \\4194242 &:= 2 + 4^2 \times (4^9 \times 1 - 4) \\4194243 &:= 3 + 4^2 \times (4^9 \times 1 - 4) \\4194244 &:= 4 + 4^2 \times (4^9 \times 1 - 4) \\4194245 &:= 5 + 4^2 \times (4^9 \times 1 - 4) \\4194246 &:= 6 + 4^2 \times (4^9 \times 1 - 4) \\4194247 &:= 7 + 4^2 \times (4^9 \times 1 - 4) \\4194248 &:= 8 + 4^2 \times (4^9 \times 1 - 4) \\4194249 &:= 9 + 4^2 \times (4^9 \times 1 - 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4194280 &:= 0 + 8 \times (2 \times 4^9 + 1 - 4) \\4194281 &:= 1 + 8 \times (2 \times 4^9 + 1 - 4) \\4194282 &:= 2 + 8 \times (2 \times 4^9 + 1 - 4) \\4194283 &:= 3 + 8 \times (2 \times 4^9 + 1 - 4) \\4194284 &:= 4 + 8 \times (2 \times 4^9 + 1 - 4) \\4194285 &:= 5 + 8 \times (2 \times 4^9 + 1 - 4) \\4194286 &:= 6 + 8 \times (2 \times 4^9 + 1 - 4) \\4194287 &:= 7 + 8 \times (2 \times 4^9 + 1 - 4) \\4194288 &:= 8 + 8 \times (2 \times 4^9 + 1 - 4) \\4194289 &:= 9 + 8 \times (2 \times 4^9 + 1 - 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4199040 &:= 0 + 40 \times ((9 + 9) \times 1)^4 \\4199041 &:= 1 + 40 \times ((9 + 9) \times 1)^4 \\4199042 &:= 2 + 40 \times ((9 + 9) \times 1)^4 \\4199043 &:= 3 + 40 \times ((9 + 9) \times 1)^4 \\4199044 &:= 4 + 40 \times ((9 + 9) \times 1)^4 \\4199045 &:= 5 + 40 \times ((9 + 9) \times 1)^4 \\4199046 &:= 6 + 40 \times ((9 + 9) \times 1)^4 \\4199047 &:= 7 + 40 \times ((9 + 9) \times 1)^4 \\4199048 &:= 8 + 40 \times ((9 + 9) \times 1)^4 \\4199049 &:= 9 + 40 \times ((9 + 9) \times 1)^4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4218750 &:= 0 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1) \times (2 + 4) \\4218751 &:= 1 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1) \times (2 + 4) \\4218752 &:= 2 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1) \times (2 + 4) \\4218753 &:= 3 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1) \times (2 + 4) \\4218754 &:= 4 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1) \times (2 + 4) \\4218755 &:= 5 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1) \times (2 + 4) \\4218756 &:= 6 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1) \times (2 + 4) \\4218757 &:= 7 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1) \times (2 + 4) \\4218758 &:= 8 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1) \times (2 + 4) \\4218759 &:= 9 + 5^7 \times (8 + 1) \times (2 + 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4259840 &:= 0 + 4^8 \times (9 + 52 + 4) \\4259841 &:= 1 + 4^8 \times (9 + 52 + 4) \\4259842 &:= 2 + 4^8 \times (9 + 52 + 4) \\4259843 &:= 3 + 4^8 \times (9 + 52 + 4) \\4259844 &:= 4 + 4^8 \times (9 + 52 + 4) \\4259845 &:= 5 + 4^8 \times (9 + 52 + 4) \\4259846 &:= 6 + 4^8 \times (9 + 52 + 4) \\4259847 &:= 7 + 4^8 \times (9 + 52 + 4) \\4259848 &:= 8 + 4^8 \times (9 + 52 + 4) \\4259849 &:= 9 + 4^8 \times (9 + 52 + 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4477460 &:= 0 + (6 + 47 - 7)^4 + 4 \\4477461 &:= 1 + (6 + 47 - 7)^4 + 4 \\4477462 &:= 2 + (6 + 47 - 7)^4 + 4 \\4477463 &:= 3 + (6 + 47 - 7)^4 + 4 \\4477464 &:= 4 + (6 + 47 - 7)^4 + 4 \\4477465 &:= 5 + (6 + 47 - 7)^4 + 4 \\4477466 &:= 6 + (6 + 47 - 7)^4 + 4 \\4477467 &:= 7 + (6 + 47 - 7)^4 + 4 \\4477468 &:= 8 + (6 + 47 - 7)^4 + 4 \\4477469 &:= 9 + (6 + 47 - 7)^4 + 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4879690 &:= 0 + 9 + (6 \times 9 - 7)^{8-4} \\4879691 &:= 1 + 9 + (6 \times 9 - 7)^{8-4} \\4879692 &:= 2 + 9 + (6 \times 9 - 7)^{8-4} \\4879693 &:= 3 + 9 + (6 \times 9 - 7)^{8-4} \\4879694 &:= 4 + 9 + (6 \times 9 - 7)^{8-4} \\4879695 &:= 5 + 9 + (6 \times 9 - 7)^{8-4}\end{aligned}$$

$$4879696 := 6 + 9 + (6 \times 9 - 7)^{8-4}$$

$$4879697 := 7 + 9 + (6 \times 9 - 7)^{8-4}$$

$$4879698 := 8 + 9 + (6 \times 9 - 7)^{8-4}$$

$$4879699 := 9 + 9 + (6 \times 9 - 7)^{8-4}$$

$$5242840 := 0 + (4^{8+2} - 4 \times 2) \times 5$$

$$5242841 := 1 + (4^{8+2} - 4 \times 2) \times 5$$

$$5242842 := 2 + (4^{8+2} - 4 \times 2) \times 5$$

$$5242843 := 3 + (4^{8+2} - 4 \times 2) \times 5$$

$$5242844 := 4 + (4^{8+2} - 4 \times 2) \times 5$$

$$5242845 := 5 + (4^{8+2} - 4 \times 2) \times 5$$

$$5242846 := 6 + (4^{8+2} - 4 \times 2) \times 5$$

$$5242847 := 7 + (4^{8+2} - 4 \times 2) \times 5$$

$$5242848 := 8 + (4^{8+2} - 4 \times 2) \times 5$$

$$5242849 := 9 + (4^{8+2} - 4 \times 2) \times 5$$

$$5242850 := 0 - 5 \times (8 - 2 - 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242851 := 1 - 5 \times (8 - 2 - 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242852 := 2 - 5 \times (8 - 2 - 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242853 := 3 - 5 \times (8 - 2 - 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242854 := 4 - 5 \times (8 - 2 - 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242855 := 5 - 5 \times (8 - 2 - 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242856 := 6 - 5 \times (8 - 2 - 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242857 := 7 - 5 \times (8 - 2 - 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242858 := 8 - 5 \times (8 - 2 - 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242859 := 9 - 5 \times (8 - 2 - 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242880 := 0 + ((8 \times 8)^2 / 4)^2 \times 5$$

$$5242881 := 1 + ((8 \times 8)^2 / 4)^2 \times 5$$

$$5242882 := 2 + ((8 \times 8)^2 / 4)^2 \times 5$$

$$5242883 := 3 + ((8 \times 8)^2 / 4)^2 \times 5$$

$$5242884 := 4 + ((8 \times 8)^2 / 4)^2 \times 5$$

$$5242885 := 5 + ((8 \times 8)^2 / 4)^2 \times 5$$

$$5242886 := 6 + ((8 \times 8)^2 / 4)^2 \times 5$$

$$5242887 := 7 + ((8 \times 8)^2 / 4)^2 \times 5$$

$$5242888 := 8 + ((8 \times 8)^2 / 4)^2 \times 5$$

$$5242889 := 9 + ((8 \times 8)^2 / 4)^2 \times 5$$

$$5359380 := 0 + ((8 + 3 \times 9) \times 5)^3 + 5$$

$$5359381 := 1 + ((8 + 3 \times 9) \times 5)^3 + 5$$

$$5359382 := 2 + ((8 + 3 \times 9) \times 5)^3 + 5$$

$$5359383 := 3 + ((8 + 3 \times 9) \times 5)^3 + 5$$

$$5359384 := 4 + ((8 + 3 \times 9) \times 5)^3 + 5$$

$$5359385 := 5 + ((8 + 3 \times 9) \times 5)^3 + 5$$

$$5359386 := 6 + ((8 + 3 \times 9) \times 5)^3 + 5$$

$$5359387 := 7 + ((8 + 3 \times 9) \times 5)^3 + 5$$

$$5359388 := 8 + ((8 + 3 \times 9) \times 5)^3 + 5$$

$$5359389 := 9 + ((8 + 3 \times 9) \times 5)^3 + 5$$

$$5764870 := 0 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$5764871 := 1 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$5764872 := 2 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$5764873 := 3 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$5764874 := 4 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$5764875 := 5 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$5764876 := 6 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$5764877 := 7 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$5764878 := 8 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$5764879 := 9 + 7^8 + 4 + (6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$5859380 := 0 - (8 - 3)^9 \times (5 - 8) - 5$$

$$5859381 := 1 - (8 - 3)^9 \times (5 - 8) - 5$$

$$5859382 := 2 - (8 - 3)^9 \times (5 - 8) - 5$$

$$5859383 := 3 - (8 - 3)^9 \times (5 - 8) - 5$$

$$5859384 := 4 - (8 - 3)^9 \times (5 - 8) - 5$$

$$5859385 := 5 - (8 - 3)^9 \times (5 - 8) - 5$$

$$5859386 := 6 - (8 - 3)^9 \times (5 - 8) - 5$$

$$5859387 := 7 - (8 - 3)^9 \times (5 - 8) - 5$$

$$5859388 := 8 - (8 - 3)^9 \times (5 - 8) - 5$$

$$5859389 := 9 - (8 - 3)^9 \times (5 - 8) - 5$$

$$5898240 := 0 + (4 + 2 \times 8) \times 9 \times 8^5$$

$$5898241 := 1 + (4 + 2 \times 8) \times 9 \times 8^5$$

$$5898242 := 2 + (4 + 2 \times 8) \times 9 \times 8^5$$

$$5898243 := 3 + (4 + 2 \times 8) \times 9 \times 8^5$$

$$5898244 := 4 + (4 + 2 \times 8) \times 9 \times 8^5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5898245 &:= 5 + (4 + 2 \times 8) \times 9 \times 8^5 \\ 5898246 &:= 6 + (4 + 2 \times 8) \times 9 \times 8^5 \\ 5898247 &:= 7 + (4 + 2 \times 8) \times 9 \times 8^5 \\ 5898248 &:= 8 + (4 + 2 \times 8) \times 9 \times 8^5 \\ 5898249 &:= 9 + (4 + 2 \times 8) \times 9 \times 8^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6249850 &:= 0 + (5^8 - 9) \times 4^2 - 6 \\ 6249851 &:= 1 + (5^8 - 9) \times 4^2 - 6 \\ 6249852 &:= 2 + (5^8 - 9) \times 4^2 - 6 \\ 6249853 &:= 3 + (5^8 - 9) \times 4^2 - 6 \\ 6249854 &:= 4 + (5^8 - 9) \times 4^2 - 6 \\ 6249855 &:= 5 + (5^8 - 9) \times 4^2 - 6 \\ 6249856 &:= 6 + (5^8 - 9) \times 4^2 - 6 \\ 6249857 &:= 7 + (5^8 - 9) \times 4^2 - 6 \\ 6249858 &:= 8 + (5^8 - 9) \times 4^2 - 6 \\ 6249859 &:= 9 + (5^8 - 9) \times 4^2 - 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6291440 &:= 0 - 4 + (4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 6291441 &:= 1 - 4 + (4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 6291442 &:= 2 - 4 + (4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 6291443 &:= 3 - 4 + (4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 6291444 &:= 4 - 4 + (4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 6291445 &:= 5 - 4 + (4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 6291446 &:= 6 - 4 + (4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 6291447 &:= 7 - 4 + (4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 6291448 &:= 8 - 4 + (4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \\ 6291449 &:= 9 - 4 + (4^{1+9} - 2) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6291460 &:= 0 + 6 \times 4^{1+9} - 2 + 6 \\ 6291461 &:= 1 + 6 \times 4^{1+9} - 2 + 6 \\ 6291462 &:= 2 + 6 \times 4^{1+9} - 2 + 6 \\ 6291463 &:= 3 + 6 \times 4^{1+9} - 2 + 6 \\ 6291464 &:= 4 + 6 \times 4^{1+9} - 2 + 6 \\ 6291465 &:= 5 + 6 \times 4^{1+9} - 2 + 6 \\ 6291466 &:= 6 + 6 \times 4^{1+9} - 2 + 6 \\ 6291467 &:= 7 + 6 \times 4^{1+9} - 2 + 6 \\ 6291468 &:= 8 + 6 \times 4^{1+9} - 2 + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$6291469 := 9 + 6 \times 4^{1+9} - 2 + 6$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6718640 &:= 0 + 4 \times 6^8 + 176 \\ 6718641 &:= 1 + 4 \times 6^8 + 176 \\ 6718642 &:= 2 + 4 \times 6^8 + 176 \\ 6718643 &:= 3 + 4 \times 6^8 + 176 \\ 6718644 &:= 4 + 4 \times 6^8 + 176 \\ 6718645 &:= 5 + 4 \times 6^8 + 176 \\ 6718646 &:= 6 + 4 \times 6^8 + 176 \\ 6718647 &:= 7 + 4 \times 6^8 + 176 \\ 6718648 &:= 8 + 4 \times 6^8 + 176 \\ 6718649 &:= 9 + 4 \times 6^8 + 176 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7968750 &:= 0 + 5^7 \times (86 + 9 + 7) \\ 7968751 &:= 1 + 5^7 \times (86 + 9 + 7) \\ 7968752 &:= 2 + 5^7 \times (86 + 9 + 7) \\ 7968753 &:= 3 + 5^7 \times (86 + 9 + 7) \\ 7968754 &:= 4 + 5^7 \times (86 + 9 + 7) \\ 7968755 &:= 5 + 5^7 \times (86 + 9 + 7) \\ 7968756 &:= 6 + 5^7 \times (86 + 9 + 7) \\ 7968757 &:= 7 + 5^7 \times (86 + 9 + 7) \\ 7968758 &:= 8 + 5^7 \times (86 + 9 + 7) \\ 7968759 &:= 9 + 5^7 \times (86 + 9 + 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8387840 &:= 0 + 4 \times (8^7 - 8 \times 3 \times 8) \\ 8387841 &:= 1 + 4 \times (8^7 - 8 \times 3 \times 8) \\ 8387842 &:= 2 + 4 \times (8^7 - 8 \times 3 \times 8) \\ 8387843 &:= 3 + 4 \times (8^7 - 8 \times 3 \times 8) \\ 8387844 &:= 4 + 4 \times (8^7 - 8 \times 3 \times 8) \\ 8387845 &:= 5 + 4 \times (8^7 - 8 \times 3 \times 8) \\ 8387846 &:= 6 + 4 \times (8^7 - 8 \times 3 \times 8) \\ 8387847 &:= 7 + 4 \times (8^7 - 8 \times 3 \times 8) \\ 8387848 &:= 8 + 4 \times (8^7 - 8 \times 3 \times 8) \\ 8387849 &:= 9 + 4 \times (8^7 - 8 \times 3 \times 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9436860 &:= 0 - (6 - 8^6 + 3) \times 4 \times 9 \\ 9436861 &:= 1 - (6 - 8^6 + 3) \times 4 \times 9 \\ 9436862 &:= 2 - (6 - 8^6 + 3) \times 4 \times 9 \\ 9436863 &:= 3 - (6 - 8^6 + 3) \times 4 \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$9436864 := 4 - (6 - 8^6 + 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9436865 := 5 - (6 - 8^6 + 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9436866 := 6 - (6 - 8^6 + 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9436867 := 7 - (6 - 8^6 + 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9436868 := 8 - (6 - 8^6 + 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9436869 := 9 - (6 - 8^6 + 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9437220 := 0 + ((2 + 2)^{7+3} + 4) \times 9$$

$$9437221 := 1 + ((2 + 2)^{7+3} + 4) \times 9$$

$$9437222 := 2 + ((2 + 2)^{7+3} + 4) \times 9$$

$$9437223 := 3 + ((2 + 2)^{7+3} + 4) \times 9$$

$$9437224 := 4 + ((2 + 2)^{7+3} + 4) \times 9$$

$$9437225 := 5 + ((2 + 2)^{7+3} + 4) \times 9$$

$$9437226 := 6 + ((2 + 2)^{7+3} + 4) \times 9$$

$$9437227 := 7 + ((2 + 2)^{7+3} + 4) \times 9$$

$$9437228 := 8 + ((2 + 2)^{7+3} + 4) \times 9$$

$$9437229 := 9 + ((2 + 2)^{7+3} + 4) \times 9$$

$$9437940 := 0 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9437941 := 1 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9437942 := 2 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9437943 := 3 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9437944 := 4 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9437945 := 5 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9437946 := 6 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9437947 := 7 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9437948 := 8 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9437949 := 9 + (4^9 + 7 \times 3) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$9638720 := 0 - (-2 + 78)^3 + 6^9$$

$$9638721 := 1 - (-2 + 78)^3 + 6^9$$

$$9638722 := 2 - (-2 + 78)^3 + 6^9$$

$$9638723 := 3 - (-2 + 78)^3 + 6^9$$

$$9638724 := 4 - (-2 + 78)^3 + 6^9$$

$$9638725 := 5 - (-2 + 78)^3 + 6^9$$

$$9638726 := 6 - (-2 + 78)^3 + 6^9$$

$$9638727 := 7 - (-2 + 78)^3 + 6^9$$

$$9638728 := 8 - (-2 + 78)^3 + 6^9$$

$$9638729 := 9 - (-2 + 78)^3 + 6^9$$

$$9765560 := 0 - 65 + 5^{-6+7+9}$$

$$9765561 := 1 - 65 + 5^{-6+7+9}$$

$$9765562 := 2 - 65 + 5^{-6+7+9}$$

$$9765563 := 3 - 65 + 5^{-6+7+9}$$

$$9765564 := 4 - 65 + 5^{-6+7+9}$$

$$9765565 := 5 - 65 + 5^{-6+7+9}$$

$$9765566 := 6 - 65 + 5^{-6+7+9}$$

$$9765567 := 7 - 65 + 5^{-6+7+9}$$

$$9765568 := 8 - 65 + 5^{-6+7+9}$$

$$9765569 := 9 - 65 + 5^{-6+7+9}$$

3.3 Symmetric and Nonsecutive

$$00025 := 5^2 + 000$$

$$00125 := 5^2 + 100$$

$$00225 := 5^2 + 200$$

$$00325 := 5^2 + 300$$

$$00425 := 5^2 + 400$$

$$00525 := 5^2 + 500$$

$$00625 := 5^2 + 600$$

$$00725 := 5^2 + 700$$

$$00825 := 5^2 + 800$$

$$00925 := 5^2 + 900$$

$$000025 := 5^2 + 0000$$

$$001125 := 5^2 + 1100$$

$$002225 := 5^2 + 2200$$

$$003325 := 5^2 + 3300$$

$$004425 := 5^2 + 4400$$

$$005525 := 5^2 + 5500$$

$$006625 := 5^2 + 6600$$

$$007725 := 5^2 + 7700$$

$$008825 := 5^2 + 8800$$

$$009925 := 5^2 + 9900$$

$$328510 := 01 + (5 + 8^2)^3$$

$$328521 := 12 + (5 + 8^2)^3$$

$$328532 := 23 + (5 + 8^2)^3$$

$$328543 := 34 + (5 + 8^2)^3$$

$$328554 := 45 + (5 + 8^2)^3$$

$$328565 := 56 + (5 + 8^2)^3$$

$$328576 := 67 + (5 + 8^2)^3$$

$$328587 := 78 + (5 + 8^2)^3$$

$$328598 := 89 + (5 + 8^2)^3$$

$$937500 := 00 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937511 := 11 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937522 := 22 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937533 := 33 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937544 := 44 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937555 := 55 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937566 := 66 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937577 := 77 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937588 := 88 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937599 := 88 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$0000126 := 6 \times 21 + 0000$$

$$0001126 := 6 \times 21 + 1000$$

$$0002126 := 6 \times 21 + 2000$$

$$0003126 := 6 \times 21 + 3000$$

$$0004126 := 6 \times 21 + 4000$$

$$0005126 := 6 \times 21 + 5000$$

$$0006126 := 6 \times 21 + 6000$$

$$0007126 := 6 \times 21 + 7000$$

$$0008126 := 6 \times 21 + 8000$$

$$0009126 := 6 \times 21 + 9000$$

$$0000153 := 3 \times 51 + 0000$$

$$0001153 := 3 \times 51 + 1000$$

$$0002153 := 3 \times 51 + 2000$$

$$0003153 := 3 \times 51 + 3000$$

$$0004153 := 3 \times 51 + 4000$$

$$0005153 := 3 \times 51 + 5000$$

$$0006153 := 3 \times 51 + 6000$$

$$0007153 := 3 \times 51 + 7000$$

$$0008153 := 3 \times 51 + 8000$$

$$0009153 := 3 \times 51 + 9000$$

$$0000688 := 8 \times 86 + 0000$$

$$0001688 := 8 \times 86 + 1000$$

$$0002688 := 8 \times 86 + 2000$$

$$0003688 := 8 \times 86 + 3000$$

$$0004688 := 8 \times 86 + 4000$$

$$0005688 := 8 \times 86 + 5000$$

$$0006688 := 8 \times 86 + 6000$$

$$0007688 := 8 \times 86 + 7000$$

$$0008688 := 8 \times 86 + 8000$$

$$0009688 := 8 \times 86 + 9000$$

$$0000289 := (9 + 8)^2 + 0000$$

$$0001289 := (9 + 8)^2 + 1000$$

$$0002289 := (9 + 8)^2 + 2000$$

$$0003289 := (9 + 8)^2 + 3000$$

$$0004289 := (9 + 8)^2 + 4000$$

$$0005289 := (9 + 8)^2 + 5000$$

$$0006289 := (9 + 8)^2 + 6000$$

$$0007289 := (9 + 8)^2 + 7000$$

$$0008289 := (9 + 8)^2 + 8000$$

$$0009289 := (9 + 8)^2 + 9000$$

$$0000216 := 6^{1+2} + 0000$$

$$0001216 := 6^{1+2} + 1000$$

$$0002216 := 6^{1+2} + 2000$$

$$0003216 := 6^{1+2} + 3000$$

$$0004216 := 6^{1+2} + 4000$$

$$0005216 := 6^{1+2} + 5000$$

$$0006216 := 6^{1+2} + 6000$$

$$0007216 := 6^{1+2} + 7000$$

$$0008216 := 6^{1+2} + 8000$$

$$0009216 := 6^{1+2} + 9000$$

$$0000125 := 5^{2+1} + 0000$$

$$0001125 := 5^{2+1} + 1000$$

$$0002125 := 5^{2+1} + 2000$$

$$0003125 := 5^{2+1} + 3000$$

$$0004125 := 5^{2+1} + 4000$$

$$0005125 := 5^{2+1} + 5000$$

$$0006125 := 5^{2+1} + 6000$$

$$0007125 := 5^{2+1} + 7000$$

$$0008125 := 5^{2+1} + 8000$$

$$0009125 := 5^{2+1} + 9000$$

$$0010468 := 8 \times (6^4) + 0100$$

$$0011468 := 8 \times (6^4) + 1100$$

$$0012468 := 8 \times (6^4) + 2100$$

$$0013468 := 8 \times (6^4) + 3100$$

$$0014468 := 8 \times (6^4) + 4100$$

$$0015468 := 8 \times (6^4) + 5100$$

$$0016468 := 8 \times (6^4) + 6100$$

$$0017468 := 8 \times (6^4) + 7100$$

$$0018468 := 8 \times (6^4) + 8100$$

$$0019468 := 8 \times (6^4) + 9100$$

$$0015300 := 00 + 3 \times 5100$$

$$0015311 := 11 + 3 \times 5100$$

$$0015322 := 22 + 3 \times 5100$$

$$0015333 := 33 + 3 \times 5100$$

$$0015344 := 44 + 3 \times 5100$$

$$0015355 := 55 + 3 \times 5100$$

$$0015366 := 66 + 3 \times 5100$$

$$0015377 := 77 + 3 \times 5100$$

$$0015388 := 88 + 3 \times 5100$$

$$0015399 := 99 + 3 \times 5100$$

$$0012600 := 00 + 6 \times 2100$$

$$0012611 := 11 + 6 \times 2100$$

$$0012622 := 22 + 6 \times 2100$$

$$0012633 := 33 + 6 \times 2100$$

$$0012644 := 44 + 6 \times 2100$$

$$0012655 := 55 + 6 \times 2100$$

$$0012666 := 66 + 6 \times 2100$$

$$0012677 := 77 + 6 \times 2100$$

$$0012688 := 88 + 6 \times 2100$$

$$0012699 := 99 + 6 \times 2100$$

$$0000025 := 5^2 + 00000$$

$$0001025 := 5^2 + 01000$$

$$0002025 := 5^2 + 02000$$

$$0003025 := 5^2 + 03000$$

$$0004025 := 5^2 + 04000$$

$$0005025 := 5^2 + 05000$$

$$0006025 := 5^2 + 06000$$

$$0007025 := 5^2 + 07000$$

$$0008025 := 5^2 + 08000$$

$$0009025 := 5^2 + 09000$$

$$0010125 := 5^2 + 10100$$

$$0011125 := 5^2 + 11100$$

$$0012125 := 5^2 + 12100$$

$$0013125 := 5^2 + 13100$$

$$0014125 := 5^2 + 14100$$

$$0015125 := 5^2 + 15100$$

$$0016125 := 5^2 + 16100$$

$$0017125 := 5^2 + 17100$$

$$0018125 := 5^2 + 18100$$

$$0019125 := 5^2 + 19100$$

$$0020225 := 5^2 + 20200$$

$$0021225 := 5^2 + 21200$$

$$0022225 := 5^2 + 22200$$

$$0023225 := 5^2 + 23200$$

$$0024225 := 5^2 + 24200$$

$$0025225 := 5^2 + 25200$$

$$0026225 := 5^2 + 26200$$

$$0027225 := 5^2 + 27200$$

$$0028225 := 5^2 + 28200$$

$$0029225 := 5^2 + 29200$$

$$0030325 := 5^2 + 30300$$

$$0031325 := 5^2 + 31300$$

$$0032325 := 5^2 + 32300$$

$$0033325 := 5^2 + 33300$$

$$0034325 := 5^2 + 34300$$

$$0035325 := 5^2 + 35300$$

$$0036325 := 5^2 + 36300$$

$$0037325 := 5^2 + 37300$$

$$0038325 := 5^2 + 38300$$

$$0039325 := 5^2 + 39300$$

$$0040425 := 5^2 + 40400$$

$$0041425 := 5^2 + 41400$$

$$0042425 := 5^2 + 42400$$

$$0043425 := 5^2 + 43400$$

$$0044425 := 5^2 + 44400$$

$$0045425 := 5^2 + 45400$$

$$0046425 := 5^2 + 46400$$

$$0047425 := 5^2 + 47400$$

$$0048425 := 5^2 + 48400$$

$$0049425 := 5^2 + 49400$$

$$0050525 := 5^2 + 50500$$

$$0051525 := 5^2 + 51500$$

$$0052525 := 5^2 + 52500$$

$$0053525 := 5^2 + 53500$$

$$0054525 := 5^2 + 54500$$

$$0055525 := 5^2 + 55500$$

$$0056525 := 5^2 + 56500$$

$$0057525 := 5^2 + 57500$$

$$0058525 := 5^2 + 58500$$

$$0059525 := 5^2 + 59500$$

$$0060625 := 5^2 + 60600$$

$$0061625 := 5^2 + 61600$$

$$0062625 := 5^2 + 62600$$

$$0063625 := 5^2 + 63600$$

$$0064625 := 5^2 + 64600$$

$$0065625 := 5^2 + 65600$$

$$0066625 := 5^2 + 66600$$

$$0067625 := 5^2 + 67600$$

$$0068625 := 5^2 + 68600$$

$$0069625 := 5^2 + 69600$$

$$0070725 := 5^2 + 70700$$

$$0071725 := 5^2 + 71700$$

$$0072725 := 5^2 + 72700$$

$$0073725 := 5^2 + 73700$$

$$0074725 := 5^2 + 74700$$

$$0075725 := 5^2 + 75700$$

$$0076725 := 5^2 + 76700$$

$$0077725 := 5^2 + 77700$$

$$0078725 := 5^2 + 78700$$

$$0079725 := 5^2 + 79700$$

$$0080825 := 5^2 + 80800$$

$$0081825 := 5^2 + 81800$$

$$0082825 := 5^2 + 82800$$

$$0083825 := 5^2 + 83800$$

$$0084825 := 5^2 + 84800$$

$$0085825 := 5^2 + 85800$$

$$0086825 := 5^2 + 86800$$

$$0087825 := 5^2 + 87800$$

$$0088825 := 5^2 + 88800$$

$$0089825 := 5^2 + 89800$$

$$0090925 := 5^2 + 90900$$

$$0091925 := 5^2 + 91900$$

$$0092925 := 5^2 + 92900$$

$$0093925 := 5^2 + 93900$$

$$0094925 := 5^2 + 94900$$

$$0095925 := 5^2 + 95900$$

$$0096925 := 5^2 + 96900$$

$$0097925 := 5^2 + 97900$$

$$0098925 := 5^2 + 98900$$

$$0099925 := 5^2 + 99900$$

$$0068800 := 00 + 8 \times 8600$$

$$0068811 := 11 + 8 \times 8600$$

$$\begin{aligned}0068822 &:= 22 + 8 \times 8600 \\0068833 &:= 33 + 8 \times 8600 \\0068844 &:= 44 + 8 \times 8600 \\0068855 &:= 55 + 8 \times 8600 \\0068866 &:= 66 + 8 \times 8600 \\0068877 &:= 77 + 8 \times 8600 \\0068888 &:= 88 + 8 \times 8600 \\0068899 &:= 99 + 8 \times 8600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1562500 &:= 00 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1) \\1562511 &:= 11 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1) \\1562522 &:= 22 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1) \\1562533 &:= 33 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1) \\1562544 &:= 44 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1) \\1562555 &:= 55 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1) \\1562566 &:= 66 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1) \\1562577 &:= 77 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1) \\1562588 &:= 88 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1) \\1562599 &:= 99 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1953905 &:= 50 + 9^3 + 5^9 + 1 \\1953916 &:= 61 + 9^3 + 5^9 + 1 \\1953927 &:= 72 + 9^3 + 5^9 + 1 \\1953938 &:= 83 + 9^3 + 5^9 + 1 \\1953949 &:= 94 + 9^3 + 5^9 + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2137404 &:= -40 + 4 \times 731^2 \\2137413 &:= -31 + 4 \times 731^2 \\2137422 &:= -22 + 4 \times 731^2 \\2137431 &:= -13 + 4 \times 731^2\end{aligned}$$

$$3255210 := 01 + (25^5 + 2)/3$$

$$\begin{aligned}3255221 &:= 12 + (25^5 + 2)/3 \\3255232 &:= 23 + (25^5 + 2)/3 \\3255243 &:= 34 + (25^5 + 2)/3 \\3255254 &:= 45 + (25^5 + 2)/3 \\3255265 &:= 56 + (25^5 + 2)/3 \\3255276 &:= 67 + (25^5 + 2)/3 \\3255287 &:= 78 + (25^5 + 2)/3 \\3255298 &:= 89 + (25^5 + 2)/3\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3581507 &:= -70 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3 \\3581516 &:= -61 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3 \\3581525 &:= -52 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3 \\3581534 &:= -43 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3 \\3581543 &:= -34 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3 \\3581552 &:= -25 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3 \\3581561 &:= -16 + (51 \times (8 - 5))^3\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3652304 &:= 40 + (32 \times 5 - 6)^3 \\3652315 &:= 51 + (32 \times 5 - 6)^3 \\3652326 &:= 62 + (32 \times 5 - 6)^3 \\3652337 &:= 73 + (32 \times 5 - 6)^3 \\3652348 &:= 84 + (32 \times 5 - 6)^3 \\3652359 &:= 95 + (32 \times 5 - 6)^3\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}9765065 &:= -560 + 5^{-6+7+9} \\9765164 &:= -461 + 5^{-6+7+9} \\9765263 &:= -362 + 5^{-6+7+9} \\9765362 &:= -263 + 5^{-6+7+9} \\9765461 &:= -164 + 5^{-6+7+9}\end{aligned}$$

3.4 General Representations

$$\begin{aligned}125 &:= 5^{2+1} \\216 &:= 6^{1+2} \\289 &:= (9 + 8)^2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}343 &:= (3 + 4)^3 \\625 &:= 5^{-2+6} \\0135 &:= 5^3 + 10\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0236 &:= 6^3 + 20 & 21844 &:= (-4 + 4^8)/(1 + 2) \\ 3125 &:= 5^{2 \times 1 + 3} & 21848 &:= (8 + 4^8)/(1 + 2) \\ 3375 &:= (5 + 7 + 3)^3 & 21952 &:= (2 \times (5 + 9))^{1+2} \\ 3378 &:= (8 + 7)^3 + 3 & 22757 &:= 7 \times (57^2 + 2) \\ 4088 &:= -8 + 8^{04} & 23326 &:= 6^{2+3} \times 3 - 2 \\ 6144 &:= 4^{4+1} \times 6 & 23328 &:= (8 - 2)^{3+3}/2 \\ 8192 &:= 2^{9+1} \times 8 & 23392 &:= (2 + 9^3) \times 32 \\ & & 24336 &:= ((6 + 33) \times 4)^2 \\ 01022 &:= -2 + 2^{010} & 24367 &:= 7 \times (63 - 4)^2 \\ 01024 &:= (4 - 2)^{010} & 26244 &:= (4 \times 42 - 6)^2 \\ 01286 &:= 6^{8/2} - 10 & 28224 &:= ((4 + 2) \times 28)^2 \\ 01782 &:= 2^8 \times 7 - 10 & 29929 &:= (92 + 9 \times 9)^2 \\ 02284 &:= 48^2 - 20 & 32768 &:= 8^{(6+7+2)/3} \\ 03155 &:= 5^5 \times 1 + 30 & 32771 &:= (1 + 7)^{7-2} + 3 \\ 06848 &:= 8 \times (-4 + 860) & 32835 &:= 5 \times (3^8 + 2 \times 3) \\ 10368 &:= 8 \times 6^{3+01} & 34991 &:= -1 + (9 + 9)^4/3 \\ 11163 &:= 3 \times 61^{1+1} & 34993 &:= (3 + (9 + 9)^4)/3 \\ 12288 &:= (8 \times 8)^2 \times (2 + 1) & 38427 &:= (7 \times 2)^4 + 8 + 3 \\ 13725 &:= 5 \times ((2 \times 7)^3 + 1) & 39304 &:= (40 + 3 - 9)^3 \\ 13823 &:= (32 - 8)^3 - 1 & 39356 &:= 6 \times (-5 + 3^9)/3 \\ 13824 &:= (4^2 + 8)^3 \times 1 & 39363 &:= -3 + 6 \times 3^9/3 \\ 13825 &:= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1 & 39366 &:= 6 \times (6 - 3)^9/3 \\ 14641 &:= ((1 + 4) + 6)^4 \times 1 & 39369 &:= (9 + 6 \times 3^9)/3 \\ 15562 &:= 2 \times (6^5 + 5 \times 1) & 39382 &:= 2 \times (8 + (3 \times 9)^3) \\ 15585 &:= 5 \times (-8 + 5^5 \times 1) & 41468 &:= (8 \times 6^4 - 1) \times 4 \\ 15625 &:= 5^{2 \times 6 - 5 - 1} & 41472 &:= 2 \times (7 + 4 + 1)^4 \\ 15655 &:= (5^5 + 6) \times 5 \times 1 & 46632 &:= (2 \times 3)^6 - 6 \times 4 \\ 16225 &:= 52^2 \times 6 + 1 & 46633 &:= -3^3 + 6^6 + 4 \\ 16374 &:= 4^7 - 3 - 6 - 1 & 46644 &:= -4 - 4 + 6^6 - 4 \\ 16377 &:= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} & 46648 &:= -8 + 4 + 6^6 - 4 \\ 16384 &:= ((4 + 8)/3)^{6+1} & 46651 &:= -1^5 + 6^6 - 4 \\ 16783 &:= -3 \times 8 + 7^{6-1} & 46656 &:= 6^{(5 \times 6 - 6)/4} \\ 16794 &:= -4 - 9 + 7^{6-1} & 46661 &:= 1^6 + 6^6 + 4 \\ 16807 &:= 7^{0 \times 8 + 6 - 1} & 46663 &:= -3 + 6^6 + 6 + 4 \\ 17925 &:= 5 \times (2^9 \times 7 + 1) & 46673 &:= 3 \times 7 + 6^6 - 4 \\ 19683 &:= 3^8 \times (-6 + 9 \times 1) & 46684 &:= 4 \times 8 + 6^6 - 4 \\ 19736 &:= (6 + 3^7) \times 9 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52483 &:= 3^8 \times 4 \times 2 - 5 & 014346 &:= 6 \times ((4 + 3)^4 - 10) \\ 52498 &:= 8 \times 9^4 + 2 \times 5 & 014651 &:= (1 \times 5 + 6)^4 + 10 \\ 53248 &:= 8^4 \times (2^3 + 5) & 015562 &:= 2 \times (6^5 - 5 + 10) \\ 55296 &:= 6 \times 9 \times 2^{5+5} & 015575 &:= 5^7 / 5 - 5 \times 10 \\ 59038 &:= -8 - 3 + 09^5 & 015615 &:= 5^{16+5} - 10 \\ 59049 &:= 94 \times 0 + 9^5 & 015665 &:= 5^6 + 6 \times 5 + 10 \\ 59052 &:= -2 + 5 + 09^5 & 016235 &:= 5^{3 \times 2} + 610 \\ 59129 &:= 9^2 - 1 + 9^5 & 016265 &:= 5^6 + 2^6 \times 10 \\ 59375 &:= 5^{7-3} \times 95 & 016384 &:= 4^{8+3+6-10} \\ 59392 &:= (-2 + 9)^3 + 9^5 & 016747 &:= 7^4 \times 7 - 6 \times 10 \\ 59409 &:= 90 \times 4 + 9^5 & 016817 &:= 7^{-18+6} + 10 \\ 63994 &:= (49 - 9)^3 - 6 & 016957 &:= 7^5 + (9 + 6) \times 10 \\ 65484 &:= 4^8 + 4 - 56 & 017368 &:= 8 \times (-6 + 3^7 + 10) \\ 65488 &:= 8 \times (8 \times 4^5 - 6) & 017517 &:= (7 \times 1)^5 + 710 \\ 65528 &:= -8 + 2^{5+5+6} & 019673 &:= 3^{(7-6) \times 9} - 10 \\ 65536 &:= (6/3)^{5+5+6} & 019693 &:= (3 \times 9)^{-6+9} + 10 \\ 66339 &:= (9 \times 3)^3 + 6^6 & 021504 &:= 4^{05} \times (1 + 20) \\ 68644 &:= (4^4 + 6)^{8-6} & 021755 &:= 5^5 \times 7 - 120 \\ 78125 &:= 5^{(2-1)^8 \times 7} & 021855 &:= 5^5 \times (8 - 1) - 20 \\ 78132 &:= (2 + 3)^{-1+8} + 7 & 023273 &:= 37^2 \times (-3 + 20) \\ 82952 &:= (2^5 \times 9)^2 + 8 & 023546 &:= -6 + 4^5 \times (3 + 20) \\ 98415 &:= 5 \times (-1 - 4 + 8)^9 & 023552 &:= 2^{5+5} \times (3 + 20) \\ & & 026136 &:= 6^3 \times (1 + 6 \times 20) \\ 001692 &:= 2 \times 9 \times (-6 + 100) & 032558 &:= 8^5 - (5 + 2) \times 30 \\ 002248 &:= 8^4 / 2 + 200 & 032738 &:= 8^{(3+7)/2} - 30 \\ 002395 &:= -5 + (9 + 3) \times 200 & 032742 &:= 2 \times (4^7 + 2) - 30 \\ 002448 &:= (8 + 4) \times (4 + 200) & 032789 &:= -9 + 8^{7-2} + 30 \\ 003159 &:= 9 \times (51 + 300) & 032798 &:= 8^{-9+7 \times 2} + 30 \\ 003295 &:= -5 + (9 + 2) \times 300 & 033158 &:= 8^5 + 13 \times 30 \\ 007492 &:= 2^{9+4} - 700 & 033488 &:= 8 \times (8^4 + 3 \times 30) \\ 008568 &:= -8 + 6^5 + 800 & 036936 &:= 6^3 \times (-9 + 6 \times 30) \\ 009468 &:= 8 \times 6^4 - 900 & 038912 &:= 2^{1+9} \times (8 + 30) \\ 012288 &:= (8 + 8/2) \times 2^{10} & 039328 &:= -8 + 2 \times 3^9 - 30 \\ 013814 &:= ((4 - 1) \times 8)^3 - 10 & 039336 &:= 6/3 \times 3^9 - 30 \\ 013832 &:= -2 + (3 \times 8)^3 + 10 & 039343 &:= 34^3 + 9 + 30 \\ 013935 &:= 5 \times (-3 + 9 \times 310) & 039396 &:= 6 \times 9^3 \times 9 + 30 \\ 013995 &:= 5 \times (9 + 9 \times 310) & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}046568 &:= (-8 + 6^5) \times 6 - 40 \\046608 &:= -8 + 06^6 - 40 \\046613 &:= -3 + 1 \times 6^6 - 40 \\046616 &:= 6^{1^6 \times 6} - 40 \\046624 &:= 4 \times 2 + 6^6 - 40 \\046637 &:= 7 \times 3 + 6^6 - 40 \\046655 &:= -5/5 + 6^6 + 4 \times 0 \\046679 &:= 9 \times 7 + 6^6 - 40 \\047396 &:= 6^{9-3} + 740 \\052438 &:= 8 \times 3^{4 \times 2} - 50 \\059499 &:= 9 \times 9^4 + 9 \times 50 \\072192 &:= 2^9 \times (1 + 2 \times 70) \\093492 &:= 2 \times ((9 \times 4)^3 + 90) \\097674 &:= 4^7 \times 6 - 7 \times 90 \\098394 &:= 4^9 \times 3/8 + 90 \\104975 &:= ((-5 + 7) \times 9)^4 - 01 \\116635 &:= 5 \times 3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1 \\116675 &:= 5 \times (7 + 6^6 / (1 + 1)) \\117567 &:= 7^6 - 5 - 7 \times 11 \\117577 &:= 7 \times 7^5 - 71 - 1 \\117643 &:= (3 + 4)^6 - 7 \times 1 + 1 \\117649 &:= (9 + 4 - 6)^{7 \times 1 - 1} \\117729 &:= 9^2 + 7^{7-1} - 1 \\118336 &:= (6 + 338)^{1+1} \\126737 &:= (7^3 + 7 + 6)^2 + 1 \\131072 &:= 2^{(7-01) \times 3} - 1 \\132651 &:= (15 + 6^2)^3 \times 1 \\134457 &:= 7^5 \times (-4 + 4 \times 3) + 1 \\136079 &:= 9 \times 70 \times 6^3 - 1 \\136945 &:= (5^4 + 9) \times 6^3 + 1 \\137842 &:= 2 \times (48 - 7)^3 \times 1 \\139264 &:= 4^6 \times ((2 + 9) \times 3 + 1) \\139964 &:= 4 \times (6 \times (9 + 9)^3 - 1) \\139966 &:= (6^6 \times 9 - 9) / 3 + 1 \\140608 &:= (-8 + 060)^{4-1} \\145232 &:= 232 \times (5^4 + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}146411 &:= 11^4 \times (6 + 4) + 1 \\147419 &:= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\147429 &:= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\147469 &:= 9 \times (6 + 4^7) - 41 \\147491 &:= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\153097 &:= 7 \times (90 \times 3^5 + 1) \\155684 &:= 4 \times ((8 + 6^5) \times 5 + 1) \\156252 &:= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6 - 5} + 1) \\157457 &:= -7 + 54^{7-5+1} \\157469 &:= (9 \times 6)^{-4+7} + 5 \times 1 \\157752 &:= 2 \times (5^7 + 751) \\159375 &:= 5^{-7+3+9} \times 51 \\172773 &:= 3^7 \times (72 + 7 \times 1) \\177147 &:= (7 - 4)^{17-7+1} \\177153 &:= 3^{5-1+7} + 7 - 1 \\179275 &:= 5 \times (-7 + 2^9) \times 71 \\183704 &:= 4 \times (07 \times 3^8 - 1) \\186615 &:= (5 - 1) \times 6^6 - 8 - 1 \\186623 &:= 32 \times 6^6 / 8 - 1 \\186624 &:= 4 \times (2 + 6^6) - 8 \times 1 \\186631 &:= (1 + 3) \times 6^6 + 8 - 1 \\186644 &:= 4 \times (-4 + 6^6 + 8 + 1) \\186646 &:= -6 + 4 \times (6^6 + 8 - 1) \\186648 &:= -8 + 4 \times (6^6 + 8 \times 1) \\186684 &:= 4 \times (8 + 6^6 + 8 - 1) \\187277 &:= (7 \times 7)^2 \times 78 - 1 \\194471 &:= (17 + 4)^4 - 9 - 1 \\194489 &:= (9 + 8 + 4)^4 + 9 - 1 \\196517 &:= (7 + 1)^5 \times 6 - 91 \\196589 &:= -9 + 8^5 \times 6 - 9 - 1 \\196608 &:= 8^{06} \times 6 / (9 - 1) \\196618 &:= 8^{-1+6} \times 6 + 9 + 1 \\196832 &:= 2 \times (3^8 \times (6 + 9) + 1) \\207936 &:= (6 \times (-3 + 9 + 70))^2 \\209764 &:= (467 - 9)^{02} \\211595 &:= -5 + (9 \times 51 + 1)^2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 214375 &:= (5 \times 7)^3 \times (4 - 1 + 2) & 262143 &:= -3 + (4 \times 1 \times 2)^6 + 2 \\ 221184 &:= 48^{1 \times 1 + 2} \times 2 & 262146 &:= (6 + 4 \times 1 - 2)^6 + 2 \\ 225625 &:= ((5^2 - 6) \times 5^2)^2 & 262148 &:= 8^{(4-1) \times 2} + 6 - 2 \\ 225792 &:= 2^9 \times (7 \times (5 - 2))^2 & 262158 &:= 8^{5+1} + 2 \times 6 + 2 \\ 227529 &:= (9^2 \times 5 + 72)^2 & 262168 &:= 8^6 \times 1 + 26 - 2 \\ 228484 &:= (4 - 8 + 482)^2 & 262178 &:= 8^{7-1} - 2 + 6^2 \\ 229374 &:= 4^7 \times (3 + 9 + 2) - 2 & 262194 &:= 4^9 - 12 + 62 \\ 232324 &:= (-4 + 2 \times 3^{2+3})^2 & 262268 &:= 8^6 + 2 \times (2^6 - 2) \\ 233255 &:= 5 \times (-5 + (2 \times 3)^{3 \times 2}) & 262288 &:= 8^{8-2} + (2 \times 6)^2 \\ 233289 &:= (-9 + 82 \times (3 + 3))^2 & 263169 &:= (9 \times 61 - 36)^2 \\ 234222 &:= -2 + 22^4 - 32 & 263424 &:= (4 + 24)^3 \times 6 \times 2 \\ 234247 &:= ((7 + 4) \times 2)^4 - 3^2 & 265695 &:= (5 + 9^6 - 56)/2 \\ 234256 &:= ((6 + 5) \times 2)^4 \times (3 - 2) & 265721 &:= (1 + (2 \times 7 - 5)^6)/2 \\ 234265 &:= ((5 + 6) \times 2)^4 + 3^2 & 267126 &:= 6 \times (217 - 6)^2 \\ 234375 &:= 5^7 \times 3 \times (4 - 3)^2 & 267289 &:= ((9 + 8^2) \times 7 + 6)^2 \\ 235282 &:= 2 \times (-8 + (2 + 5)^{3 \times 2}) & 268324 &:= (4^{2 \times 3} / 8 + 6)^2 \\ 235298 &:= (8 + 9 + 2^5)^3 \times 2 & 268868 &:= 8^6 + (88 - 6)^2 \\ 235445 &:= 5 \times (44 \times 5 - 3)^2 & 269361 &:= (1 + (6/3)^9 + 6)^2 \\ 235956 &:= 6 \times (5 + 9) \times 53^2 & 273125 &:= 5^{2+1} \times (3^7 - 2) \\ 236196 &:= (6 \times 9 \times (1 \times 6 + 3))^2 & 273455 &:= (5 + 5^{4+3}) \times 7/2 \\ 237169 &:= ((9 + 61) \times 7 - 3)^2 & 275625 &:= ((5 \times 2 + 65) \times 7)^2 \\ 238326 &:= 62^3 - 8 + 3 \times 2 & 276576 &:= 6^7 - 5 \times 672 \\ 239432 &:= 2 \times (349 - 3)^2 & 279666 &:= 6 \times (6^6 - 9 \times (7 - 2)) \\ 241664 &:= 4^6 \times (61 - 4 + 2) & 279742 &:= (2 + 4)^7 - 97 \times 2 \\ 247301 &:= 103 \times 7^4 - 2 & 279934 &:= (4 + 3 - 9/9)^7 - 2 \\ 248834 &:= (4 \times 3)^{8/8+4} + 2 & 279936 &:= 6^{(3+9+9-7)/2} \\ 253984 &:= 4 \times (-8 + (9 + 3^5)^2) & 279938 &:= (8 \times 3 - 9 - 9)^7 + 2 \\ 254448 &:= (-8 + 4^4) \times (4^5 + 2) & 283215 &:= 5 \times (-1 + 238^2) \\ 255025 &:= (5 \times 20 \times 5 + 5)^2 & 283235 &:= 5 \times (3 + 238^2) \\ 255367 &:= 7 \times (6^3 - 5 \times 5)^2 & 283392 &:= 2 \times (9 + 3)^3 \times 82 \\ 260846 &:= -6^4 + 8^{06} - 2 & 285374 &:= (4 \times 7)^3 \times (5 + 8) - 2 \\ 261568 &:= 8^6 - ((5 - 1) \times 6)^2 & 287296 &:= (6 \times (9^2 + 7) + 8)^2 \\ 262136 &:= -6 + ((3 + 1) \times 2)^6 - 2 & 288369 &:= (9 + 6 \times (3 + 8) \times 8)^2 \\ 262138 &:= -8 + ((3 + 1) \times 2)^6 + 2 & 291595 &:= -5 + ((9 + 51) \times 9)^2 \\ 262141 &:= -1 + (4 \times 1 \times 2)^6 - 2 & 294864 &:= 4 \times (-6 + 8^4 \times 9) \times 2 \\ 262142 &:= (2 + 4 \times 1 + 2)^6 - 2 & 294883 &:= (-3 + 8 \times 8^4) \times 9 - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 294888 &:= -8 + 8 \times (8^4 \times 9 - 2) & 353673 &:= 3 \times (7^6 + 3^5) - 3 \\ 294892 &:= -2 + 9 \times (8^{-4+9} - 2) & 354276 &:= 6 \times ((7 - 2 + 4)^5 - 3) \\ 294894 &:= 4 \times 9 \times (8^4 - 9) \times 2 & 368549 &:= (9 + 4)^5 - (8 + 6)^3 \\ 294912 &:= 2^{1+9+4} \times 9 \times 2 & 369757 &:= 7^5 \times (7 + 9 + 6) + 3 \\ 294948 &:= (8 + 4^9/4) \times 9/2 & 373238 &:= (8 \times 3^2)^3 - 7 - 3 \\ 294965 &:= 5 \times ((-6 + 9^4) \times 9 - 2) & 373244 &:= -4 + 4 \times (2 \times 3)^7/3 \\ 295159 &:= (9^5 - 1) \times 5 - 9^2 & 373246 &:= -6 + 4 \times (2 \times 3)^7/3 \\ 295235 &:= 5 \times (3 \times (-2 + 5)^9 - 2) & 373248 &:= (84 - 2 - 3 - 7)^3 \\ 295243 &:= 3^{4 \times 2} \times 5 \times 9 - 2 & 373269 &:= (9 \times (6 + 2))^3 + 7 \times 3 \\ 295335 &:= 5 \times ((3 \times 3)^5 + 9 \times 2) & 379459 &:= (-9 + 5^4)^{9-7} + 3 \\ 298116 &:= (6 \times (1 + 1 + 89))^2 & 383856 &:= 6 \times ((5 \times 8)^3 - 8 \times 3) \\ 300763 &:= (3 - 6 + 70)^{03} & 387577 &:= -7 + 757 \times 8^3 \\ 314432 &:= (23 + 4 + 41)^3 & 388999 &:= -9 - 9 + (9 + 8 \times 8)^3 \\ 314922 &:= (-2 + (2 \times 9)^4) \times 1 \times 3 & 389017 &:= (-7 + (1 + 09) \times 8)^3 \\ 314924 &:= -4 + (2 \times 9)^4 \times 1 \times 3 & 390224 &:= 4^2 \times (20 + 9)^3 \\ 314931 &:= (((-1 + 3) \times 9)^4 + 1) \times 3 & 390625 &:= 5^{2-6+09+3} \\ 316227 &:= 72^2 \times 61 + 3 & 391355 &:= 5^{5+3} + 1 + 9^3 \\ 318864 &:= (4^6 - 8) \times (81 - 3) & 391385 &:= 5^8 + 31 + 9^3 \\ 324555 &:= -5^5 + 5 \times 4^{2^3} & 391625 &:= 5^{2+6} + (1 + 9)^3 \\ 326424 &:= 42 \times (-4 + 6^{2+3}) & 392784 &:= (4^8 - 72) \times (9 - 3) \\ 326634 &:= (4 + 3) \times (6 + 6^{2 \times 3}) & 393222 &:= (2 + 2^{2^3+9}) \times 3 \\ 326697 &:= 7 \times (9 + 6 + 6^{2 \times 3}) & 393545 &:= 5 \times (4 \times (-5 + 3^9) - 3) \\ 328509 &:= (9 + 058 + 2)^3 & 393645 &:= 5 \times (4 \times (6 - 3)^9 - 3) \\ 331749 &:= (-9 + (47 + 1)^3) \times 3 & 396568 &:= -8 + 6^5 \times (6 \times 9 - 3) \\ 331764 &:= (-4 + (6 \times (7 + 1))^3) \times 3 & 399492 &:= (2^9 + 4 \times 9) \times 9^3 \\ 331768 &:= -8 + (6 \times (7 + 1))^3 \times 3 & 404968 &:= 8 \times ((6 + 9)^4 - 04) \\ 331773 &:= 3 \times (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 - 3 & 411771 &:= (1 - 7^7)/(1 + 1 - 4) \\ 331776 &:= (6 \times 7 + 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 & 411772 &:= 2 \times (7^7 \times 1 + 1)/4 \\ 331782 &:= (2 + (8 \times (7 - 1))^3) \times 3 & 411773 &:= (3 + 7^7) \times (1 + 1)/4 \\ 343007 &:= 70^{03} + 4 + 3 & 413343 &:= (3 + 4) \times (3 \times 3)^{1+4} \\ 343656 &:= (6^5 + 6^3) \times 43 & 419886 &:= (6^8 - 8 \times 9)/(1 \times 4) \\ 344148 &:= 84 \times (1 + (4 \times 4)^3) & 419904 &:= 4 \times (09 + 9 \times 1)^4 \\ 348758 &:= 85 \times (7 + 8^4) + 3 & 421875 &:= (5 \times (7 + 8))^{12/4} \\ 349464 &:= (-46 + 4^9) \times 4/3 & 435456 &:= 6^5 \times (4 \times 5 \times 3 - 4) \\ 349494 &:= (4^9 \times 4 - 94)/3 & 436875 &:= 5 \times ((-7 + 8^6)/3 - 4) \\ 352947 &:= 7^{4+9-2-5} \times 3 & 437656 &:= ((6 + 5^6) \times 7 - 3) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 442368 &:= (8 \times 6)^3 + 24^4 \\ 442369 &:= (96^3 \times 2 + 4) / 4 \\ 446168 &:= 86 \times (1 + 6^4) \times 4 \\ 456968 &:= -8 + (6 + 9 + 6 + 5)^4 \\ 456973 &:= -3 + (7 \times (9 - 6) + 5)^4 \\ 456976 &:= (6 + (7 - 9 + 6) \times 5)^4 \\ 457885 &:= 5^8 + (8 + 7^5) \times 4 \\ 458672 &:= 2 \times 7 \times (-6 + 8^5) + 4 \\ 458688 &:= -8 + (8 + 6) \times (8^5 - 4) \\ 458746 &:= -6 + 4^7 \times (8 + 5 \times 4) \\ 458748 &:= 8/4 \times 7 \times 8^5 - 4 \\ 458847 &:= 7 \times (4^8 + 8 + 5) + 4 \\ 458868 &:= (8 + 6) \times (8 + 8^5) + 4 \\ 458872 &:= 2 \times (7 \times (8 + 8^5) + 4) \\ 466553 &:= -3 + (5 + 5) \times 6^6 - 4 \\ 466556 &:= 6^5 \times 5 \times (6 + 6) - 4 \\ 466557 &:= -7 + (5 + 5) \times 6^6 + 4 \\ 467455 &:= -5^5 + 4 \times (7^6 - 4) \\ 468794 &:= ((-4 + 9)^7 + 8) \times 6 - 4 \\ 472386 &:= -6 + 8 \times 3^{2 \times 7 - 4} \\ 473256 &:= 6^{5-2} \times (3^7 + 4) \\ 493837 &:= -7 + 38^3 \times 9 - 4 \\ 493852 &:= (-2 + 5 \times 8)^3 \times 9 + 4 \\ 497664 &:= 4 \times 6 \times (6 \times (-7 + 9))^4 \\ 517536 &:= 6^3 \times (-5 + 7^{-1+5}) \\ 521645 &:= (54 \times 6 - 1)^2 \times 5 \\ 524181 &:= (181 \times 4)^2 + 5 \\ 524248 &:= 8 \times (4^{2+4+2} - 5) \\ 524281 &:= (-1 + 8^{2+4}) \times 2 - 5 \\ 524282 &:= 2 \times (8^{2+4} + 2 - 5) \\ 524284 &:= -4 + 8 \times 2 \times (4 \times 2)^5 \\ 524288 &:= (8 + 8) \times (2 + 4 + 2)^5 \\ 524294 &:= 4^9 \times 2 - 4 + 2 \times 5 \\ 524298 &:= 8^{9-2} / 4 + 2 \times 5 \\ 524384 &:= 4 \times 8 \times (3 + 4^{2+5}) \\ 528369 &:= 9^6 - 3 \times (8/2)^5 \\ 528384 &:= (4 + 8^3) \times (8/2)^5 \\ 530469 &:= 9^6 - 4 \times 03^5 \\ 531433 &:= 3^{3 \times 4} \times 1 - 3 - 5 \\ 531436 &:= ((6 - 3)^4 \times 1)^3 - 5 \\ 531438 &:= -8 + (3^4 \times 1)^3 + 5 \\ 531439 &:= (9 \times 3)^4 \times 1 + 3 - 5 \\ 531441 &:= (1 + 4 + 4)^{1^3+5} \\ 531443 &:= 3^{4 \times (4-1)} - 3 + 5 \\ 531469 &:= 9^6 + 4 \times (-1 + 3 + 5) \\ 537743 &:= -3^4 + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5 \\ 537817 &:= -7 + (18 - 7 + 3)^5 \\ 537822 &:= -2 + (2 + 8 + 7 - 3)^5 \\ 537824 &:= (4^2 + 8 - 7 - 3)^5 \\ 544768 &:= (8 \times 67 - 4) \times 4^5 \\ 546875 &:= 5^7 \times (8 \times 6/4 - 5) \\ 549948 &:= 84 \times (-9 + 9^4 - 5) \\ 552771 &:= 177 \times (-2 + 5^5) \\ 567137 &:= 73 \times (-1 \times 7 + 6^5) \\ 567648 &:= (8 \times (4 + 6) - 7) \times 6^5 \\ 571434 &:= -4 + 34 \times 1 \times 7^5 \\ 571574 &:= (4 + 7^5) \times (-1 + 7 \times 5) \\ 581358 &:= 85^3 + 1 - 8^5 \\ 589662 &:= (2 \times 6 + 6) \times (-9 + 8^5) \\ 589672 &:= 2 \times (-76 + 9 \times 8^5) \\ 589792 &:= 2 \times (-9 - 7 + 9 \times 8^5) \\ 589817 &:= -7 + (1 + 8 + 9) \times 8^5 \\ 589837 &:= (7 - 3)^8 \times 9 + 8 + 5 \\ 589847 &:= (7 + 4^8) \times 9 - 8 \times 5 \\ 589962 &:= 2 \times (69 + 9 \times 8^5) \\ 589972 &:= 2 \times (-7 + 9 \times (9 + 8^5)) \\ 589986 &:= (-6 + 8) \times 9 \times (9 + 8^5) \\ 606476 &:= (6 + 7) \times (-4 + 6^{06}) \\ 614653 &:= -3 + 56^4 / 16 \\ 624683 &:= ((38 + 6)^4 + 2) / 6 \\ 625687 &:= (786 + 5)^2 + 6 \\ 629856 &:= 6^5 \times (89 - 2 - 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 640024 &:= 4 \times (20^{04} + 6) & 823527 &:= 7^{2 \times 5 - 3} - 2 \times 8 \\ 652808 &:= 808^2 - 56 & 823543 &:= (3 + 4)^{5 - 3 \times 2 + 8} \\ 655354 &:= 4 \times (5 + 3)^5 \times 5 - 6 & 823677 &:= 7^7 + 63 \times 2 + 8 \\ 655384 &:= (4^8 + 3) \times (5 + 5) - 6 & 827992 &:= (2 + 9) \times 97^2 \times 8 \\ 655584 &:= 4 \times (8^5 \times 5 + 56) & 828092 &:= (2 + 908)^2 - 8 \\ 656187 &:= 7 \times (-8 - 1 + 6 \times 5^6) & 830536 &:= (-6 + (-3 + 50)^3) \times 8 \\ 656196 &:= 6 \times (-9 + (1 + 6) \times 5^6) & 839763 &:= 3 \times (6^7 + 9 - 3 \times 8) \\ 656376 &:= 6 \times 7 \times (-3 + 6 + 5^6) & 839816 &:= 6^{1+8} / (9 + 3) + 8 \\ 658497 &:= (-7 + 94)^{8-5} - 6 & 843648 &:= (8 \times 4 - 6)^3 \times 48 \\ 663588 &:= ((8 + 8 \times 5)^3 + 6) \times 6 & 845649 &:= (-9 + (46 + 5)^4) / 8 \\ 663759 &:= 9 \times (5^7 - 3^6 \times 6) & 851942 &:= (-2 + 4^{9-1}) \times (5 + 8) \\ 668736 &:= 6^{-3+7} \times 86 \times 6 & 851968 &:= 8^6 + 9 \times (-1 + 5)^8 \\ 671742 &:= -2 + 4^7 \times (-1 + 7 \times 6) & 852384 &:= (4^8 + 32) \times (5 + 8) \\ 733824 &:= 42 \times 8 \times (-3 + 3^7) & 857157 &:= 7^5 \times (-1 \times 7 + 58) \\ 734811 &:= (1 \times 18^4 - 3) \times 7 & 857359 &:= 95^3 - (7 - 5) \times 8 \\ 734824 &:= 4 \times (-2 + 84 \times 3^7) & 857565 &:= (56 - 5) \times (7^5 + 8) \\ 742558 &:= (8 + 5)^5 \times 2 - 4 \times 7 & 859375 &:= 5^7 \times (-3 + 9) + 5^8 \\ 746496 &:= 6 \times 9 \times (4 \times 6)^{-4+7} & 885695 &:= 5 \times 9^6 / (-5 + 8) + 8 \\ 753569 &:= (96 - 5)^3 + 5 - 7 & 885735 &:= 5 \times 3^{75-8 \times 8} \\ 753664 &:= 46 \times (6 + 3 - 5)^7 & 917495 &:= (5 + 9) \times 4^{7+1} - 9 \\ 754279 &:= 97 \times (2 + 4)^5 + 7 & 923521 &:= (-1 + 2^5)^{-3-2+9} \\ 759368 &:= ((8 - 6) \times 3 + 9)^5 - 7 & 937495 &:= -5 + (9 - 4)^7 \times (3 + 9) \\ 759381 &:= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7 & 937512 &:= (2 - 1 + 5^7) \times (3 + 9) \\ 765276 &:= -6 + 7^2 \times (5^6 - 7) & 937524 &:= (4 - 2 + 5^7) \times (3 + 9) \\ 765429 &:= (9 - 2) \times (-4 + 5^6) \times 7 & 937525 &:= 5^2 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\ 765527 &:= 7^2 \times (5 + 5^6 - 7) & 937536 &:= (6 - 3 + 5^7) \times (3 + 9) \\ 765597 &:= 7 \times (-9 + 5 + 5^6 \times 7) & 937539 &:= (9 + 3) \times 5^7 + 39 \\ 765625 &:= (-5 + 2 \times 6) \times 5^6 \times 7 & 937544 &:= 44 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\ 773879 &:= -97 \times 8^3 + 7^7 & 937548 &:= (8 - 4 + 5^7) \times (3 + 9) \\ 776887 &:= -(7 - 8/8)^6 + 7^7 & 944777 &:= -7 + (7 + 7 + 4)^4 \times 9 \\ 786431 &:= -1 + 3 \times 4^{-6+8+7} & 944784 &:= (4 + 8 \times 7/4)^4 \times 9 \\ 786583 &:= 3 \times (8^5 + 6) \times 8 + 7 & 944811 &:= (-1 + 18^4 + 4) \times 9 \\ 792098 &:= 890^2 - 9 + 7 & 944815 &:= -5 + (18^4 + 4) \times 9 \\ 805295 &:= 5 \times ((9 + 2)^5 + 08) & 970299 &:= 99^{(20+7)/9} \\ 822657 &:= (7 + (5 \times 6)^2)^2 + 8 & 979767 &:= 7 \times 6^7 / (9 - 7) - 9 \\ 823287 &:= 7^{8/2+3} - 2^8 & & \\ 823487 &:= 7 \times (-8 + (4 + 3)^{-2+8}) & & \end{aligned}$$

From now onwards the results are with unnecessary extra brackets, such as, "(...)" . After simplifications, these can be removed easily.

$$\begin{aligned}
 0012546 &:= -((6 \times ((4 + 5) - 2100))) & 0057362 &:= ((26 \times (3^7)) + 500) \\
 0012565 &:= -((5 + (6 \times (5 - 2100)))) & 0059549 &:= ((9^{45/9}) + 500) \\
 0012625 &:= 5^2 + 6 \times 2100 & 0061697 &:= -(((7 + 96) \times (1 - 600))) \\
 0013968 &:= -(((8 \times 6) \times (9 - (3 \times 100)))) & 0066128 &:= -((8 - ((2^{16}) + 600))) \\
 0014741 &:= (((1 \times 4) + 7)^4) + 100 & 0066136 &:= (((6/3)^{16}) + 600) \\
 0015273 &:= -((3 \times ((7 + 2) - 5100))) & 0068288 &:= -((8 \times ((8^2) - 8600))) \\
 0015325 &:= 5^2 + 3 \times 5100 & 0068448 &:= -((8 \times (44 - 8600))) \\
 0015525 &:= (((5^{2+5})/5) - 100) & 0068728 &:= -((8 \times ((2 + 7) - 8600))) \\
 0015545 &:= ((5 \times (4 + (5^5))) - 100) & 0068744 &:= -(((4 + 4) \times (7 - 8600))) \\
 0015725 &:= (((5^{-2+7}) \times 5) + 100) & 0068825 &:= 5^2 + 8 \times 8600 \\
 0015984 &:= (4 \times ((8^{9-5}) - 100)) & 0078327 &:= ((7 + 2) \times (3 + 8700)) \\
 0016284 &:= ((4 \times ((8/2)^6)) - 100) & 0081498 &:= -(((8 + 94) \times (1 - 800))) \\
 0016474 &:= (((4^7) - 4) - 6) + 100 & 0091698 &:= -((((8 + 9) \times 6) \times (1 - 900))) \\
 0016484 &:= ((4 \times ((8 - 4)^6)) + 100) & 0096595 &:= -((5 - ((9 + 5) \times 6900))) \\
 0017388 &:= -((8 - ((8 \times (3^7)) - 100))) & 0099315 &:= ((5 \times ((1 \times 3)^9)) + 900) \\
 0017507 &:= ((7^{05}) + (7 \times 100)) & 0099325 &:= ((5 \times (2 + (3^9))) + 900) \\
 0019783 &:= ((3^{(8-7) \times 9}) + 100) & 0104966 &:= (((6^6) \times 9)/4) - 010 \\
 0021485 &:= (5 \times (((8^4) + 1) + 200)) & 0112786 &:= (((6 \times 8) \times 7)^2) - 110 \\
 0023528 &:= (((8 - 2)^5) \times 3) + 200 & 0114768 &:= ((8 \times 6) \times (((7^4) \times 1) - 10)) \\
 0025472 &:= ((2^7) \times ((4 - 5) + 200)) & 0114944 &:= ((4^4) \times (9 + (4 \times 110))) \\
 0025995 &:= -((5 \times ((9/9) - 5200))) & 0116565 &:= -(((5 - (6^5)) \times ((6 - 1) + 10))) \\
 0026995 &:= -((5 - (9 \times ((9 + 6) \times 200)))) & 0117652 &:= (((((2 + 5)^6) - 7) \times 1) + 10) \\
 0028692 &:= -(((2 \times 9) \times (6 - (8 \times 200)))) & 0117667 &:= ((7^6) - (6 \times ((7 \times 1) - 10))) \\
 0032168 &:= (8 \times ((61^2) + 300)) & 0124396 &:= ((6 \times ((9 + 3)^4)) - (2 \times 10)) \\
 0032186 &:= -(((6 + 8) \times (1 - 2300))) & 0124426 &:= (((6 \times 2)^4) \times (4 + 2)) + 10 \\
 0032468 &:= (((8^6)/4)/2) - 300 & 0124436 &:= ((6 \times ((3 \times 4)^4)) + (2 \times 10)) \\
 0032495 &:= ((5 \times ((9^4) - 2)) - 300) & 0124626 &:= ((6 \times ((2 \times 6)^4)) + 210) \\
 0037692 &:= -(((2 \times 9) \times (6 - (7 \times 300)))) & 0125952 &:= (((2 \times 59) + 5) \times (2^{10})) \\
 0037795 &:= -((5 - (9 \times ((7 + 7) \times 300)))) & 0127125 &:= -(((5^{2+1}) \times (7 - (2^{10})))) \\
 0042898 &:= (89 \times (82 + 400)) & 0129125 &:= ((5^{2+1}) \times (9 + (2^{10}))) \\
 0042984 &:= -((((4 + 8) \times 9) \times (2 - 400))) & 0129585 &:= -((5 - (((8 \times 5) \times 9)^2) - 10))) \\
 0046248 &:= -((8 - (((4 + 2)^6) - 400))) & 0134385 &:= (((5^{8-3}) \times 43) + 10) \\
 0046256 &:= (((6^{5+2})/6) - 400) & 0135437 &:= (((7 \times 3)^4) + 5) - (3^{10}) \\
 0046655 &:= -((((5/5) - (6^6)) + (4 \times 00))) & 0136166 &:= (661 \times ((6^3) - 10)) \\
 0046795 &:= -((5 - (9 \times ((7 + 6) \times 400)))) & 0137167 &:= -(((7 - ((6 - 1)^7)) - (3^{10}))) \\
 0051896 &:= -(((6 + 98) \times (1 - 500))) & 0137175 &:= (((5^7) + (1^7)) + (3^{10})) \\
 0053995 &:= -((5 - (9 \times ((9 + 3) \times 500)))) & 0137862 &:= (2 \times (((6 \times 8) - 7)^3) + 10) \\
 0054549 &:= (9 \times (((4 + 5)^4) - 500)) & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

- 0138235** := $-(5 - (((32 - 8)^3) \times 10))$
0138753 := $((3^5) \times ((7 \times 83) - 10))$
0138875 := $-(5 - (((7 \times 8) \times 8) \times 310))$
0139328 := $((8^2) \times ((3 \times (9^3)) - 10))$
0139648 := $((8 \times 4) \times ((6 \times (9^3)) - 10))$
0142924 := $((42 \times 9)^2) + (4 \times 10)$
0143755 := $((5^5) + ((7^3) \times 410))$
0143758 := $(((((8 \times 5) - 7)^3) \times 4) + 10)$
0144855 := $(5 \times (((5 + 8)^4) + 410))$
0146535 := $((5^3) + (((5 + 6)^4) \times 10))$
0147466 := $((6 \times 6) \times ((4^7)/4) + 10)$
0147479 := $((9 \times (7 + (4^7))) - (4 \times 10))$
0147493 := $-(3 - ((9 \times (4^7)) + (4 \times 10)))$
0147496 := $-(6 - ((9 \times ((4^7) + 4)) + 10))$
0155835 := $-(5 \times (3 + ((8 - (5^5)) \times 10)))$
0155895 := $(5 \times (9 - ((8 - (5^5)) \times 10)))$
0155955 := $-(5 \times (59 - ((5^5) \times 10)))$
0157546 := $((6^4) + (((5^7)/5) \times 10))$
0157713 := $(3 \times (1 + (7 \times 7510)))$
0159432 := $((2 + ((3^{4+9}) - 5))/10)$
0163745 := $-(5 - (((4^7) - 3) - 6) \times 10))$
0171165 := $((5^6) \times 11) - 710$
0177147 := $((7 - 4)^{177+10})$
0177325 := $-(5 - (23 \times 7710))$
0178782 := $((2^8) - 7) \times (8 + 710)$
0179448 := $-(8 + ((4^4) \times (9 - 710)))$
0183477 := $(7 \times (7 + (4 \times ((3^8) - 10))))$
0183714 := $-(4 \times (1 - (7 \times (3^8)))) - 10$
0183744 := $-(4 - (4 \times ((7 \times (3^8)) + 10)))$
0183748 := $((8 - 4) \times ((7 \times (3^8)) + 10))$
0186622 := $((2 + 2) \times (6^6)) + (8 - 10)$
0186624 := $((4 + 2)^6) \times ((6 + 8) - 10)$
0186625 := $(5 \times ((2 + ((6^6) \times 8))/10))$
0186626 := $((6 - 2) \times (6^6)) - (8 - 10)$
0186634 := $((4 \times (3 + (6^6))) + (8 - 10))$
0186641 := $-(1 - ((4 \times (6^6)) + (8 + 10)))$
0186643 := $-(3 - ((4 \times ((6^6) + 8)) - 10))$
0186674 := $((4 \times (7 + ((6^6) + 8))) - 10)$
0186688 := $(8 \times (8 - ((6^6)/(8 - 10)))$
0189535 := $-(5 - (((3^5) - 9) \times 810))$
0194176 := $((6^{7+1}) + (4^9))/10$
0195312 := $-(2 \times 1 + 3 - (5^9))/10$
0195313 := $((3 - 1) + 3 + (5^9))/10$
0195314 := $((4 + 1) \times 3 + (5^9))/10$
0195375 := $((5^{7-3}) + (5^9))/10$
0196518 := $((8 \times 1)^5) \times 6 - (9 \times 10)$
0196584 := $((4 - (8^5)) \times 6) \times (9 - 10)$
0197365 := $-(5 - ((6 + (3^7)) \times (9 \times 10)))$
0216493 := $((3^9) \times ((4 + 6) + 1)) - 20$
0227549 := $((94 \times 5) + 7)^2 + 20$
0229587 := $(7 \times (8^5)) - (9 - 220)$
0232635 := $-(5 - (((3^6) - 2) \times 320))$
0233265 := $(5 \times (((6^2)^3) - 3)) + (2 \times 0)$
0233275 := $-(5 - (((7 + 2)^3) \times 320))$
0233365 := $(5 \times ((6^{3+3}) - (3 - 20)))$
0233643 := $-(3 + (4^6)) \times (3 - (3 \times 20))$
0234253 := $(-3 + 5^2)^4 - 3 + 2 \times 0$
0234256 := $((6 + 5) \times 2)^4 + (32 \times 0)$
0234375 := $((5^7) \times 3) + ((4 \times 32) \times 0)$
0234395 := $((5^{9/3+4}) \times 3) + 20$
0235948 := $-(8 - (4 \times ((9^5) - (3 \times 20))))$
0238462 := $-(2 - (((6^4) \times 8) \times (3 + 20)))$
0245695 := $-(5 - ((9 \times 65) \times 420))$
0247624 := $((4 \times 26) \times ((7^4) - 20))$
0253245 := $((-(5 - 42))^3) \times 5 - (20)$
0257376 := $((6^7) - (3 \times 7520))$
0257948 := $((8^4) \times 9) \times 7 - (5 \times 20)$
0261524 := $((4^{2 \times 5 - 1}) - 620)$
0262122 := $-(2 - ((2^{(1+2) \times 6}) - 20))$
0262124 := $((4 + 2) \times 1 + 2)^6 - 20$
0262128 := $(-(8 \times 2)) \times (1 - (2^{-6+20}))$
0262137 := $-(7 - (((3 + 1) \times 2)^6)) + (2 \times 0)$
0262138 := $((8^3) \times 1)^2 - 6 + (2 \times 0)$
0262157 := $-(7 - (((5 - 1) \times 2)^6) + 20)$
0262162 := $-(2 - (((6 \times 1) + 2)^6) + 20)$
0262164 := $((4 + 6) \times 1 - 2)^6 + 20$
0262168 := $((8^6) \times 1) - 2 + 6 + 20$
0262224 := $(4 \times ((2^{22-6}) + 20))$

$$\begin{aligned} 0262264 &:= ((4^{(6/2)^2}) + (6 \times 20)) & 0376875 &:= -((5 - ((7 \times 8) \times 6730))) \\ 0262268 &:= (((8^6) + 2) + 2) + (6 \times 20)) & 0377344 &:= (((4 + 4)^3) \times (7 + 730)) \\ 0269568 &:= (8 \times ((6^{-5+9}) \times (6 + 20))) & 0387337 &:= ((73^3) - ((7 \times 8) \times 30)) \\ 0273395 &:= (((5^9/3) \times (3^7)) + 20) & 0390355 &:= ((5^{5+3}) - (09 \times 30)) \\ 0274432 &:= (((2^3)^4) \times (47 + 20)) & 0390385 &:= ((5^8) - ((30 \times 9) - 30)) \\ 0278176 &:= ((6^7) - ((1 + 87) \times 20)) & 0390595 &:= (((5^9)/5) - ((0 \times 9) + 30)) \\ 0278816 &:= ((6^{-1+8}) - ((8 \times 7) \times 20)) & 0390685 &:= (((5^8) + 60) + ((9/3) \times 0)) \\ 0279216 &:= ((6^{-1 \times 2+9}) - (720)) & 0390985 &:= (((5^8) + 90) + (9 \times 30)) \\ 0279616 &:= ((6^{1+6}) - ((9 + 7) \times 20)) & 0391195 &:= ((5^{9-1}) + (19 \times 30)) \\ 0279796 &:= ((6^{9+7-9}) - (7 \times 20)) & 0391555 &:= (((5 \times 5)^{5-1}) + 930) \\ 0279916 &:= (((((6 \times 1) + 9) - 9)^7) - 20) & 0392485 &:= ((5^8) + ((4 - 2) \times 930)) \\ 0279953 &:= -((3 - (((5 + (9/9))^7) + 20))) & 0393246 &:= ((6 \times (4^{2-3+9})) + 30) \\ 0279956 &:= ((6^{(5+9)/(9-7)}) + 20) & 0393475 &:= -((5 \times (7 - ((4 \times (3^9)) - 30)))) \\ 0280376 &:= ((6^7) + ((30 - 8) \times 20)) & 0393564 &:= (4 \times (6 + ((5 \times (3^9)) - 30))) \\ 0280776 &:= ((6^7) - (70 \times (8 - 20))) & 0393594 &:= -(((4 \times (9 - (5 \times (3^9)))) + 30)) \\ 0285327 &:= ((7^2) \times (3 + 5820)) & 0395245 &:= -((5 - (425 \times 930))) \\ 0287776 &:= ((6^7) + (((7 \times 7) \times 8) \times 20)) & 0396175 &:= -((5 - ((71 \times 6) \times 930))) \\ 0294886 &:= -((6 - ((8 \times ((8^4) \times 9)) - 20))) & 0411773 &:= (((3 + (7^7))/(1 + 1)) + (4 \times 0)) \\ 0294891 &:= (-1) + ((9 \times (8^{-4+9})) - (20)) & 0458668 &:= -(((8 + 6) \times ((6 - (8^5)) + (4 \times 0)))) \\ 0294892 &:= (((2^9+8)/4) \times 9) - 20 & 0458712 &:= (((2 \times 1) \times 7) \times (8^5)) - 40 \\ 0294932 &:= (((2^3)^{9-4}) \times 9) + 20 & 0458752 &:= (((2 + 5) + 7) \times (8^5)) + (4 \times 0) \\ 0294985 &:= -((5 \times ((8 - (9^4)) \times 9) - 20)) & 0458792 &:= -((((2 - 9) - 7) \times (8^5)) - 40) \\ 0294986 &:= (((6 + (8^9-4)) \times 9) + 20) & 0458827 &:= ((7 \times ((2^8+8) + 5)) + 40) \\ 0295955 &:= (((5^5) \times 95) - 920) & 0466555 &:= -((5 - (((5 + 5) \times (6^6)) + (4 \times 0)))) \\ 0296855 &:= (((5^5) \times (86 + 9)) - 20) & 0466652 &:= (2 \times ((5 \times (6^6)) + (6 + 40))) \\ 0314462 &:= (((2^6) + 4)^{4-1}) + 30 & 0483113 &:= ((3 \times (11^{-3+8})) - 40) \\ 0316386 &:= (((6 + 8) \times (3^6)) \times (1 + 30)) & 0493839 &:= (((9 \times (38^3)) - 9) + (4 \times 0)) \\ 0325155 &:= ((5 \times ((51 \times 5)^2)) + 30) & 0497624 &:= (((4^2) \times ((6^7)/9)) - 40) \\ 0326617 &:= -(((7 \times (1 - (6^6))) - (2 + 30))) & 0516348 &:= -((84 \times (3 - 6150))) \\ 0326652 &:= (((2 + 5) \times (6^6)) + (2 \times 30)) & 0522192 &:= (((((2^9) - 1)^2) \times 2) - 50) \\ 0331446 &:= (((6 \times 4)^4) \times 1) - 330 & 0523848 &:= (8 \times (((4^8) - 3) - 2) - 50)) \\ 0331746 &:= (((6 \times 4)^{7 \times 1-3}) - 30) & 0523888 &:= (8 \times (((8^8-3) \times 2) - 50)) \\ 0334656 &:= (((6^5) + 6) \times 43) + 30 & 0524188 &:= (((8^8-1)/4) - (2 \times 50)) \\ 0354259 &:= (((9^5) \times (2 + 4)) - (5 + 30)) & 0524234 &:= -((4 - (((32^4)/2) - 50))) \\ 0354294 &:= ((4 \times ((9^2+4) \times 5))/30) & 0524238 &:= (((((8^3)^2) \times 4)/2) - 50) \\ 0371568 &:= (8 \times ((6^{5+1}) - (7 \times 30))) & 0524329 &:= -((9 - ((2^3+4^2) + 50))) \\ 0373271 &:= (((1 \times 72)^3) - 7) + 30 & 0524338 &:= (((8^3+3) \times (4 - 2)) + 50) \\ 0373458 &:= (((8 \times (5 + 4))^3) + (7 \times 30)) & 0524346 &:= (((64^3) + 4) \times 2) + 50) \\ 0376826 &:= -((6 + ((2^8+6) \times (7 - 30))) & 0524688 &:= (8 \times (((8 - 6)^4^2) + 50)) \end{aligned}$$

- 0525888 := $((8 + 8) \times ((8^5) + (2 \times 50)))$
0527488 := $((8 \times 8) \times (((4^7)/2) + 50))$
0531391 := $((1 \times 9)^{(3-1) \times 3} - 50)$
0531393 := $((3^{9+3}) - ((1 - 3) + 50))$
0531491 := $((1 \times 9)^{4-1+3} + 50)$
0531493 := $(((((3 \times 9)^4) - 1) + 3) + 50)$
0531591 := $((1 \times 9)^{5+1} + (3 \times 50))$
0531791 := $((1 \times 9)^{7-1} + 350)$
0532272 := $-((2^7) - ((22^3) \times 50))$
0533736 := $((6^3) \times 7) \times (3 + 350)$
0546757 := $((7 \times ((5^7) - (6 \times 4))) + 50)$
0546775 := $((5^7) \times 7) - ((6 - 4) \times 50)$
0547075 := $((5^7) \times 07) + (4 \times 50)$
0548864 := $((4^6) \times ((88 - 4) + 50))$
0556271 := $-((1 - (72 \times ((6^5) - 50))))$
0583879 := $((97 - 8) \times (3^8)) - 50$
0589424 := $((4^2)^4 \times 9) - (8 \times 50)$
0589841 := $((1 + (4^8)) \times 9) + 8 + (5 \times 0)$
0589842 := $((2 + (4^8)) \times 9) + ((8 \times 5) \times 0)$
0589843 := $((3 + (4^8)) \times 9) - 8 + (5 \times 0)$
0589882 := $((2^{8+8}) \times 9) + (8 + 50)$
0599375 := $((5^{7-3}) \times (9 + 950))$
0614597 := $((7 \times (9 - 5))^4) + (1 - 60)$
0614715 := $((5 - 1) \times 7)^4 - 1 + 60$
0622592 := $-((2^{9+5}) \times (22 - 60))$
0622744 := $-((4 + (4^7)) \times (22 - 60))$
0623475 := $-((5 - ((7^4) - 3) \times 260))$
0624255 := $-((5 - ((5 + 2)^4) \times 260))$
0629496 := $(6 \times (((9 \times 4) \times 9)^2) - 60)$
0635993 := $-((3 - (((9 \times 9) + 5)^3) - 60))$
0640264 := $(4 \times (6 + ((20^4) + 60)))$
0649479 := $((9 \times (7 + 4)) \times (9^4)) - 60$
0655378 := $((87^3) - (5^5)) + (6 \times 0)$
0657813 := $((31 + 8) \times ((7^5) + 60))$
0694656 := $-(((6^5)/6) \times (4 - (9 \times 60)))$
0698875 := $-((5 - (78 \times 8960)))$
0699835 := $-((5 - (((3^8)/9) \times 960)))$
0737495 := $(5 \times ((9 \times ((4^7) - 3)) + 70))$
0746426 := $((6/2) \times 4)^6 / 4 - 70$
0746488 := $-(((8 - (((8 + 4)^6)/4)) + (7 \times 0)))$
0759445 := $((5 \times 4) + 4 - 9)^5 + 70$
0762799 := $((9 \times 97)^2) + 670$
0765695 := $-(((5 - (9 \times 6)) \times (5^6)) - 70)$
0823297 := $((7^{9-2}) - (3 \times (2 + 80)))$
0823377 := $((7^7) - 3) - 3 - (2 \times 80)$
0823461 := $((1 + 6)^{4+3}) - (2 + 80)$
0823477 := $((7^7) + ((4 \times 3) + 2) - 80)$
0823617 := $((7^{1+6}) - ((3 \times 2) - 80))$
0823677 := $((7^7) + ((6^3) - 2) - 80)$
0824256 := $((6^5) \times ((24 + 2) + 80))$
0824544 := $(4 \times (454^2)) + 80$
0830497 := $-(7 - ((94^{03}) - 80))$
0831875 := $(5 \times ((7 \times 8) - 1)^3) + (8 \times 0)$
0839728 := $((8 - 2)^7 \times 9) / 3 - 80$
0839776 := $((6^7) + 7) + 9 \times 3 - 80$
0852329 := $(923^2) + (5 \times 80)$
0885743 := $((3^{4+7}) \times 5) + 8 + (8 \times 0)$
0885935 := $((5 \times 3) \times ((9^5) + 8)) + 80$
0937593 := $((3 + 9) \times (5^7)) + (3 + 90)$
0979776 := $((6^7) \times 7) / (9 - 7) + (9 \times 0)$
1036324 := $((4^{2+3}) - 6)^{3-01}$
1038944 := $(4 \times ((4^9) - (8 \times 301)))$
1042568 := $8 \times (-6 + 5^2)^4 \times 01$
1047573 := $((3^7) \times ((5 + 7) \times 40) - 1)$
1048448 := $-((8 \times 4) \times (4 - (8^{4+01})))$
1048479 := $(97 - ((4 \times 8)^4)) \times (0 - 1)$
1048488 := $((88 - ((4 \times 8)^4)) \times (0 - 1))$
1048497 := $((79 - ((4 \times 8)^4)) \times (0 - 1))$
1048528 := $((8 \times 2)^5 - 8) - 40 \times 1$
1048544 := $((4 \times 4)^5 + 8) - 40 \times 1$
1048572 := $(2^{7+5+8}) - (4 \times 01)$
1048573 := $-((3 - (((7 - 5) \times 8)^{4+01})))$
1048575 := $((5 \times 7) + 5) - 8^4 - 01$
1048576 := $((6 - 7) + 5) \times 8^4 \times 01$
1048577 := $((-7/7 + 5) \times 8)^4 + 01$
1048579 := $((9 + 7)^5 + 8) - 4 - 01$
1048581 := $((1 + ((8^5) \times 8)) \times 4) + 01$
1048588 := $((8 + 8)^5 + 8) + 4 \times 01$

$$\begin{aligned} 1048608 &:= (((8^0)^6 + 8) \times 4) \times 01) \\ 1048826 &:= -((6 - ((2^8) \times ((8^4) + 01)))) \\ 1048968 &:= (((8^6) + 98) \times 4) \times 01) \\ 1062892 &:= (2 \times ((9^{8-2}) + (6 - 01))) \\ 1066368 &:= (((8^6) \times 3) + (6^{6+01})) \\ 1071637 &:= (7 \times (((3^{6+1}) \times 70) + 1)) \\ 1119762 &:= (((2 \times (6^7)) + 9) \times ((1 \times 1) + 1)) \\ 1119764 &:= ((4 \times (6^7)) + ((9 \times 1) + 11)) \\ 1124863 &:= (((((3 \times 6) + 8) \times 4)^{2+1}) - 1) \\ 1124864 &:= (-((4 \times (6 - (8 \times 4))))^{2 \times 1+1}) \\ 1138489 &:= ((984 + 83)^{1+1}) \\ 1143582 &:= (((-((2 - 85))^3) + (4)) \times (1 + 1)) \\ 1156547 &:= ((74 \times (((5^6) + 5) - 1)) + 1) \\ 1157665 &:= (5 \times ((6^6) + ((7^5) \times 11))) \\ 1166125 &:= ((5^2) \times (((1 \times 6)^6) - 11)) \\ 1166325 &:= -(((5^2) \times (3 - (((6^6) + 1) - 1)))) \\ 1166355 &:= -((5 \times ((5 \times (3 - ((6^6) + 1))) - 1))) \\ 1166374 &:= (((4 \times 7) - 3) \times ((6^6) - 1)) - 1) \\ 1166395 &:= (5 \times (((9 - 3)^6) \times (6 - 1)) - 1) \\ 1166425 &:= ((5^{-2+4}) \times (((6^6) + 1) \times 1)) \\ 1166525 &:= ((5^2) \times (5 + (((6^6) + 1) - 1))) \\ 1166555 &:= (5 \times ((5 \times (5 + ((6^6) + 1))) + 1)) \\ 1171853 &:= ((3 \times (((5^8) - 1) - 7)) + (1 + 1)) \\ 1171875 &:= ((5^7) \times (((8 - 1) + 7) \times 1) + 1) \\ 1179644 &:= (4 \times (((4^6) \times 9) \times (7 + 1)) - 1) \\ 1179648 &:= (8 \times (((4 \times 6) \times (9 + 7))^{1+1})) \\ 1185408 &:= (((80 + 4)^{-5+8}) \times (1 + 1)) \\ 1185921 &:= (-1 + 29 + 5)^{8/(1+1)} \\ 1187652 &:= ((2 + (5^6)) \times ((78 - 1) - 1)) \\ 1192463 &:= (((364^2) \times 9) - 1) \times 1) \\ 1193857 &:= (((-((7 - 58))^3) \times 9) - (1 + 1)) \\ 1194832 &:= (2 \times (((3^8) + 4) \times 91) + 1) \\ 1225043 &:= (((3 \times (40 - 5)) + 2)^{2+1}) \\ 1229312 &:= (2 \times ((1 + (3 \times 9))^{2+2 \times 1})) \\ 1229328 &:= (8 \times (2 + ((392^2) \times 1))) \\ 1229368 &:= (8 \times (6 + ((392^2) + 1))) \\ 1229474 &:= (((4 \times 7)^4) + (9^2)) \times (2 \times 1) \\ 1235277 &:= (((((7^7) - 25) \times 3)/2) \times 1) \\ 1235377 &:= (((7^7) \times 3) + (5^3))/(2 \times 1) \\ 1237249 &:= (((9 + 4)^2) \times 7321) \\ 1240113 &:= (((3 \times 1)^{10} + 4) \times 21) \\ 1243225 &:= ((5 \times 223)^{4-2 \times 1}) \\ 1245184 &:= ((4^8) \times (((1 \times 5) + 4) \times 2) + 1) \\ 1249375 &:= (((5^7) - 39) \times (4^2)) - 1) \\ 1254144 &:= ((4^4) \times (((14 \times 5)^2) - 1)) \\ 1254399 &:= (((99 - 3) + (4^5))^2) - 1) \\ 1257728 &:= ((8/2) \times (-((7 - 75)^{2+1})) \\ 1257744 &:= (-4) \times (-4) - (-((7 - 75)^{2+1})) \\ 1259328 &:= ((8^2) \times (((3^9) - 5) - 2) + 1) \\ 1259711 &:= (((117 - 9)^{5-2}) - 1) \\ 1259712 &:= ((2^{-1+7}) \times ((9^5)/(2 + 1))) \\ 1265382 &:= -(((2 - 83) \times (((5^6) - 2) - 1))) \\ 1265399 &:= -(((9 \times ((9 \times (3 - (5^6)))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 1265472 &:= ((2 + 7) \times (-((4 - 56)^{2+1})) \\ 1265664 &:= -(((4^6) \times (6 - (5 \times (62 + 1)))) \\ 1265786 &:= -((((6 - 87) \times ((5^6) + 2)) + 1)) \\ 1265788 &:= (((88 - 7) \times ((5^6) + 2)) + 1) \\ 1272368 &:= (((86^3) + (2^7)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 1272383 &:= (3 \times (-8 + 3 \times 2^7))^2 - 1) \\ 1274641 &:= ((1 + ((4 \times 6) \times 47))^2 \times 1) \\ 1276899 &:= (-9 + (9 + 8) \times 67)^2 - 1) \\ 1277408 &:= ((80 - 4) \times ((7^7-2) + 1)) \\ 1277952 &:= ((2^{5+9}) \times ((7 + 72) - 1)) \\ 1279365 &:= -((5 \times (6 - ((3^9) \times ((7 \times 2) - 1)))) \\ 1279394 &:= (((4 + 9) \times (3^9)) \times (7 - 2)) - 1) \\ 1279395 &:= ((5 \times ((9/3)^9)) \times ((7 \times 2) - 1)) \\ 1288411 &:= (((11^4) \times 88) + 2) + 1) \\ 1288429 &:= (((9 + 2)^4) \times 88) + 21) \\ 1294139 &:= (((9 + 3) - 1) \times (49^{2+1})) \\ 1295029 &:= ((9 + (20 \times 5))^{9/(2+1)}) \\ 1299375 &:= ((5^{7-3}) \times (99 \times 21)) \\ 1310725 &:= (5 \times ((2^{(7-01) \times 3}) + 1)) \\ 1325424 &:= (424 \times ((5^{2+3}) + 1)) \\ 1327757 &:= (((7^5) \times (7 + 72)) + (3 + 1)) \\ 1328319 &:= (9 \times (-1 + 3 \times 8))^2 \times 31) \\ 1328465 &:= (((5^6) + 4) \times ((82 + 3) \times 1)) \\ 1336243 &:= ((34^{-2+6}) - ((3 \times 31))) \\ 1336336 &:= (((6 \times (3 + 3)) - (6/3))^{3+1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1337472 &:= (((2^7) + (4^7)) \times (3^{3+1})) \\
 1338649 &:= (((9 + 4) \times (6 + 83))^{3-1}) \\
 1342374 &:= ((473^2) \times ((4 + 3) - 1)) \\
 1343488 &:= -(((8 \times (8^4)) \times ((3 - 43) - 1))) \\
 1344557 &:= ((((((7^5) \times 5) \times 4) \times 4) - 3) \times 1) \\
 1344575 &:= (5 \times (((((7^5) \times 4) \times 4) + 3) \times 1)) \\
 1344896 &:= (((6^9)/8) + ((44^3) \times 1)) \\
 1346875 &:= ((5^{7-8+6}) \times 431) \\
 1348237 &:= ((73^2) \times ((84 \times 3) + 1)) \\
 1353594 &:= (((4^9) \times 5) + ((35^3) - 1)) \\
 1358196 &:= (69 \times (((1 + 8)^5)/3) + 1)) \\
 1361367 &:= (7 \times (((6 - 3) \times (1 + 6))^{3+1})) \\
 1362942 &:= (2 \times ((-((4 - 92))^{6-3}) - 1)) \\
 1364769 &:= (9 \times ((6 + (7^4)) \times (63 \times 1))) \\
 1367185 &:= ((((((5^8) - 1) \times 7)/6) \times 3) + 1) \\
 1367631 &:= (-(((1 - 36) - 76))^3 \times 1) \\
 1369598 &:= (((((8 \times 9) + 5)^{9-6}) \times 3) - 1) \\
 1371249 &:= ((9^4) \times ((21 \times (7 + 3)) - 1)) \\
 1372104 &:= (4012 \times ((7^3) - 1)) \\
 1372567 &:= ((((((7^6) \times 5) - 2) \times 7)/3) \times 1) \\
 1372575 &:= (((5 \times (7^{5+2})) + 7)/3) + 1) \\
 1372585 &:= (5 \times ((8 + ((5 + 2)^7))/(3 \times 1))) \\
 1375896 &:= -((6 \times (((9 - (8^5)) \times 7) - (3 \times 1)))) \\
 1376244 &:= -(((4 - ((4^{2+6}) \times 7)) \times (3 \times 1))) \\
 1376248 &:= -((8 - ((4^{2+6}) \times ((7 \times 3) \times 1))) \\
 1376588 &:= (((8 + (8^5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - (3 + 1)) \\
 1378539 &:= ((9^3) \times ((5 + (8 \times 7)) \times 31)) \\
 1382399 &:= (-9 + 9^3)^2 \times 8/3 - 1 \\
 1382927 &:= (7 \times (2 + (9 \times ((28^3) - 1)))) \\
 1382947 &:= -(((7 \times (4 - (9 \times (28^3)))) + 1)) \\
 1382973 &:= -((3 - ((7 \times 9) \times ((28^3) \times 1))) \\
 1384448 &:= ((8^4) \times (((4^4) + 83) - 1)) \\
 1396555 &:= -(((5^5) - (5 \times (6^{9-3+1}))) \\
 1397493 &:= ((3^9) \times (4 + (((7 \times 9) + 3) + 1))) \\
 1399655 &:= -((5 \times (5 - (6^{(9+9)/3+1}))) \\
 1399665 &:= (5 \times ((6^{6+9/9}) - (3 \times 1))) \\
 1399676 &:= ((6^7) + (((6^9)/9) - 3) - 1)) \\
 1399685 &:= (5 \times (((8 \times 6) \times ((9 + 9)^3)) + 1)) \\
 1399765 &:= ((5 \times (6^7)) + (((9 \times 9) + 3) + 1)) \\
 1404928 &:= ((8 \times ((2 \times 9) - 4))^{04-1}) \\
 1405536 &:= 6 \times (-3 + 5 \times 5)^{04} \times 1 \\
 1411773 &:= (3 \times (((7^{7-1}) - 1) \times 4) - 1)) \\
 1416959 &:= ((((((9^5) - 9) \times 6) \times 1) \times 4) - 1) \\
 1417496 &:= ((((((6 + 9)^4) \times 7) - 1) \times 4) \times 1) \\
 1419837 &:= -(((7 \times 3) - ((8 + 9)^{1+4}) + 1))) \\
 1419842 &:= -(((2^4) - (((8 + 9)^{1+4}) + 1))) \\
 1419846 &:= -6 - 4 + (8 + 9)^{1+4} - 1 \\
 1419847 &:= -7 - 4 + (8 + 9)^{1+4} + 1 \\
 1419851 &:= -(((1 \times 5) - (((8 + 9)^{1+4}) - 1))) \\
 1419855 &:= -(((5/5) - (((8 + 9)^{1+4}) - 1))) \\
 1419856 &:= ((((((6 - 5) \times 8) + 9)^{1+4}) - 1) \\
 1419857 &:= (((((7 \times 5) - 8) - 9) - 1)^{4+1}) \\
 1419861 &:= -(((1 - 6) - (((8 + 9)^{1+4}) - 1))) \\
 1419862 &:= -(((2 - 6) - (((8 + 9)^{1+4}) + 1))) \\
 1419872 &:= ((2 \times 7) + (((8 + 9)^{1+4}) + 1)) \\
 1419894 &:= ((4 \times 9) + (((8 + 9)^{1+4}) + 1)) \\
 1428846 &:= (6 \times (((488^2) - 4) + 1)) \\
 1431643 &:= ((((((3 \times 4) \times 6) - 1)^3) \times 4) - 1) \\
 1431765 &:= (((5 \times 6) + (71^3)) \times 4) + 1) \\
 1431772 &:= ((2^7) + (((71^3) \times 4) \times 1)) \\
 1434631 &:= -(((1 - (((3 \times 6)^4)/3)) \times 41)) \\
 1434666 &:= -((6 - (((6^6)/4) \times 3) \times 41))) \\
 1434672 &:= ((2 + 7) \times (((6^4) \times 3) \times 41)) \\
 1437465 &:= (5 \times (((6 \times (4 + 7))^3) - (4 - 1))) \\
 1439665 &:= -((5 + ((6 - (6^9))/(3 + 4) \times 1)))) \\
 1439671 &:= (((1^7) + (6^9))/(3 + 4) \times 1)) \\
 1441197 &:= (((7^{9-1}) - 1)/4) - (4 - 1)) \\
 1441792 &:= ((2^{9+7-1}) \times (44 \times 1)) \\
 1442488 &:= (8 \times (((8^4) + 2) \times 44) - 1)) \\
 1442897 &:= (((7 + 98) + (2 \times 4))^{4-1}) \\
 1446336 &:= -(((6^{3+3}) \times ((6 + 4) - 41))) \\
 1449459 &:= (9 \times (-(((5 - 49)/4))^{4+1})) \\
 1459838 &:= -((8 - (38 \times (((9 + 5)^4) + 1)))) \\
 1459846 &:= ((6 + (4 \times 8)) \times (((9 + 5)^4) + 1)) \\
 1468481 &:= (((18^4) + (8^6)) \times 4) + 1) \\
 1471888 &:= -((88 \times (81 - (7^{4+1})))) \\
 1473335 &:= ((5 + ((33^3) - 7)) \times 41) \\
 1473704 &:= (((40 - 7)^3) + 7) \times 41)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1474109 &:= -((90 \times (1 - ((4^7) - 4))) + 1)) \\
 1474199 &:= (((9 \times (9 + 1)) \times ((4^7) - 4)) - 1) \\
 1474536 &:= (6 \times (((3 \times 5) \times (4^7)) - (4 \times 1))) \\
 1474635 &:= ((5 \times 3) \times ((6 \times (4^7)) + (4 + 1))) \\
 1474695 &:= (5 \times ((9 + (6 \times (4^7)))) \times (4 - 1)) \\
 1474919 &:= (((9 + 1) \times 9) \times ((4^7) + 4)) - 1) \\
 1474925 &:= (5 \times (((2 \times 9) \times ((4^7) + 4)) + 1)) \\
 1475925 &:= ((5^2) \times (((9^5) - 7) - 4) - 1)) \\
 1475955 &:= (5 \times ((5 \times (((9^5) - 7) - 4)) + 1)) \\
 1476734 &:= ((4 + (3^7)) \times (674 \times 1)) \\
 1478575 &:= -((((5 - 7^5)) \times 8) \times (7 + 4)) + 1)) \\
 1479808 &:= ((80 + 8) \times (9 + (7^{4+1}))) \\
 1482752 &:= ((2 + (5 \times 72)) \times ((8^4) \times 1)) \\
 1483524 &:= ((42^{5-3}) \times 841) \\
 1484375 &:= ((5^7) \times (((3 + 4) + 8) + 4) \times 1)) \\
 1485139 &:= ((((((9 + 3) + 1)^5) - 8) \times 4) - 1) \\
 1485141 &:= ((((((14 - 1)^5) - 8) \times 4) + 1) \\
 1485172 &:= (((2 \times 7) - 1)^5) \times ((8 - 4) \times 1)) \\
 1485344 &:= (4 \times (43 + ((5 + 8)^{4+1}))) \\
 1486485 &:= -(((5 - (8 \times 46)) \times ((8^4) - 1))) \\
 1492263 &:= -(((3^6) \times (2 - (((2^9) \times 4) + 1)))) \\
 1492864 &:= ((4 - (6^{8-2})) \times (9 - 41)) \\
 1493027 &:= (((72^{03}) + 9) \times 4) - 1) \\
 1495867 &:= ((76 \times ((8 - 5)^9)) - 41) \\
 1500625 &:= (-5^2 + 60)^{05-1} \\
 1503769 &:= (((9 - (67^3)) \times (0 - 5)) - 1) \\
 1518742 &:= -((2 \times (4 - (((7 + 8) \times 1)^5) \times 1)))) \\
 1518748 &:= ((8/4) \times (((7 + 8) \times 1)^5) - 1)) \\
 1518752 &:= (2 \times ((-(((5 - 7) \times 8) + 1))^5) + 1)) \\
 1518756 &:= (-6) \times ((-5) \times ((7 + 8)^{-1+5})) - 1)) \\
 1518762 &:= (2 \times (6 + (((7 + 8) \times 1)^5) \times 1)) \\
 1527696 &:= (((6 \times (96 + 7))^2) \times (5 - 1)) \\
 1532645 &:= (((((5^4) - 6) \times 2)^{-3+5}) + 1) \\
 1535883 &:= (3 \times ((8 \times (((8 \times 5)^3) - 5)) + 1)) \\
 1536153 &:= (3 \times (((5 \times 16)^3) + 51)) \\
 1541835 &:= ((5 \times (3^8)) \times ((1 + 45) + 1)) \\
 1548288 &:= (((8^{8-2}) - (8^4)) \times (5 + 1)) \\
 1548384 &:= (-4 + 8^3)^{8/4} \times (5 + 1) \\
 1555848 &:= (8 \times ((4 + (85/5))^{5-1}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1560447 &:= (((7^4) - 4) \times 0651) \\
 1562452 &:= (((25^4) - (2 \times 6)) \times (5 - 1)) \\
 1562492 &:= -(((2 - ((9 - 4)^{2+6})) \times (5 - 1))) \\
 1562494 &:= ((4 \times ((9 - 4)^{2+6})) - (5 + 1)) \\
 1562495 &:= -((5 - (((9 - 4)^{2+6}) \times (5 - 1)))) \\
 1562512 &:= (2 + 1 + 5^{2+6}) \times (5 - 1) \\
 1562524 &:= (4 + 2 + 5^{2+6}) \times (5 - 1) \\
 1562525 &:= 5^2 + 5^{2+6} \times (5 - 1) \\
 1562532 &:= (2^3 + 5^{2+6}) \times (5 - 1) \\
 1562536 &:= (6 + 3 + 5^{2+6}) \times (5 - 1) \\
 1562548 &:= (8 + 4 + 5^{2+6}) \times (5 - 1) \\
 1562551 &:= -((((1 - 5) \times (5^{2+6})) - 51)) \\
 1562755 &:= -((5 \times (((5^7) \times (2 - 6)) - 51))) \\
 1562775 &:= ((5 + ((7 + 7)^2)) \times ((6^5) - 1)) \\
 1562976 &:= (((67 \times 9) \times 2) \times (6^{5-1})) \\
 1566957 &:= (((7^{-5+9}) + (6)) \times 651) \\
 1572594 &:= (((4^9) - 52) + 7) \times (5 + 1)) \\
 1572732 &:= (((237^2) \times 7) \times (5 - 1)) \\
 1572768 &:= (((((8^6) - 7) - 2) - 7) \times (5 + 1)) \\
 1572822 &:= (((2^{2 \times 8+2}) - 7) \times (5 + 1)) \\
 1572841 &:= -((((1 - (4^8)) \times 2) \times (7 + 5)) - 1)) \\
 1572862 &:= -((2 - (6 \times ((8^2)^{7-5+1}))) \\
 1572863 &:= ((3 \times (-((6 - 8)^{2 \times 7+5})) - 1) \\
 1572864 &:= ((4^{6+8+2-7}) \times (5 + 1)) \\
 1572868 &:= -((((8^6) \times (8 - (2 \times 7))) - (5 - 1))) \\
 1572869 &:= ((96 \times ((8/2)^7)) + (5 \times 1)) \\
 1572944 &:= -((4 - (((4^9) + (2 \times 7)) \times (5 + 1)))) \\
 1572947 &:= (((7 + ((4^9)/2)) \times (7 + 5)) - 1) \\
 1572948 &:= (((8 - 4)^9) + (2 \times 7)) \times (5 + 1)) \\
 1579854 &:= -((4 - ((5 + 89) \times ((7^5) \times 1)))) \\
 1579857 &:= -((((7^5) \times ((8 - 97) - 5)) + 1)) \\
 1579859 &:= (((95 + 8) - 9) \times (7^5)) + 1) \\
 1579951 &:= -((1 + ((5 - 99) \times ((7^5) + 1)))) \\
 1586375 &:= -((((5 \times 7)^3) \times ((6 + 8) - 51))) \\
 1589976 &:= (((6^7)/9) + (9 \times 8)) \times 51) \\
 1592645 &:= (((((5^4) + 6)^2) \times (9 - 5)) + 1) \\
 1593369 &:= (((9^6) \times 3) - 3) - 951) \\
 1593837 &:= ((73 + 8) \times ((3^9) - 5) - 1)) \\
 1593909 &:= (9 \times ((09 \times ((3^9) - 5)) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 1593918** := $(81 \times (((9/3)^9) - 5) \times 1)$
1593919 := $((((9 \times 1) \times 9) \times ((3^9) - 5)) + 1)$
1593927 := $((7 + 2) \times ((9 \times ((3^9) - 5)) + 1))$
1593972 := $-((27 \times ((9 + 3) - ((9^5) - 1))))$
1593989 := $((9 \times (8 + (9 \times ((3^9) - 5)))) - 1)$
1593999 := $((9 \times 9) \times (((9/3)^9) - 5) + 1)$
1594266 := $-((6 - (((6/2)^{4+9}) - 51)))$
1594272 := $((-(((2 - 7) + 2))^{4+9}) - (51))$
1594293 := $((((3^{9+2}) - 4) \times 9) + (5 + 1))$
1594296 := $((((6 \times 9) \times 2)/4) \times ((9^5) - 1))$
1594309 := $-((9 - ((03^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1))))$
1594311 := $(((1 - 1) - 3) \times (4 - (9^{5+1})))$
1594312 := $((2 - 1) - (3 \times (4 - (9^{5+1}))))$
1594313 := $((((3^{13}) + 4) - 9) - 5) \times 1$
1594314 := $((4 - 1) - (3 \times (4 - (9^{5+1}))))$
1594315 := $((5 - 1) - (3 \times (4 - (9^{5+1}))))$
1594316 := $((6 - 1) - (3 \times (4 - (9^{5+1}))))$
1594317 := $((((7 - 1) - 3)^{4+9}) - (5 + 1))$
1594318 := $((((8 + 1)/3)^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1))$
1594319 := $((((9 \times 1)/3)^{4+9}) - (5 - 1))$
1594321 := $((1 \times 2) + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 - 1)))$
1594322 := $((2 + 2) + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594323 := $3^{2^3/4 \times 9 - 5 \times 1}$
1594324 := $((4 + 2) + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594325 := $((5 + 2) + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594326 := $((6 + 2) + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594327 := $((((7 + 2)/3)^{4+9}) + (5 - 1))$
1594328 := $((((8 - 2) - 3)^{4+9}) + (5 \times 1))$
1594329 := $((((9 - (2 \times 3))^{4+9}) + (5 + 1))$
1594341 := $(14 + ((3^{4+9}) + (5 - 1)))$
1594342 := $(24 + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594344 := $((4 \times 4) + ((3^{4+9}) + (5 \times 1)))$
1594347 := $((7 \times 4) + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 - 1)))$
1594352 := $(25 + ((3^{4+9}) + (5 - 1)))$
1594353 := $(35 + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594354 := $-(((4 \times 5) - ((3^{4+9}) + 51)))$
1594358 := $((8 \times 5) + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594359 := $-((9 \times (5 - (3 \times (4 + ((9^5) - 1))))))$
1594362 := $-((2 \times 6) - ((3^{4+9}) + 51))$
1594363 := $(36 + ((3^{4+9}) + (5 - 1)))$
1594364 := $(46 + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594365 := $((5 \times 6) + (3 \times (4 + (9^{5+1}))))$
1594367 := $-((7 - (((6 - 3)^{4+9}) + 51)))$
1594369 := $((((9^6) \times 3) + 4) - 9) + 51$
1594374 := $(47 + ((3^{4+9}) + (5 - 1)))$
1594375 := $(57 + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594377 := $((7 \times 7) + ((3^{4+9}) + (5 \times 1)))$
1594379 := $((((9^7)/3) - 4) + 9) + 51$
1594381 := $-(((1 - 8) - ((3^{4+9}) + 51)))$
1594383 := $(3 \times (((8 \times 3) - 4) + (9^{5+1})))$
1594385 := $(58 + ((3^{4+9}) + (5 - 1)))$
1594386 := $(68 + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594389 := $((9 \times 8) + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 + 1)))$
1594392 := $((2 \times 9) + ((3^{4+9}) + 51))$
1594396 := $(69 + ((3^{4+9}) + (5 - 1)))$
1594397 := $(79 + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594399 := $((9 \times 9) + ((3^{4+9}) - (5 \times 1)))$
1594432 := $(((23 + 4) \times (4 + (9^5))) + 1)$
1594443 := $(3 \times ((44 - 4) + (9^{5+1})))$
1594539 := $((9 \times 3) \times ((5 + 4) + ((9^5) - 1)))$
1594593 := $((3 \times 9) \times ((5 + 4) + ((9^5) + 1)))$
1594729 := $(((9^2) \times (((7 - 4)^9) + 5)) + 1)$
1595283 := $(3 \times (((8^2) \times 5) + (9^{5+1})))$
1595534 := $-((4 - ((3^5) \times (5 + (9^{5-1}))))))$
1595759 := $((95 \times ((7^5) - 9)) - 51)$
1595791 := $(19 \times (((7^5) - 9) \times 5) - 1)$
1601494 := $(((4 \times (9^4)) + 10) \times 61)$
1605877 := $((7 \times 7) \times (((8^5) + 06) - 1))$
1622388 := $((((8 + (8^3))^2) - 2) \times (6 \times 1))$
1625523 := $(3 + (-2 + 5^5)^2)/6 + 1$
1627595 := $((((5^9) \times 5) - (7^2))/6) - 1$
1632925 := $-(((5 \times (2 - 9)) \times (((2 \times 3)^6) - 1)))$
1633689 := $((9 \times (86 - 3)) \times (3^{6+1}))$
1638405 := $((50 \times ((4 \times 8)^3)) + (6 - 1))$
1638415 := $(((5 \times ((1 \times 4)^8)) + 3) \times (6 - 1))$
1638425 := $-((5 \times ((2 - ((4^8) + 3)) \times (6 - 1))))$
1646977 := $-((((7^7) - (9 \times 6)) \times (4 - 6)) + 1))$
1646994 := $((4 \times 99) + 6) \times ((4^6) + 1)$

- 1647072** := $((2 \times ((7^{07}) - 4)) - (6 \times 1))$
1647075 := $((5 - (7^{07})) \times (4 - 6)) - 1$
1647078 := $-((8 + ((7^{07}) \times ((4 - 6) \times 1))))$
1647087 := $((7^8)/(0 - 7)) \times (4 - 6) + 1$
1647772 := $(2 \times ((7^7) + ((7^4)/(6 + 1))))$
1648595 := $(5 \times (((9^5) - (8^4)) \times 6) + 1)$
1653344 := $-(((4 - (4 \times ((3 \times 3)^5))) \times (6 + 1)))$
1656249 := $((94 + (2 \times 6)) \times (5^6)) - 1$
1656369 := $(-9 + 6^3 \times 6)^{-5+6+1}$
1671159 := $-((9 - (51 \times ((1 + 7)^{6-1})))$
1673439 := $((9^3) + 4) \times 3 \times 761$
1676269 := $-(((9 \times 62) - (6^7)) \times 6) - 1$
1676543 := $-(((3 \times (4^5)) - (((6^7) \times 6) - 1)))$
1676699 := $-((((9 \times 9) \times 6) - (6^7)) \times 6) + 1$
1677386 := $((6^8) - (3^7)) - ((7 \times 6) + 1)$
1678986 := $((6^8) - ((98 + 7) \times 6) \times 1)$
1679186 := $((6^8) - ((1 + 9) \times ((7 \times 6) + 1)))$
1679386 := $((6^8) - ((3 \times 97) - 61))$
1679486 := $((6^8) - 4) - (9 \times ((7 + 6) + 1))$
1679494 := $((4 \times 9)^4) - ((9 - 7) \times 61)$
1679536 := $((6^{3+5}) - ((9 + 7) \times (6 - 1)))$
1679568 := $-((8 - (6^{5+9-7})) \times (6 \times 1))$
1679585 := $((-5) + (-((8 - 5) - 9)^7)) \times 6 - 1$
1679586 := $((6^8) + ((5 \times 9) - 76) + 1)$
1679608 := $-((8 - (06^{9-7+6} \times 1)))$
1679612 := $-((2 - (((1 + ((6^9) - 7))/6) - 1)))$
1679613 := $-(((31 - ((6^9) + 7))/6) - 1)$
1679614 := $-(((4 + 1) - ((6^9) - 7))/(6 \times 1))$
1679615 := $((5 + (1^6))^{9-7+6}) - 1$
1679616 := $(6^{1697+6+1})$
1679617 := $((7 - (1^6))^{9-7+6}) + 1$
1679621 := $((1 + (-((2 \times (6 - 9))^7))) \times 6) - 1$
1679623 := $((3 \times 2)^{6+9-7}) + (6 + 1)$
1679624 := $((4 \times 2) + (6^{9-7+6} \times 1))$
1679625 := $((5 \times 2) + ((6^{9-7+6}) - 1))$
1679626 := $((6^{2+6}) + (((9 + 7) - 6) \times 1))$
1679633 := $((3 + (((3 - 6) + 9)^7)) \times 6) - 1$
1679637 := $((7 \times 3) + (6^{9-7+6} \times 1))$
1679648 := $((8 \times 4) + (6^{9-7+6} \times 1))$
1679664 := $(4 \times (((((6^6) \times 9) + 7) + 6) - 1))$
1679669 := $((9 \times 6) + ((6^{9-7+6}) - 1))$
1679676 := $(((((6^7) - 6) + 9) + 7) \times 6) \times 1$
1679679 := $((9 \times 7) + (6^{9-7+6} \times 1))$
1679686 := $(((((6^8) + 69) + 7) - 6) \times 1)$
1679689 := $((9 \times 8) + ((6^{9-7+6}) + 1))$
1679696 := $((6^9)/6) + ((9 + 7) \times (6 - 1))$
1679986 := $((6^8) - 9) + ((9 \times 7) \times 6) + 1$
1686183 := $((3^8) + (((1 \times 6)^8) + 6) \times 1)$
1692546 := $((6^4 + 5)^2) - ((9 \times 6) + 1)$
1693168 := $(86 \times (((1 \times 3)^9) + 6) - 1)$
1712392 := $(29 \times ((3^{2+1+7}) - 1))$
1741824 := $((-(4 - (2 \times 8))^{1+4}) \times (7 \times 1))$
1747928 := $((82 + 9) \times (7^4)) \times (7 + 1)$
1753541 := $-((1 - ((4^5) \times 3)) \times 571)$
1755625 := $((5 \times 265)^{-5+7 \times 1})$
1756876 := $-((6 - ((7 \times (8^6)) - ((5^7) + 1))))$
1756877 := $-((7 - ((7 \times (8^6)) - ((5^7) - 1))))$
1763856 := $-(((6^5) - (((8 + 3)^6) + 71)))$
1764735 := $((5 \times 3) \times (7^{4-6+7+1}))$
1766495 := $((5^9) - ((4 \times (6^6)) + (7 - 1)))$
1769472 := $((2 + 7) \times ((4^9) \times 6))/(7 + 1)$
1769508 := $((8^{05}) \times 9) + 6 \times (7 - 1)$
1771489 := $-((9 \times 8) - (((4 \times 1) + 7)^{7-1}))$
1771511 := $((11^{5+1}) - ((7 \times 7) + 1))$
1771547 := $((7 + 4)^{5+1}) - ((7 + 7) \times 1)$
1771553 := $-((3 + 5) - (((5 - 1) + 7)^{7-1}))$
1771555 := $((55/5)^{-1+7}) - (7 - 1)$
1771558 := $-((8 - 5) - (((5 - 1) + 7)^{7-1}))$
1771574 := $((4 + 7)^{5+1}) + ((7 + 7) - 1)$
1771611 := $((11^6) + (((1 \times 7) \times 7) + 1))$
1771632 := $((2 + 3) + 6)^{-1+7} + 71$
1771638 := $((8 + 3)^6) - 1 + 7 + 71$
1773156 := $((6^5) + 1) \times 3 \times (77 - 1)$
1775568 := $-((8 \times ((6 - ((5^5) + 7)) \times 71)))$
1784675 := $-(((5^7) - 6) \times 4) - ((8^7) - 1))$
1796875 := $(5^7) \times (86 - ((9 \times 7) \times 1))$
1796985 := $((-((5 - 8) - 9)^6) - (9^7)) \times (-1)$
1799576 := $(((((6^7) \times 5) - 9) \times 9)/7) - 1$

- 1815157** := $((7^5) \times ((1 + 5) \times 18)) + 1$
1834847 := $(7 \times (((4^8) \times 4) - ((3 \times 8) - 1)))$
1834868 := $((((8^6) - 8) - (4 \times 3)) \times (8 - 1))$
1834959 := $((((9 - 5)^9) - 4) - 3) \times (8 - 1)$
1834994 := $((((4^9) - 9) + 4) + 3) \times (8 - 1)$
1835177 := $(7 \times (((7 + 1)^5) + 3) \times 8) + 1$
1837085 := $(5 \times ((8 \times 07) \times (3^8)) + 1)$
1853564 := $-(((4 \times 6) + 5)^3) \times (5 - 81)$
1856458 := $((((8 + 5)^4) \times 65) - 8) + 1$
1856576 := $((((6 + 7)^5) + 6) \times 5) + 81$
1866045 := $-(5 \times (40 - (((6^6) \times 8) + 1)))$
1866125 := $-(5 \times (((2 + 1) - (6^6)) \times 8) - 1)$
1866165 := $-(5 \times (6 + (((1 - (6^6)) \times 8) + 1)))$
1866168 := $(8 \times (((6 - 1) \times (6^6)) - (8 + 1)))$
1866169 := $-(((9 - ((6 - 1) \times (6^6))) \times 8) - 1)$
1866195 := $(5 \times ((9 - 1) \times (6^6)) - (8 + 1))$
1866225 := $-(5 \times (2 - (((2 \times 6)^6) / 8) - 1))$
1866231 := $-(((1 - ((3 + 2) \times (6^6))) \times 8) + 1)$
1866235 := $(5 \times (((3 \times 2) + 6)^6) / 8) - 1$
1866239 := $(((9 / 3) + 2) \times ((6^6) \times 8)) - 1$
1866241 := $((1 + 4) \times (((2 \times 6)^6) / 8) + 1)$
1866245 := $(5 \times (((4 - 2) \times 6)^6) / 8) + 1$
1866249 := $((9 - 4) \times (2 + ((6^6) \times 8))) - 1$
1866265 := $(5 \times (6 + (((2 \times 6)^6) / 8) - 1))$
1866275 := $(5 \times (7 + (((2 \times 6)^6) / 8) \times 1))$
1866285 := $(5 \times (8 + (((2 \times 6)^6) / 8) + 1))$
1866295 := $(5 \times ((9 + 2) + (((6^6) \times 8) \times 1)))$
1866315 := $-(5 \times (((1 - 3) - (6^6)) \times 8) + 1)$
1866345 := $-(5 \times (4 - (((3 + (6^6)) \times 8) + 1)))$
1866351 := $-(((1 - (5 \times (3 + (6^6)))) \times 8) + 1)$
1866355 := $-(5 - (5 \times ((3 + (6^6)) \times (8 \times 1))))$
1866361 := $-(((1 - 6) \times ((3 + (6^6)) \times 8)) - 1)$
1866365 := $(5 \times (((6 - 3) + (6^6)) \times 8) + 1)$
1866405 := $(5 \times ((04 + (6^6)) \times 8) + 1)$
1866457 := $((7 + (5 \times (4 + (6^6)))) \times 8) + 1$
1866485 := $-(5 \times ((8 \times (4 - (6^6))) - 81))$
1866525 := $(5 \times (((2 + 5) + (6^6)) \times 8) + 1)$
1866559 := $(((9 \times 5) - 5) \times ((6^6) + 8)) - 1$
1866565 := $(5 \times (65 + (((6^6) \times 8) \times 1)))$
1866568 := $(8 \times (6 + (5 \times (((6^6) + 8) - 1))))$
1866576 := $((((6 \times 7) + (5 \times (6^6))) \times (8 \times 1)))$
1866645 := $(5 \times (((4 + ((6^6) + 6)) \times 8) + 1))$
1866765 := $(5 \times (((6 + 7) + (6^6)) \times 8) + 1)$
1866885 := $(5 \times (((8 + 8) + (6^6)) \times 8) + 1)$
1869893 := $((3^9) \times (89 + 6)) + (8 \times 1)$
1874073 := $((37^{04}) - 7) - 81$
1874163 := $((((36 + 1)^4) - 7) + 8) + 1$
1874235 := $((((5 + 32)^4) - 7) + 81)$
1874473 := $(37^4) + ((4 \times 78) \times 1)$
1874946 := $(6 \times ((4 \times ((9 - 4)^7)) - (8 + 1)))$
1874964 := $(4 \times ((6 \times ((9 - 4)^7)) - (8 + 1)))$
1875003 := $(3 \times (((005^7) \times 8) + 1))$
1875153 := $(3 \times (51 + (((5^7) \times 8) \times 1)))$
1875164 := $-((4 \times ((6 \times (1 - ((5^7) + 8)))) + 1))$
1875181 := $(-1 + 8)^{-1+5} \times 781$
1875193 := $((3 \times (9 - 1)) \times ((5^7) + 8)) + 1$
1875243 := $(3 \times (((4 \times 2) \times (5^7)) + 81))$
1875246 := $(6 \times ((4 \times (2 + ((5^7) + 8))) + 1))$
1875264 := $((4 \times 6) \times (2 + (((5^7) + 8) + 1)))$
1875313 := $(3 \times ((13 + (5^7)) \times 8)) + 1$
1875324 := $(4 \times (((2 \times 3) \times (5^7)) + 81))$
1875359 := $((((9 \times 5) + (3 \times (5^7))) \times 8) - 1)$
1875384 := $((48 + (3 \times (5^7))) \times (8 \times 1))$
1875456 := $-(6 \times (5 - ((4 \times (5^7)) + 81)))$
1875486 := $(6 \times (((8 - 4) \times (5^7)) + 81))$
1875623 := $((3 \times ((26 + (5^7)) \times 8)) - 1)$
1875933 := $(3 \times (((39 + (5^7)) \times 8) - 1))$
1881567 := $((((7^6) - 51) \times (8 + 8)) - 1)$
1882367 := $((((7^6) + 3) \times 2) - 8) \times 8 - 1$
1882377 := $((((7 \times 7)^3) \times 2) \times 8) - 8 + 1$
1889481 := $((18^{-4+9}) - ((88 - 1)))$
1889559 := $-(((9^5) \times ((5 - 9) \times 8)) + (8 + 1))$
1889592 := $((((2 \times 9)^5) + 9) + 8) + 8 - 1$
1896448 := $((8^4) \times (((4 + (6 \times 9)) \times 8) - 1))$
1920358 := $-(((8^5) - ((3 + 02)^9) + 1))$
1922373 := $((3^7) \times 3) \times (2 + 291)$
1927525 := $((5^2) \times ((5^7) - (2^{9+1})))$
1932645 := $-(((5 \times (4^6)) - (((2 + 3)^9) \times 1)))$

- 1935495** := $((5 \times (9^4)) \times ((5 \times (3 + 9)) - 1))$
1938483 := $-(((3 + 8)^4) - (((8 - 3)^9) - 1)))$
1939678 := $((8^7) - (((6 \times 9)^3) + 9) + 1))$
1939688 := $(8 \times ((8^6) - (((9/3)^9) \times 1)))$
1943964 := $((((4 \times (6 + 9))^3) - 4) \times (9 \times 1))$
1946595 := $((5^9) - (5 \times (((6^4) + 9) + 1)))$
1948938 := $((8 - 3)^9) - ((8^4) + 91))$
1950525 := $-((52 \times 50) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1950964 := $-(((4 \times 6) \times 90) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1951263 := $-((3 \times 621) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1951485 := $-(((5 \times 8) \times 41) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1951828 := $-(((8 \times 2) \times 81) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1951972 := $-(((2^7) \times 9) - (((1 \times 5)^9) - 1))$
1952045 := $-((540 \times 2) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952125 := $-(((5 \times 2)^{1+2}) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952165 := $-((((5 \times 6) + 1)^2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952285 := $-((((58/2)^2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952299 := $-(((9 \times 92) - 2) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952325 := $-(((5^2) \times 32) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952363 := $-(((3^6) + 32) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952392 := $-((2 + ((9^3) + 2)) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952393 := $-(((3^{9-3}) + 2) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952394 := $-((4 + ((9^3) - 2)) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952395 := $((5^9) - ((3^{2-5+9}) + 1))$
1952396 := $((-((6 - 9))^{3 \times 2}) - ((5^9))) \times (-1))$
1952398 := $-((8 \times (93 - 2)) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952399 := $-(((9^{9/3}) - 2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952415 := $-((5 \times 142) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952439 := $-(((9^3) - 42) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952468 := $-((8 + ((6^4)/2)) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952469 := $-((9 + ((6^4)/2)) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952485 := $-(((5 \times 8) \times (4^2)) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952495 := $((5^9) - (42 \times ((5 + 9) + 1)))$
1952496 := $-(((6 + 9) \times 42) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952516 := $-(((61 \times 5) \times 2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952526 := $-((6 \times ((2 \times 5)^2)) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952549 := $-((9 \times (4^{5-2})) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952565 := $-(((56 \times 5) \times 2) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952612 := $-((2 \times (16^2)) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952628 := $-(((8 \times ((2^6) - 2)) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952642 := $-((((2^4) + 6)^2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952657 := $-((7 \times (5 + 62)) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952658 := $-(((8 + 5) \times (6^2)) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952667 := $-(((76 \times 6) + 2) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952678 := $-(((8 \times 7) \times (6 + 2)) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952685 := $-((5 \times (86 + 2)) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952692 := $((2 - 9) \times 62) + ((5^9) + 1))$
1952693 := $-(((3 + 9) \times (6^2)) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952694 := $-((((4 \times 9) \times 6) \times 2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952706 := $-(((60 \times 7) - 2) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952724 := $-(((4 \times (2 - 7))^2) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952726 := $-(((6 + (2 \times 7))^2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952732 := $-(((2^3) \times (7^2)) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952745 := $-(((54 \times 7) + 2) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952748 := $-(((8 \times 47) + 2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952757 := $-((7 + (5 \times 72)) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952758 := $-((8 + (5 \times 72)) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952762 := $-(((26 \times 7) \times 2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952763 := $-(((3^6) - 7)/2) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952771 := $-((177 \times 2) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952776 := $-((6 + ((7 \times 7^2)) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952781 := $((1 - 8) \times (7^2)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1952783 := $-((38 \times (7 + 2)) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952784 := $-((4 \times (87 - 2)) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952786 := $-((((6 \times 8) \times 7) + 2) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952795 := $((5^9) - ((7 \times (2 + (5 \times 9))) + 1))$
1952804 := $-(((40 \times 8) + 2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952805 := $((5 \times (0 - (8^2))) + ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952816 := $-((618/2) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952836 := $-(((6 \times 3) \times 8) \times 2) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952837 := $-(((7 - (3 \times 8))^2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952838 := $-((8 \times (38 - 2)) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952854 := $-((45 \times (8 - 2)) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952868 := $-(((8 - 6)^8) + 2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952885 := $-(((5 \times 8) \times (8 - 2)) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1952892 := $-(((29 \times 8) + 2) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1952899 := $-((9 \times (9 + (8 \times 2))) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1952937 := $-(((7 \times 3) \times 9) - 2) - ((5^9) - 1))$

1952939 := -(((93 + 92) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952942 := (((2 - 4) × 92) + ((5⁹) + 1))
1952946 := -((((6 + 4) × 9) × 2) - ((5⁹) + 1)))
1952948 := -(((84 + 92) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952949 := -(((94 + (9²)) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952952 := ((2 × (5 - 92)) + ((5⁹) + 1))
1952953 := -(((3 × (59 - 2)) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952954 := -(((4 × ((5 × 9) - 2)) - ((5⁹) + 1)))
1952956 := -(((6 × ((5 + 9) × 2)) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952957 := -(((75 + 92) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952958 := -(((85 + (9²)) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952963 := -((((36 × 9)/2) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1952964 := (((4 - 6) × (9²)) + ((5⁹) + 1))
1952966 := -(((66 + 92) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952967 := -(((76 + (9²)) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952969 := -((((9 + 69) × 2) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1952971 := -((((17 × 9) + 2) - ((5⁹) + 1)))
1952972 := (((2 - 79) × 2) + ((5⁹) + 1))
1952973 := (((3 - 79) × 2) + ((5⁹) × 1))
1952974 := (((4 - 79) × 2) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1952975 := -(((57 + 92) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952976 := -(((67 + (9²)) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952978 := -((((8 × 7) + 92) - ((5⁹) + 1)))
1952979 := -((((9 + 7) × 9) + 2) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1952991 := -(((19 × (9 - 2)) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952993 := -(((39 + 92) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952994 := -(((49 + (9²)) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952995 := ((5⁹) - ((9 × 2) - 5) × (9 + 1))
1952997 := -((((7 × (9 + 9)) + 2) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1952998 := -((((8 × 9) - 9) × 2) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1952999 := -((((9 + 9) × (9 - 2)) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1953004 := ((40 × (0 - 3)) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1953011 := -(((110 + 3) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1953016 := -(((6 + 103) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1953029 := -(((92 + 03) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1953031 := -((((1 + 30) × 3) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1953032 := -(((2 + (30 × 3)) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1953033 := -((((3 × 30) + 3) - ((5⁹) + 1)))
1953038 := -(((83 + 03) - ((5⁹) - 1)))

1953042 := -((((2 × 40) + 3) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1953043 := -((((3⁴) - (((0 × 3) + 5)⁹) - 1)))
1953046 := -((((6 × 40)/3) - ((5⁹) + 1)))
1953047 := -(((74 + 03) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1953056 := -(((65 + 03) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1953061 := -((((1 + 60) + 3) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1953062 := -(((2⁶) - (((0 × 3) + 5)⁹) + 1))
1953064 := -((((4 + 60) - 3) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1953065 := ((5⁶⁺⁰³) - (59 + 1))
1953069 := -(((9 × 6) + 03) - ((5⁹) + 1))
1953074 := -(((47 + 03) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1953075 := -(((5 × (7 + 03)) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1953077 := -(((7 × 7) - (((0 × 3) + 5)⁹) + 1))
1953083 := -(((38 + 03) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1953085 := (((5 + 8) × (0 - 3)) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1953092 := (((2 + 9) × (0 - 3)) + ((5⁹) × 1))
1953093 := -((((3 + 90)/3) - ((5⁹) - 1)))
1953094 := -(((4 + (9 × 03)) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1953095 := -(((5 × (9 - 03)) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1953096 := (((6 - 90)/3) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1953099 := (((9 - 90)/3) + ((5⁹) + 1))
1953102 := -((((20 × 1) + 3) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1953104 := ((40/(1 - 3)) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1953105 := ((5 × ((0 - 1) - 3)) + ((5⁹) × 1))
1953106 := ((6 × ((0 × 1) - 3)) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1953107 := -((((7 - 01) × 3) - ((5⁹) × 1)))
1953108 := ((8 × (01 - 3)) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1953111 := (((1 - 1) - 13) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1953112 := (((2 - 1) - 13) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1953113 := (((3 - 1) - 13) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1953114 := ((4 × ((1 - 1) - 3)) + ((5⁹) + 1))
1953115 := ((5 × ((1 × 1) - 3)) + ((5⁹) × 1))
1953116 := (((6 - 1) × (1 - 3)) + ((5⁹) + 1))
1953117 := (((7 - 1) - 13) + ((5⁹) - 1))
1953118 := ((8 × ((1 + 1) - 3)) + ((5⁹) + 1))
1953119 := (((9 - 11) × 3) + ((5⁹) × 1))
1953141 := (((1 × 4) + 1) × 3) + ((5⁹) + 1))
1953142 := ((2⁴) + (((1³) × 5)⁹) + 1))
1953143 := (((3 + 4) - 1) × 3) + ((5⁹) × 1))

$$\begin{aligned} 1953144 &:= (((4 \times 4) - 1) + 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953145 &:= ((5 \times 4) + (((1^3) \times 5)^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953146 &:= (((6 \times 4) - 1) - 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953147 &:= ((7 + ((4 + 1) \times 3)) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953148 &:= ((8 + ((4 + 1) \times 3)) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953149 &:= ((9 \times 4) - 13) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953152 &:= ((25 + (1^3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953153 &:= (((3 + 5) + 1) \times 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953154 &:= ((4 \times ((5 - 1) + 3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953155 &:= (((5 \times 5) + 1) + 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953156 &:= ((6 \times 5) + (((1^3) \times 5)^9) + 1)) \\ 1953157 &:= (((7 \times 5) \times 1) - 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953158 &:= ((8 \times (5 - (1^3))) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953159 &:= (((9 \times (5 - 1)) - 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953162 &:= (((2 \times 6) \times 1) \times 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953163 &:= (((36 - 1) + 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953164 &:= ((4 \times ((6 + 1) + 3)) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953165 &:= ((5 \times ((6 - 1) + 3)) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953166 &:= (((6 \times 6) + 1) + 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953167 &:= ((7 \times 6) + (((1^3) \times 5)^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953168 &:= (((8 + 6) \times 1) \times 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953169 &:= (((9 + 6) \times 1) \times 3) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953172 &:= ((2 \times ((7 + 1) \times 3)) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953174 &:= ((47 + (1^3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953175 &:= ((5 \times ((7 \times 1) + 3)) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953176 &:= (((6 \times (7 + 1)) + 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953177 &:= (((7 \times 7) - 1) + 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953178 &:= (((8 \times 7) - 1) - 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953179 &:= ((9 \times (7 - (1^3))) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953181 &:= (((18 + 1) \times 3) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953182 &:= -(((28 \times (1 - 3)) - ((5^9) + 1))) \\ 1953185 &:= ((58 + (1^3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953186 &:= ((6 \times ((8 - 1) + 3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953187 &:= ((7 \times (8 + (1^3))) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953188 &:= ((8 \times 8) + (((1^3) \times 5)^9) - 1)) \\ 1953189 &:= ((9 \times (8 - (1^3))) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953195 &:= (((5^9) - 1) + (((3 + 5) \times 9) - 1)) \\ 1953196 &:= ((69 + (1^3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953197 &:= (((7 \times (9 + 1)) + 3) + ((5^9) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1953198 &:= ((8 \times 9) + (((1^3) \times 5)^9) + 1)) \\ 1953199 &:= (((9 \times (9 - 1)) + 3) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953209 &:= (((9^{02}) + 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953213 &:= (((31 - 2) \times 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953214 &:= -(((4 \times (1 - 23)) - ((5^9) + 1))) \\ 1953216 &:= ((6 \times (12 + 3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953218 &:= (((8 \times 12) - 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953221 &:= ((12 \times (2^3)) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953224 &:= ((4 \times (2 + 23)) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953225 &:= (((52 \times 2) - 3) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953226 &:= (((6^2) - 2) \times 3) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953227 &:= (((7^2) \times 2) + 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953228 &:= (((8 + 2)^2) + 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953229 &:= (((9^2) + 23) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953232 &:= (((2 \times 3)^2) \times 3) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953233 &:= (((3 + 3)^2) \times 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953234 &:= (((4 + 32) \times 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953235 &:= (((53 \times 2) + 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953236 &:= (((6^3)/2) + 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953241 &:= (((1 + 4) \times 23) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953243 &:= ((3 \times (42 - 3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953245 &:= (((5 \times 4) \times 2) \times 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953246 &:= (((6 \times 4) \times (2 + 3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953252 &:= ((2^{5 \times 2 - 3}) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953254 &:= (((4^5)/(2^3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953256 &:= ((6 \times ((5^2) - 3)) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953258 &:= -(((8 - 52) \times 3) - ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953261 &:= -(((1 - (6 \times 23)) - ((5^9) - 1))) \\ 1953262 &:= -(((2 - (6 \times 23)) - ((5^9) + 1))) \\ 1953266 &:= (((6 + 6)^2) - 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953269 &:= (((96/2) \times 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953271 &:= (((1 \times 7)^2) \times 3) + ((5^9) - 1)) \\ 1953272 &:= (((2 \times 72) + 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953273 &:= (((3 \times 7)^2)/3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953275 &:= ((5 \times (7 + 23)) + ((5^9) \times 1)) \\ 1953277 &:= (((77 \times 2) - 3) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953278 &:= -(((8 - (7 \times 23)) - ((5^9) \times 1))) \\ 1953279 &:= ((9 \times ((7 \times 2) + 3)) + ((5^9) + 1)) \\ 1953282 &:= ((2 \times (82 - 3)) + ((5^9) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 1953284** := $((4 \times 8) \times (2 + 3)) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1953287 := $((((7 \times 8) - 2) \times 3) + ((5^9) \times 1))$
1953289 := $-(((9 - (8^2)) \times 3) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1953292 := $((2 \times ((9^2) + 3)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953295 := $((59 - 2) \times 3) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1953316 := $((61 + 3) \times 3) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1953322 := $((22 \times 3) \times 3) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1953323 := $((3 \times 2) \times 33) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953324 := $((4 + 2) \times 33) + ((5^9) + 1)$
1953327 := $((7 \times (2 + (3^3))) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953329 := $((9 \times 23) - 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953332 := $((23 \times 3) \times 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953335 := $-((5 - ((3 + 3)^3)) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1953336 := $((6^3 - 3) - 3) + ((5^9) + 1)$
1953338 := $((8 \times (3^3)) - 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953339 := $((9 - 3)^3 - 3) + ((5^9) + 1)$
1953341 := $((-((1 - 4) - 3))^3) + (((5^9) \times 1))$
1953342 := $((24 \times 3) \times 3) + ((5^9) + 1)$
1953346 := $((6 \times (4 + 33)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953364 := $((4 \times (63 - 3)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953369 := $((9 \times ((6 - 3)^3)) + ((5^9) + 1))$
1953376 := $((6 \times 7) \times (3 + 3)) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1953378 := $((87 - 3) \times 3) + ((5^9) + 1)$
1953382 := $((2^8) + (((3 - 3) + 5^9) + 1))$
1953383 := $((3 + 83) \times 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953384 := $-((4 - (8 \times 33)) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1953385 := $-((5 - (8 \times 33)) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1953387 := $((783/3) + ((5^9) + 1))$
1953388 := $((8 \times ((8 + 3) \times 3)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953395 := $((5^9) + (((3 + 3) \times 5) \times 9) \times 1)$
1953397 := $-((7 - (93 \times 3)) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1953404 := $((40 \times (4 + 3)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953407 := $((70 \times 4) + 3) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1953412 := $((2 \times 143) + ((5^9) + 1))$
1953425 := $((5^2 \times 4) \times 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953444 := $((4^4 + 4^3)) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1953446 := $((6^4/4) - 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953467 := $((7 \times (6 + 43)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953469 := $((9 - 6) + 4)^3 + ((5^9) + 1)$
1953485 := $((5 \times (8 + (4^3))) + ((5^9) \times 1))$
1953531 := $((135 \times 3) + ((5^9) + 1))$
1953538 := $((83 \times 5) - 3) + ((5^9) + 1)$
1953548 := $((84 \times 5) + 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953555 := $(5 \times ((5^{5+3}) - (5 - 91)))$
1953595 := $((5^9) + (5 \times 3)) + (5 \times 91)$
1953596 := $-((6 - (9 \times 53)) - ((5^9) \times 1))$
1953608 := $((80 \times 6) + 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953613 := $((3 \times 163) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953628 := $-((8 - ((2 + 6)^3)) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1953629 := $-((9 - ((2 + 6)^3)) - ((5^9) + 1))$
1953636 := $((6/3 + 6)^3 + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953638 := $((8^3 + (6/3)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953639 := $((9^3 - 6^3) + ((5^9) + 1))$
1953665 := $((5 \times 6) \times 6) \times 3 + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953677 := $((7 \times (76 + 3)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953691 := $((1 \times 9) \times 63) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1953708 := $((8 \times 073) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953718 := $((8 \times (1 + 73)) + ((5^9) + 1))$
1953745 := $((5^4 - 7) + 3) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1953749 := $((9 - 4)^{7-3} + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953781 := $((1 + 8) \times 73) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1953792 := $-((2 \times (9 - (7^3))) - ((5^9) - 1))$
1953812 := $((2 \times (-((1 - 8)^3)) + ((5^9) + 1))$
1953828 := $((8^2 \times (8 + 3)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953845 := $((5 \times 48) \times 3) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953854 := $-((4 - 5) - 8)^3 + (((5^9) \times 1))$
1953855 := $((5/5 + 8)^3 + ((5^9) + 1))$
1953872 := $((2 + 7) \times 83) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1953889 := $((9 \times (88 - 3)) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1953963 := $((3 + 6) \times 93) + ((5^9) + 1)$
1953989 := $((9 \times 8) \times (9 + 3)) + ((5^9) \times 1)$
1954125 := $((5 \times 2)^{-1+4} + (((5^9) \times 1))$
1954144 := $((4^4 - 1) \times 4) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1954145 := $-((5 - (4^{1+4}) + ((5^9) + 1)))$
1954148 := $((8^4 \times 1)/4) + ((5^9) - 1)$
1954152 := $((2 \times 514) + ((5^9) - 1))$
1954154 := $((4^5 \times 1) + 4) + ((5^9) + 1)$
1954292 := $((292 \times 4) + ((5^9) - 1))$

$$\begin{aligned} 1954349 &:= (((9 \times 4) \times 34) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 1985529 &:= ((9 - 2) \times (((5^5) - 8) \times 91)) \\ 1954405 &:= ((5 \times (04^4)) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 1985895 &:= ((5^9) + (((8^5) - 8) + 9) + 1)) \\ 1954416 &:= (((((6 \times 1)^4) - 4) + ((5^9) - 1)) & 1990584 &:= (((4 + 8)^5) - 09) \times (9 - 1)) \\ 1954417 &:= (((((7 - 1)^4) - 4) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 2030625 &:= (((5^2) \times (60 - 3))^{02}) \\ 1954636 &:= (((63 \times 6) \times 4) + ((5^9) - 1)) & 2052866 &:= -((((6^6) \times ((8 - 2) - 50)) - 2)) \\ 1954662 &:= (((2^6) \times 6) \times 4) + ((5^9) + 1)) & 2054184 &:= -(((4 - ((8 \times 1)^4)) \times 502)) \\ 1954885 &:= (((5 \times 88) \times 4) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 2064368 &:= (8 \times ((63 \times (4^6)) - 02)) \\ 1955172 &:= ((2^{7-1+5}) + ((5^9) - 1)) & 2074688 &:= (8 \times ((8^6) - (4 \times 702))) \\ 1955313 &:= ((3^{-1+3+5}) + (((5^9) + 1))) & 2084195 &:= ((5^9) - ((1 - (4^8)) \times 02)) \\ 1955329 &:= ((9 \times (2 + (3^5))) + ((5^9) - 1)) & 2085136 &:= ((6 + ((3 - 1)^5))^{8/02}) \\ 1955339 &:= ((9 \times (3 + (3^5))) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 2088025 &:= ((5 - (20 \times (8 - 80)))^2) \\ 1955349 &:= ((9 \times (4 + (3^5))) + ((5^9) + 1)) & 2096378 &:= (((8^7) - (3^6)) - (90/2)) \\ 1955446 &:= (((6^4) + (4^5)) + ((5^9) + 1)) & 2096448 &:= (8 \times (((4 + 4)^6) - 90) + 2)) \\ 1955544 &:= ((44 \times 55) + ((5^9) - 1)) & 2096878 &:= ((8^7) - ((8 + (6 \times 90))/2)) \\ 1955595 &:= ((5^9) + (5 \times ((55 \times 9) - 1))) & 2096972 &:= (((2^7)^{9-6}) - (90 \times 2)) \\ 1955599 &:= (((99 \times 5) \times 5) + ((5^9) - 1)) & 2096978 &:= ((8^7) - ((96 - 9) \times 02)) \\ 1955864 &:= ((4 \times 685) + ((5^9) - 1)) & 2097071 &:= (((1 + 7)^{07}) - (9^{02})) \\ 1955868 &:= (((8 + 6)^{8-5}) + ((5^9) - 1)) & 2097078 &:= (((8^7) + 07) - (9^{02})) \\ 1956192 &:= (((2^9) - 1) \times 6) + ((5^9) + 1)) & 2097107 &:= (((7 + 01)^7) - (90/2)) \\ 1956255 &:= (((5^5) - 2) + 6) + ((5^9) + 1)) & 2097134 &:= (((4 + 3) + 1)^7) - (9 \times 02)) \\ 1956575 &:= ((575 \times 6) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 2097143 &:= (((((3 + 4) + 1)^7) - 9) + (0 \times 2)) \\ 1956778 &:= (((87 \times 7) \times 6) + ((5^9) - 1)) & 2097144 &:= ((4 - (4^{17+9})) \times (0 - 2)) \\ 1957222 &:= ((2^{-2+2 \times 7}) + (((5^9) + 1))) & 2097145 &:= (((((5 + 4) - 1)^7) - 9) + 02) \\ 1957228 &:= (((8^2)^2) + 7) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 2097146 &:= -((6 - ((4^{17+9}) \times 02))) \\ 1957248 &:= (((8^4) + 27) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 2097148 &:= -(((8 - 4) - ((1 + 7)^{9-02})) \\ 1957646 &:= ((646 \times 7) + ((5^9) - 1)) & 2097151 &:= -(((5^5) - ((1 + 7)^{9-02}))) \\ 1957694 &:= ((4 \times (9^6)) - ((7^5) \times (9 + 1))) & 2097152 &:= 2^{(5-1) \times 7-9+02} \\ 1957977 &:= (((77 \times 9) \times 7) + ((5^9) + 1)) & 2097154 &:= (((4 + 5) - 1)^7) + ((9 \times 0) + 2)) \\ 1958245 &:= (((5 \times 4) \times (2^8)) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 2097161 &:= (((((1 + 6) + 1)^7) + 9) + (0 \times 2)) \\ 1958767 &:= ((7 \times ((6^7) - (8 \times (5 + 9)))) - 1) & 2097163 &:= (((((3 + 6) - 1)^7) + 9) + 02) \\ 1959066 &:= ((660 \times 9) + ((5^9) + 1)) & 2097168 &:= (((8^{6+1}) + (7 + 9)) + (0 \times 2)) \\ 1959683 &:= (((3^8) + 6) - 9) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 2097184 &:= (((4^8) + 1) \times ((7 + 9) \times 02)) \\ 1959685 &:= (((-(5 - 8))^6) \times 9) + (((5^9) - 1))) & 2097233 &:= (((3 + 3) + 2)^7) + (9^{02}) \\ 1959749 &:= (((9^4) + (7 \times 9)) + ((5^9) \times 1)) & 2097278 &:= ((8^7) - ((27 - 90) \times 2)) \\ 1959957 &:= ((759 \times 9) + ((5^9) + 1)) & 2097326 &:= -(((6 - ((2^3)^7)) - (90 \times 2))) \\ 1966125 &:= (5 \times (((2^{16}) \times 6) + 9) \times 1)) & 2097332 &:= (((2 + 3) + 3)^7) + (90 \times 2)) \\ 1968659 &:= (((9 \times (5^6)) \times (8 + 6)) - 91) & 2097348 &:= ((8 + ((4^{3+7}) + 90)) \times 2) \\ 1973853 &:= 3 \times (-5^8 + (3 - 7)^{9+1}) & 2097719 &:= (((9 - 1)^7) + (7 \times (9^{02}))) \\ 1976855 &:= (5 \times ((5^8) + (6 \times 791))) & 2097863 &:= (((3^6) + (8^7)) - (9 \times 02)) \end{aligned}$$

- 2101242** := $-(2 \times (4 - (((2^{10}) + 1)^2)))$
2101262 := $(2 \times (6 + (((2^{10}) + 1)^2)))$
2109375 := $((5^7) \times (39 - 012))$
2117673 := $(3 \times (((7^6) \times (7 - 1)) - (1 + 2)))$
2117674 := $-(((4 - ((7^6) \times ((7 + 1) + 1))) \times 2))$
2117675 := $-((5 - (((7^6) \times (7 + 11)) - 2)))$
2117676 := $-((6 - ((7^6) \times ((7 - 1) + 12))))$
2117677 := $-((7 - (((7^6) \times (7 + 11)) + 2)))$
2117736 := $((6 \times 3) \times ((7^{7-1}) + (1 + 2)))$
2119936 := $(((((6 \times 3) \times 9) \times 9) - 1) - 1)^2$
2122416 := $((6 \times (1 + (4^2)))^{2+1}) \times 2$
2125694 := $((4 \times (9^6)) - (5 \times (2 + 12)))$
2125763 := $((((3^6) \times (7 - 5))^2) - (1^2))$
2125764 := $(4 \times ((6^{7+5}) / (2^{12})))$
2125836 := $((6 + (3^{8+5-2})) \times 12)$
2126084 := $(4 \times (80 + ((6/2)^{12})))$
2134521 := $((1 + (2 \times (((5 + 4)^3) + 1)))^2)$
2137428 := $-(((8/2) \times (4 - (731^2))))$
2137564 := $(4 \times ((6 \times 5) + (731^2)))$
2143296 := $((6 + (((9 \times 2)^3) / 4))^{1 \times 2})$
2146176 := $((6^{7-1}) \times (((6 \times 4) - 1) \times 2))$
2146689 := $((9 \times 86) / 6)^{4+1-2}$
2147466 := $(6 \times ((64 + 7)^{4+1-2}))$
2172676 := $((67 \times (((6/2) \times 7) + 1))^2)$
2174958 := $-(((8 - (5^9)) - (471^2)))$
2175278 := $((8^7) + 2) + (((5^7) + 1) - 2))$
2175625 := $((5^2) \times ((65 - 7) + 1))^2$
2187367 := $(7 \times (((63 + 7) \times 8) - 1))^2$
2187547 := $((7 \times ((4 \times (5^7)) + (8 - 1))) - 2)$
2196324 := $(4 \times ((2 + (((3^6) + 9) + 1))^2))$
2204498 := $((8 \times (9^4)) \times (40 + 2)) + 2$
2214137 := $-((7 - (((31 \times 4) \times 12)^2)))$
2217121 := $((1 \times 21) \times 71) - 2)^2$
2217618 := $((81 \times (6 + 7))^{1 \times 2}) \times 2$
2224455 := $(5 \times (((5^4) + 42)^2) + 2)$
2225286 := $6 \times (-8 \times 2 + 5^{2 \times 2})^2$
2232958 := $-(((8 - (5^9)) - ((23^2)^2)))$
2237299 := $((9 \times 9)^2) \times ((7^3) - 2) - 2$
2239356 := $(6 \times (((5 + 3) \times 9)^3) - 22)$
2239466 := $((6^6) \times 4) \times (9 + 3) - 22$
2239476 := $((6^7) \times 4) - ((9/3) \times 2) \times 2$
2239484 := $((48 \times ((4 \times 9)^3)) - (2 + 2))$
2239486 := $((6^8) \times 4) - 9) / 3 + (2/2)$
2239488 := $((8 - (8/4))^9) / (3^2) \times 2$
2239489 := $((9 \times 8)^4) / (9 + 3) + (2/2)$
2239496 := $((6^9) + (4 \times 9)) / (3^2) \times 2$
2239658 := $((85 + ((6^9) / (3^2))) \times 2)$
2244937 := $((7^3) \times ((9^4) - (4^2))) + 2$
2254716 := $((6 + 1) \times ((7 + 4)^5 \times 2)) + 2$
2254718 := $((8 - 1) \times ((7 + 4)^5)) + 2 \times 2$
2254737 := $(7 \times (3 + (((7 + 4)^5) \times 2))) + 2$
2254777 := $(7 \times (7 + (((7 + 4)^5) \times 2) + 2))$
2263543 := $(345 \times (3^{6+2})) - 2$
2265925 := $(5 \times ((29 \times ((5^6) + 2)) + 2))$
2268036 := $((6 + (30 \times ((8 \times 6) + 2)))^2)$
2272375 := $((5 \times 7)^3) \times (2 + ((7^2) + 2))$
2274558 := $((8 + (5^5)) \times (4 + 722))$
2278125 := $(5 \times ((2 + 1) \times ((8 + 7)^2))^2)$
2284146 := $(6 \times (((4 + 1)^4) - 8)^2) + 2$
2285564 := $((4^6) \times 558) - 2 - 2$
2286144 := $(4 \times ((41 + 6) \times 8) + 2)^2$
2286166 := $((6^6) \times (1 + (6 \times 8))) + 22$
2291856 := $(6 \times ((5^8) - ((1 + 92)^2)))$
2292196 := $(6 \times 9 \times (-1 + 29) + 2)^2$
2293758 := $((8^5) \times 7) \times ((3 + 9) - 2) - 2$
2295568 := $-((8 \times (((6 - (5^5)) \times 92) + 2)))$
2307361 := $((1 + (6^3)) \times 7)^{0 \times 3 + 2}$
2313435 := $((5 + 34)^{3+1}) - (3 \times 2)$
2313439 := $((9 \times 3) + (4 \times 3))^{1+3} - 2$
2313443 := $((3 \times ((4 \times 4) - 3))^{1+3}) + 2$
2313846 := $6 \times (4 - (8 - 3)^{1+3})^2$
2322427 := $(7 \times ((24^2)^2)) - (3 + 2)$
2322446 := $((6 \times 4)^4) + 2 \times ((2 + 3) + 2)$
2322467 := $(7 \times (((6 \times 4)^2)^2) + 3) + 2$
2322576 := $((6 \times 7) - 5) + 2)^2 + 3)^2$
2325625 := $((5^2) \times ((6 + 52) + 3))^2$
2331729 := $(9 \times (((2 + 7) - 1)^3) - 3)^2$
2334744 := $((4 + (4 \times (7^4))) \times (3^{3+2}))$

$$\begin{aligned}2334784 &:= (4 \times ((8 + ((7 \times 4) \times (3^3)))^2)) \\2336048 &:= (8 \times (((40 + 6)^3) \times 3) - 2) \\2336256 &:= (6 \times ((52 \times ((6 + 3) + 3))^2)) \\2339568 &:= (((8^6) - 5) \times 9) - (3^3) \\2343314 &:= ((41^3) \times (((3 \times 4) \times 3) - 2)) \\2343685 &:= (((5^8) \times 6) - 3) - ((4^3) - 2) \\2343745 &:= -((5 - (((4 \times 7) - 3)^4) \times 3) \times 2)) \\2343854 &:= -((((4 - 5^8) \times 3) - (4^3)) \times 2) \\2343961 &:= (((16 \times 93) + 43)^2) \\2345776 &:= ((6 \times (((7 + 7) + 5)^4) \times 3)) - 2) \\2347024 &:= (-4 + 2^{07} \times 4 \times 3)^2 \\2352635 &:= ((((((5 - 3)^6) \times 2) + 5)^3) - 2) \\2352639 &:= (((93 + ((6 + 2) \times 5))^3) + 2) \\2356225 &:= (5 \times ((2 - 2^6) \times 5 + 3))^2 \\2358648 &:= (((8 + 4) \times 6) \times ((8^5) - (3^2))) \\2358786 &:= -((6 + (8 \times ((7 - 8^5)) \times (3^2)))) \\2358798 &:= -((((8 \times 9) \times (7 - (8^5))) - (3 \times 2))) \\2358864 &:= ((4 + 68) \times ((8^5) - (3 \times 2))) \\2358936 &:= ((63 + 9) \times (((8^5) - 3) - 2)) \\2359159 &:= ((9 \times (((5 - 1)^9) - (5 \times 3))) - 2) \\2359251 &:= (((((1 + 5) - 2)^9) - 5) \times (3^2)) \\2359268 &:= ((((((8^6) - 2) \times 9) - 5) - 3) - 2) \\2359269 &:= ((9 \times ((6 - 2)^9)) + (5 - 32)) \\2359283 &:= (((3 \times ((8/2)^9)) - 5) \times 3) + 2) \\2359288 &:= -((8 - ((8^{2+9-5}) \times (3^2)))) \\2359292 &:= ((((((2^9)^2) \times 9) - 5) + 3) - 2) \\2359293 &:= -((3 - (9 \times ((2 \times (9 - 5))^{3 \times 2}))) \\2359294 &:= (((4^9) - 2) \times 9) + ((5 + 3) \times 2) \\2359296 &:= (((6 + 9) + (((2^9) - 5) \times 3))^2) \\2359298 &:= (((8^9 - 2) \times 9) / (5 + 3)) + 2) \\2359313 &:= (((3 \times ((1 + 3)^9)) + 5) \times 3) + 2) \\2359323 &:= ((3^2) \times (3 + ((9 - 5)^{3^2}))) \\2359341 &:= (((((1^4) + 3)^9) + 5) \times (3^2)) \\2359368 &:= (((8^6) + 3) \times 9) + (5 \times (3^2)) \\2359419 &:= ((9 \times ((1 \times 4)^9)) + ((5^3) - 2)) \\2359423 &:= (((3^2) \times (4^9)) + ((5^3) + 2)) \\2359433 &:= (((3 \times 3) \times ((4^9) + (5 \times 3))) + 2) \\2359449 &:= (9 \times ((4 + (4^9)) + ((5 \times 3) - 2))) \\2359458 &:= (((8 + 5) + ((4^9) + 5)) \times (3^2)) \\2359828 &:= (((8^{-2+8}) \times 9) + 532) \\2361954 &:= (((4 \times 5) \times (9^{-1+6})) - 3) \times 2) \\2361985 &:= (-5) \times ((-8) \times (9^{-1+6})) - ((3 + 2)) \\2362927 &:= (7 \times ((2 + ((9 \times (2^6)) + 3))^2)) \\2368521 &:= ((((((1 \times 2)^5) \times 8) \times 6) + 3)^2) \\2370816 &:= (((6 + 18) \times 07^3) / 2) \\2371841 &:= -((1 - (((4 \times 8) + 1)^{7-3}) \times 2)) \\2371842 &:= (((24 + 8) + 1)^{7-3}) \times 2) \\2373846 &:= (6 \times ((4 + ((8 - 3)^{7-3}))^2)) \\2377764 &:= ((-4 + (67 + 7) \times 7) \times 3)^2 \\2381643 &:= ((3^{4+6-1}) \times ((8 + 3)^2)) \\2384928 &:= 8 \times (-2 + 9 \times 4 + 8^3)^2 \\2386578 &:= -(((8 - ((7^5) \times (68 + 3))) \times 2) \\2386944 &:= (((4^4) \times 9) \times ((6 + (8^3)) \times 2)) \\2387025 &:= ((5 + ((20 \times 7) \times (8 + 3)))^2) \\2387357 &:= -((7 \times (5 - ((3 + (7 \times 83))^2)))) \\2387392 &:= -(((2 - 9) \times ((3 + (7 \times 83))^2)) \\2391479 &:= ((((((9^7) - 4) - 1) - 9) + 3) / 2) \\2391483 &:= (((3^{8-4+1+9}) - 3) / 2) \\2391849 &:= (((9^{-4+8}) + 1) \times (-9^3)) / (-2) \\2392137 &:= (73 \times (1 + (2^{9+3 \times 2}))) \\2393284 &:= ((4 \times 823) \times ((9^3) - 2)) \\2396304 &:= (((40 + 3) \times 6) \times (9 - 3))^2) \\2408704 &:= (4 \times ((0780 - 4)^2)) \\2421875 &:= ((5^7) \times (((8 + 1) + 24) - 2)) \\2424573 &:= -((37 \times (5 - (((4^2)^4) - 2)))) \\2424832 &:= (((2 + 3) + (8 \times 4)) \times (2^4)) \\2426976 &:= (6 \times (((79 \times (6 + 2)) + 4)^2) \\2436357 &:= ((7 \times 53) \times (6 + ((3^4)^2))) \\2436564 &:= (4 \times ((6 - 5^6)) \times (3 - 42)) \\2437632 &:= ((2^{3+6}) \times ((73 - 4)^2)) \\2439474 &:= (((47^4) - ((9^3) + 4)) / 2) \\2439841 &:= (1 + (4 - (8 + 9) \times 3)^4) / 2) \\2439844 &:= (4 \times ((48 + ((9^3) + 4))^2) \\2442969 &:= (((9 - 6) \times (9 + (2 \times (4^4))))^2) \\2452356 &:= (((((6 \times 5) - 3) + 2) \times 54)^2) \\2453584 &:= ((4 \times (85^3)) - (54^2)) \\2455324 &:= -((4 - ((2^3) \times (554^2)))) \\2455328 &:= -(((8 \times (2 - 3)) \times (554^2)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2455528 &:= (8 \times (25 + (554^2))) & 2519476 &:= (((6^7) + 4) \times 9) + (-((1 - 5))^2) \\ 2455568 &:= (8 \times ((6 \times 5) + (554^2))) & 2519496 &:= (((6^9)/4) + (9 \times ((1 + 5) + 2))) \\ 2457582 &:= -((2 - ((8^5) \times 75)) + (4^2)) & 2519682 &:= ((2^8) - (((6^9)/(1 - 5)) - 2)) \\ 2457586 &:= -(((6 - ((8^5) \times 75)) + (4 \times 2))) & 2528193 &:= (3 \times (((918^2) + 5) + 2)) \\ 2457587 &:= -((7 - (((8^5) \times 75) - 4) - 2)) & 2528199 &:= ((9 + (918^2)) \times (5 - 2)) \\ 2457589 &:= -((9 - (((8^5) \times 75) - 4) + 2)) & 2537857 &:= ((7^5) \times (87 + ((3 + 5)^2))) \\ 2457592 &:= (((2^{9+5}) \times 75) - 4) \times 2 & 2538763 &:= -(((36 + 7) \times (8 - ((3^5)^2)))) \\ 2457648 &:= (8 \times (((4^6) \times 75) + 4) + 2) & 2544025 &:= (((((5 \times 20) \times 4) \times 4) - 5)^2) \\ 2459325 &:= ((5^2) \times (((3^9) \times 5) - 42)) & 2544224 &:= (4 \times (-((2 - (2 \times 44))^{5-2})) \\ 2464768 &:= (8 \times ((6 + (7^4)) \times (64 \times 2))) & 2544768 &:= (8 \times ((6 \times (74 + (4 \times 5)))^2)) \\ 2470613 &:= ((3 \times ((1 + 6)^{07})) - (4^2)) & 2558495 &:= (5 \times ((9 \times (4^8)) - (5^{5+2}))) \\ 2470629 &:= ((9 + (2 \times 6)) \times (07^{4+2})) & 2558783 &:= (((((3^8) \times 78) \times 5) - 5) - 2) \\ 2470743 &:= -((3 \times (4 - ((7^{07}) + 42)))) & 2559373 &:= (((3 \times 7) \times 39) \times (5^5)) - 2 \\ 2474075 &:= -((5 - (70 \times ((47 \times 4)^2)))) & 2559948 &:= (8 \times (4 - 9))^{9-5} - 52 \\ 2474329 &:= (9 \times 23 \times 4 - 7^4)^2 & 2564375 &:= ((5^{7-3}) \times (((4^6) + 5) + 2)) \\ 2475429 &:= (((9 - 2) + (4^5)) \times (7^4)) - 2 & 2566055 &:= ((55 \times (06^6)) - (5^2)) \\ 2475447 &:= (((7^4) \times ((4^5) + 7)) + (4^2)) & 2566115 &:= (5 \times ((11 \times (6^6)) + (5 + 2))) \\ 2475768 &:= ((86 \times (7 + 5)) \times ((7^4) - 2)) & 2566117 &:= (((7 + (11 \times (6^6))) \times 5) + 2) \\ 2477476 &:= ((6 + ((7 \times 4) \times ((7 + 7) \times 4)))^2) & 2566118 &:= (((8 + (11 \times (6^6))) \times 5) - 2) \\ 2477659 &:= (((9^5) \times 6) \times 7) - ((7^4) - 2) & 2566296 &:= 6 \times (9 + 2 - 665)^2 \\ 2479938 &:= -((((8 - ((3^9) \times 9)) \times 7) + 4) \times 2) & 2566355 &:= (55 \times (3 + ((6 \times (6^5)) + 2))) \\ 2486658 &:= -(((8^5) - ((6 \times ((6^8)/4)) + 2))) & 2566695 &:= -((5 \times (9 - (66 \times ((6^5) + 2)))) \\ 2489152 &:= (((2^5) \times 19) \times ((8^4) - 2)) & 2571353 &:= (-((3 - (5 \times ((3 + 1) \times 7))))^{5-2} \\ 2505377 &:= (7 \times (((7 \times 3) + 50)^{5-2})) & 2576813 &:= -((3 - (((((1 + 8) + 6) + 7)^5)/2))) \\ 2509585 &:= ((5 + (85 \times (9^{05}))) / 2) & 2576814 &:= -(((4 - (((1 + 8) + 6) + 7)^5) / 2) \\ 2515396 &:= ((6 + (((9 \times 35) + 1) \times 5))^2) & 2576944 &:= (((4^4) + (((9 + 6) + 7)^5)) / 2) \\ 2515456 &:= (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (5 - 1))^{5-2} & 2577597 &:= -((((7 + 9) - (5^7)) \times ((7 \times 5) - 2))) \\ 2516582 &:= ((((((2 \times 8)^5) \times 6) - 1) / 5) \times 2) & 2578125 &:= ((5^{-2+1+8}) \times ((7 \times 5) - 2)) \\ 2517399 &:= (9 \times (((9 - 3)^7) - (15^2))) & 2583697 &:= -(((79 \times (63 - (8^5))) - 2)) \\ 2519296 &:= (((6^9) - (2^9)) / ((1 + 5) - 2)) & 2588674 &:= (((4 + 7) + 68) \times (8^5)) + 2 \\ 2519372 &:= (((2^7) \times (3^9)) - (1 \times 52)) & 2595321 &:= ((1 + (23 \times ((5 + 9) \times 5)))^2) \\ 2519421 &:= -((1 + (((2 + 4)^9) / (1 - 5)) + 2))) & 2598068 &:= -((((8 - 60) + 8) \times ((9^5) - 2))) \\ 2519422 &:= -((2 - (((2 + 4)^9) / ((1 + 5) - 2)))) & 2598148 &:= -((8 - ((4 + 18) \times ((9^5) \times 2)))) \\ 2519423 &:= -((3 + (((2 + 4)^9) / (1 - 5)) - 2))) & 2598154 &:= (((4 + ((5 \times 1) \times 8)) \times (9^5)) - 2) \\ 2519424 &:= (((4 - 2) + 4)^9) / ((1 + 5) - 2) & 2598156 &:= (((6 \times 5) \times 1) - 8) \times ((9^5) \times 2) \\ 2519426 &:= (((6^{2+4}) \times 9) \times (1 + 5)) + 2 & 2598244 &:= (((4 \times 4) + 28) \times ((9^5) + 2)) \\ 2519428 &:= -((((8 + ((2 + 4)^9)) / (1 - 5)) - 2)) & 2598544 &:= (4 \times (((4 + 5) \times 89) + 5)^2) \\ 2519433 &:= (3 \times (3 - (((4 \times 9)^{-1+5}) / (-2)))) & 2599344 &:= ((44 \times ((3^9) + 9)) \times (5 - 2)) \\ 2519436 &:= (((6^{3+4}) \times 9) + ((1 + 5) \times 2)) & 2608225 &:= (((5 - 2) + (2 \times 806))^2) \end{aligned}$$

- 2612736** := $((63 - 7) \times (216^2))$
2612738 := $((((8^3) \times 7) \times ((2 + 1)^6)) + 2)$
2613685 := $5 \times (8 + (6 - (3 \times 1)^6)^2)$
2621161 := $((1611 + 2) + 6)^2$
2621395 := $-((5 \times (9 - (((3 + 1) \times 2)^6) \times 2))))$
2621475 := $(5 \times (7 + (((4 \times 1) \times 2)^6) \times 2))$
2621568 := $((((8^6) \times 5) + ((1 \times 2)^6)) \times 2)$
2624395 := $-5 + (9 \times 3 \times (4 - 2^6))^2$
2627641 := $((1 + (((4 \times 67) + 2) \times 6))^2)$
2628072 := $((((2^7) + 08) + 2)^{6/2})$
2633854 := $(((-(4 \times (5 - (8 \times 3))))^3) \times 6) - 2)$
2633868 := $(((((8 + 68)^3) \times 3) + 6) \times 2)$
2633872 := $((((-((2 - 78))^3) + 3) \times 6) - 2)$
2633964 := $(4 \times ((-((6 - 93))^3) - (6 \times 2)))$
2643868 := $-((8 - (((6 \times 8) \times 34) - 6^2)))$
2643876 := $((((6 - 7) + (8 \times 34)) \times 6)^2)$
2646272 := $((2^7) \times (((2 \times 6)^4) - 62))$
2646432 := $-((((2 \times 3)^4) \times (6 - ((4^6)/2))))$
2646945 := $-((5 \times ((4 - (9^6)) + ((4^6)/2))))$
2652695 := $(5 \times (((9^6) - 2) - ((5 \times 6)^2)))$
2653583 := $((((3 \times 8)^5)/3) - (5^{6-2}))$
2654204 := $-((4 - (((024^5)/6) \times 2)))$
2654206 := $-(((6 - (024^5))/(6/2)))$
2654208 := $(((((8 \times 0) + 24)^5)/6) \times 2)$
2654224 := $((4^2) + (((24^5)/6) \times 2))$
2654228 := $((8 + 2) + ((24^5)/6)) \times 2$
2654239 := $((93 + (24^5))/(6/2))$
2654248 := $(((((8 + 4) \times 2)^4) + 5) \times (6 + 2))$
2654388 := $((8 \times ((8 \times 3)^4)) + (5 \times (6^2)))$
2654395 := $(5 \times (((9 \times 3)^4) - 562))$
2655892 := $-((2 \times (9 - (85 \times ((5^6) - 2))))))$
2656695 := $(5 \times ((9^6) - (6 \times (5 + (6 \times 2))))))$
2656905 := $(5 \times ((09^6) - ((5 \times 6) \times 2)))$
2656915 := $(5 \times (((1 \times 9)^6) - 56) - 2)$
2656923 := $((3 + 2) \times ((9^6) - 56)) - 2$
2656925 := $((5 \times 2) \times ((9^6) - 56))/2$
2656927 := $((7 - 2) \times ((9^6) - 56)) + 2$
2656935 := $(5 \times (3 + (((9^6) + 5) - 62)))$
2656963 := $-((((36 - (9^6)) \times 5) + 62))$
2656965 := $(5 \times (6 + (((9^6) - 56) + 2)))$
2656968 := $-((((8 \times 6) - (9^6)) \times 5) - (6/2))$
2656974 := $-((((47 - (9^6)) \times 5) - (6 - 2)))$
2656985 := $-(((5 \times (8 - (9^6))) + (5 \times (6^2))))$
2656987 := $-((((7 \times 8) - (9^6)) \times 5) - 62)$
2657143 := $((3^{4+1+7}) \times 5) - 62$
2657145 := $(5 \times (((4 - 1)^{7+5}) - (6 \times 2)))$
2657169 := $(((((9^6) - 1) - 7) \times 5) + 6) - 2$
2657192 := $(((-2) + (9^{-1+7})) \times 5) - (6/2)$
2657195 := $5 \times (9^{175 \times 6} - 2)$
2657196 := $(-6) + (((9^{-1+7}) \times 5) - (6/2))$
2657215 := $(5 \times (((((1 \times 2) \times 7) - 5)^6) + 2))$
2657225 := $(5 \times (2 + (((2 \times 7) - 5)^6) + 2))$
2657265 := $(5 \times (((6/2)^{7+5}) + (6 \times 2)))$
2657695 := $(5 \times ((9^6) - ((7 - 56) \times 2)))$
2657792 := $((2^9) \times (7 + (((7 + 5) \times 6)^2)))$
2659965 := $-((5 \times (6 - (9 \times ((9^5) + 62))))))$
2661336 := $(6 \times ((3 \times ((31 + 6) \times 6))^2))$
2663424 := $(4 \times (2 - 4^3 - 6) \times 6)^2$
2678424 := $(42 \times ((4^8) - ((7 \times 6)^2)))$
2678544 := $-((4 \times (((4 - (5^8))/7) \times (6 \times 2))))$
2683044 := $((4 \times (403 + 8)) - 6)^2$
2684739 := $-((9 - (3 \times (((7 + 4) \times 86)^2))))$
2686445 := $(5 \times ((4 + (((4 \times 6)/8)^6))^2))$
2687085 := $-((((5^8) - ((07^8) - 6))/2))$
2712609 := $(90 \times 6 - (2 + 1)^7)^2$
2715932 := $(23 \times (((9^5) \times 1) - 7) \times 2)$
2722572 := $((2 \times (7^5)) - 2) \times ((2 + 7)^2)$
2722732 := $((2 \times (((3 \times 7)^2)^2) \times 7) - 2)$
2722736 := $(((((63 \times 7)^2) \times 2) \times 7) + 2)$
2725888 := $(88 \times (((8 + 5)^2) + 7)^2)$
2729376 := $((6^7) \times 3) + ((9 \times 2)^{7-2})$
2731568 := $(8 \times (((((6 \times 5) - 1)^3) \times 7) \times 2))$
2731572 := $(2 \times (((7 + 51)^3) \times 7) + 2)$
2734375 := $((5^7) \times (((3 + 4) + 3) \times 7)/2)$
2734385 := $(5 \times (((8 - 3)^{4+3}) \times 7) + 2)$
2734485 := $(((((5^8) + 4) + (4 \times 3)) \times 7) - 2)$
2737947 := $((7 - 4) \times (97^3)) - 72$
2737996 := $-((((6 - 9) \times ((97^3) - 7)) + 2))$

- 2739025 := $(5 \times (2 - 09 \times 37))^2$
2739375 := $((5^{7-3}) \times (9 + ((3^7) \times 2)))$
2742336 := $((((6^3)/3) \times ((2^4) + 7))^2)$
2747168 := $(8 \times (((6 + ((1 + 7)^4))/7)^2))$
2751924 := $(42 \times (((9 - 1)^5) - 7) \times 2)$
2752464 := $((4 \times 6) \times ((4^{2+5}) \times 7) - 2)$
2752466 := $((((6^6) - 4) \times (2 + 57)) - 2)$
2752848 := $-(((8 + (4^8)) \times (((2 - 5) \times 7) \times 2)))$
2757414 := $(41 \times ((4 \times ((7^5) + 7)) - 2))$
2766495 := $-((5 \times ((9^4) + ((6 - (6^7)) \times 2))))$
2767713 := $((((3 + 1)^7) - 7) \times ((6 + 7)^2))$
2768888 := $-((8 - (((8 + 8) \times 8) \times (6 + 7)^2)))$
2768896 := $(((((6 + 9) \times 8) + 8) \times (6 + 7))^2)$
2769487 := $7 \times (8 - 49 \times (6 + 7))^2$
2773155 := $((55 \times 1) \times 3) \times (7^{7-2})$
2775303 := $((3 \times 03)^5) \times ((7 \times 7) - 2)$
2775556 := $((6 - 55) \times 5 + 7) \times 7^2$
2785875 := $(5 \times ((7 + (8^5)) \times ((8 + 7) + 2)))$
2788385 := $-((5 \times (8 - ((3^8) \times (87 - 2)))))$
2794762 := $((2 \times 6) \times ((7^4) \times 97)) - 2$
2794766 := $((6 + 6) \times ((7^4) \times 97)) + 2$
2795584 := $(((((4 \times 8) + 5) \times 5) \times 9) + 7)^2$
2822404 := $((40 \times 42)^2) + (8/2)$
2823572 := $(2 \times (((7^5) \times 3) \times 28) - 2)$
2823573 := $-((3 - (((7^5) \times 3) \times 28) \times 2))$
2823576 := $((6 \times (7^5)) \times ((3 \times 2) + 8) \times 2)$
2823674 := $((4 + (7^6)) \times (32 - 8)) + 2$
2823768 := $((8 \times 6) \times ((7^3)^2) + 8)/2$
2825761 := $((1675 - 2) + 8)^2$
2829124 := $(4 \times (((2 + 1) \times 9) + 2)^{8/2})$
2829492 := $((29^4) + 92) \times 8/2$
2832489 := $((9 + ((8 + 4)^2)) \times (3 + 8))^2$
2834136 := $-(((6^3) \times ((1^4) - ((3^8) \times 2))))$
2834196 := $(6 \times (((9^{1+4}) - 3) \times 8) - 2)$
2834288 := $-((8 \times (8 - ((2 + 4) \times (3^{8+2})))))$
2834336 := $(((((6 \times 3) \times 3)^4)/3) - (8 \times 2))$
2834346 := $((6^4) \times (3^{4+3})) - (8 - 2)$
2834352 := $((2^5) \times ((3^4)^3))/(8 - 2)$
2834368 := $(8 \times (((6^3)/4) \times (3^8)) + 2)$
2834384 := $(4 \times (8 + ((3 \times 4) \times (3^{8+2}))))$
2837368 := $-((8 - ((6^3) \times ((7 + (3^8)) \times 2))))$
2838448 := $((8^4) + (48 \times (3^{8+2})))$
2838528 := $((82 - 5) \times (((8 \times 3) \times 8)^2))$
2839225 := $((-5) \times (-2) - (((2 - 9)^3) - 8))^2$
2839698 := $((((8 + 9)^{(6+9)/3}) - 8) \times 2)$
2839712 := $-2 + 17^{-9/3+8} \times 2$
2846016 := $(61 \times (06^{(4+8)/2}))$
2849344 := $(4^4 - (3^{9-4} \times 8))^2$
2852721 := $(1 - (2^7 + 2) \times (5 + 8))^2$
2861566 := $-((((((6 + 6)^5) + 1) - (6^8)) \times 2))$
2861568 := $((8 \times (6^5)) \times (((1 \times 6) \times 8) - 2))$
2862256 := $-(((6 - ((5^2)^2)) \times (68^2)))$
2863178 := $((8 \times ((71^3) - 6) - 8) + 2)$
2866392 := $((((2 \times 9)^3) - 6) \times 6) \times 82$
2872559 := $-((((9^5)/(5 - 2)) - (7^8))/2)$
2875836 := $-(((6 + (3^8)) - ((5 + (7^8))/2)))$
2879236 := $-(((6329 - (7^8))/2))$
2879328 := $((8 + ((2 \times 3)^9))/7) - 8) \times 2$
2882358 := $(-85 + (-3 + 2 + 8)^8)/2$
2882387 := $(((((7^8) - 3)/2) - 8) - (8/2))$
2882391 := $(-19 + (3 - 2 - 8)^8)/2$
2882393 := $-3 + (-9 + (3 - 2 - 8)^8)/2$
2882394 := $(-4 - 9 + (3 - 2 - 8)^8)/2$
2882397 := $-(((7 - ((9 + ((3 \times 2) - 8))^8))/2))$
2882792 := $-(((2 + 9) \times (72 - (8^{8-2}))))$
2883144 := $(44 \times (((1 + 3)^8) - 8) - 2)$
2883234 := $-(((4 - (32^3)) \times 88) - 2)$
2883551 := $-((((1 + 5) + 5) \times (3 - (8^{8-2}))))$
2883581 := $-((1 - (((8^5) \times ((3 + 8) \times 8)) - 2)))$
2883582 := $-((2 - ((8^5) \times ((3 \times 8) + (8^2)))))$
2883583 := $-((3 - (((8^5) \times ((3 + 8) \times 8)) + 2)))$
2883584 := $((4 \times (8^5)) \times (38 - (8 \times 2)))$
2883586 := $((-((6 - 8)^{5 \times 3}) \times 88) + 2)$
2883588 := $((8 \times (8^5)) \times (3 + 8)) + (8/2)$
2883683 := $((3 + 8) \times ((6 + 3) + (8^{8-2})))$
2883688 := $((8 + (8^6)) \times (3 + 8)) + (8 \times 2)$
2883689 := $((9 + (8^6)) \times (3 + 8)) + (8 - 2)$
2884288 := $((88/2) \times ((4^8) + (8 \times 2)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2889658 &:= (((8^5) + 69) \times 88) + 2 \\
 2889816 &:= 6 \times ((1 - 8) \times 98 - 8)^2 \\
 2892666 &:= -((6 - ((6^6) \times ((2^9)/8) - 2))) \\
 2892672 &:= (((2 + 7) \times 62) \times ((9 \times 8)^2)) \\
 2893597 &:= ((7 + ((9^5) - 3)) \times (98/2)) \\
 2893737 &:= ((7 \times 3) \times ((7 \times (3^9)) + (8 \times 2))) \\
 2894283 &:= (((3^8) + 2) \times (((4 + 9) + 8)^2)) \\
 2896896 &:= (69 \times (((8 - 6)^9) \times 82)) \\
 2920681 &:= ((1 - 860) \times 2 + 9)^2 \\
 2926125 &:= (5 \times (((21 \times (6^2)) + 9)^2)) \\
 2927521 &:= (((1 \times 2) + 57) \times 29)^2 \\
 2929593 &:= -(((3 \times ((9 - (5^9))/2)) + (9^2))) \\
 2934369 &:= (9 + 6 - 3 \times 4^3 \times 9)^2 \\
 2939328 &:= (((8^2) \times ((3^9)/3)) \times (9 - 2)) \\
 2939349 &:= (((((9 \times 4)^3) \times 9) + 3) \times (9 - 2)) \\
 2939657 &:= (7 \times (((5 + (6^{9-3})) \times 9) + 2)) \\
 2941225 &:= ((5 + 2)^{2+1} \times (4 - 9))^2 \\
 2944656 &:= ((6 - (5 \times ((6 - 44) \times 9)))^2) \\
 2949158 &:= (((((8^5) \times (1 + 9)) + 4) \times 9) + 2) \\
 2949849 &:= (9 \times (((4^8) \times (9 - 4)) + (9^2))) \\
 2952936 &:= (6 \times (((3^9) \times 25) + (9^2))) \\
 2957312 &:= (2 \times ((1 + (((3^7) \times 5)/9))^2)) \\
 2958375 &:= (((5 \times 7)^3) \times ((8 + 59) + 2)) \\
 2965282 &:= -((2 - ((82 \times ((5 \times 6) - 9))^2))) \\
 2981958 &:= (((8^5) \times 91) + ((8 \times 9) - 2)) \\
 2985464 &:= (((((4 \times 6)^4) - 58) \times 9) + 2) \\
 2985626 &:= (((6 \times 2)^6) - (((5 \times 8) \times 9) - 2)) \\
 2985634 &:= (((4 \times 3)^6) - (5 \times ((8 \times 9) - 2))) \\
 2985892 &:= (((2 \times 9) \times 8)^{-5+8}) - (92) \\
 2985966 &:= (((6 + 6)^{9+5-8}) - (9 \times 2)) \\
 2985968 &:= -((8 \times (((6^9)/(5 - 8) \times 9)) + 2))) \\
 2985982 &:= -((2 - (((8 \times 9)^5)/8)/(9^2))) \\
 2985984 &:= (4 \times (((((8 + 9) - 5) \times 8) \times 9)^2)) \\
 2986016 &:= ((6 + 10) \times (((6^8)/9) + 2)) \\
 2986048 &:= (8 \times ((4 + ((06^8)/9)) \times 2)) \\
 2986057 &:= (((7 + 5)^{06}) - 8) + (9^2) \\
 2986075 &:= (((5 + 7)^{06}) + 89) + 2 \\
 2986084 &:= (((4 + 8)^{06}) + 8) + 92 \\
 2986162 &:= (((2 \times 6) \times 1)^6) + (89 \times 2) \\
 2986273 &:= (((3 + 7) + 2)^6) + ((8 + 9)^2) \\
 2986368 &:= (8 \times (((6^3) + (6^8))/9) \times 2) \\
 2986568 &:= 8 \times (6 - 5 - 68 \times 9)^2 \\
 2986626 &:= (((6 \times 2)^6) - 6) + (8 \times (9^2)) \\
 2986632 &:= ((2^3) \times (((6^6) \times 8) + (9^2))) \\
 2986675 &:= (((5 + 7)^6) + 689) + 2 \\
 2986688 &:= (8 \times ((8 \times (6^6)) + (8 \times (9 + 2)))) \\
 2999824 &:= ((4 + ((2 \times 8) \times (9 + 99)))^2) \\
 3046875 &:= ((5^7) \times (((8 - 6) + 40) - 3)) \\
 3048625 &:= ((5 + ((2 \times 68) + 4))^{03}) \\
 3079329 &:= ((9 + 2) \times ((-(3 - 9))^7 + 03)) \\
 3111453 &:= -(((3^5) - ((41 + 1)^{1+3})) \\
 3111696 &:= (((6 + 9) + 6) \times (1 + 1)^{1+3}) \\
 3112128 &:= -((8 - ((2 + (12^{1+1}))^3))) \\
 3112136 &:= (((6 \times (3 - 1))^2) + (1 + 1)^3) \\
 3125688 &:= 8 \times (86 + 5^{(2 \times 1)^3}) \\
 3127323 &:= (3 - 2^{3+7})^2 \times 1 \times 3 \\
 3145671 &:= ((((((1 + 7)^6) - 5) \times 4) + 1) \times 3) \\
 3145686 &:= ((6 + (((8^6) - 5) \times 4)) \times (1 \times 3)) \\
 3145719 &:= ((((((9 \times 1) + 7)^5) - 4) + 1) \times 3) \\
 3145722 &:= -(((2 - ((27 + 5)^4)) \times (1 \times 3))) \\
 3145724 &:= -((4 - (((27 + 5)^4) \times 1) \times 3)) \\
 3145728 &:= (((8 \times ((2 + 7) - 5))^4) \times (1 \times 3)) \\
 3145731 &:= (((((1 \times 37) - 5)^4) + 1) \times 3) \\
 3145734 &:= (((4^{3+7}) + ((5 - 4) + 1)) \times 3) \\
 3145746 &:= ((6 + (((4 + 7) + 5)^{4+1})) \times 3) \\
 3145848 &:= (8 \times ((4 + (((8^5) \times 4) + 1)) \times 3)) \\
 3146829 &:= (((92 + (8^6)) \times 4) - 1) \times 3 \\
 3149255 &:= -((5 \times (5 - (((2 \times 9)^{4+1})/3))) \\
 3149256 &:= (6 \times ((5 \times ((2 \times 9)^4)) - (1 + 3))) \\
 3149265 &:= (5 \times ((6 \times ((2 \times 9)^4)) - (1 \times 3))) \\
 3149295 &:= (5 \times ((9 + ((2 \times 9)^{4+1}))/3)) \\
 3176523 &:= (((((32 - 5) - 6) \times 7) \times 1)^3) \\
 3176709 &:= (((9 \times ((07^6) + 7)) - 1) \times 3) \\
 3176736 &:= (((6 + 3) \times (7^6)) + 71) \times 3 \\
 3176739 &:= (((9 \times 3) \times (7^6)) + ((7 - 1)^3)) \\
 3176793 &:= ((3 \times 9) \times (((7^6) + 7) \times 1) + 3) \\
 3183597 &:= (((((7 + 95)^3) - 8) - 1) \times 3) \\
 3186247 &:= -((((7^4) - 2) - (6 \times (81^3))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3188376 &:= -((6 \times ((7 + 38) - (81^3)))) \\ 3188436 &:= -((6 \times ((3 + (4 \times 8)) - (81^3)))) \\ 3188556 &:= (6 \times ((5 \times (5 - 8)) + (81^3))) \\ 3188564 &:= -((4 + (6 \times ((5 + 8) - (81^3)))) \\ 3188598 &:= (((8 - 9) - 5) \times (8 - (81^3))) \\ 3188638 &:= -((8 + ((3 \times (6 - 8)) \times (81^3)))) \\ 3188643 &:= -((3 - (((4 - 6) + 8) \times (81^3)))) \\ 3188646 &:= (6 \times (((4 + 68) + 8) + 1^3)) \\ 3188662 &:= ((2^6) - (6 \times (8 - (81^3)))) \\ 3188673 &:= -(((3 \times 7) - (6 \times (8 + (81^3)))) \\ 3188676 &:= (6 \times (((7 + 6) - 8) + (81^3))) \\ 3188683 &:= -(((3 + 8) - (6 \times (8 + (81^3)))) \\ 3188692 &:= -((2 - (((9^6) + 8) \times ((8 + 1) - 3)))) \\ 3188694 &:= (((4 \times 9)/6) \times (8 + (81^3))) \\ 3188696 &:= ((6 \times ((9^6) + 8)) + (8/(1 + 3))) \\ 3188976 &:= (6 \times (((7 \times 9) - 8) + (81^3))) \\ 3189186 &:= (6 \times ((81 + 9) + (81^3))) \\ 3217767 &:= (7 \times (((677 + 1)^2) - 3)) \\ 3218513 &:= (31 \times (((5 \times (8 + 1)) + 2)^3)) \\ 3222928 &:= (82 \times (((9 \times 2) \times 2) - 2)^3)) \\ 3223716 &:= (6 \times (((1 + 732)^2) - 3)) \\ 3223734 &:= (((4 + ((3^7)/3))^2) \times (2 \times 3)) \\ 3226572 &:= (((((2 \times 7)^5) - 62) \times 2) \times 3) \\ 3227256 &:= (6 \times (52 + ((7 \times 2)^{2+3}))) \\ 3232539 &:= ((((((9^3) + 5)^2) \times 3) \times 2) + 3) \\ 3233984 &:= (((4 + (8 \times (9 - 3)))^3) \times 23) \\ 3234816 &:= (((6 - 1) + 8) \times ((4 \times 3)^{2+3})) \\ 3241792 &:= (((297 - 1)/4) \times 2^3) \\ 3250812 &:= (2 - 1805)^2 + 3 \\ 3255136 &:= -((((6^3) + 1) - ((5^5)^2))/3) \\ 3255181 &:= -(((1 + 81) - ((5^5)^2))/3) \\ 3255182 &:= (((2 - 81) + ((5^5)^2))/3) \\ 3255186 &:= -((((68 - 1) - ((5^5)^2))/3) \\ 3255195 &:= -((((5 \times (9 - 1)) - ((5^5)^2))/3) \\ 3255205 &:= (((5 \times (0 - 2)) + ((5^5)^2))/3) \\ 3255209 &:= (((((9 \times 0) + 25)^5) + 2)/3) \\ 3255225 &:= (52 + 25^5 - 2)/3 \\ 3263547 &:= (((7 \times (453 - 6))^2)/3) \\ 3265915 &:= -((5 \times (1 - ((9 + 5) \times ((6^2)^3)))) \\ 3265935 &:= (5 \times (3 + ((9 + 5) \times ((6^2)^3)))) \\ 3277457 &:= -(((7^5) - (4 \times ((7^7) + 23)))) \\ 3292515 &:= (5 \times (((1 + 5) \times 29)/2)^3) \\ 3294077 &:= (((7^7) \times 04) - 92) - 3) \\ 3294177 &:= (((((7^7) + 1) \times 4) + 9) - (2^3)) \\ 3294184 &:= (4 \times (((8 - (1^4))^{9-2}) + 3)) \\ 3294187 &:= (((7^{8-1}) \times 4) + ((9 \times 2) - 3)) \\ 3296748 &:= (84 \times (((7^6) + 92)/3)) \\ 3296875 &:= (-((5^7)) - (-8) \times (-((6 - (9^2))^3))) \\ 3308226 &:= ((6 + (2 \times ((2 + 80)^3))) \times 3) \\ 3308256 &:= (6 \times (5 + (((2 + 80)^3) + 3))) \\ 3311289 &:= (((((9^8) - 2) - 1)/13) + 3) \\ 3316897 &:= -((7 - ((9 + 8) \times ((61 - 3)^3)))) \\ 3322293 &:= (39 \times ((2 \times 22)^3) + 3) \\ 3327756 &:= -((6 \times (5 - ((7^{7-2}) \times 33))) \\ 3333456 &:= (6 \times (((54 + 3)^3) \times 3) - 3) \\ 3337929 &:= (((9 \times 29) \times 7)^{(3+3)/3}) \\ 3339549 &:= ((9^4) \times (((5 + (9/3))^3) - 3)) \\ 3342489 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((4^2)^4) + 3) \times 3) \\ 3343665 &:= (5 \times (((6^6)/3) \times 43) - 3) \\ 3355862 &:= (((2 \times (6^8)) + 5) - ((5 \times 3)^3)) \\ 3358764 &:= (4 \times (((6^7) - (8 \times 5)) \times 3) + 3) \\ 3358896 &:= (((6^9) - 8) - (8 \times (5^3)))/3) \\ 3358989 &:= (9 \times (((8 \times 9)^{8-5}) - (3^3))) \\ 3359169 &:= -((9 \times ((6 + 1) - ((9 \times (5 + 3))^3)))) \\ 3359227 &:= (((7 - (2/2))^9) - (5 \times 3))/3) \\ 3359231 &:= (((1 + ((3 \times 2)^9) + 5))/3) - 3) \\ 3359234 &:= ((4 + (((3 \times 2)^9) + 5) - 3))/3) \\ 3359235 &:= (((5 \times ((3 \times 2)^9))/(5 \times 3)) + 3) \\ 3359236 &:= (((6^3)^2) + ((9 - 5) \times 3))/3) \\ 3359237 &:= ((7 + (((3 \times 2)^9) + 5) + 3))/3) \\ 3359259 &:= (9 \times ((5 - 2) + ((9 \times (5 + 3))^3))) \\ 3359262 &:= (((2 \times (6^{-2+9})) + (5)) \times (3 + 3)) \\ 3359286 &:= (((6^8) \times 2) + 9) + ((5 \times 3) \times 3) \\ 3359375 &:= ((5^7) \times ((39 - 5) + (3 \times 3))) \\ 3359376 &:= (((6^7) + 3) + 9) \times ((5 \times 3) - 3) \\ 3359799 &:= (9 \times ((9 \times 7) + ((9 \times (5 + 3))^3))) \\ 3362797 &:= -((((7^9) - 7)/((2 - 6) \times 3)) + 3) \\ 3365793 &:= ((3^9) \times ((75 - (6 \times 3)) \times 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3374583 &:= (3 \times ((8 \times ((5 + 47)^3)) - 3)) \\ 3374586 &:= -((6 - (8 \times (((5 + 47)^3) \times 3)))) \\ 3374592 &:= ((2^9) \times (((5 \times 4) - 7)^3) \times 3) \\ 3374986 &:= -(((6 + 8) - ((9 + (47 \times 3))^3))) \\ 3374991 &:= -(((1 \times 9) - ((9 + (47 \times 3))^3))) \\ 3374995 &:= -((5 - (((9 \times 9) - 4) + 73)^3)) \\ 3374997 &:= (((((7 \times 9) + 94) - 7)^3) - 3) \\ 3374999 &:= -(((9/9) - ((9 + (47 \times 3))^3))) \\ 3375003 &:= ((-((300/(5 - 7)))^3) + 3) \\ 3376528 &:= (8 \times (2 + (((5^6) + 7) \times (3^3)))) \\ 3412935 &:= (((53 \times 9)^2) \times ((1 + 4) \times 3)) \\ 3417958 &:= -((8 - (((((5^9) \times 7) + 1)/4) - 3))) \\ 3417972 &:= (((((-((2 - 7)^9) \times (-7)) - 1)/(-4)) + 3) \\ 3424361 &:= (1 - 6 \times 3)^4 \times (-2 + 43) \\ 3428352 &:= (((2^{5+3}) - 8) \times (24^3)) \\ 3441667 &:= -(((7 - (6^{6-1})) \times 443)) \\ 3442688 &:= (((88 - 6)^2) \times ((4 + 4)^3)) \\ 3442951 &:= (((15 + 92) + 44)^3) \\ 3445435 &:= ((5 \times ((3 + 4)^5)) \times (44 - 3)) \\ 3463911 &:= -((11 \times ((9 - ((3 \times 6)^4)) \times 3))) \\ 3469824 &:= ((4 + ((2^8) - 9)) \times ((6 \times 4)^3)) \\ 3479616 &:= (((6^{-1+6}) - 9) \times (7 \times (4^3))) \\ 3482859 &:= (((9 \times (5^8)) + 2) - ((8 \times 4)^3)) \\ 3483642 &:= -(((2 - (((4 \times 6)^3) \times 84)) \times 3)) \\ 3483644 &:= -((4 - (((4 \times 6)^3) \times 84) \times 3)) \\ 3483648 &:= (((((8 - 4) \times 6)^3) \times 84) \times 3) \\ 3492544 &:= -(((4 - 45) \times (((2 + 9) \times 4)^3))) \\ 3497859 &:= (9 \times ((5^8) - ((7 \times 94) \times 3))) \\ 3499875 &:= ((5 \times (7 + 8)) \times (9 + ((9 \times 4)^3))) \\ 3511799 &:= -((9 - ((97 + (11 \times 5))^3))) \\ 3511808 &:= (8 \times (((081 \times 1) - 5)^3)) \\ 3515594 &:= (-4) - (-9) \times (((5 \times 5)^{-1+5}) - 3)) \\ 3515625 &:= ((5^{2 \times 6 - 5}) \times (15 \times 3)) \\ 3515759 &:= ((9 \times (((5^7) \times 5) + 1)) + (5^3)) \\ 3515949 &:= (9 \times ((4 \times 9) + (5^{1 \times 5 + 3}))) \\ 3518667 &:= (((((76 \times 6)/8)^{-1+5})/3) \\ 3519376 &:= ((67 \times ((3 \times 9) + 1))^{5-3}) \\ 3529467 &:= -((((7^6) \times ((4 - 9) - 25)) + 3)) \\ 3536492 &:= (((((29^4) + (6 \times 3)) \times 5) - 3) \\ 3538476 &:= -(((6 \times (((((7 - (4^8)) \times 3) + 5) \times 3))) \\ 3538884 &:= (4 \times (((8 + 88)^3) - (5 \times 3))) \\ 3538929 &:= ((9 \times ((2^{9+8}) \times 3)) - (5 \times 3)) \\ 3538942 &:= -((2 - (4 \times (((98 + 3) - 5)^3))) \\ 3538944 &:= (4 \times (((((4 + 9) \times 8) - 3) - 5)^3)) \\ 3542964 &:= (4 \times (6 + (((9^{2+4}) \times 5)/3))) \\ 3543122 &:= 2 \times (2 - 13)^{4+5-3} \\ 3545856 &:= ((6^5) \times ((8 - 5) + 453)) \\ 3563777 &:= (7 \times ((7^7) - ((3 + 65)^3))) \\ 3566592 &:= -(((2 - (9 \times 5)) \times (((6 + 6)^5)/3))) \\ 3576742 &:= (2 \times (((4 + 7)^6) + ((7^5) + 3))) \\ 3577728 &:= (((8 - 2) \times 7) \times (((7 \times 7) - 5)^3)) \\ 3579891 &:= (((1 + 9) \times 8) - 9) \times ((7^5) \times 3) \\ 3586446 &:= -((6 \times ((4 \times (4^6)) - (85^3)))) \\ 3595278 &:= (((87^2) \times 5) \times 95) + 3) \\ 3609576 &:= -(((6 - ((7^5) - 90)) \times (6^3))) \\ 3612672 &:= ((2^{7+6}) \times (21^{6/3})) \\ 3631688 &:= -((8 - (8 \times (((61^3) \times 6)/3))) \\ 3639168 &:= (((8 + 61) + 9) \times (36^3)) \\ 3639375 &:= -(((5^{7-3}) \times (9 - ((3 \times 6)^3))) \\ 3647079 &:= (9 \times (7 + (074^{6-3}))) \\ 3649536 &:= ((6 \times (35 + 9)) \times ((4 \times 6)^3)) \\ 3652257 &:= -((7 - (((5 + 2) \times 2) \times (5 + 6)^3))) \\ 3652262 &:= -((2 - (((6 - 2) + (25 \times 6)^3))) \\ 3652264 &:= (((((4 + 6)^2) - 2) + 56)^3) \\ 3652328 &:= ((8^2) + (((32 \times 5) - 6)^3)) \\ 3654996 &:= -(((69 - (9^4)) \times 563)) \\ 3656223 &:= ((3^2) \times ((26 \times (5^6)) - 3)) \\ 3656229 &:= -(((9 \times (2 - (26 \times (5^6)))) + 3)) \\ 3656235 &:= -(((5 - ((3 \times 26) \times (5^6))) \times 3)) \\ 3656276 &:= ((6 + 7) \times (2 + (6 \times ((5^6) \times 3)))) \\ 3656367 &:= (((7 \times 6) - 3) \times ((6 \times (5^6)) + 3)) \\ 3657879 &:= -((9 - (78 \times ((7 + (5^6)) \times 3))) \\ 3671875 &:= ((5^7) \times (((8 \times 1) \times 7) - 6) - 3)) \\ 3675648 &:= (8 \times (((4^6) \times 5) + (76^3))) \\ 3678724 &:= ((4 - 278) \times 7)^{6/3} \\ 3687936 &:= -(((6 - (3 \times 9)) \times ((7 \times 8)^{6-3})) \\ 3691478 &:= (((8^7) + 4) - 1) + ((9^6) \times 3) \\ 3718383 &:= (((((3^8) - 3) \times 81) \times 7) - 3) \end{aligned}$$

- 3723875** := (((((5 - 7) + 83) × 2) - 7)³)
3732475 := -((5 - (((74 - 2)³) × (7 + 3))))
3748096 := (((6 × ((9 × 0) + 8)) - 4)⁷⁻³)
3748169 := (9 - 61 + 8)⁴ + 73
3748312 := 2 × (1 - 38)⁴ - 7 - 3
3748322 := (2 × (((2 + 3) + (8 × 4))⁷⁻³))
3748439 := (((9 + 3) + (4 × 8))⁴) + (7³)
3748699 := -((((9 - 9⁶) - (8⁴) × 7) - 3))
3749848 := -((8 - (48 × ((9 - 4)⁷) - 3)))
3759453 := 3⁻⁵⁺⁴⁺⁹ × 573
3759459 := (9 × (((5⁴) + (9⁵)) × 7)) - 3
3764695 := -((((5 + 9)⁶) / (4 - 6)) + 73)
3764768 := (((8 + 6)⁷) / (((4 × 6) + 7) - 3))
3767815 := -((5 × ((1 × 8) - (((7 + 6) × 7)³))))
3767825 := (5 × ((2 - 8) + (((7 + 6) × 7)³)))
3767855 := (5 × (((5 + 87) + 6) - 7)³)
3767865 := -((5 × ((6 - 8) - (((7 + 6) × 7)³))))
3772575 := (575 × ((2 + 7)⁷⁻³)
3773077 := ((7 + (70³)) × ((7 + 7) - 3))
3774372 := -((2 × (((7 × 3)⁴) - (7⁷)) × 3))
3778896 := (((((6⁹) / 8) - 87) + 7) × 3)
3779328 := ((8²) × (((3⁹) + (7 / 7)) × 3))
3779486 := (((((6⁸) / 4) × 9) + 7) + (7³))
3781575 := ((5 × (7⁵)) × (((1 × 8) + 7) × 3))
3796416 := (((61 + 4) - 6) + 97)³
3796875 := (5 × ((7 + 8)⁶⁺⁹⁻⁷⁻³)
3796878 := ((8 + (((7 + 8)⁶) / 9) - 7) × 3)
3816336 := (6 × (((33 + 61) - 8)³)
3837776 := -(((6⁷) + (((7⁷) × (3 - 8)) + 3)))
3840243 := (((3⁴) + ((20⁴) × 8)) × 3)
3840264 := ((4 × 6) × (((20⁴) + 8) + 3))
3841673 := (37 × (6 + (-((1 - 48)³)))
3843202 := (2 × ((02 + ((3 + 4)⁸)) / 3))
3843228 := ((82 + (2 × ((3 + 4)⁸))) / 3)
3843359 := ((95³) + ((3 × 48)³)
3859573 := (-3) + (7 × (-((5 - 95) + 8)³)))
3865221 := (((((1 × 22)⁵) × 6) / 8) - 3)
3865224 := (((4 + (22⁵)) × 6) / 8) - 3)
3865228 := (((8 + ((22⁵) × 6)) / 8) + 3)
3865368 := ((((((8 + 6) - 3)⁵) + 6) × 8) × 3)
3865386 := ((6 + (((8 + 3)⁵) + 6) × 8)) × 3)
3866472 := (((2 - 74) + (6⁶)) × 83)
3866624 := -(((4²⁺⁶) × ((6 - 68) + 3)))
3866628 := (82 × ((6⁶) + (6 × 83)))
3868215 := (-51 + (2 - 8)⁶) × 83
3869878 := -(((8 + 7) - ((89 + 68)³)))
3869893 := (((((3 × 9) × 8) + 9) - 68)³)
3869896 := -(((6 - 9) - ((89 + 68)³)))
3875236 := -((((6 + 3) × 2)⁵) - ((7⁸) + 3))
3893395 := (-5) × (9 - (-((3 + 3) - 98)³))
3893475 := (-5) × (-7 - (-((4 - ((3 + 9) × 8))³)))
3895864 := (4 × ((6 + (8⁵)) + (98³)))
3897432 := (2 × (((3⁴⁺⁷) + 9) × (8 + 3)))
3898657 := (((7 + 5)⁶) + ((89 + 8)³)
3906295 := (((5⁹) × 2) + ((6 + 09) × 3))
3918464 := (46 × (-((4 × (8 - 19))³)))
3931775 := -((5 × (77 - ((1 + 3)⁹) × 3))
3931985 := -((5 × (8 + ((9 - ((1 + 3)⁹) × 3))))
3932155 := -((5 - (5 × (((1²) + 3)⁹) × 3))
3932295 := (5 × ((9 + ((2 / 2) + 3)⁹) × 3))
3932745 := (5 × (((4⁷⁺²) + 39) × 3))
3935585 := -((5 × (((8 × 5) × (5 - (3⁹))) + 3))
3936585 := (5 × (((8 × 5) × ((6 - 3)⁹) - 3))
3942396 := (((69³) + 24) × (9 + 3))
3943095 := (5 × (((9⁰³) + (4⁹)) × 3))
3944165 := (5 × (((6 + 1)⁴) + ((4⁹) × 3))
3944311 := (-1) + (-((1 - (3 × (4 + 49))))³)
3944312 := (((2 × ((1 × 3)⁴) - 4)^{9/3})
3954396 := (((69³) + (4⁵)) × (9 + 3))
3956376 := ((67 × ((3 + 6)⁵)) + 93)
3981309 := (((9 + 03)⁻¹⁺⁸) / 9) - 3)
3981315 := (((((5 - 1) × 3)⁻¹⁺⁸) / 9) + 3)
3984375 := ((5⁷) × ((3 × 48) - 93))
3987375 := (((5 × 7)³) × ((7 + 89) - 3))
3998416 := (((61 × (4⁸)) - 9) + (9³))
4100625 := (((52 - 6) - 001)⁴)
4117565 := -((5 × ((6 × 5) - (7¹¹⁻⁴)))
4117675 := (5 × (((7⁶) × 7) - ((1 + 1) × 4)))

- 4117705 := $(5 \times (((07^7) + 1) + 1) - 4)$
4117765 := $((5 + 6) + ((7^7) - 1)) \times (1 + 4)$
4117768 := $((8 \times 6) + (((7^7) + 1) \times (1 + 4)))$
4117769 := $((9 \times 6) + ((7^7) \times ((1 \times 1) + 4)))$
4117775 := $(5 \times (((((7^7) + 7) + 1) \times 1) + 4))$
4117785 := $((5 + 8) + ((7^7) + 1)) \times (1 + 4)$
4117795 := $(5 \times (9 + (((7^7) + 11) - 4)))$
4117835 := $(5 \times ((3 \times 8) + (7^{11-4})))$
4128768 := $((((8^6) \times 7) \times ((8 + 2) - 1)) / 4)$
4128894 := $((((4^9) + 8) \times ((8^2) - 1)) / 4)$
4148871 := $(-1) - (-7) \times (-8) + (84^{-1+4})))$
4148924 := $(-4) - ((2 - 9) \times (84^{-1+4})))$
4148928 := $((8 \times 2) - 9) \times (84^{-1+4})$
4149248 := $-(((8^4) \times ((2 + 9) - (4^{1+4}))))$
4168136 := $((((6^3) + 1) \times 8) \times ((6 + 1)^4))$
4173263 := $(-((3 \times 6) + ((23 \times 7)^{-1+4}))$
4173272 := $(-((2 + 7) + ((23 \times 7)^{-1+4}))$
4173279 := $(-((9 - 7) + ((23 \times 7)^{-1+4}))$
4173281 := $(-(((1 - 8) \times 23))^{7 \times 1 - 4})$
4178304 := $((403 \times 8) \times ((7 - 1)^4))$
4192479 := $((9 \times 7) + (4 \times 2)) \times (9^{1+4})$
4193684 := $((4 \times ((8^6) - 39)) + 1) \times 4$
4193782 := $(2 \times ((8^7) - (3 \times (91 - 4))))$
4193792 := $-(((2^9) - (((7 - 3)^{9+1}) \times 4)))$
4194062 := $(-((2 + ((60 - (4^{9+1})) \times 4)))$
4194064 := $(-((4 \times (60 - (((4^9) \times 1) \times 4))))$
4194172 := $(-(((2^7) + ((1 - (4^{9+1})) \times 4)))$
4194178 := $((8^{7+1}) / 4) - (9 \times 14)$
4194192 := $(-(((29 - 1) - (4^{9+1})) \times 4))$
4194212 := $(-(((21 + 2) - (4^{9+1})) \times 4))$
4194223 := $(-(((3^2)^2) - ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)))$
4194224 := $((4 \times 2) \times 2) \times (((4^9) - 1) - 4)$
4194232 := $(-(((2 \times (3^2)) - (4^{9+1})) \times 4))$
4194251 := $(-(((1 + 52) - ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)))$
4194256 := $((6 + (5 \times 2)) \times (((4^9) + 1) - 4))$
4194257 := $(-((7 + (((5 \times 2) - (4^{9+1})) \times 4)))$
4194259 := $(-(((9 \times 5) - (2^{4 \times 9 - 14})))$
4194264 := $((((4^6)^2) / 4) - ((9 + 1) \times 4))$
4194266 := $(-(((6 \times 6) + 2) - ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)))$
4194268 := $((8^6) \times (2^4)) - ((9 \times 1) \times 4)$
4194272 := $((2^{(7-2) \times 4}) - (9 - 1)) \times 4$
4194274 := $(-(((4 \times 7) + 2) - ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)))$
4194277 := $(-((7 + (((7 - 2) - (4^{9+1})) \times 4)))$
4194292 := $((2^{9 \times 2 + 4}) - ((9 - 1) + 4))$
4194294 := $((4^{9+2}) - (((4 + 9) + 1) - 4))$
4194299 := $((((9 + 9) - 2) \times (4^9)) - (1 + 4))$
4194302 := $(-((2 - (((0 \times 3) + 4)^{9+1}) \times 4)))$
4194303 := $((3 / (0 - 3)) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4))$
4194304 := $(4^{034-9-14})$
4194306 := $((6 / 03) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4))$
4194307 := $((7 \times 0) + 3) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)$
4194308 := $(-((8 + (((0 - 3) - (4^{9+1})) \times 4)))$
4194311 := $(-((1 + (((1 - 3) - (4^{9+1})) \times 4)))$
4194312 := $((2 \times 1)^3) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)$
4194313 := $((3 \times 1) \times 3) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)$
4194315 := $(-((5 - ((1 + 3) \times (((4^9) + 1) \times 4))))$
4194316 := $((6 \times 1) - 3) + (4^{9+1}) \times 4$
4194318 := $(-(((8 \times (1 - 3)) \times (4^9)) - 14))$
4194322 := $(-((2 - (((2 + 3) + (4^{9+1})) \times 4)))$
4194324 := $(4 \times ((2 + 3) + (((4^9) \times 1) \times 4)))$
4194325 := $((5 + 2) \times 3) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)$
4194328 := $(8 \times ((2 \times (3 + (4^9))) + (1 - 4)))$
4194331 := $((1 \times 3)^3) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)$
4194332 := $(-(((2 - (3 \times 3)) - (4^{9+1})) \times 4))$
4194335 := $(-((5 - (((3 \times 3) + (4^{9+1})) \times 4)))$
4194336 := $((6 / 3)^3) + (4^{9+1}) \times 4$
4194337 := $((7 \times 3) + ((3 + (4^{9+1})) \times 4))$
4194344 := $((4^4)^3 / 4) + ((9 + 1) \times 4)$
4194346 := $((6 \times (4 + 3)) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4))$
4194348 := $((8 - 4) \times (3 + (4^9))) - 1 \times 4$
4194352 := $((2 \times (5 + 3)) \times (((4^9) - 1) + 4))$
4194357 := $(-((7 - (((5 \times 3) + (4^{9+1})) \times 4)))$
4194367 := $((7 \times (6 + 3)) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4))$
4194368 := $((8 \times 6) / 3) \times (((4^9) \times 1) + 4)$
4194372 := $((2 \times 7) + 3) + (4^{9+1}) \times 4$
4194379 := $((9 \times 7) + ((3 + (4^{9+1})) \times 4))$
4194384 := $((48 / 3) \times (((4^9) + 1) + 4))$
4194396 := $((69 / 3) + (4^{9+1})) \times 4$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4194416 &:= (((6+1) \times 4) + (4^{9+1})) \times 4 \\
 4194432 &:= ((2^{3+4}) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)) \\
 4194435 &:= -((5 - ((34 + (4^{9+1})) \times 4))) \\
 4194448 &:= (((8 \times 4)^4) + (4 \times 9)) \times (1 \times 4) \\
 4194452 &:= (((2^5)^4) + ((4 \times 9) + 1)) \times 4 \\
 4194464 &:= (4 \times (((6+4) + (4^9)) \times (1 \times 4))) \\
 4194476 &:= (((6 \times 7) + ((4 \times (4^9)) + 1)) \times 4) \\
 4194484 &:= (4 \times (((8 \times 4)^4) + (9 \times (1+4)))) \\
 4194492 &:= ((2 \times 94) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)) \\
 4194504 &:= ((40 \times 5) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)) \\
 4194528 &:= (((8 \times (2+5)) + (4^{9+1})) \times 4) \\
 4194529 &:= ((9 \times 25) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)) \\
 4194536 &:= (((63-5) + (4^{9+1})) \times 4) \\
 4194547 &:= (((7-4)^5) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)) \\
 4194562 &:= -((2 - ((65 + (4^{9+1})) \times 4))) \\
 4194564 &:= (4 \times (65 + (((4^9) \times 1) \times 4))) \\
 4194588 &:= (((8 \times (((8^5) \times 4) + 9)) - 1) \times 4) \\
 4194624 &:= ((4^2) \times (6 + ((4^9) + 14))) \\
 4194684 &:= (4 \times (((8^6) \times 4) + 91) + 4) \\
 4194688 &:= ((8 \times 8) \times (6 + (((4^9) \times 1)/4))) \\
 4194766 &:= ((66 \times 7) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)) \\
 4194944 &:= (4 \times (((4^9) + (4 \times (9+1))) \times 4)) \\
 4194997 &:= ((7 \times 99) + ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)) \\
 4196488 &:= (((8^8)/4) + ((6 \times 91) \times 4)) \\
 4197468 &:= (((8^6) \times 4) + 791) \times 4 \\
 4214782 &:= -((2 - (((8 \times 7)^{4-1}) \times 24))) \\
 4214784 &:= (4 \times (((8 \times 7)^{4-1}) \times (2+4))) \\
 4214809 &:= (((9 + ((08^4) + 1))^2)/4) \\
 4218557 &:= -(((7^5) \times (5 - (((8 \times 1)^2) \times 4)))) \\
 4229826 &:= 6 \times (2 + 89^{-2/2+4}) \\
 4239872 &:= (2 \times (((7-8) + (9^3))^2) \times 4) \\
 4243686 &:= (6 \times (((8+63) - 42)^4)) \\
 4249448 &:= -((8 \times ((4^4) - ((9^{4+2}) - 4)))) \\
 4251528 &:= (8 \times (((2 \times 5) + 15) + 2)^4) \\
 4251532 &:= ((2 \times (((3^5) \times (1+5))^2)) + 4) \\
 4251536 &:= (((6 \times (3^{5+1+5})) + 2) \times 4) \\
 4251544 &:= (4 \times (((4+5)^{1+5}) \times 2) + 4) \\
 4251548 &:= ((8 \times (((4+5)^{1+5}) + 2)) + 4) \\
 4251696 &:= ((6 + ((9^6) + 15)) \times (2 \times 4)) \\
 4253472 &:= (((27^4) + (3^5)) \times (2 \times 4)) \\
 4253929 &:= (((9 \times 2) \times 9)^3 + ((5+2)^4)) \\
 4258776 &:= -(((6 - (7 \times ((78 \times 5)^2))) \times 4)) \\
 4259571 &:= ((17^5) \times (((9+5)/2) - 4)) \\
 4259598 &:= (((8+9)^5) + 9) \times ((5+2) - 4) \\
 4263188 &:= -((8 - ((8 \times ((1+(3^6))^2)) - 4))) \\
 4292356 &:= (((6^5) \times 3) \times 2) \times 92 + 4 \\
 4294296 &:= 6 \times (9 \times (2 - 49))^2 \times 4 \\
 4296805 &:= (((5^08) - 6) \times (9+2)) - 4 \\
 4296875 &:= ((5^7) \times (((8 \times 6) + 9) + 2) - 4) \\
 4302557 &:= -((7 \times (5 - (((5^2) + 03)^4)))) \\
 4302592 &:= (((2 \times (9+5))^{2+03})/4) \\
 4313468 &:= (((8^6) \times 4) + (31^3)) \times 4 \\
 4354094 &:= -(((4-90) \times (4 + ((5 \times 3)^4)))) \\
 4358148 &:= (((8^{4+1}) \times (8 + (5^3))) + 4) \\
 4373968 &:= -((8 - (6 \times (((9 \times (3+7))^3) - 4)))) \\
 4373996 &:= ((6 \times ((9 \times ((9/3) + 7))^3)) - 4) \\
 4374752 &:= (2 \times (((5^7) - 4) \times 7) - 3) \times 4) \\
 4375056 &:= ((6+50) \times (((5^7) - 3) + 4)) \\
 4375168 &:= ((8+6) \times (((1 \times 5)^7) + 3) \times 4) \\
 4375448 &:= (8 \times (((4+4) + (5^7)) \times (3+4))) \\
 4375688 &:= (8 \times (86 + ((5^7) \times (3+4)))) \\
 4385662 &:= -((2 - ((6^6) \times ((5+8) + (3^4)))))) \\
 4394532 &:= (((((2+3)^{5+4}) \times 9) + 3)/4) \\
 4423655 &:= -((5 \times (5 - ((6^3) \times ((2 \times 4)^4)))))) \\
 4423695 &:= (5 \times (((96^3) + 2) + (4/4))) \\
 4437279 &:= (9 \times (((72+7)^3) - 4) - 4) \\
 4455516 &:= (6 \times (((1 + (5 \times 5))^5)/(4 \times 4))) \\
 4462655 &:= (-5 + (5 - 6 - 2^6)^4)/4 \\
 4464773 &:= (((3^7) - 74)^{6-4}) + 4 \\
 4473132 &:= -((23 \times (1 - (((3 \times 7)^4) + 4)))) \\
 4476516 &:= -(((615 - ((6^7) \times 4)) \times 4)) \\
 4476924 &:= -((4 + (((2^9) - ((6^7) \times 4)) \times 4))) \\
 4477335 &:= -5^3 + (3 - 7 \times 7)^4 + 4 \\
 4477388 &:= -8 \times 8 + (3 - 7 \times 7)^4 - 4 \\
 4477397 &:= -7 \times 9 + (3 - 7 \times 7)^4 + 4 \\
 4477446 &:= -6 - 4 + (4 \times 7 - 74)^4 \\
 4477448 &:= -((8 - (((4/4) + ((7 \times 7) - 4))^4))) \\
 4477452 &:= (((2 \times (((5+4) + 7) + 7))^4) - 4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4477453 &:= -((3 - (((5 - 4) + ((7 \times 7) - 4))^4))) \\
 4477456 &:= ((((((6 - 5) + 4) \times 7) + 7) + 4)^4) \\
 4478464 &:= -((((4^6) - ((4 + 8)^7)/(4 + 4))) \\
 4478768 &:= ((8 + (((6^7) - 8) - 7) \times 4) \times 4) \\
 4478848 &:= -(((8 - ((48/8)^7)) \times (4 \times 4))) \\
 4478968 &:= -((8 - ((6^{9-8})^{7}) \times (4 \times 4))) \\
 4478973 &:= -((3 - (((((7 - 9) + 8)^7) \times 4) \times 4))) \\
 4478976 &:= ((6^7) \times (((9 - 8) + 7)/4)^4) \\
 4478996 &:= ((((((6^9)/9) + 8) - 7) + 4) \times 4) \\
 4479312 &:= ((21 + (-((3 - 9))^7)) \times (4 \times 4)) \\
 4479328 &:= (8 \times ((2 \times (-((3 - 9))^7)) + 44)) \\
 4481163 &:= ((3^{6+1}) \times (1 + (8 \times (4^4)))) \\
 4484877 &:= -((((7^7) - 8) - ((48^4) - 4)) \\
 4497392 &:= (((2^9) \times ((3^7) + 9)) - 4) \times 4) \\
 4521984 &:= ((4^8) \times (9 + (((1 + 2) \times 5) \times 4))) \\
 4546777 &:= ((77 \times (((7 + 6) - 4)^5)) + 4) \\
 4555696 &:= ((6 \times ((9 + 6)^5)) - 554) \\
 4556196 &:= (6 \times (((((9 \times 1) + 6)^5) - 5) - 4)) \\
 4556226 &:= (6 \times (((((2 + 2) + 6) + 5)^5) - 4)) \\
 4556246 &:= ((6 \times (((4^2) - 6) + 5)^5)) - 4) \\
 4556276 &:= ((6 \times (((7 + 2) + 6)^5) + 5)) - 4) \\
 4587275 &:= -((5 \times ((7^2) - (7 \times ((8^5) \times 4)))) \\
 4587457 &:= (7 \times ((5 \times ((4^7) \times 8)) - (5 + 4))) \\
 4587475 &:= (5 \times ((7 \times ((4^7) \times 8)) - (5 + 4))) \\
 4587479 &:= -((((9 - (7 \times ((4^7) \times 8))) \times 5) - 4)) \\
 4587488 &:= -(((8 - (((8^4) \times 7) \times 8) \times 5)) \times 4) \\
 4587492 &:= -(((2 - 9) \times (((4^7) \times 8) \times 5) - 4)) \\
 4587495 &:= -((5 \times (9 - (((4 \times 7) \times (8^5)) + 4)))) \\
 4587496 &:= -(((6 - ((9 - 4) \times 7) \times (8^5))) \times 4) \\
 4587504 &:= (4 \times (((05 \times 7) \times (8^5)) - 4)) \\
 4587512 &:= -(((2 - (((1 \times 5) \times 7) \times (8^5))) \times 4)) \\
 4587513 &:= -((3 + ((1 - ((5 \times 7) \times (8^5))) \times 4))) \\
 4587515 &:= -((5 - (((1 \times 5) \times 7) \times ((8^5) \times 4))) \\
 4587517 &:= -((7 - ((1 + ((5 \times 7) \times (8^5))) \times 4))) \\
 4587521 &:= ((1^2) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((8^5) \times 4))) \\
 4587524 &:= ((((((4^2)^5) \times 7)/8) \times 5) + 4) \\
 4587531 &:= -((1 - ((3 + ((5 \times 7) \times (8^5))) \times 4))) \\
 4587535 &:= ((5 \times 3) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((8^5) \times 4))) \\
 4587552 &:= ((2^5) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((8^5) \times 4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4587568 &:= ((8 \times 6) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((8^5) \times 4))) \\
 4587574 &:= (((((4^7) \times 5) \times 7) \times 8) + 54) \\
 4587585 &:= (5 \times ((8 + 5) + (7 \times ((8^5) \times 4)))) \\
 4587592 &:= (((2 \times 9) + ((5 \times 7) \times (8^5))) \times 4) \\
 4587675 &:= (5 \times (7 + ((6 + (7 \times (8^5))) \times 4))) \\
 4587745 &:= -((5 \times (4 - (7 \times (7 + ((8^5) \times 4)))))) \\
 4593655 &:= (55 \times (((6 - 3) + 9) + 5)^4) \\
 4595616 &:= ((6^{-1+6}) \times (595 - 4)) \\
 4618944 &:= (((44 \times 9) \times (8 + 1)) \times (6^4)) \\
 4644862 &:= -((2 - (((6 + 8) \times (4^4)) \times (6^4)))) \\
 4644864 &:= (((4 + 6) + 8) - 4) \times ((4 \times 6)^4) \\
 4652843 &:= -(((3 - (4^8)) \times ((2 + 5) + 64))) \\
 4665125 &:= ((5^2) \times (1 - ((5 - (6^6)) \times 4))) \\
 4665556 &:= -((((6 + 5) - ((5 \times 5) \times (6^6))) \times 4)) \\
 4665568 &:= -(((8 - (((6 \times 5) - 5) \times (6^6))) \times 4)) \\
 4665571 &:= -((1 + ((7 - ((5 \times 5) \times (6^6))) \times 4))) \\
 4665576 &:= ((((((6^7) \times 5) \times 5)/6) - 6) \times 4) \\
 4665584 &:= (((4 - 8) + ((5 \times 5) \times (6^6))) \times 4) \\
 4665585 &:= -((5 \times ((8 - 5) - (5 \times ((6^6) \times 4)))) \\
 4665586 &:= -(((6 + 8) - ((5 \times 5) \times ((6^6) \times 4))) \\
 4665591 &:= -(((1 \times 9) - ((5 \times 5) \times ((6^6) \times 4))) \\
 4665592 &:= (2 \times (((9 \times 5) + 5) \times (6^6)) - 4) \\
 4665593 &:= -((3 - (((95 + 5) \times (6^6)) - 4)) \\
 4665595 &:= -((5 - (((9 \times 5) \times 5) \times ((6 + 6)^4)))) \\
 4665596 &:= (((((6 + 9) + 5) \times 5) \times (6^6)) - 4) \\
 4665597 &:= -((7 - (((95 + 5) \times (6^6)) + 4)) \\
 4665599 &:= -(((9/9) - ((5 \times 5) \times ((6^6) \times 4))) \\
 4665625 &:= ((5^2) \times ((6 - 5) + ((6^6) \times 4))) \\
 4665655 &:= (5 \times ((5 + 6) + (5 \times ((6^6) \times 4)))) \\
 4665725 &:= -(((5 \times (2 - 7)) \times (5 + ((6^6) \times 4)))) \\
 4665775 &:= (5 \times (7 + ((7 + (5 \times (6^6))) \times 4))) \\
 4674244 &:= (((4 + 42) \times 47)^{6-4}) \\
 4687506 &:= ((60 \times (5^7)) + ((8 - 6) + 4)) \\
 4687552 &:= (((((2 \times 5) \times (5^7)) + 8) \times 6) + 4) \\
 4688531 &:= -((1 - (3 \times (((5^8) + 86) \times 4)))) \\
 4718492 &:= (((2 \times 9) \times ((4^8) - 1)) - 7) \times 4) \\
 4718529 &:= -((9 \times ((2 + 5) - (((8 \times 1)^7)/4)))) \\
 4718664 &:= (((4 \times 6) - 6) \times ((8^{-1+7}) + (4))) \\
 4718692 &:= (2 \times ((9 \times (6 + (8^{-1+7}))) - (4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4719744 &:= (((4 + (4^7)) \times 9) \times ((1 + 7) \times 4)) \\
 4734936 &:= (((6 + (3 \times 9))^4) - (3^7)) \times 4 \\
 4735872 &:= -(((2^7) - (((8 \times 5)^3) \times 74))) \\
 4739574 &:= ((47 \times ((5 \times 9) - 3)) \times (7^4)) \\
 4741626 &:= -((6 - (((2 \times 6) \times 14)^{7-4})) \\
 4741632 &:= (((2 \times 3) + 6) \times 14)^{7-4} \\
 4741975 &:= (((5 \times 79) \times (1 + 4)) \times (7^4)) \\
 4743328 &:= -(((82 - ((33^4) - 7)) \times 4)) \\
 4743364 &:= -((4 \times (6 - ((33^4) - 74)))) \\
 4743368 &:= -(((86 - ((33^4) + 7)) \times 4)) \\
 4743564 &:= -((4 \times ((6 \times 5) - ((3 \times (4 + 7))^4)))) \\
 4743644 &:= -((4 \times ((4 + 6) - ((3 \times (4 + 7))^4)))) \\
 4743653 &:= -((3 - (((5 + 6) \times 3)^4) - 7) \times 4)) \\
 4743656 &:= ((((((6 \times 5) + 6) - 3)^4) - 7) \times 4) \\
 4743684 &:= (4 \times (((8 + 6) + ((3 \times 4) + 7))^4)) \\
 4764064 &:= (4 \times ((60 + 46)^{7-4})) \\
 4776479 &:= (((9^7) - ((4^6) - 7)) - (7^4)) \\
 4778279 &:= ((9^7) + (2 \times ((8 \times 7) - (7^4)))) \\
 4779542 &:= -((((2 + (4^5)) - (9^7)) + (7^4))) \\
 4779855 &:= -((((5^5) - 8) - ((9^7) + 7) - 4)) \\
 4781679 &:= (((9^7) + 6) - (-(((1^8) - 7))^4)) \\
 4782273 &:= (((3^7)^2) - ((2 \times 87) \times 4)) \\
 4782619 &:= (((9^{1+6}) - 2) - (87 \times 4)) \\
 4782679 &:= (((9^7) - 6) - (2^8)) - (7 \times 4)) \\
 4782699 &:= (9 \times ((9^6) - ((2 + 8) \times (7 - 4)))) \\
 4782786 &:= -((6 + (8 \times ((7 - 2^8)) \times (7^4)))) \\
 4782791 &:= (((1 \times 9)^7) - ((2 \times 87) + 4)) \\
 4782909 &:= ((9^{09-2}) - ((8 \times 7) + 4)) \\
 4782919 &:= ((9 \times (1 + ((9^{-2+8}) - (7)))) + (4)) \\
 4782929 &:= ((9^{-2+9}) + ((2 \times (8 - (7 \times 4)))) \\
 4782933 &:= (((3^{3+9+2}) - 8) - (7 \times 4)) \\
 4782945 &:= (((5 + 4)^{9-2}) - (8 \times (7 - 4))) \\
 4782949 &:= ((9^{-4+9+2}) + ((8 - (7 \times 4)))) \\
 4782953 &:= ((3^{5+9}) - ((28/7) \times 4)) \\
 4782957 &:= -(((7 + 5) - (9^{2+8-7+4})) \\
 4782965 &:= ((((((5 + 6) - 9)/2) + 8)^7) - 4) \\
 4782972 &:= (((2 + 7)^{9-2}) - ((8 - 7) - 4)) \\
 4782973 &:= ((((((3 + 7) - 9)^2) + 8)^7) + 4) \\
 4782979 &:= (((9^7) + 92) - 8) - 74)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4782993 &:= (((3^9) \times (9^2)) + 8) \times (7 - 4)) \\
 4783133 &:= ((3 \times ((3^{13}) + (8 \times 7))) - 4) \\
 4783279 &:= (((9^7) + 2) + (((3 + 8) \times 7) \times 4)) \\
 4783481 &:= (((1 + 8)^{4+3}) + (8^{7-4})) \\
 4783879 &:= ((9^7) + (((8^3) + 8) \times 7)/4) \\
 4785137 &:= -((7 \times (3 - ((1 + ((5^8) \times 7))/4)))) \\
 4785165 &:= (((5 + ((6 + 1) \times (5^8))) \times 7)/4) \\
 4785172 &:= (((2 + (7 \times (1 + (5^8)))) \times 7)/4) \\
 4785379 &:= ((9^7) - ((3 \times (5 - 8)) - (7^4))) \\
 4785529 &:= ((9^{2+5}) + (5 \times (8^{7-4}))) \\
 4785929 &:= ((9^{-2+9}) + ((5 \times 8) \times 74)) \\
 4790756 &:= (((6^5) + 7) + ((09^7) + 4)) \\
 4793488 &:= -((8 \times ((8 - (4^{3+9}))/7 \times 4))) \\
 4794633 &:= (((3 + 3)^6) + (4 \times (9^7)))/4) \\
 4795465 &:= (((5^6) \times 4)/5) + ((9^7) - 4)) \\
 4796384 &:= (((4^8) - ((3^6) - 9)) \times 74) \\
 4813636 &:= ((6 + (((3^6) \times 3) + 1))^{8/4}) \\
 4822416 &:= ((61 \times ((4 + 2)^2))^{8/4}) \\
 4826685 &:= (((5 + 8)^6) - ((62 \times 8)/4)) \\
 4826723 &:= (((((3 \times 2) + 7)^6) - 2) - 84) \\
 4826745 &:= (((5 \times 4) - 7)^6) - ((2 \times 8) \times 4)) \\
 4826767 &:= -(((7 \times 6) - ((7 + 6)^{2+8-4})) \\
 4826793 &:= (3 - 9 - 7)^6 - 2^{8-4} \\
 4826795 &:= -(((5 + 9) - ((7 + 6)^{2+8-4})) \\
 4826797 &:= (-((7 + 9)) + (((7 + 6)^{-2+8}) + (4))) \\
 4826805 &:= (((5 + 08)^6) - ((2 \times 8)/4)) \\
 4826815 &:= ((((((5 \times 1) + 8)^6) + 2) + 8) - 4) \\
 4826816 &:= (((6 - 1) + 8)^6) + (28/4)) \\
 4826823 &:= ((((((3 + 2) + 8)^6) + 2) + 8) + 4) \\
 4826841 &:= (((((1 + 4) + 8)^6) + 28) + 4) \\
 4826849 &:= (((9 - 4) + 8)^6) + ((2 + 8) \times 4)) \\
 4826873 &:= (((3 \times 7) - 8)^6) + ((2 \times 8) \times 4)) \\
 4828896 &:= (((6 \times 9) - 8) \times (((8 + 2) + 8)^4)) \\
 4848776 &:= -(((67 + 7) \times (8 - ((4^8) - 4)))) \\
 4849368 &:= (((86 - 3) - 9) \times ((4^8) - 4)) \\
 4849655 &:= -((5 - (((5 + 69) \times (4^8)) - 4))) \\
 4849659 &:= -((9 - (((5 + 69) \times (4^8)) + 4))) \\
 4851499 &:= (((99^{4-1}) \times 5) + (8 - 4)) \\
 4855625 &:= -(((5 + 2) - (6^5)) \times (5^{8-4}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4876552 &:= -((2 - ((5 + (5^6)) \times 78)) \times 4)) \\ 4876555 &:= -((5 - ((5 + (5^6)) \times (78 \times 4)))) \\ 4879579 &:= -97 - 5 + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4879588 &:= 8 + 85 + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4879597 &:= 79 + 5 + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4879627 &:= (7 + 2) \times 6 + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4879647 &:= 7 \times 4 + 6 + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4879651 &:= -1 \times 5 \times 6 + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4879663 &:= -((3 \times 6) - (((6 \times 9) - 7)^{8-4})) \\ 4879672 &:= -((2 + 7) - (((6 \times 9) - 7)^{8-4})) \\ 4879676 &:= -6 + 7 - 6 + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4879679 &:= -((9 - 7) - (((6 \times 9) - 7)^{8-4})) \\ 4879681 &:= (((((1 - 8) \times 6) + 97) - 8)^4) \\ 4879682 &:= 2/(8 - 6) + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4879687 &:= -(7 - 8) \times 6 + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4879688 &:= (8 \times (((86 \times 9) + 7)^{8/4})) \\ 4879716 &:= (6 - 1) \times 7 + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4879723 &:= 3 \times 2 \times 7 + (9 - 7 \times 8)^4 \\ 4882795 &:= (((5^9) - 7)/2) \times ((8/8) + 4) \\ 4917248 &:= (8 \times (((4^2) - 7) + 19)^4) \\ 4921875 &:= (((5^7) \times (8 + 1)) \times ((2 + 9) - 4)) \\ 4925887 &:= -(((7^8) - (8 \times ((5 + 29)^4)))) \\ 4926617 &:= (((7^{1+6}) \times 6) - ((2 + 9)^4)) \\ 4933872 &:= (((-(2 - (7 \times 8)))^3)/3) \times 94 \\ 4939776 &:= (6 \times ((7^7) - (((9 \times 3) \times 9) + 4))) \\ 4941257 &:= -((((7^{5+2}) + 1) - (49^4))) \\ 4941576 &:= (6 \times (((7^5) + 1) \times 49) + 4) \\ 4942776 &:= (6 \times (((7^7) + 249) + 4)) \\ 4943445 &:= -((((5 - (4^4)) \times 3) \times (4 + (9^4)))) \\ 4943835 &:= (5 \times ((3 \times ((8 \times 3)^4)) - (9^4))) \\ 4946994 &:= (((4 + 9) \times ((9 \times 6) + 4)) \times (9^4)) \\ 4950967 &:= (7 \times (((6 + 9) + 05) + 9)^4) \\ 4952172 &:= (2 \times (((7 + 12)^5) - 9) - 4) \\ 4959648 &:= -(((84 \times (6 - (9^5))) - (9 \times 4))) \\ 4965912 &:= (21 \times (((9^5) + 69) \times 4)) \\ 4967195 &:= (5 \times (((9 + (1^7))^6) - (9^4))) \\ 4976645 &:= (5 \times ((4 + (((6 + 6)^7)/9))/4) \\ 4976675 &:= (5 \times (7 + (((6 + 6)^7)/9)/4)) \\ 4999482 &:= ((2 - (8 \times (4 - 99))) \times (9^4)) \\ 5038608 &:= -((((80 - (6^8)) \times 3) + (0 \times 5))) \\ 5038627 &:= -((((72 - (6^8)) \times 3) - (0 - 5))) \\ 5038823 &:= 3 \times (2 - 8)^8 - 30 + 5 \\ 5038824 &:= (((((4 + 2)^8) - 8) \times 3) + (0 \times 5)) \\ 5038827 &:= (-7 + (2 - 8)^8) \times (3 + 0 \times 5) \\ 5038853 &:= (((((3 - 5) + 8)^8) \times 3) + 05) \\ 5038863 &:= ((3 \times (((6^8) + 8) - 3)) + (0 \times 5)) \\ 5038866 &:= ((6 + (6^8)) \times (8 - ((3 \times 0) + 5))) \\ 5038933 &:= 3 \times (3 - 9)^8 + 30 - 5 \\ 5078125 &:= ((5^{-2+1+8}) \times (70 - 5)) \\ 5153617 &:= (((7 - ((1 - 6) \times 3))^5) - 15) \\ 5153623 &:= -(((3^2) - (((6 \times 3) + 5) - 1)^5)) \\ 5153624 &:= -(((4 \times 2) - (((6 \times 3) + 5) - 1)^5)) \\ 5153625 &:= -(((5 + 2) - (((6 \times 3) + 5) - 1)^5)) \\ 5153626 &:= (((6 - 2) + (6 \times 3))^5) - (1 + 5) \\ 5153627 &:= (((((72 - 6)/3)^5) \times 1) - 5) \\ 5153628 &:= (((8/2) + (6 \times 3))^5) + (1 - 5) \\ 5153631 &:= (((13 + 6) + 3)^5) - (1^5) \\ 5153632 &:= (((((2^3) \times 6)/3) + 5) + 1)^5 \\ 5153633 &:= ((3/3) + (((6 \times 3) + 5) - 1)^5) \\ 5153637 &:= (((7 + ((3 \times 6) - 3))^5) + (1 \times 5)) \\ 5153638 &:= (((((8 + 3) \times 6)/3)^5) + 1) + 5 \\ 5153647 &:= (((((7 + 4) \times 6)/3)^5) + 15) \\ 5153888 &:= -((8 \times ((8 + ((8 + 3)^5)) \times (1 - 5)))) \\ 5156255 &:= (((5^{5+2}) \times (65 + 1)) + 5) \\ 5156575 &:= (((5^7) + 5) \times (65 + 1)) - 5 \\ 5176548 &:= -((8 - ((4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7^{1+5}))) \\ 5196488 &:= -((88 \times ((4 - 6) - ((9 \times 1)^5)))) \\ 5222545 &:= (5 \times (((4^5) - 2)^2) + 25) \\ 5231945 &:= (5 \times ((4^{9+1}) - (3^{2+5}))) \\ 5234365 &:= (((5^6) \times (3 + (4^3))) - 2) \times 5 \\ 5234375 &:= ((5^7) \times (((34 - 3) \times 2) + 5)) \\ 5234576 &:= (67 \times ((5^{4+3}) - (2 - 5))) \\ 5239615 &:= (((((51 \times 6) - 9)^3) + 2)/5) \\ 5239755 &:= -(((5^5) - (((7 + 9)^{3+2}) \times 5))) \\ 5242537 &:= -(((7^3) - (5 \times (((2 \times 4) \times 2)^5)))) \\ 5242565 &:= -((5 \times ((65 - 2) - ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5242755 &:= -((5 \times ((5 \times (7 - 2)) - ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5242775 &:= -((5 \times ((7 + (7 \times 2)) - ((4^2)^5)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5242799 &:= -((9 \times 9) - ((7 - 2) \times ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5242835 &:= -((5 \times (((3 + 8) - 2) - ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5242864 &:= (4 \times (6 + (((8^{2+4}) - 2) \times 5))) \\ 5242875 &:= (5 \times ((7 - 8) + (((2 \times 4) \times 2)^5))) \\ 5242895 &:= (5 \times (((9 - 8) + 2) + ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5242915 &:= (5 \times (((1 \times 9) - 2) + ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5242925 &:= (5 \times (((2 \times 9)/2) + ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5242945 &:= (5 \times (((((4^9) \times 2) + 4) \times 2) + 5)) \\ 5242965 &:= (5 \times (((6 + 9) + 2) + ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5243255 &:= (5 \times (((5^2) \times 3) + ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5243505 &:= (5 \times ((05^3) + ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5245755 &:= (5 \times (575 + ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5246525 &:= (5 \times ((-((2 - 5)^6) + ((4^2)^5))) \\ 5267712 &:= (-((2 \times (1 - 7))) \times (76^{-2+5})) \\ 5294295 &:= ((5 \times 9) \times (2 + (49^{-2+5}))) \\ 5308418 &:= ((81 \times (4^8)) + ((0 - 3) + 5)) \\ 5308446 &:= (6 \times (((4 \times 4) + 80)^3 + 5)) \\ 5314392 &:= -((2 \times (9 - (((3^4) \times 1)^3) \times 5))) \\ 5314683 &:= (((3 + 8)^6) \times (((4 + 1) \times 3)/5)) \\ 5315597 &:= -((7 \times ((9 - 5) - (((5 \times 1) \times 3)^5))) \\ 5315625 &:= ((5 + 2) \times (((6 + 5) + 1) + 3)^5) \\ 5315667 &:= (7 \times (6 + (((6 + 5) + 1) + 3)^5)) \\ 5315877 &:= (7 \times (((7 + 8)^5) + 1) + 35) \\ 5322672 &:= (((2 \times (76 - 2))^2) \times (3^5)) \\ 5334336 &:= (((6 + (3/3)) \times 4)^3) \times (3^5) \\ 5334341 &:= (((-(((1 - (4^3)) \times 4)^3)/3) + (5)) \\ 5334381 &:= ((1 + 8) \times (((3^4) + 3)^3) + 5) \\ 5338224 &:= (((4^2) + (28^3)) \times (3^5)) \\ 5359375 &:= (((5^7) \times (((3 + 9) - 5)^3))/5) \\ 5370592 &:= ((29 \times ((50 + 7)^3)) - 5) \\ 5373459 &:= ((9^5) \times ((4 \times ((3 \times 7) + 3)) - 5)) \\ 5380839 &:= -(((9 - (3^{8+08}))/3 + 5)) \\ 5386591 &:= -((((1 + 9) + 5)^6) - (8^{3+5})) \\ 5386676 &:= (((6 + 7)^6) + (((6^8)/3) - 5)) \\ 5422464 &:= ((4 \times (6^4)) \times (22 + (4^5))) \\ 5455296 &:= ((6 \times 9) \times (((2 \times 5)^5) + (4^5))) \\ 5468722 &:= (2 - (2 - 7)^8) \times (6 - 4 \times 5) \\ 5468755 &:= (5 \times (((5^7) \times (8 + 6)) - (4 - 5))) \\ 5468856 &:= -((6 + (((5^8) + 8) \times (6 - (4 \times 5)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5468857 &:= (((7 + (5^8)) \times (8 + 6)) + (4 + 5)) \\ 5475564 &:= -(((4 + (6 \times 5)) \times (5 - ((7 + 4)^5))) \\ 5475734 &:= -((((4 - 3) - (7 \times 5)) \times ((7 + 4)^5))) \\ 5522495 &:= (((5 \times 94)^2) \times 25) - 5) \\ 5528536 &:= (((6^3) + 5) \times 8) \times (2 + (5^5)) \\ 5534375 &:= (((5 + 7)^3) + 43) \times (5^5) \\ 5541136 &:= ((6 \times ((31 \times 1)^4)) + (5 + 5)) \\ 5546875 &:= ((5^7) \times (((8 - 6)^4) + 55)) \\ 5563415 &:= ((5 \times 143) \times ((6^5) + 5)) \\ 5582969 &:= (((9^6) \times 9) + ((2^8) \times (5^5))) \\ 5585863 &:= -(((3 - (6^8)) - ((5^8) \times (5 + 5)))) \\ 5587653 &:= -((((3^{5+6}) - (7^8)) + (5/5)) \\ 5598665 &:= (((5 \times 6) \times ((6^8)/9)) - 55) \\ 5598693 &:= -((3 \times (9 - (((6^8)/9) \times (5 + 5)))) \\ 5598696 &:= -((6 \times (9 - (((6^8)/9) \times 5) + 5))) \\ 5614272 &:= -(((2 - 724) \times ((1 \times 6)^5))) \\ 5622264 &:= ((4 \times 6) \times ((22^{-2+6}) + (5))) \\ 5631995 &:= -((5 - (((9 \times 9) - 1)^3) \times (6 + 5))) \\ 5632044 &:= ((4 + ((40 \times 2)^3)) \times (6 + 5)) \\ 5639817 &:= (((7 + 1) \times (89^3)) + 65) \\ 5643918 &:= -(((81 \times 9) \times (34 - (6^5))) \\ 5646786 &:= (6 \times ((8 \times (7^6)) + (4 - 65))) \\ 5668693 &:= ((((((3^9) \times 6) \times 8) \times 6) - 6) - 5) \\ 5668697 &:= -((7 - (96 \times ((8 + (6/6))^5))) \\ 5668698 &:= (((8 \times ((9^6) \times 8)) - 6)/6) - 5) \\ 5668704 &:= (((4 + 07) - 8)^6) \times (6^5) \\ 5681826 &:= (((6/2)^8) \times (1 + 865)) \\ 5682393 &:= (((3 \times 93)^2) \times (8 + 65)) \\ 5682881 &:= (1 - 8)^8 - 2^{8+6} \times 5 \\ 5687655 &:= (5 \times ((5 \times (6^7)) - ((8^6) + 5))) \\ 5694817 &:= (7 \times (1 - 8))^4 - 9 \times 6^5 \\ 5702375 &:= (((5 \times 7)^3) \times ((2^{07}) + 5)) \\ 5714375 &:= -((5 - (((7^3) - 4) + 1) \times (7^5))) \\ 5725832 &:= (((((23 + 8)^5) + 2) + 7)/5) \\ 5728529 &:= ((92 + 5) \times (8 + ((2 + 7)^5))) \\ 5729772 &:= (2 - 77 \times 9)^2 \times (7 + 5) \\ 5731187 &:= ((7^8) - ((1 + (1^3)) \times (7^5))) \\ 5734405 &:= ((50 \times ((4^{4+3}) \times 7)) + 5) \\ 5740875 &:= (5 \times 7 - 80)^4 \times 7/5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5747994 &:= ((49^{(9+7)/4}) - (7^5)) \\
 5748412 &:= (((2+1)+4)^8) - ((4^7) + 5)) \\
 5756337 &:= ((73 \times ((3^6) + (5^7))) - 5) \\
 5762743 &:= -((((3+4) \times (7^2)) \times (6 - (7^5)))) \\
 5763777 &:= (((7^7) \times 7) - ((3-6) + 7^5)) \\
 5764477 &:= (((7 \times 7)^4) - (4 \times (6+75))) \\
 5764687 &:= ((7^8) + (6 \times (((4-6) \times 7) - 5))) \\
 5764729 &:= (((((9-2) \times 7)^4) - 67) - 5) \\
 5764765 &:= (((56-7)^4) - (6^{7-5})) \\
 5764771 &:= -(((1 - (((7 \times 7)^4) + 6)) + (7 \times 5))) \\
 5764775 &:= -((((5 - (((7^7) - 4) + 6)) \times 7) + 5)) \\
 5764776 &:= -((6 - (((((7^7) + 4) - 6) \times 7) - 5))) \\
 5764777 &:= ((7 \times ((7^7) - 4)) + ((6-7) + 5)) \\
 5764787 &:= ((7^8) - (((7-4) + 67)/5)) \\
 5764791 &:= -(((1+9) - (7^{4+6-7+5}))) \\
 5764797 &:= ((((((7^9)/7) + 4) - 6) - 7) + 5) \\
 5764816 &:= (((6+1)^8) + (((4+6) - 7) \times 5)) \\
 5764817 &:= (((7 \times 1)^8) + (4 \times ((6-7) + 5))) \\
 5764825 &:= (((5+2)^8) - (4 \times ((6-7) - 5))) \\
 5764834 &:= (((4+3)^8) - 4) + ((6 \times 7) - 5) \\
 5764852 &:= (((2+5)^8) - ((4 \times 6) - 75)) \\
 5764917 &:= ((7^{-1+9}) - ((4 \times (6 - (7 \times 5)))))) \\
 5764987 &:= (((7^8) - 9) + ((46-7) \times 5)) \\
 5765187 &:= (((7^8) - 1) + ((56 \times 7) - 5)) \\
 5765825 &:= (((5+2)^8) + (((5+6) - 7)^5)) \\
 5767168 &:= (((8^6) \times (17-6)) \times (7-5)) \\
 5767784 &:= (((4^8) + 7) \times ((7+6) + 75)) \\
 5772975 &:= (((5^7) - (9 \times (2^7))) \times 75) \\
 5781604 &:= -(((4 - ((06+1)^8)) - (7^5))) \\
 5781608 &:= (((((8 \times 0) + 6) + 1)^8) + (7^5)) \\
 5781624 &:= (((4^2) + ((6+1)^8)) + (7^5)) \\
 5798415 &:= (((5-1)^4) + 89) \times (7^5) \\
 5826417 &:= (((((7 \times 1)^4) + 6)^2) + (8^5)) \\
 5831995 &:= (((((5 \times 9) \times (9-1))^3)/8) - 5) \\
 5845856 &:= (((6+5) \times ((8-5)^{4+8})) + 5) \\
 5858343 &:= -((3 \times ((43 \times 8) - ((5^8) \times 5)))) \\
 5858643 &:= -((3 \times (4 + (((6 \times 8) - (5^8)) \times 5)))) \\
 5858745 &:= -(((5^4) - (((7+8) \times (5^8)) - 5))) \\
 5859183 &:= (3 \times ((8 \times (1-9)) + ((5^8) \times 5))) \\
 5859213 &:= (3 \times (1 - (((2+9) - (5^8)) \times 5))) \\
 5859215 &:= -((5 \times (((1+2) \times (9 - (5^8))) + 5))) \\
 5859232 &:= -((2 + (3 \times (2 + ((9 - (5^8)) \times 5)))))) \\
 5859235 &:= ((5 - (3 \times ((2+9) - (5^8)))) \times 5) \\
 5859238 &:= -((8 - (3 \times (2 - ((9 - (5^8)) \times 5)))))) \\
 5859243 &:= -((3 \times ((4 \times (2+9)) - ((5^8) \times 5))) \\
 5859265 &:= ((5 - ((6/2) \times (9 - (5^8)))) \times 5) \\
 5859285 &:= (((5^8) - (2 \times (9 - (5^8)))) \times 5) \\
 5859315 &:= -((((5 \times 1) \times 3) \times (9 - ((5^8) + 5)))) \\
 5859325 &:= (5 \times (2 - (3 \times (9 - ((5^8) + 5)))))) \\
 5859339 &:= -(((9/3) \times ((3+9) - ((5^8) \times 5)))) \\
 5859342 &:= -(((2+4) + (3 \times (9 - ((5^8) \times 5)))))) \\
 5859346 &:= -(((6-4) + (3 \times (9 - ((5^8) \times 5)))))) \\
 5859366 &:= -(((6 \times 6) - (3 \times (9 + ((5^8) \times 5)))))) \\
 5859374 &:= -(((4 \times 7) - (3 \times (9 + ((5^8) \times 5)))))) \\
 5859375 &:= ((5^7) \times (((3+9) - 5) + 8) \times 5) \\
 5859393 &:= -((3 \times (((9/3) - 9) - ((5^8) \times 5)))) \\
 5859395 &:= (((5^9) \times 3) - (((9-5) - 8) \times 5)) \\
 5859396 &:= -((6 - ((9/3) \times (9 + ((5^8) \times 5)))))) \\
 5859414 &:= ((4-1) \times ((4+9) + ((5^8) \times 5))) \\
 5859483 &:= (3 \times (((8-4) \times 9) + ((5^8) \times 5))) \\
 5859513 &:= (3 \times ((1 + (5 \times 9)) + ((5^8) \times 5))) \\
 5859525 &:= ((5-2) \times (5 + ((9 + (5^8)) \times 5))) \\
 5859527 &:= -((((7^2) + (5^9)) \times (5-8)) - 5) \\
 5859532 &:= -((2 - (3 \times (((5^9) + 58) - 5)))) \\
 5859537 &:= -((7 - ((3 \times ((5^9) + 58)) - 5))) \\
 5859543 &:= (3 \times ((4 \times (5+9)) + ((5^8) \times 5))) \\
 5859552 &:= -(((2-5) \times (59 + ((5^8) \times 5)))) \\
 5859555 &:= ((55 + ((5^9) + 5)) \times (8-5)) \\
 5859562 &:= -((((2^6) + (5^9)) \times (5-8)) + 5) \\
 5859573 &:= (3 \times ((7+59) + ((5^8) \times 5))) \\
 5859579 &:= (((9 \times 7) + ((5^9) + 5)) \times (8-5)) \\
 5859585 &:= (((((5^8) + 5) + 9) \times 5) \times (8-5)) \\
 5859597 &:= ((79 + ((5^9) - 5)) \times (8-5)) \\
 5859645 &:= ((54 - ((6-9) \times (5^8))) \times 5) \\
 5860995 &:= (((5^9) + (90 \times 6)) \times (8-5)) \\
 5863087 &:= ((7^8) + ((0-3) \times (6 - (8^5)))) \\
 5865472 &:= (((2^7) + 45) + 6) \times (8^5) \\
 5873664 &:= (((4^6) \times 6) \times ((3 \times 78) + 5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5877627 &:= -((((7^2) - (6^7)) \times 7) \times (8 - 5)) \\ 5878483 &:= -((((3^8) - ((4^8) \times 7)) \times (8 + 5)) \\ 5878651 &:= -((((1 - 5) \times (((6^8) \times 7)/8)) + 5) \\ 5878656 &:= (((6^{56/8}) \times 7) \times (8 - 5)) \\ 5878664 &:= (((4 \times (6 + ((6^8) \times 7)))/8) + 5) \\ 5892143 &:= ((3 \times (((4 - 1) + 2)^9)) + (8^5)) \\ 5896615 &:= -((5 \times (1 + ((6 \times 6) \times (9 - (8^5)))))) \\ 5896635 &:= (5 \times (3 - ((6 \times 6) \times (9 - (8^5)))))) \\ 5898425 &:= (((5 + (2 \times (4^8))) \times 9) - 8) \times 5) \\ 5899257 &:= (((7^5) \times ((2 \times 9) + 9)) \times (8 + 5)) \\ 5904725 &:= -(((5^2) \times (7 - (4 \times (09^5)))))) \\ 5915965 &:= -(((5 + 6) \times (9 - (((5 \times 1) + 9)^5)))) \\ 5924342 &:= (((2434^2) - 9) - 5) \\ 5940688 &:= ((8 + 8) \times (((6 \times 0) + 4) + 9)^5) \\ 5972366 &:= (((6^6) + 3) \times (2^7)) + (9 + 5) \\ 5972466 &:= (((6^6) + 4) \times (2^7)) - (9 + 5) \\ 5990193 &:= ((3 + 910) \times (9^{9-5})) \\ 5991865 &:= (-5) \times ((-6) - (8^{-1+9})/(9 + 5)) \\ 5992618 &:= (((816^2) - 9) \times 9) - 5) \\ 5992896 &:= ((6 \times (98^2)) \times (9 + 95)) \\ 6029432 &:= ((23 \times (4^9)) + (20 \times 6)) \\ 6158768 &:= -(((8 + (6^7)) \times (8 - ((5 \times 1) \times 6)))) \\ 6171875 &:= ((5^7) \times (((8 + 1) \times 7) + 16)) \\ 6186675 &:= (5 \times (((7^6) \times 6) + ((8 + 1)^6))) \\ 6223424 &:= (((42^4) + 3) \times 2) + 26) \\ 6234375 &:= (((5 \times (7 + 3))^4) - ((3 + 2)^6)) \\ 6249974 &:= (4 - 7 \times 9 + 9)^4 - 26) \\ 6254638 &:= -((8 - (((3 - 6) + (4^5))^2) \times 6)) \\ 6254646 &:= (((6/(4 - 6)) + (4^5))^2) \times 6) \\ 6259135 &:= -(((53 \times (1 - (9^5) \times 2))) + 6) \\ 6283264 &:= -(((4^6) \times (2 - ((3 \times 8) \times (2^6)))))) \\ 6284949 &:= -(((9^4) - ((9 + (4^{8+2})) \times 6))) \\ 6286848 &:= (8 \times (((4^8) - (6 \times 8)) \times (2 \times 6))) \\ 6289464 &:= (4 \times ((6 \times ((4^9) - 82)) - 6)) \\ 6291348 &:= (((8 \times 4)^{3+1}) - (9 \times 2)) \times 6) \\ 6291372 &:= -((2 \times ((7 - (((3 + 1)^9) \times 2)) \times 6))) \\ 6291384 &:= ((4 + 8) \times (((3 + 1)^9) \times 2) - 6) \\ 6291404 &:= -((40 - (((4^{1+9}) - 2) \times 6)) \\ 6291413 &:= -((31 - (((4^{1+9}) - 2) \times 6)) \\ 6291414 &:= -((((4 + 1) - ((4^{1+9}) - 2)) \times 6)) \\ 6291422 &:= -((22 - (((4^{1+9}) - 2) \times 6)) \\ 6291426 &:= -((((6/2) - ((4^{1+9}) - 2)) \times 6)) \\ 6291428 &:= -(((8 \times 2) - (((4^{1+9}) - 2) \times 6))) \\ 6291431 &:= -((13 - (((4^{1+9}) - 2) \times 6)) \\ 6291432 &:= ((2 \times 3) \times ((4^{1+9}) + (2 - 6))) \\ 6291434 &:= -((4 - (3 \times (((4^{1+9}) \times 2) - 6)))) \\ 6291438 &:= -((((8 - 3) - ((4^{1+9}) + 2)) \times 6)) \\ 6291453 &:= (3 \times (5 + (((4^{1+9}) \times 2) - 6)) \\ 6291474 &:= -(((4 - 7) \times (((4^{1+9}) \times 2) + 6))) \\ 6291478 &:= -((8 - ((7 + ((4^{1+9}) - 2)) \times 6)) \\ 6291482 &:= -((((2 - 8) \times (4^{1+9})) - 26)) \\ 6291486 &:= ((6 \times (8 + ((4^{1+9}) - 2))) - 6) \\ 6291494 &:= -((4 - ((9 + ((4^{1+9}) - 2)) \times 6)) \\ 6291504 &:= (4 \times (((05 - 1)^9) + 2) \times 6) \\ 6291528 &:= ((((((8 \times 2)^5) + 1) + 9) + 2) \times 6) \\ 6291564 &:= (((4^{6+5-1}) + (9 \times 2)) \times 6) \\ 6291582 &:= (((((2 \times 8)^5) + 19) + 2) \times 6) \\ 6291684 &:= (((4 \times (8^6)) + (19 \times 2)) \times 6) \\ 6291783 &:= (3 \times (((8^7) + 1) + ((9 \times 2) \times 6))) \\ 6291941 &:= -((1 - (((4^{9+1}) + (9^2)) \times 6)) \\ 6298555 &:= -5 + 5 \times (-5 + 8)^9 \times 2^6) \\ 6298596 &:= (((6^9) \times 5)/8) - (9 \times (2 - 6)) \\ 6327354 &:= ((45 \times ((3 + (7^2))^3)) - 6) \\ 6331631 &:= ((-((1 - ((3 \times 61) + 3)))^3) + (6)) \\ 6343944 &:= (4 \times (((4^9) + (3^{4+3})) \times 6)) \\ 6367192 &:= -((2 + ((9 - ((17 \times 6)^3)) \times 6)) \\ 6367239 &:= -((9 - (((3 + (2 \times 7)) \times 6)^3) \times 6)) \\ 6367244 &:= -((4 - (((4 \times 27) - 6)^3) \times 6)) \\ 6367248 &:= ((((((8 + 4) - 2) + 7) \times 6)^3) \times 6) \\ 6376536 &:= (6 \times (((3^{5+6}) - (7 \times 3)) \times 6)) \\ 6376943 &:= (((3 \times 4) \times (9^6)) - ((7^3) + 6)) \\ 6377284 &:= -((4 \times (8 - (((2 + 7)^7)/3) + 6)) \\ 6377288 &:= (8 \times (((((8 \times 2) - 7)^7) - 3)/6)) \\ 6377324 &:= (4 \times (2 + (((3^{7+7})/3) + 6)) \\ 6377436 &:= (6 \times (((3^{4+7}) + (7 - 3)) \times 6)) \\ 6378448 &:= -((8 \times (((4 - (4^8)) \times 73)/6)) \\ 6379473 &:= ((3^7) + ((4 \times (9^7)/3)) - 6) \\ 6388956 &:= (((6^5) + 988) \times (3^6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6391872 &:= (((2^7) + 8) + 1) \times ((9 - 3)^6)) \\
 6422528 &:= ((8 \times ((2 + 5) \times 2)^2)) \times (4^6) \\
 6432247 &:= (((7 + (4^2))^{2+3}) - (4^6)) \\
 6434846 &:= ((-(6 - (48 \times 4)))^3) - (4 + 6)) \\
 6434866 &:= ((-(6 - ((6 \times 8) \times 4)))^3) + (4 + 6)) \\
 6438528 &:= (((8 - 2)^5) \times (834 - 6)) \\
 6438952 &:= ((-(2 \times (5 - 98)))^3) + (4^6) \\
 6484375 &:= ((5^7) \times (((3^4) - 8) + 4) + 6)) \\
 6531245 &:= -((5 - ((421 - 3) \times (5^6)))) \\
 6534567 &:= ((((((7 \times 6)^5)/4) - 3)/5) + 6) \\
 6539259 &:= (((((9 + 5)^2) - 9)^3) + 56) \\
 6552694 &:= (((4^9) - (6^2)) \times (5 \times 5)) - 6) \\
 6552945 &:= (5 \times (((4^9) - 25) \times 5) - 6)) \\
 6553594 &:= (((4^9) \times (((5 \times 3) + 5) + 5)) - 6) \\
 6553681 &:= ((((((1 \times 8)^6) + 3) \times 5) \times 5) + 6) \\
 6553945 &:= (5 \times (((4^9) + (3 \times 5)) \times 5) - 6)) \\
 6573883 &:= ((388 + 3) \times (7^5) + 6)) \\
 6587728 &:= (8 \times (2 + (((7^7) - 85) + 6))) \\
 6587768 &:= (8 \times ((6 + (7^7)) - ((8 + 5) \times 6))) \\
 6587778 &:= ((8 \times ((7^7) - 7)) - (85 \times 6)) \\
 6587798 &:= -((((8 \times 9) - (7^7)) \times 8) - (5 \times 6)) \\
 6588347 &:= (((7^{4+3}) \times 8) - ((8 - 5) - 6)) \\
 6588377 &:= ((((((7^7) + 3) \times 8) + 8) - 5) + 6) \\
 6588778 &:= ((8 \times (7^7)) + ((88 \times 5) - 6)) \\
 6588792 &:= (((-(2 - 9))^7) \times 8) + (8 \times 56)) \\
 6625152 &:= -((((2 \times 5) - 152) \times (6^6)) \\
 6656242 &:= -((2 - ((426 \times (5^6)) - 6))) \\
 6656248 &:= -((8 - ((426 \times (5^6)) + 6))) \\
 6656274 &:= ((4 + ((7 + (2^6)) \times (5^6))) \times 6) \\
 6657156 &:= (6 \times (((5 - 1) + (7^5)) \times 66)) \\
 6657684 &:= (((4 \times 8) + (6 \times (7^5))) \times 66) \\
 6671808 &:= ((80 + ((8 + 1) \times 7)) \times (6^6)) \\
 6681897 &:= (((7^9) - 81) - (8^6))/6) \\
 6684671 &:= (((17 \times 6) \times (4^8)) - (6/6)) \\
 6684689 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((6 \times (4^8)) + (6/6))) \\
 6705993 &:= (((3 + 9) + (9 \times 5)) \times (07^6)) \\
 6717996 &:= ((((((6^9)/9) - 71) - 7) \times 6) \\
 6718164 &:= (4 \times (((6 \times 1)^8) + 1) - 76)) \\
 6718464 &:= ((4 \times 648)^{1+7-6}) \\
 6718476 &:= ((((((6^7) \times 4) + 8) + 1) - 7) \times 6) \\
 6718486 &:= ((((((6^8) \times 4) + 8) + 1) + 7) + 6) \\
 6718624 &:= -((4 \times ((2 - (6^8)) - ((1 \times 7) \times 6)))) \\
 6718628 &:= ((8/2) \times (((6^8) - 1) + (7 \times 6))) \\
 6718638 &:= (((8 \times 3) \times ((6^{8-1}) + 7)) + 6) \\
 6718664 &:= ((4 \times (6 + (6^8))) + 176) \\
 6718674 &:= (((4 \times (7 + (6^{8-1}))) + 7) \times 6) \\
 6718864 &:= ((4 \times ((6^8) + 81)) + 76) \\
 6720048 &:= ((8 + ((400^2) \times 7)) \times 6) \\
 6731586 &:= (((6^8) \times (5 - 1)) + ((3^7) \times 6)) \\
 6734864 &:= (-4) \times (-(((6^8) + 4) - (-((3 - 7)^6))) \\
 6795952 &:= (2 \times (((5^9)/5) \times 9) - (7^6)) \\
 6796515 &:= (51 \times ((5^6) - 9) + (7^6)) \\
 6796875 &:= ((5^7) \times (((8 - 6) + 9) + 76)) \\
 6815718 &:= (((8 + 1) - (7 \times 5)) \times (1 - (8^6))) \\
 6815737 &:= -((7 - (((3 \times 7) + 5) \times ((1 \times 8)^6))) \\
 6815744 &:= ((4 + (((4 \times 7) - 5) - 1)) \times (8^6)) \\
 6826668 &:= (((86 - 6)^{6-2} + 8)/6) \\
 6837608 &:= (((80 + 6)^{7-3})/8) + 6) \\
 6854676 &:= (6 \times (((((7 + 6)^4) \times 5) \times 8) + 6)) \\
 6865625 &:= ((5^2) \times (65^{6/(8-6)})) \\
 6873862 &:= (((2 + (6^8)) \times 3) + (7 \times (8^6))) \\
 6875698 &:= -((((8 - 96) \times ((5^7) + 8)) + 6) \\
 6907823 &:= ((3 - (2 \times 8)) \times (70 - (9^6))) \\
 6908629 &:= -((((9 - 2) + 6) \times (8 - (09^6))) \\
 6908733 &:= (((3 + 3) + 7) \times (((8 \times 0) + 9)^6)) \\
 6908837 &:= (((7 \times 3) - 8) \times (8 + (09^6))) \\
 6927478 &:= (((8 \times 7) \times 47)^2) + (9 \times 6) \\
 6940323 &:= (((3^2) + 30)^4) \times (9 - 6) \\
 6957264 &:= -(((46 \times ((2 - (7^5)) \times 9)) + 6)) \\
 6967871 &:= (((178 + 7) + 6)^{9-6}) \\
 6999744 &:= -(((4^4) - (7 \times (((9/9) + 9)^6)))) \\
 7062667 &:= (((7^6) + 62) \times 60) + 7) \\
 7109375 &:= ((5^7) \times (((3 + 9) + 01) \times 7)) \\
 7112448 &:= ((((((84^4) - 2) + 1) + 1)/7) \\
 7163152 &:= -((2 - ((51^3) \times (61 - 7)))) \\
 7169757 &:= ((((((7^5) - 7) - 9) \times 61) \times 7) \\
 7176589 &:= (((9 \times 8) - 5) - 6) \times (7^{-1+7}) \\
 7177016 &:= (61 \times ((07^{7-1}) + 7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7198355 &:= (-5) \times (((-((5-3)-8))^9) + 1)/(-7)) & 7529641 &:= (((14^6) - 9) + (2 \times 57)) \\ 7235532 &:= -(((23^5) - ((5^3)^2 \times 7))) & 7529659 &:= (((9+5)^6) + 9) + (2 \times 57)) \\ 7252256 &:= (6 - 52^2 + 5)^2 + 7 & 7529668 &:= (((8+6)^6) + ((9+2) \times (5+7))) \\ 7254282 &:= (2 + (8 - 2 - 4^5)^2) \times 7 & 7532668 &:= (((8+6)^6) + (((2+3)^5) + 7)) \\ 7263314 &:= (41 \times ((3^{3+6+2}) + 7)) & 7558124 &:= -((4 \times ((2 - (18^5)) + (5 \times 7)))) \\ 7282646 &:= -(((6 - ((4^6) \times ((2^8) - 2))) \times 7)) & 7558224 &:= (4 \times (((2 + (2 \times 8))^5) - (5 + 7))) \\ 7285776 &:= (6 \times (((7^7) + (5^8)) + (2^7))) & 7558244 &:= (4 \times (((4+2) \times (8-5))^5) - 7)) \\ 7301391 &:= (((193+1)^{03}) + 7) & 7558266 &:= -((6 - ((6^{2+8})/(5/5) + 7))) \\ 7311525 &:= ((52^{5-1}) - (13 \times 7)) & 7558272 &:= (27 \times (((2 \times 8) - 5) - 5)^7)) \\ 7311568 &:= -((8 \times 6) + ((51+1)^{-3+7})) & 7558284 &:= ((4 \times (((8+2) + 8)^5)) + (5+7)) \\ 7311584 &:= -((4 \times 8) + ((51+1)^{-3+7})) & 7577933 &:= -((((3 - ((3^9) \times 77)) \times 5) + 7)) \\ 7311609 &:= (9 - 061)^{1+3} - 7 & 7577939 &:= -((9 - (((3^9) \times 77) \times 5) - 7)) \\ 7311623 &:= (3^2 - 61)^{1+3} + 7 & 7578125 &:= (((5 \times 2) \times 1) + 87) \times (5^7)) \\ 7332256 &:= -(((6^5) - ((2^{23-3}) \times 7))) & 7586796 &:= ((6^9) - (76 \times ((8^5) + 7))) \\ 7339864 &:= -((4 \times ((6 - (8^{9/3+3})) \times 7))) & 7595525 &:= ((((((5^2)^5) + 5)/9) + 5) \times 7) \\ 7340144 &:= (((4 + (4^{10})) + (4 \times 3)) \times 7) & 7598464 &:= -((464 \times (8 - ((9-5)^7)))) \\ 7375823 &:= (((3 \times (28^5)) - (7^3))/7) & 7646925 &:= 5 \times ((-2+9)^6 - 4) \times (6+7) \\ 7378896 &:= (6 \times (((9 \times 8) + ((8 \times 7)^3)) \times 7)) & 7656285 &:= ((5 + (((8^2) + 6) \times (5^6))) \times 7) \\ 7394592 &:= (((2 \times 9)^5) + (((4^9) \times 3) \times 7)) & 7666582 &:= (((2 \times 8)^5) + ((6^6) - 6)) \times 7) \\ 7397435 &:= ((53^4) - ((79^3) + 7)) & 7666624 &:= (((4 \times ((2+6)^6)) + (6^6)) \times 7) \\ 7411779 &:= (9 \times (((((7^7) - 1) \times 1) - 4) - 7)) & 7668459 &:= (9 \times (5 + (((4^8) + 6) \times (6+7)))) \\ 7411799 &:= -(((9 \times (9 - (7^{11-4}))) + 7)) & 7724367 &:= (7 \times (((6^{3+4}) + 2) + (7^7))) \\ 7411869 &:= (9 \times ((6-8) + ((11-4)^7))) & 7734375 &:= (((5^7) \times 3) \times ((4 \times (3+7)) - 7)) \\ 7411877 &:= (((7^7) \times (8+1)) + ((1-4) - 7)) & 7754572 &:= ((2 - 7 \times 5)^4 - 5^7) \times 7 \\ 7411879 &:= ((9 \times (7^{8-1})) - ((1^4) + 7)) & 7765296 &:= ((6 + (((9-2)^5) \times 6)) \times 77) \\ 7411887 &:= (((7^8) \times (8+1))/(1^4 \times 7)) & 7765625 &:= (((5 \times 2)^6) + ((5^6) \times 7)) \times 7) \\ 7413679 &:= (((9 \times (7^6)) + ((3+1)^4)) \times 7) & 7789422 &:= ((2 + ((2 \times (4+9)) \times (8^7)))/7) \\ 7414875 &:= ((5 \times (7 + (8 \times 4)))^{-1 \times 4 + 7}) & 7798784 &:= ((4^8) \times (((7+8) + 9) - 7) \times 7) \\ 7421875 &:= ((5^7) \times (81 - ((2-4) \times 7))) & 7812495 &:= (((5^9) \times 4) + 2) - ((1^8) \times 7) \\ 7421951 &:= -((1 - (((5 \times 91) - 2) \times (4^7)))) & 7812528 &:= ((8/2) \times ((5^{2-1+8}) + 7)) \\ 7425855 &:= (5 \times (((((5+8)^5) - 2) \times 4) + 7)) & 7812544 &:= (4 \times (4 + ((5^{2-1+8}) + 7))) \\ 7431259 &:= (((((9+5)^2) - 1)^3) + (4^7)) & 7836693 &:= -((3 + ((9 - (6^6)) \times ((3 \times 8) \times 7)))) \\ 7439922 &:= -((2 \times (((2 \times 9) - ((9 \times 3)^4)) \times 7))) & 7838152 &:= (((2 \times (((5+1)^8)/3)) - 8) \times 7) \\ 7439936 &:= (((6 \times ((3^9) \times 9)) - 34) \times 7) & 7838264 &:= (((4 \times (6^{2+8-3})) + 8) \times 7) \\ 7439992 &:= -((2 \times ((9 - (((9 \times 9)^3) - 4)) \times 7))) & 7850784 &:= -((4 \times ((8 \times (7^{05})) - (8^7)))) \\ 7448779 &:= ((9 \times ((7^7) + (8^4))) + (4 \times 7)) & 7863885 &:= (5 \times (((8 \times 8)^3) \times 6) - 87)) \\ 7471275 &:= (57 \times (((2^{17}) - 4) + 7)) & 7885435 &:= ((53^4) - (58 \times 87)) \\ 7529536 &:= (6 + 3 + 5)^{9 \times 2 - 5 - 7} & 7885693 &:= -((3 - (((9^6) - (5^8)) \times (8 \times 7)))) \\ 7529627 &:= (((7 \times 2)^6) + (((9 \times 2) - 5) \times 7)) & 7912559 &:= (((9^5) \times ((5^{2+1}) + 9)) - 7) \end{aligned}$$

- 7914864** := -((((46 - 8)⁴) - ((1 + 9)⁷)))
7929848 := -((8 - ((4⁸) × ((9 + 2)⁹⁻⁷)))
7962546 := (((((6 × 4)⁵) - 2) - 69) - 7)
7962564 := (((((4 × 6)⁵) + 2) - 69) + 7)
7962631 := (((((1 + 3) × 6)²⁻⁶⁺⁹) + 7)
7964136 := ((6³) × (((1 × 4)⁶) × 9) + 7))
7971535 := (5 × ((3⁵⁺¹⁺⁷) - (9 + 7)))
7978176 := (((6⁷) × (1 + (8 × 7)))/(9 - 7))
7994184 := (((4⁸) - 1) × 49) + (9⁷)
8103375 := (((5 × 7) × 3)³) × ((0 - 1) + 8))
8154875 := -(((5 - ((7 × 8)⁴)) + ((5 + 1)⁸)))
8257284 := (((4⁸) - 2) × 7) × ((5 × 2) + 8))
8257536 := (63 × (-((5 - 7)^{5²⁻⁸})))
8258048 := (8 - 4^{0×8+5})² × 8
8290528 := (8 × (((2 × 509)²) - 8))
8290584 := ((4 × 8) × (509²)) - 8)
8298592 := (-2) + (9 × ((5⁸) + (9⁻²⁺⁸)))
8345168 := -(((8 - 61) × ((54³) - 8))
8345584 := (((48 + 5) × (54³)) - 8)
8349696 := ((6⁹) - (((6 + 9) × 4)³) × 8))
8353125 := (((5 × ((2 - 1) × 3)⁵) × (3 + 8))
8355815 := -((((51 × 8⁵) - 5) × (3 - 8))
8365427 := ((-((7 × ((2 - 4) - 56))³)/8)
8376944 := (((4⁴⁺⁹) - ((6⁷)/3))/8)
8382455 := (((5⁵) - ((4 + 2)⁸) × (3 - 8))
8382464 := (((4⁶⁺⁴) - ((2⁸) × 3)) × 8)
8384512 := (((((2 × 1)⁵)⁴) - (8³)) × 8)
8384544 := (((((4 × 4)⁵) + 4) - (8³)) × 8)
8385288 := (((8⁸)/2) - ((5 × 83) × 8))
8386784 := ((4 × 8⁷) - ((6 × 8) × 38))
8387584 := -(((4 - (8⁵)) × ((7 - 8) + 3)⁸)))
8387592 := -((((2 - ((9 - 5)⁷)) × (8³)) - 8))
8387864 := (4 × ((6 + (8⁷)) - ((8 × 3) × 8))
8388224 := ((4²) × (((2⁸⁺⁸) - 3) × 8))
8388288 := (((8⁸)/2) + ((8 × 8) × (3 - 8))
8388446 := -((((6⁴) - (4⁸⁺⁸⁻³))/8)
8388472 := -((((2 × (7 - ((4⁸) × 8))) + 3) × 8))
8388528 := (8 × (-((2 × 5) + ((8 + 8)⁻³⁺⁸)))
8388542 := -((2 - (((4⁵⁺⁸) - (8³))/8))
8388544 := (((4 × 4)⁵) × 8) - ((8³)/8))
8388564 := -((4 × ((6 + 5) - ((8 × 8)³) × 8))
8388582 := (((((2 × 8)⁵) - 8) × 8) + 38)
8388584 := ((4 × ((8⁵) × 8) × 8) - (3 × 8))
8388592 := -(((2 - ((9 - 5) × ((8 × 8)³))) × 8))
8388599 := -((9 - ((9 - 5) × ((8 × 8)³) × 8))
8388608 := ((8⁰⁶) × (((8/8) + 3) × 8))
8388613 := -((3 - (((16⁸)/8³)) + 8))
8388622 := ((2 × ((2⁶⁺⁸⁺⁸) + 3)) + 8)
8388624 := -((4 × ((2 - 6) - ((8 × 8)³) × 8))
8388632 := (((2^{3×6+8})/8) + (3 × 8))
8388648 := (8 × ((4⁻⁶⁺⁸⁺⁸) - ((3 - 8))
8388684 := (4 × (((8⁶) × 8) + 8) + 3) + 8))
8388784 := ((4 × 8⁷) + ((8 + 8) × (3 + 8))
8388864 := (((4 × 6) + 8) × ((8 × 8)³) + 8))
8388928 := (8 × (((2⁹⁺⁸) + (8 - 3)) × 8))
8389272 := ((2^{7×2+9}) + (83 × 8))
8389464 := (((4 × (6 + (4⁹))) + 83) × 8)
8389472 := ((27 + (4⁹)) × ((8 × 3) + 8))
8391584 := (4 × (((8⁵⁺¹) + 93) × 8))
8394955 := -(((5⁵) - ((9 - 4) × ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8395178 := -((((8⁷) × (1 - 5)) - 9) - (3⁸))
8397455 := (-5) × ((5⁻⁴⁺⁷) - ((9 - 3)⁸))
8397685 := -((5 × ((86 - 7) - ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8397955 := -((5 × ((5⁹⁻⁷) - ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8398055 := -((5 × (5 - (((0 × 8) + 9) - 3)⁸)))
8398065 := (((5 × (6⁰⁸)) + 9) - (3 × 8))
8398075 := (5 × ((7 - 08) + ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8398085 := (5 × ((8/08) + ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8398115 := -((5 × (((1 × 1) - 8) - ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8398125 := (5 × (((2 - 1) + 8) + ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8398135 := (5 × (((3 × 1) + 8) + ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8398145 := (5 × (((4 + 1) + 8) + ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8398155 := (5 × (((5 + 1)⁸) - 9) + (3 × 8))
8398165 := ((5 × ((6 × 1)⁸)) + (93 - 8))
8398175 := (5 × (((7 - 1)⁸) + ((9 × 3) - 8))
8398215 := -((5 × ((1 - 28) - ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8398235 := (5 × ((3 + 28) + ((9 - 3)⁸)))
8398245 := (5 × (((4 + 2)⁸) + 9) + (3 × 8))

$$\begin{aligned}
 8398355 &:= (5 \times ((5 \times (3 + 8)) + ((9 - 3)^8))) & 8912913 &:= (((((3 + 1)^9) \times 2) + 1) \times (9 + 8)) \\
 8398595 &:= (5 \times ((95 + 8) + ((9 - 3)^8))) & 8954912 &:= (2 \times 1 - 94)^{-5+9}/8 \\
 8399225 &:= (5 \times (229 + ((9 - 3)^8))) & 8957684 &:= (4 \times ((8 \times (6^7)) - (59 + 8))) \\
 8399555 &:= (5 \times ((5 \times 59) + ((9 - 3)^8))) & 8957688 &:= ((8 \times ((8 - (6^7)) \times (5 - 9))) - 8) \\
 8437536 &:= (((((6 + 3) \times (5^7)) + 3) \times (4 + 8)) & 8957728 &:= -((((8 - 2)^7) - 7) \times ((5 - 9) \times 8))) \\
 8437572 &:= ((2 + 7) \times (((5^7) \times 3) \times 4) + 8) & 8957824 &:= 4 \times ((-2 + 8)^7 + 5 - 9) \times 8 \\
 8439296 &:= ((6^9) + ((2 - (9 \times 3)) \times (4^8))) & 8957937 &:= -((7 + (((3 + 9)^7)/(5 - 9)) + 8)) \\
 8454137 &:= -((7 - (((31 \times 4) + 5) \times (4^8))) & 8957952 &:= -((((2 - 5) + 9)^7) \times ((5 - 9) \times 8)) \\
 8454144 &:= ((4 + (((4 + 1)^4)/5)) \times (4^8)) & 8958176 &:= -((((6^7) - 1) + 8) \times ((5 - 9) \times 8)) \\
 8467271 &:= -((1 - (72 \times ((7^6) - 48))) & 8984375 &:= ((5^7) \times ((34 + 89) - 8)) \\
 8496483 &:= -((((3^8) + 4) - (((6 \times 9)^4) - 8)) & 9150616 &:= (((61 - 6)^{05-1}) - 9) \\
 8515196 &:= ((6^9) + ((1 - 5) \times ((1 \times 5)^8))) & 9152595 &:= ((5 \times (9^5)) \times ((2^5) - (1^9))) \\
 8552448 &:= ((8^4) \times ((4 + (2^5)) \times 58)) & 9156875 &:= ((5 \times 7) \times ((8^6) - 519)) \\
 8584696 &:= ((6^9) - ((6 \times ((4 + 8)^5)) + 8)) & 9174945 &:= (5 \times (((((4^9) - 4) \times 7) \times 1) + 9)) \\
 8588553 &:= -((3 \times (5 - (((5^8) - (8^5)) \times 8))) & 9176676 &:= (6 \times (((7^6) \times (6 + 7)) + (1 \times 9))) \\
 8588568 &:= (((8^6) - ((5^8) \times 8)) \times (5 - 8)) & 9229426 &:= (((62 \times 49)^2) - (2 \times 9)) \\
 8593222 &:= -((22 \times ((2 \times (3 + 9)) - (5^8))) & 9237624 &:= -((((4 \times 2) - (6^7)) \times 3) \times (2 + 9)) \\
 8593551 &:= -((1 + (((5 \times 5) - 3) \times (9 - (5^8)))) & 9237699 &:= ((99 \times (((6^7)/3) - 2)) + 9) \\
 8593552 &:= -((((2 + 5) + (5 \times 3)) \times (9 - (5^8))) & 9237822 &:= ((-2) + (-((2 - 8)^7)) \times (3 \times (2 + 9))) \\
 8593745 &:= -((5 - (((4 \times 7) + 3) - 9) \times (5^8))) & 9253827 &:= ((7 + ((2 \times ((8^3) - 5))^2)) \times 9) \\
 8593816 &:= (((6 - 1)^8) + 3) \times ((9 + 5) + 8) & 9273339 &:= (-((93^3)) + (-(((3 - 7) - 2))^9)) \\
 8594542 &:= ((2 + (4 \times 5)) \times ((4 \times 9) + (5^8))) & 9289728 &:= (((8/2)^7) \times ((9 \times (8^2)) - 9)) \\
 8605184 &:= (((4 \times (8 - 1))^5)/(0 - 6) + 8) & 9294645 &:= ((5 + ((4 + 6)^4)) \times 929) \\
 8632455 &:= (5 \times (((5^{4+2}) \times 3) + (6^8))) & 9296875 &:= ((5^7) \times (((8 + 6) \times 9) + 2) - 9) \\
 8671875 &:= ((5^7) \times ((8 - 1) + ((7 + 6) \times 8))) & 9329733 &:= -((3 \times (3 - ((79 \times 2) \times (3^9)))) \\
 8683515 &:= -((5 \times (1 - (53 \times ((8^6)/8)))) & 9329736 &:= -((6 - (((3 \times 79) \times 2) \times (3^9))) \\
 8683535 &:= (5 \times (3 + (53 \times ((8^6)/8)))) & 9336411 &:= (((1 + (146^3))/3) \times 9) \\
 8693345 &:= (5 \times (4 + ((3 \times (3^9)) + (6^8)))) & 9374856 &:= -(((6 - (5^8)) \times (((4 + 7) \times 3) - 9))) \\
 8731989 &:= (9 \times (((8 + 91)^3) - 78)) & 9375024 &:= -(((4 + (20 \times (5^7))) \times (3 - 9))) \\
 8739348 &:= ((8 + 4) \times (((3^9) \times 37) + 8)) & 9375285 &:= (5 \times ((8 \times ((2 + (5^7)) \times 3)) + 9)) \\
 8750672 &:= ((2 \times 7) \times ((6 + (05^7)) \times 8)) & 9393084 &:= ((480 - 3) \times (9 + (3^9))) \\
 8782768 &:= (((8^6) + (7 \times ((2 + 8)^7)))/8) & 9414684 &:= (4 \times (((8^6) - ((4 + 1)^4)) \times 9)) \\
 8814592 &:= -((((29 - 5)^{4+1}) - (8^8)) & 9427968 &:= (((8^6) - ((9 + 7)^2)) \times (4 \times 9)) \\
 8817896 &:= (((((6^9)/8) \times 7) \times 1) - 88) & 9435268 &:= -((8 + ((6^2) \times (53 - (4^9)))) \\
 8817936 &:= -(((6 - (((3^9) \times 7) \times 1) \times 8)) \times 8) & 9436536 &:= ((6^{-3+5}) \times (-((6 \times 3) - (4^9)))) \\
 8817968 &:= -((8 - (((((6^9) \times 7) \times 1)/8) - 8)) & 9436824 &:= (((4^{2+8}) - (6 + 34)) \times 9) \\
 8823675 &:= -(((5 \times (7^6)) \times (((3 - 2) - 8) - 8)) & 9436833 &:= -((((3^3) - (((8^6) - 3) \times 4)) \times 9)) \\
 8863742 &:= -((2 + ((4^7) \times (3 - (68 \times 8)))) & 9436878 &:= (((8^7)/(8 - 6)) - 34) \times 9) \\
 8912897 &:= -((7 - (((9 + 8) \times (2^{19})) + 8)) & 9436968 &:= ((((((8^6) - 9) + 6) - 3) \times 4) \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9437139 &:= (9 \times (((3+1)^{7+3}) + (4-9))) & 9565839 &:= -((((9-(3^{8+5})) \times 6) + (5 \times 9))) \\ 9437144 &:= -((4 - (((4^{1 \times 7+3}) - 4) \times 9))) & 9565879 &:= (((9^7)/(8-5)) \times 6) - 59 \\ 9437148 &:= (((8 \times 4)^{1^7+3}) - 4) \times 9 & 9565929 &:= (((9 \times 2) \times (9^5)) - (6-5)) \times 9 \\ 9437157 &:= -(((7 - (((5-1)^{7+3}) + 4)) \times 9)) & 9565932 &:= -((2 \times (3 - (9^{5+6+5-9}))) \\ 9437177 &:= -((7 - (((71-7)^3) \times 4) \times 9)) & 9565934 &:= (((4 \times ((3 \times 9)^5))/6) + (5-9)) \\ 9437182 &:= -((2 - (((8+1) \times (7-3)) \times (4^9)))) & 9576477 &:= -((((7^7) \times ((4-6) \times 7)) + (5^9))) \\ 9437184 &:= (((((4+8) + 17) + 3)^4) \times 9) & 9586982 &:= -((2 - (((8^9) + (6 \times 8))/(5+9)))) \\ 9437247 &:= ((7 + (((42-7) - 3)^4)) \times 9) & 9599973 &:= (3 \times ((-(79-99))^5) - 9) \\ 9437247 &:= ((7 + (((42-7) - 3)^4)) \times 9) & 9653628 &:= -((8 - (2 \times (((6 \times 3) - 5)^6) + 9))) \\ 9437264 &:= -((4 - ((6 \times 2) \times (7 + (3 \times (4^9)))))) & 9653636 &:= ((6/3) \times (((6 \times 3) - 5)^6) + 9) \\ 9437265 &:= ((5 + (((6-2)^{7+3}) + 4)) \times 9) & 9657521 &:= -((((1 \times 25) \times (7^5)) - (6^9))) \\ 9437268 &:= (((8+6) - 2) \times (7 + (3 \times (4^9)))) & 9657861 &:= ((1 + ((6^8)/(7+5))) \times 69) \\ 9437291 &:= -((1 - ((9+27) \times (3 + (4^9)))))) & 9664359 &:= -((((9^5) \times (3+4)) - 6) - (6^9)) \\ 9437292 &:= (((2^{9+2+7}) + 3) \times (4 \times 9)) & 9684516 &:= ((6 \times ((1+5) - (4^8))) + (6^9)) \\ 9437328 &:= ((((((8^2)^3) + 7) - 3) \times 4) \times 9) & 9685343 &:= -((((3 \times 4)^3) + (5^8)) - (6^9)) \\ 9437346 &:= ((6 + ((4^{3+7}) + (3 \times 4))) \times 9) & 9720063 &:= (((3 \times (600^2)) + 7) \times 9) \\ 9437436 &:= ((6^3) + (((4^{7+3}) + 4) \times 9)) & 9745942 &:= (((2^4) + 9)^5) - (-((4-7)^9)) \\ 9437499 &:= -((9 - (9 \times ((4^{7+3}) + (4 \times 9)))))) & 9745952 &:= (((2 + (5^9)) \times 5) - (-((4-7)^9)) \\ 9437544 &:= (((4^{4+5}) + (7+3)) \times (4 \times 9)) & 9747715 &:= ((5 \times 17) \times ((7 \times (4^7)) - 9)) \\ 9437877 &:= ((77 + ((8 \times (7-3))^4)) \times 9) & 9764867 &:= ((7^6) \times ((8 \times 4) + ((6 \times 7) + 9))) \\ 9437964 &:= (4 \times (6 + (9 \times ((7 \times 3) + (4^9)))))) & 9765549 &:= (((((9-4) \times 5)^5) - 67) - 9) \\ 9440295 &:= (59 \times (((20^4) - 4) + 9)) & 9765551 &:= -((1 - (((5 \times 5)^5) + 6) - 79)) \\ 9441792 &:= (((2^9) + (((7+1) \times 4)^4)) \times 9) & 9765553 &:= -(((3 - (((5 \times 5)^5) - 6)) + (7 \times 9))) \\ 9445536 &:= (((((6 \times 3)^5) \times 5) - (4^4) \times 9)) & 9765556 &:= (((((6 \times 5) - 5)^5) - 6) - (7 \times 9)) \\ 9446445 &:= ((5 + ((4 + (4^6)) \times (4^4))) \times 9) & 9765559 &:= -(((9 - (((5 \times 5)^5) + 6)) + (7 \times 9))) \\ 9447795 &:= (-5) \times (9 - (((7+7) + 4)^{-4+9})) & 9765585 &:= -((5 \times (8 - (5^{5+6+7-9}))) \\ 9447876 &:= ((((((6^7) \times (8+7))/4) + 4) \times 9) & 9765593 &:= (-(((3 \times 9) + 5)) + 5^{-6+7+9}) \\ 9449568 &:= (8 \times ((6 + (5 \times (9^4))) \times (4 \times 9))) & 9765594 &:= (-(((4 \times 9) - 5)) + 5^{-6+7+9}) \\ 9459684 &:= (4 \times (((8^6) \times 9) + ((5^4) \times 9))) & 9765597 &:= (-((7 \times (9-5))) + 5^{-6+7+9}) \\ 9463419 &:= -((9 \times (1 - (4 \times ((3^6) + (4^9)))))) & 9765613 &:= (((31-6)^5) + (6 \times (7-9))) \\ 9463428 &:= (((8^{2+4}) + (3^6)) \times (4 \times 9)) & 9765614 &:= -(((4+1) + 6)) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \\ 9476909 &:= (((90^{9-6}) - 7) \times (4+9)) & 9765615 &:= ((5^{-1+6+5}) + (((6-7) - 9))) \\ 9492289 &:= ((9^8) + ((2^{-2+9}) \times (-4^9))) & 9765616 &:= (6-1)^{6+5+6-7} - 9 \\ 9528759 &:= -((9 \times ((5 - ((7^8-2) - 5)) \times 9))) & 9765617 &:= (-((7 + (1^6))) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \\ 9529612 &:= (((21^6)/9) - 2) + (5 \times 9) & 9765618 &:= -((8 - (1^6))) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \\ 9529672 &:= (((2 + (7^6)) \times (9^2)) - 59) & 9765621 &:= (-((1-26)^5) - ((6+7) - 9)) \\ 9532345 &:= -((5 \times (((4+32)^3) - (5^9)))) & 9765624 &:= ((4/(2-6)) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \\ 9549684 &:= (4 \times (((8^6) + ((9-4)^5)) \times 9)) & 9765625 &:= 5^{2-65-6+79} \\ 9565837 &:= -((((7 - (3^{8+5})) \times 6) + 59)) & 9765631 &:= (((1^3) \times 6) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9765632 &:= -(((2-3)-6)) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \\
 9765635 &:= (((5^{3+6}) \times 5) - ((6-7)-9)) \\
 9765637 &:= (((7+(3 \times 6))^5) - (6 \times (7-9))) \\
 9765643 &:= (((3 \times 4) + 6) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \\
 9765645 &:= ((5^{4+6}) + (5 \times ((6+7)-9))) \\
 9765647 &:= (((7 \times 4) - 6) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \\
 9765661 &:= (((1 \times 6) \times 6) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \\
 9765687 &:= (((7 \times 8) + 6) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \\
 9765735 &:= ((5^{3+7}) + (5 \times ((6+7)+9))) \\
 9765753 &:= ((-((3-5))^7) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \\
 9765825 &:= ((5^2) \times (8 + (5^{6-7+9}))) \\
 9765865 &:= (((5 \times 6) \times 8) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \\
 9765915 &:= ((5^{1+9}) + (5 \times (67-9))) \\
 9765949 &:= (((9 \times 4) \times 9) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \\
 9765985 &:= (((5 \times 8) \times 9) + (5^{-6+7+9})) \\
 9786715 &:= ((51 + ((7 \times 6) \times (8^7)))/9) \\
 9797657 &:= ((7 \times ((5 \times (6^7)) - (9+7))) + 9) \\
 9797765 &:= (((5 \times (6^7)) - (7-9)) \times 7) - 9) \\
 9821955 &:= ((((((5^5) + 9) \times 1)^2) + 8) - 9) \\
 9825792 &:= ((2^9) \times ((75 \times (2^8)) - 9)) \\
 9834427 &:= (((((7 \times 2) \times 4)^4) + 3) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 9834478 &:= ((((((8 \times 7)^4) - 4) + 3) - 8) - 9) \\
 9834487 &:= (((7 \times 8)^4) + (((4+3)-8) \times 9)) \\
 9834496 &:= (((6+9) \times 4) - 4)^{3-8+9} \\
 9834516 &:= (((((61-5)^4) + 3) + 8) + 9) \\
 9835487 &:= (((7 \times 8)^4) + (((5^3) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 9861183 &:= -(((3^8) \times ((1-168) \times 9))) \\
 9874764 &:= ((4 + (67 \times ((4^7) - 8))) \times 9) \\
 9921875 &:= -(((5^7) \times ((8 \times (1 - (2 \times 9))) + 9))) \\
 9933894 &:= ((4 + (((9^8) - 3)/39)) \times 9) \\
 9951797 &:= -(((7 \times ((9^{7-1}) - (5^9))) - 9)) \\
 9959384 &:= -(((4^8) - (((39^5)/9) + 9))) \\
 9977874 &:= (((((4^7) \times 87) \times 7) + 9) + 9) \\
 9981576 &:= (((6 \times (7^5)) - 18) \times 99) \\
 9999991 &:= (1 + 9)^{9-(9+9)/9} - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

4 Summary: Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers** [2, 3, 4]. Friedmann [6, 7] also made some study in this direction. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Following subsections give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers are with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **Quadratic numbers**, **Cubic numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. The other way of writing **selfie numbers** is by use of **permutable powers**, where **bases** and **exponents** are of same digits. See the subsection below with some examples.

4.1 Permutable Powers

Below are some examples of **permutable power selfie numbers**. By **permutable powers**, we understand that bases and exponents are of same digits with different permutations. Some times we may call them as **flexible power selfie numbers**.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &:= 1^1 & 1654 &:= -1^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5 \\
 23 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 & 1837 &:= 1^8 - 8^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 \\
 1239 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & 2137 &:= -2^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^2 \\
 1364 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3 & 2173 &:= -2^3 + 1^2 - 7^1 + 3^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2537 &:= 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^7 + 7^3 & 46350 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^4 \\
 3125 &:= -3^2 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 5^5 & 46360 &:= 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 - 6^3 + 0^6 \\
 3275 &:= -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5 & 397612 &:= 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3 \\
 3435 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 & 423858 &:= 4^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^8 + 8^5 \\
 3529 &:= -3^3 + 5^5 + 2^9 - 9^2 & 637395 &:= 6^5 + 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^6 + 5^7 \\
 4316 &:= 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^4 + 6^3 & 758014 &:= 7^7 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 0^5 + 1^4 - 4^8 \\
 4355 &:= 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5 & 778530 &:= 7^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 3^0 + 0^8 \\
 39339 &:= -3^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 9^3 & 804637 &:= 8^0 + 0^4 - 4^8 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15647982 &:= 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 7^7 - 9^1 + 8^8 + 2^6 \\
 17946238 &:= 1^6 + 7^8 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 6^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 8^7 \\
 57396108 &:= -5^6 + 7^9 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^7 + 1^1 + 0^0 + 8^8 \\
 134287690 &:= 1^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 8^9 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^1 \\
 387945261 &:= 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^6 + 9^9 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 1^5 \\
 392876054 &:= 3^0 + 9^9 - 2^2 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 + 0^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 \\
 392876540 &:= -3^0 + 9^9 - 2^4 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 - 5^3 + 4^6 + 0^2
 \end{aligned}$$

More details can be seen in author's work [20].

4.2 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders:

$$\begin{aligned}
 13825 &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 14641 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 &= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 \\
 15552 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 16377 &:= (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \\
 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8 - 2)^{3+3} / 2 \\
 116565 &:= (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) &= 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 131072 &:= (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned}
 656250 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 0 = 0 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656251 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 1 = 1 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 656252 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 2 = 2 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656253 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 3 = 3 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656254 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 4 = 4 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656255 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 5 = 5 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656256 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 6 = 6 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656257 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 7 = 7 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656258 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 8 = 8 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656259 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 9 = 9 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

The past work up to 6 digits numbers can be seen in [14, 15, 16]. In this work, along with past work, we extended it to 7 digits numbers.

4.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\
 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\
 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\
 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\
 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and are only with positive and negative coefficients. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways:

$$\begin{aligned}
 35280 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35281 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35282 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35283 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35284 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35285 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35286 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35287 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35288 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35289 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [26, 27].

4.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$2378 := -23 + \sqrt{7^8}$	$1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}}} \times 1$
$19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$	$1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9}+2-1}$
$19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$	$2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$
$19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$	$3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$
$839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$	$9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9}$
$839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$	$12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$
$839804 := (-8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$	$19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$
$839816 := (8 + (3 - 9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$	$42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$
$995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$	$59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 0 + 9^5$
$999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$	$999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$
$999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	$999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer author's work [14, 15].

4.5 Factorial and Square-Root

Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in **digit's order** and its reverse

$936 := (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6!$	$= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}}$
$1296 := \sqrt{(1 + 2)!^9 / 6}$	$= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)}$
$2896 := 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!)$	$= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2$
$331779 := 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}}$	$= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3$
$342995 := (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$	$= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3$
$759375 := (-7 + 59 - 37)^5$	$= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7}$
$759381 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1$	$= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7$
$5040 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 0 = 0 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$	
$5041 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 1 = 1 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$	
$5042 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 2 = 2 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$	
$5043 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$	

$$\begin{aligned}
 5044 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 4 = 4 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5045 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5046 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 6 = 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5047 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 7 = 7 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5048 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 8 = 8 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5049 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 9 = 9 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!
 \end{aligned}$$

The following examples are in **digit's order** and its **reverse** separately:

$120 := ((1 + 2)! - 0)!$	$25 := 5^2$
$127 := -1 + 2^7$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$1673 := -1 - 6 + 7!/3$	$289 := (9 + 8)^2$
$1679 := 1 + (-6 + 7!)/\sqrt{9}$	$3894 := (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}) \times 3$
$1680 := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{8 + 0!}$	$4957 := 7! - 59 - 4!$
$38970 := -3!! + 8! - 9 \times 70$	$6992 := 2^9 + 9 \times 6!$
$38986 := -3 + 8! - \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^6}$	$26493 := (2 + 6)! - 4!^{\sqrt{9}} - 3$
$40310 := (\sqrt{4^{03}})! - 10$	$30792 := 3! \times ((0 + 7)! + 92)$
$90894 := -(\sqrt{9})! + ((0! + 8)! + (\sqrt{9})!!)/4$	$54476 := (5! + 4!^4 - 7!)/6$
$91560 := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! + 5! \times (6! + 0!)$	$75989 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!!) + 5^7$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [14, 15, 16].

4.6 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n + 1) = F(n) + F(n - 1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. This we have done in different situations, such as using $F(\cdot)$ and $F(F(\cdot))$ in separate works. See below examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 143 &:= -1 + F(4 \times 3) &= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 986 &:= F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6)) &= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\
 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) &= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11) \\
 2585 &:= F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) &= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2) \\
 12819 &:= 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9) &= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1 \\
 24297 &:= F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7) &= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2) \\
 39394 &:= -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)} &= (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74997 &:= -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7) &= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7 \\ 87937 &:= -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7) &= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8 \\ 98703 &:= 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03)) &= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34 &:= F(3 \times F(4)) & 36 &:= 6^{F(3)} \\ 233 &:= F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3)) & 143 &:= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\ 630 &:= F(F(6)) \times 30 & 231 &:= F(13) - 2 \\ 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) & 377 &:= F(-7 + 7 \times 3) \\ 2079 &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9 & 986 &:= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\ 4864 &:= F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) & 1165 &:= 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1)) \\ 8759 &:= -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8)) & 1596 &:= F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1))) \\ 8849 &:= -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8) + F(F(8)) & 2592 &:= F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2)) \\ 9349 &:= -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9))) & 9756 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 834660 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834661 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834662 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834663 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834664 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834665 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834666 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834667 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834668 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834669 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21960 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21961 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21962 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21963 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21964 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21965 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21966 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21967 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21968 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21969 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2. \end{aligned}$$

First three blocks are in both ways. In the last block the first column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [23, 24].

4.7 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below some examples:

1069 := $T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$	874 := $T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$
1081 := $T(1 + T(08 + 1))$	0105 := $50 + T(10)$
2887 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$	1155 := $-T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$
4965 := $T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$	1224 := $T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1$
4999 := $49 + T(99)$	2418 := $T(81) - T(42)$
99545 := $T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$	99632 := $2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$
99546 := $T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6.$	99633 := $3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

2210 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
2211 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
2212 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
2213 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
2214 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
2215 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
2216 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
2217 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
2218 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
2219 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$

For more details see author's work [21].

4.8 Binomial Coefficients

Binomial coefficients are well known in literature. They are given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

In above subsections, we gave examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. Still, one can have similar kind results using **binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways**, **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$\mathbf{6435} := C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15504 &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ 42504 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\ 54264 &:= C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4+5})!) \\ 74613 &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12650 &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) & 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\ 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) & 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\ 14950 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) & 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) & 2024 &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\ 19448 &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) & 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\ 26334 &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) & 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\ 43758 &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) & 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\ 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!). & 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)). \end{aligned}$$

Consecutive sequential representations:

$$\begin{aligned} 25920 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9,2) + 0 & 98280 &:= 0 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25921 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9,2) + 1 & 98281 &:= 1 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25922 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9,2) + 2 & 98282 &:= 2 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25923 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9,2) + 3 & 98283 &:= 3 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25924 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9,2) + 4 & 98284 &:= 4 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25925 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9,2) + 5 & 98285 &:= 5 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25926 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9,2) + 6 & 98286 &:= 6 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25927 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9,2) + 7 & 98287 &:= 7 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25928 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9,2) + 8 & 98288 &:= 8 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25929 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9,2) + 9. & 98289 &:= 9 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}). \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [22].

4.9 S-gonal numbers

The formula for **S-gonal numbers** is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

This subsection brings some examples of selfie numbrs using **S-gonal numbers**. These examples are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 4992 &:= P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & 8967 &:= 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\
 7744 &:= (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & 9504 &:= 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\
 7896 &:= 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & 9744 &:= 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\
 65485 &:= -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & 49281 &:= 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \\
 65943 &:= P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & 49548 &:= -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4 \\
 67977 &:= (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & 50424 &:= 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!}) \\
 72495 &:= -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 & 52895 &:= (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5 \\
 83544 &:= \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}. & 53995 &:= (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 86640 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 0 & 5640 &:= 0 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86641 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 1 & 5641 &:= 1 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86642 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 2 & 5642 &:= 2 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86643 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 3 & 5643 &:= 3 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86644 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 4 & 5644 &:= 4 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86645 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 5 & 5645 &:= 5 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86646 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 6 & 5646 &:= 6 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86647 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 7 & 5647 &:= 7 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86648 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 8 & 5648 &:= 8 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86649 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 9. & 5649 &:= 9 + P(4!, 6) \times 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

4.10 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The formula for **centered polygonal numbers** is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{tn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **centered polygonal numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 2883 &:= K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3 & 00938 &:= K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!) \\
 2888 &:= K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8 & 01051 &:= K(15, 010) \\
 3640 &:= K(3!, 6) \times 40 & 01199 &:= K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10) \\
 14939 &:= -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9 & 59938 &:= K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5 \\
 14959 &:= (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9 & 62424 &:= 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6) \\
 15144 &:= K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4! & 63384 &:= 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6! \\
 15347 &:= (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7) & 63744 &:= 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!) \\
 15399 &:= K(1 \times 5! / 3!, 9) \times 9 & 63973 &:= K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6).
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 99360 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99361 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99362 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99363 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99364 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99365 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99366 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99367 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99368 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99369 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

4.11 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, n > 0, n \in \mathbf{N}.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 48 := -Q(4) + Q(8) & 49 := Q(-9 + Q(4)) \\
 81 := Q(8 + 1) & 89 := Q(9) + 8 \\
 128 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(8) & 224 := (Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2)) \\
 292 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2) & 275 := Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2)) \\
 322 := Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2 & 736 := Q(Q(6) - Q(3)) + 7 \\
 1036 := 10^3 + Q(6) & 0107 := 7 + Q(010) \\
 1125 := Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5 & 0231 := -Q(13) + Q(20) \\
 1729 := 1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9) & 1257 := 7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1 \\
 9843 := (Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3 & 2239 := -Q(9) + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2)) \\
 10025 := 100^2 + Q(5) & 08136 := Q(6) + Q(Q(3) + 1 + 80) \\
 10384 := (-1 + Q(Q(03))) \times 8 \times Q(4) & 99712 := Q(Q(2)) \times 1 \times (Q(79) - 9) \\
 99378 := 9 \times (Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8 & 37293 := -3 + (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3).
 \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 12680 := (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12681 := (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12682 := (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12683 := (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12684 := (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12685 := (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12686 := (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12687 := (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12688 := (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12689 := (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))
 \end{array}$$

For more details refer author's work [25].

4.12 Cubic-Type Selfies

The formula for **cubic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^3, n > 0, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **cubic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 125 := 1^2 \times C(5) & 512 := C(2 + 1 + 5) \\
 522 := 5 \times 2 + C(C(2)) & 991 := (C(1 + 9) - 9) \\
 991 := -9 + C(9 + 1) & 0235 := 5 \times (C(3) + 20) \\
 1371 := (1 + 3) \times C(7) - 1 & 0263 := C(3) + C(6) + 20 \\
 1715 := 1 \times C(7) \times 1 \times 5 & 1735 := 5 \times (3 + C(7) + 1) \\
 2587 := -C(2) + 5 \times (C(8) + 7) & 5974 := -4 + 7 \times (C(9) + C(5)) \\
 9945 := C(9) + 9 \times 4^5 & 00157 := -C(7) + 5 \times 100 \\
 10125 := (10 - 1)^2 \times C(5) & 01928 := 8 \times (C(C(2)) + C(9) - C(10)) \\
 16444 := C(16) \times 4 + C(4) - 4 & 45194 := -4 + C(9) \times (1 + C(5) - C(4)) \\
 30375 := C(30) + C(3 + 7 + 5) & 99535 := 5 \times (C(C(3)) + C(5) + 99) \\
 99873 := C(9) \times (9 + C(8) / (7 - 3)) &
 \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 22950 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22951 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22952 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22953 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22954 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22955 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22956 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22957 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22958 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22959 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2)))
 \end{array}$$

Remark 4.1. The notation $C(., .)$ in two variables represent **binomial coefficients**, while the $C(.)$ in single variable represent **cubic numbers**.

For more details refer author's work [25].

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References

- [1] J. BARTON, Centered Polygonal Numbers, <http://www.virtuescience.com/centered-polygonal.html>.
- [2] C. ROSE, Radical Narcissistic numbers, *J. Recreational Mathematics*, **33**, (2004-2005), pp. 250-254.

- [3] **C. ROSE**, Pretty Wild Narcissistic numbers, The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, founded by N.J.A. Sloane, <https://oeis.org/A193069>, August 08, 2011.
- [4] **C. ROSE**, Pretty Wild Narcissistic numbers, <http://www.tri.org.au/numQ/pwn/>.
- [5] **H.E. DUDENEY**, Amusements in Mathematics, EBD E-Books Directory.com, 1917.
- [6] **E. FREIDMAN**, Math Magic Archive, <http://bit.ly/2wp7HWS>.
- [7] **E. FREIDMAN**, Math Magic Numbers Archive, <http://bit.ly/2Tzbo5Q>.
- [8] **H. HEINZ**, Number Patterns, <http://www.magic-squares.net>.
- [9] **R. KNOTT**, Polygonal Numbers, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Figurate/figurate.html>.
- [10] **R. KNOTT**, The Mathematical Magic of the Fibonacci Numbers, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Fibonacci/fibmaths.html>
- [11] **J.S. MADACHY**, Mathematics on Vacations, Charlers Scriber's Son, New York, 1966.
- [12] **WOLFRAM MATH WORLD**, Polygonal Numbers, <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/PolygonalNumber.html>.
- [13] **WOLFRAM MATH WORLD**, Centered Polygonal Numbers, <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/CenteredPolygonalNumber.html>.
- [14] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers - I: Symmetrical and Unified Representations, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 174, pp.1-94. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a174.pdf>.
- [15] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers - V: Six Digits Symmetrical Representations with Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Article 164, pp.1-60, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a164.pdf>.
- [16] **I.J. TANEJA**, Digit's Order Selfie Numbers: Factorial and Square-Root, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 140, pp. 1-86, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a140.pdf>.
- [17] **I.J. TANEJA**, S-gonal and Centered Polygonal Selfie Numbers, and Connections with Binomials Coefficients, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 43, pp. 1-42, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a43.pdf>.
- [18] **I.J. TANEJA**, Crazy, Selfie, Fibonacci, Triangular, Amicable Types Representations of Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 3, pp. 1-140, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a03.pdf>.
- [19] **I.J. TANEJA**, 2019 In Numbers, **Zenodo**, December 31, 2019, pp. 1-27, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2529103>.
- [20] **I.J. TANEJA**, Permutable Powers Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 15, 2019, pp. 1-227, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2566445>.
- [21] **I.J. TANEJA**, Triangular-Type Selfie Numebrs, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 17, 2019, pp. 1-91, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567571>
- [22] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 18, 2019, pp. 1-116, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571472>.

- [23] **I.J. TANEJA**, Fibonacci Sequence and Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 19, 2019, pp. 1-233, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572044>.
- [24] **I.J. TANEJA**, Simultaneous Representations of Selfie Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci and Triangular Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 20, 2019, pp. 1-115, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2574136>.
- [25] **I.J. TANEJA**, Quadratic-Type Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 25, 2019, pp. 1-315, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2577472>.
- [26] **I.J. TANEJA**, Factorial-Type Selfie Numbers in Digit's Order, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 06, 2019, pp. 1-243, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2585586>.
- [27] **I.J. TANEJA**, Factorial-Type Selfie Numbers in Reverse Order of Digits, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 06, 2019, pp. 1-227, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2585599>.
- [28] **I.J. TANEJA**, Concatenation-Type Selfie Numbers With Factorial and Square-Root, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 08, 2019, pp. 1-43, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2587751>.
- [29] **I.J. TANEJA**, Cubic-Type Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 12, 2019, pp. 1-150, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2591257>.
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